

THE SCOTTISH DIASPORA TAPESTRY:
A Case Study for Contemporary Engagement with Historic Diaspora Identity

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Abstract

The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry is a community arts project which was coordinated in Prestonpans. The exhibition comprises 305 embroidered panels stitched by volunteers from around the world, depicting stories from thirty-three countries with connections to Scotland. Some of these are historic connections dating back many centuries; others are more recent or even contemporary. The content of the tapestry was determined for the most part by diaspora-based participants, giving a strong sense of ownership to both the artwork and the heritage depicted. The tapestry therefore opens a window into the contemporary Scottish diaspora, facilitating deeper understanding of how it self-identifies and how it might most effectively be engaged. This is an opportunity to examine how Scotland and the Scottish Government engage with the Scottish diaspora, and the effectiveness of participatory and creative forms of engagement can be of importance in mobilising dormant audiences. The value of educating the homeland audience to create a receptive atmosphere to diaspora input, something the tapestry can support directly, is presented as a critical element in facilitating meaningful bilateral relationships between Scotland and the diaspora.

This thesis presents the first detailed analysis of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry both as an arts project and as a completed artwork with a legacy beyond its creation. Through a combination of participant observation, contributor surveys, content analysis and a comprehensive reading of official correspondence and evaluation of documents, the foundations for a thorough understanding of the tapestry are laid. This reveals the scale and depth of the project's engagement, the breadth and diversity of the resulting content, and reflections on how the historic diaspora is perceived by its contemporary members. By viewing that content through established theoretical frameworks it is shown that the Scottish migratory experience fulfils almost all the categories of diaspora at some point over the centuries, in distinct phases connected to geographical shifts, and that these shifts are reflected in the nature contemporary engagement with the homeland.

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Author's Declaration

I declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, that this dissertation is the result of my own work and has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

Arran Paul Johnston

Introduction

‘A remarkable and heart-felt homage to the determination, courage and achievement of Scottish migrants and their descendants across the centuries.’

Scottish Diaspora Tapestry website

The *Scottish Diaspora Tapestry* is a significant international community artwork which, both as a creative project and as a completed exhibition, provides extraordinary insights into the ways in which members of the contemporary Scottish diaspora engage with their historic connection to Scotland and the sense of diaspora identity which is its legacy; insights which facilitate an increased understanding of diaspora as a global cultural identity and the appropriate frameworks for diaspora-homeland engagements. Between 2012 and 2015 the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry project engaged over a thousand individuals in the creation of a major artwork, requiring considerable research, skill and commitment which would result in embroidered panels which would then be gifted back to a team in Scotland for exhibition. The result is a spectacular visual representation of a nation’s historic experience of both emigration and immigration, of contemporary perceptions of that experience, and of the importance it still holds to communities, families and individuals across the globe. As a project of unrivalled ambition it is worthy of study in itself, but as a case-study in diaspora engagement it is of considerable importance.

The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry website summarises how the team behind the project perceive their creation: it is ‘a remarkable and heart-felt homage to the determination, courage and achievement of Scottish migrants and their descendants across the centuries’ (accessed August 2014). This statement encapsulates many of the key themes of this thesis, and is therefore worthy of consideration. It asserts that the Scottish people have had or do have a noteworthy experience of migration, an experience which has not been confined to temporary or occasional historical episodes but has occurred right ‘across the centuries’. This is something which is both accepted and well-studied by academics (McCarthy and Mackenzie, 2016; Devine, 2011; Buelmann et al, 2015). In its use of the word ‘achievement’, the statement implies that Scots migrants and their descendants have made a positive contribution to either their host or home countries, whilst reference to their determination and courage suggests that the Scots’ experience of migration has not always been comfortable or straightforward. This too has been the subject of much attention (Wilson, 2006; Calder, 2004; Miller, 2016; Harper, 2004). The tapestry itself is introduced to us as a ‘heart-felt homage’, which necessarily implies that

its creators were mobilised by a sense of empathy or sympathy. From this springs discussion of the contemporary resonance of the historic experiences alluded to, and this also has been the cause of much discussion amongst academics (Leith and Sim, 2014; Hesse, 2014) and even governments (Scottish Government, 2010b).

That the tapestry project is indeed ‘remarkable’, as this statement from the website claims, is very much the central pillar of this thesis. The concept, the engagement processes, the creation phases and the resulting content of the tapestry must all be analysed in detail in order to establish its value, as a statement of the diaspora’s history and a manifestation of its sense of identity. That the project team identifies the tapestry as ‘heart-felt’ clearly implies that it has been created out of affection, identification or sympathy with the migratory history of the Scottish people. If the project is driven by emotion, can it still represent with authority the historic and contemporary reality of the diaspora, or is its educational value somehow undermined? In either case, the emotional drivers are themselves worthy of investigation. As well as the 1000 plus people the project engaged in the tapestry’s creation, the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry has drawn in excess of 100,000 visitors to its worldwide exhibitions in just three years, with the potential to attract many thousands more. It is therefore becoming one of the key interfaces between the history of the Scottish diaspora and contemporary audiences, especially in Scotland where the need for increased education about the diaspora has long been acknowledged (Scottish Government 2010a). As a result it is important that the tapestry is properly understood so that this legacy can be both contextualised and maximised, and if necessary supplemented. This speaks to the core purpose of this thesis: we must investigate the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry to discern what it reveals about the Scottish diaspora as both an historical experience and a contemporary identity, and how the contemporary diaspora community might best be engaged.

The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry

In physical terms the tapestry is a collection of 305 square linen panels, each measuring just over half a meter in both length and height, onto which are embroidered unique illustrations which have been hand-stitched in woollen threads. Technically it is therefore not a tapestry at all; the textile purist would immediately identify a tapestry image as being woven rather than embroidered (Labarge, 1999). There is a broader and simpler definition of tapestry however, as a fabric wall-hanging. This definition reflects the original purpose of medieval tapestries rather than simply its manufacturing process. The internationally renowned Bayeux Tapestry, stitched in the eleventh century to

commemorate the victory of William of Normandy at the Battle of Hastings and now listed on the UNESCO Memory of the World Register (UNESCO, 2016), is also embroidered rather than woven (Hicks, 2007). The use of tapestry for embroidered artworks has since become something of an artistic convention for projects which have been inspired by Bayeux, perhaps in order that they can identify with its fame. Recently there have been a considerable number of major tapestry projects: in Britain alone it is possible to visit the Quaker Tapestry, the Last Invasion Tapestry, the Battle of Prestonpans Tapestry and the Great Tapestry of Scotland, all of which are in fact embroidered. One exception to the conventional nomenclature is the Overlord Embroidery, which is not officially known as a tapestry despite having as much claim to the word as any of the other artworks named (Brooks and Eckstein, 1989). The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry therefore follows a well-established convention in terming itself a tapestry.

A Scottish Diaspora Tapestry panel may depict a fully self-contained story, a part of a larger tale which is told over a number of panels, or sometimes several stories connected to a central individual or place (Crummy et al, 2015). The nature and variety of this content will be explored in considerable detail in chapter five. The stories contained on these panels are intended to be illustrative of the experiences, activities, cultures or legacies of Scots and their descendants, and those stories cover thirty-four countries. The narrative content is therefore diverse in both nature and in relative profile: a visitor to the exhibition might well be familiar with David Livingstone or Andrew Carnegie, but few will have heard of Helen Skedd in Geelong, Australia, or William Mann Somerville in the Elqui Valley of Chile. The panels also cover a vast number of years, from a time before records to the twenty-first century.

The tapestry is a large and fascinating visual interpretation of a great many historical episodes which have all played a part in connecting Scotland and its people to the wider world. The content of the tapestry is therefore worthy of study in its own right. There is simply no other comparable illustration of that story, and this tapestry is therefore well placed to exert considerable influence on how the history of the Scottish diaspora is presented and perceived. That influence may last for many generations: as an artwork of considerable craftsmanship and appeal it is likely to survive all of its creators. This potential influence and longevity makes it important that a proper evaluation of the tapestry has been undertaken now, whilst there is still access to the relevant information and networks. This study will therefore consider the tapestry's value as a learning resource, exploring the proportionality of its content in relation to the established understanding of the Scots' migratory history. Obvious omissions or interpretive imbalances surely point to significant observations.

Understanding the content of the tapestry is not possible without exploring the process by which that content was selected. A thorough evaluation of how it was created, the context of its conception, and the relationships between the coordinators and the volunteer contributors are critical to meaningful interpretation of the project's outcomes. Those relationships are not always straightforward or consistent, a practical reality which is in itself important to understanding the content. By considering the tapestry in terms of people rather than stories, in terms of its active participants rather than just the passive portrayals in its illustrations, the value of the tapestry to the social scientist as well as the historian becomes apparent. What tales are chosen for inclusion, the weight they are given in the presentation, and the images and symbols used to represent them, are all factors which shed light on how the historical diaspora is perceived by its contemporary membership. Since the coordinating team endeavoured whenever possible to ensure the ideas and the stitching came directly from diaspora individuals and communities, then those insights extend even further.

The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry project succeeded in involving many hundreds of individuals from around the world as embroiderers, researchers and facilitators, and was thus a truly collaborative global project. The natural result is that it has become a compelling, and more importantly viable case study for how the contemporary Scottish diaspora, and indeed the Scottish homeland, engage with its history and identity. The Scottish Government is active in its research into how to best engage the diaspora (Scottish Government, 2010b), and saw the potential the tapestry project possessed in supporting its aims (see chapter three). By exploring the project, its content, and what it reveals to us about diaspora identity, this thesis will in turn facilitate a revised understanding of how Scotland, its tourism agencies and its devolved government can most effectively engage with its diaspora. There lies a potential legacy of the tapestry and, through it, this thesis.

The research questions

The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry is a significant artwork in its own right, but it is made all the more so because of the scope and scale of the engagement the project succeeded in facilitating across a massive but disparate international community. The insights which it can provide therefore relate to two discrete aspects of the tapestry: the actual visual content of the artwork; and the project processes which created it. Understanding the latter is particularly important as it identifies the authorial voice or voices of the tapestry, which is what elevates the artwork to something rather more than just a large collection of skilfully crafted illustrative embroideries. It also helps to highlight important lessons for

future engagement projects and approaches. This study is therefore fortunate in having been able to observe the project closely through all its stages, as is explained in chapter two of the thesis.

The fundamental question being addressed here is what the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry, both as a project and as an artwork, reveals to us about the Scottish diaspora today and how its members engage with their diaspora identity and heritage, the two being interlocked (Smith, 2001). In attempting to answer this question this thesis explores a number of key issues. It seeks to identify what level of direct diaspora engagement the tapestry actually succeeded in achieving, how deep that engagement was and what factors helped or hindered the project's ability to reach it (see Rutherford, 2009). This is important if the results of studying the tapestry are to have a genuine value for our overall understanding of diasporic engagement. It is important to establish the geographic spread of that engagement in order to show that some of the thirty-four countries involved contributed more directly than others, a finding which in itself has considerable meaning. This reveals that the weighting of the content – 41 Australian panels compared to just three Polish, for example – is indicative of different levels of diaspora engagement, reflecting some of the limitations of global projects run entirely in English as well as the difficulties in sustaining diaspora identities over many centuries in established host countries with their own strong nation identities (Dobson, 2000). Is this weighting of the panels, whether geographical or in regard to different time periods or historical phases, justifiable in terms of what is understood by historians of the diaspora? Once the balance of the weighting is understood, the thesis can advance its analysis beyond quantifying engagement to an assessment of what participating in this project actually meant to those who were successfully engaged, and indeed to those who experience the tapestry at its exhibitions.

This line of investigation helps lead us to the “who?” questions which evaluating the tapestry requires us to ask. Identifying the people involved in the project and therefore what forms the resulting authorial voice of its artwork, is critical if the tapestry is to have serious academic value. Its lessons for our understanding of the contemporary diaspora would be limited if, for example, all of the content decisions were made by a single Scottish historian. This study therefore analyses all the available data on the numbers of people involved and their geographic location, as well as the type and extent of their personal connection to Scotland. The factors motivating those who took part can vary considerably depending on the location or origin of the volunteers, something which is particularly evident when considering panels which were in fact not stitched in the diaspora at all but in Scotland. Nor is the analysis restricted to the stitching contribution: who was determining the content of the panels, the stories they tell and the way that they are depicted? The balance of influence between the project team in Scotland and the volunteers outside of that team is of particular interest

and is not always consistent. Having a direct influence over the content was considered more important to some participants than others; sometimes because a volunteer's primary motivation for participation was different or else because the simple act of participation was sufficient motivation and reward in itself.

There were over a thousand contributors to the tapestry whose names are known, and many others who participated as part of bigger groups, like the school pupils in Jaffa who added stitches to one of the Palestine/Israel panels but did not submit their individual names for the project team. This is a considerable success in terms of global engagement in contributory art, since community art is more commonly focussed on specifically local audiences or addressing a particular local need (Crehan, 2013), but this success makes the identification of an authorial voice more complex than if a single hand had controlled the content development. The scale of individual contribution and the extent of individual influence varied from panel to panel, and to ensure the project resulted in a coherent finished product the influence of the single artist-designer in Scotland and the project management team around him also needed to be significant. It is therefore essential not just to consider the questions of "who?" but also of "how?" How it was made, the understanding of the processes that were used to engage contributors and structure the content, are important considerations.

The idea for the project was conceived out of its own particular context in the community of Prestonpans in East Lothian (Johnston and Prestoungrange, 2013) and against the backdrop of a specific tourism agenda for Homecoming 2014 (Scottish Government, 2010b), and the project was therefore influenced by previous projects and by the structures and timetables within which it operated. It was a very small team which actually drove the project, so there were concentrated personnel influences at its conception and evolution which must be properly accounted, and resource limitations which affected the project's initial reach and longer term touring strategies. This study will explore how this team engaged with the diaspora and the barriers and opportunities which they encountered. Understanding this process is revealing, suggesting that future initiatives seeking to engage with the diaspora should carefully consider their chosen routes towards its members. In some cases the tapestry team's use of the formal structures of diaspora, such as Scottish societies, clan associations or institutions such as universities, was an obvious and successful pathway; but on other occasions that same strategy did not in fact achieve results. Evidence in this study suggests that such organisations, although regularly treated as gatekeepers (Scottish Government, 2010a), do not reach significant portions of the diaspora community who yet possess the will to become engaged. So-called horizontal networks, those within diaspora communities rather than between the diaspora and the homeland, can be more effective in extending project reach, whilst providing a sense of local

ownership and initiative is significant to the psychology of engagement (2010a). This project demonstrates the case for this approach.

Of course the strategies which the team in Scotland were able to deploy were both facilitated and constrained by material and manpower resources. The funding of the project must therefore be considered, especially as the project received considerable amounts of public funding. This in itself is noteworthy, as it suggests that the Scottish Government identified the potential of this project to support its diaspora engagement objectives (2010b). The influence of funding bodies on the project is examined to consider whether the government's economic and tourism agenda had a measurable influence on the tapestry's content, as is the absence amongst the funding agencies of a mechanism for capturing the temporary networks which resulted from the project's engagement and a means supporting the tapestry's longer-term activities. This aspect of the study is particularly relevant for drawing possible conclusions relating to government diaspora policy and tourism strategy.

Terminology

Identifying an appropriate definition for diaspora is not without its complexities, an issue which is considered in the fourth section of chapter two and returned to at appropriate points throughout the thesis. It is not the purpose of this study to enter into detailed consideration of the case for Scottish exceptionalism in regard to its diaspora experience, nor is it within the present scope to draw considered comparisons with other examples (the Irish experience being a particularly important and well-studied comparator). It should therefore be noted that the phrase 'the diaspora' will be used in this paper specifically in reference to the Scottish diaspora, since that is the principal concern of this case study. More general reference to diaspora should be readily identifiable by the lack of the definite article. The appropriateness of diaspora as a term in reference to some of the material covered in the tapestry is also something which will be considered when appropriate in this study.

The question of defining a tapestry has been addressed earlier in this introduction. The embroiderers who worked on creating the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry will be referred to most commonly as stitchers, which is the term used by the project itself, although for variety the term embroiderers may also be used. Not all volunteers who supported the creation of the tapestry were stitchers however, as some contributors provided research information and contacts rather than their embroidery skills. For the purpose of clarity these will be referred to as non-stitching contributors or research contributors.

Collectively all those involved in the project but were not part of the core management team are identified interchangeably as contributors, participants or volunteers. The management team or project team are those who co-ordinated the project directly from its base in East Lothian. Its composition is explained in chapter three.

The individual pieces of embroidery of which the tapestry is composed are known as panels. Each one has an official alphanumeric code by which it is identified and this thesis will make reference to specific panels by using those codes. They consist of an ordinal number preceded by letters identifying the country to which the story belongs. Those letters are usually but not always derived from international vehicle registration code conventions: hence Panel ZA01 is the first panel relating to South Africa (rather than SA01), but SE is used for Sweden rather than simply S as the vehicle code would have it. Northern Ireland and England are treated in the tapestry as separate countries and are differentiated by the codes GBNI and GBE respectively. PS/IL refers to Palestine/Israel, which is the form of identification requested by the contributors in order to avoid any inadvertent political insensitivity. The decision to include Palestine in the labelling nevertheless caused a very small number of complaints (just three between 2014 and 2017), but was clearly not intended as a political statement as evidenced by private correspondence surrounding the original decision. Some panel codes also have an additional letter added following their main code (for example, IT01a). This identifies a panel which was added to the list after the codes were assigned, known internally to the project team as Benchmark Two panels. This system allowed the late panels to be inserted into the exhibition at an appropriate place according to their content relevance, rather than simply being added at the end of a set. As is perhaps already becoming clear, this numbering system can cause some confusion; a full list of the panel codes and titles is therefore provided in the appendix.

As has been shown above, panels are primarily identified by the country to which their content belongs – which is not to be interpreted automatically as being the country of the panel's actual creation. A panel telling a story relating to France could for example be stitched in Scotland. For interpretation and exhibition purposes the project team usually groups these countries into what it calls 'clusters', based on broad geographical areas (see Fig.1). The names of the clusters can be deceptive however: Antarctica is treated as a country within the 'Americas' cluster for example, whilst Palestine/Israel is in 'Southern Asia' and Norway is 'Baltic'. This reflects the expansion of the tapestry beyond the originally intended countries, and the attempt to maintain a relative balance in the size of clusters so that exhibitions were proportionately divisible. There is also a 'Global Panels' cluster, which contains a small set of panels which were felt to have globally applicable or non-

territorial relevance, with themes which were felt to apply beyond national boundaries. Sections of the tapestry will regularly be referred to by use of these cluster names in this thesis.

Structure

The structure of this thesis has been designed to facilitate a straightforward navigation through a wide range of research angles, which were themselves determined by the questions set out above. As a result, the findings are compartmentalised according to the aspects of the tapestry project to which they are most immediately relevant. They are then drawn together in the final chapter to formulate the conclusions of the overall analysis.

Immediately following this introduction is a discussion of the methodology employed to facilitate this study (chapter one). It will identify and critically examine the variety of methods used to examine the tapestry, which include participant observation throughout the project's development, the collation of both qualitative and quantitative evidence relating to actual engagement in the project and its resulting exhibitions, both in the diaspora and in Scotland, and the use of coding trees for the analysis of the tapestry's narrative and visual content.

There then follows a review of the literary and theoretical context into which this research rests (chapter two). This begins with the broader context of nationhood and national identity theory, before focussing in first on Scotland's sense of nationhood and then the academic approaches to diaspora study and, ultimately, to Scotland's diaspora specifically. This exercise will demonstrate not only the considerable academic interest in the Scottish diaspora, but also the contested nature of both national identity and diaspora definition. This chapter will also demonstrate that this thesis is the first such study of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry, identifying its value in helping to establish the Scottish diaspora within the current theoretical frameworks.

Chapter three investigates the tapestry as a community artwork, from the time of its instigation and creation through to its initial exhibitions. This introduces the cultural context in which the tapestry was conceived and the project's initial aims, as well as the processes by which adequate funding and volunteer support were secured to achieve them. After two years of work the tapestry held its first exhibitions as part of Scotland's Year of Homecoming 2014. Visitor data from that initial programme

of exhibitions will be evaluated to provide insight into the tapestry's homeland reception. It will be demonstrated that the tapestry project had by this time gained such momentum that the creation process did not end as expected with the opening of the exhibitions, and the ways in which the project responded to this as it evolved from creation to exhibition will be considered.

Having established what the project aimed to achieve and the stratagems used to do so, chapter four looks at the important issue of the tapestry's authorial voice with a detailed analysis of the panels' contributors. Here the division of contribution, especially between the project management team, the embroiderers and the researchers, will be evaluated in terms of its significance to understanding the value of the tapestry as an educational device and as a case study in engagement. This will lead into an appraisal of how the contributors were found and motivated, expanding on some of the issues raised in chapter three, and what can be learned about diaspora networks and how best to access them. Importantly, the chapter also examines what has been learned about the social makeup of the volunteer contributors, identifying the most significant age-groups involved and considering the possibility of age or gender bias and any possible implications this may have in interpreting the tapestry. This information is drawn primarily from the results of responses to a survey instrument distributed to known contributors at the conclusion of the creative phases of the project, as is the important analysis of what has been discovered regarding the factors which motivated active participation. Throughout this chapter important comparisons will be shown between those who stitched in Scotland and those who were based abroad. This chapter is critical in revealing the extent to which the tapestry can be considered to speak with a truly diaspora voice, rather than simply as a small team in Scotland's perception of one.

Chapter five introduces the narrative content of the panels themselves, particularly focusing on the types of historical episodes represented and whether their weightings are proportional to what we know of the historical narrative. The content will be also considered in terms of diaspora theory, especially in relation to Cohen's attempts to classify diaspora communities (2008), to demonstrate how the tapestry content covers several different classifications. This suggests that a universal Scottish diaspora experience is hard to define historically, despite the global commonality of its cultural legacy and resonance. The tapestry helps to identify how different classifications of diaspora are appropriate for application to different host countries and different historical timeframes, and that these differences can be seen reflected in the levels and nature of the engagement in this project.

The sixth chapter of the thesis develops this investigation of the content of the tapestry panels further by considering not just the nature of the stories shown but the ways in which they are depicted. The role of the central artist is of course considerable in this regard, but there was demonstrable contributor input (see chapter five). It is therefore important to examine how the tapestry reflects common identity markers – the symbols of “Scottishness” – which can then be considered in the context of ethnosymbolist theories of nationhood (see chapter one). It will be shown that the tapestry does not generally rely on the direct imagery of standardised Scottish symbolism, but that historical linkages are maintained both through genealogical connectivity and through the physical manifestations of historical contact, the built heritage of the host community. Identifying these identity markers is not only important for considerations of diaspora theory however; they can also be of practical value in its practical applications, such as the potential for heritage conservation initiatives to serve as a vehicle for fostering trans-national relationships and sustaining diaspora identities in both a localised and a global context.

In chapter seven the tapestry’s potential legacies are considered, both in terms of how it has been used in the years since its completion and in current expectations regarding its future. This includes its educational potential and plans for its long-term settlement. Here the analysis will reflect what lessons were learned during the project, particularly in regard to building and maintaining networks between Scotland and its diaspora countries, and much reference will be made to the Scottish Government’s diaspora policy and the importance of educating homeland audiences. The tapestry’s immediate role in this regard is not inconsiderable, and is capable of yielding greater fruit in the future if the potential is properly harnessed. This leads to considerations, drawing back to aspects covered in chapter three, of how the project was evaluated by funding bodies and the possible shortcomings of such agencies in harnessing such potential formally.

These issues prepare the way for the final chapter, which draws together the findings of this investigation into a range of conclusions identifying the several voices represented within the tapestry, the importance of both visual symbols and physical markers in maintaining diaspora identity, and the relationship between a community’s engagement with that identity and the nature of its historical connection with the homeland. The thesis will finally conclude that the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry is indeed of considerable value in understanding diaspora identity and its relevance to both homeland and host country identities, and that this investigation lays the foundations on which any future consideration of the tapestry should be based. It is a clear demonstration of the value of locally-rooted decentralised engagement initiatives, of the depth and breadth of potential engagement between

diaspora audiences and homeland initiatives when appropriately conceived and targeted, and of the a continued desire to express a belonging to and an engagement with an historically-rooted identity which coexists un-competitively with national identity.

THE BALTIC (28)	WESTERN EUROPE (39)	CANADA (37)
Lithuania (4) Norway (5) Poland (3) Russia (6) Sweden (10)	France (12) Germany (4) Italy (8) Netherlands (12) Portugal (3)	Canada (37)
THE AMERICAS (42)	ASIA (44)	AUSTRALASIA & AFRICA (67)
Antarctica (1) Argentina (5) Brazil (3) Chile (2) Jamaica (5) United States of America (26)	China (10) India (24) Pakistan (5) Palestine/Israel (2) Sri Lanka (2) Taiwan (1)	Australia (41) Ethiopia (1) Malawi (3) New Zealand (11) South Africa (8) Tristan da Cunha (1) Zimbabwe (2)
THE BRITISH ISLES (33)	GLOBAL PANELS (15)	CLUSTERS IN SIZE ORDER
England (21) Northern Ireland (5) Republic of Ireland (7)		Australasia & Africa (67) Asia (44) The Americas (42) Western Europe (39) Canada (37) The British Isles (33) The Baltic (28) Globals (15)

Fig. 0-1. Countries represented in the Tapestry, arranged in exhibition “Clusters” with number of panels shown in brackets.

Chapter One:

Methodology

This thesis is a case study in contemporary engagement with historic diaspora identity. The value and variable nature of case study research is in itself a subject of discussion, with different theorists variously considering case study as either an individual method or an overarching strategic design which can in turn deploy a range of methods (Harrison et al, 2017). It is the later sense in which it is understood for the purposes of this thesis. Despite the terminological ambiguity, there does appear to be a consensus that as an exploratory strategy for complex issues requiring multangular methodological approaches case study is both viable and valuable (Harrison et al, 2017). Effective case study encourages consideration of both qualitative and quantitative data and allows a level of depth within the subject of analysis which, when properly contextualised, can support learning for wider application (Johansson, 2003).

The fact that modern case study methods have evolved out of the context of anthropological, historical and sociological investigations, studying real lives and experiences, supports its relevance to the fields of interest enclosed within this study (Johansson, 2017), and although there will be some description elements as have been common in early twentieth century case studies (Merriam, 2009) this thesis will follow more recent practice of using a wider set of methods to create in-depth analysis too (Harrison et al, 2017). However, it should be acknowledged that in the case of this thesis it was in fact the evident potential value of the project under investigation which triggered research into what wider insights studying it might reveal, rather than a conscious search for a subject for case study. This chapter therefore focuses on the different strategies deployed in order to record, analyse and interpret the insights of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry as a valuable case study in contemporary engagement with historic identity in a global diaspora setting.

In order to glean as much insight as possible from the study of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry it was important that the project was analysed at each of its main stages: from conception to creation; from creation to completion; the year of Homecoming exhibitions in 2014; the global tour and its lessons for beyond 2017. These phases each involved a different set of processes and engagements, and it is therefore to be expected that different methods have been employed in the process of their evaluation

and appraisal. These in turn created different types of datasets which themselves required different forms of analysis in order to reach meaningful conclusions. This chapter explains those various methods and how they fit together to satisfy the requirements of the different research questions which have driven this study.

Document analysis and observation methods

It is important at the outset to identify that this evaluation of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry has been actively supported and assisted by the project's management team from the Prestoungrange Arts Festival, who encouraged the early involvement of academics from the University of the West of Scotland as part of the search for information and contacts during the project's content development (Strategy Group Minutes 08/13). The author of this thesis was already involved in the project at this point in a supporting capacity, having been previously involved with the similar project which created the Prestonpans Tapestry in 2010. From July 2013 the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry team were all aware that evaluation resulting in this thesis was being undertaken (Strategy Group Minutes 07/13). This study was accordingly granted full access to all aspects of the project; including to data created prior to the formal initiation of this research study in October 2013, as the author had been present at all the principal project meetings since the tapestry's conception. Access has been available throughout to all internal meetings and to their minutes, and also to meetings with external agents such as the Scottish Government and Homecoming Scotland. In addition the researcher held regular informal meetings with other members of the management team. This study has drawn upon all those meetings, their official notes and the researcher's own observations, as well as other relevant official documents such as funding applications and evaluative feedback provided to funders.

These documents are not in the public domain and access was privileged, with official minutes being shared in a password protected area of the project's website and access granted only to a small group of agreed individuals. These documents have therefore been analysed with appropriate discretion and are only quoted in this study where necessary and without prejudice to confidentiality. All meeting minutes were agreed as a true record as appropriate at subsequent meetings, providing for the reliability of their contents and the acceptance of those present as to their veracity. Minutes from formal project meetings held by the management team and invited guests or advisors are usually referenced as Strategy Group Minutes, followed by the code used in the archive comprising the meeting's ordinal number and the year. For example, the first formal meeting was held in 2012 and is listed as 01/12. These documents remain unpublished and are not available to the public, and to maintain confidentially individual viewpoints expressed in meetings are not quoted, only collective

reports or decisions. Unpublished correspondence between the project team and funders is also approached with due caution and no commercially sensitive information is reproduced. Letters are referenced according to the writer and receiver and the date on the material. This wealth of written evidence forms the main documentary data set which, allied to the direct observation of the researcher, informs our understanding of the chronology and decision-making processes of the tapestry's creation from 2012 to 2015, the last minuted strategy meeting occurring in May of that year (Strategy Group Minutes 20/15). These documents are relatively uncomplicated sources to study and have been analysed using very simple coding techniques to identify salient moments and themes, which are particularly drawn upon in chapter three. This study of the archival material would ordinarily be considered an unobtrusive research method (Webb et al, 1966), but it must be noted that the researcher was present at many of the events which then informed the documents. Consideration must therefore be given to the role of the author as a participant observer.

It has already been shown that the author was personally present at almost all of the key meetings held throughout the project's evolution, and it is important therefore to understand the potential effects of this role as well as the obvious benefits. Although present and able to express views, the researcher's responsibilities on the project were primarily focused on the logistical planning of the 2014 exhibitions, the practical requirements of transporting the tapestry in 2014 into 2015, and editorial work on the panel histories published in the tapestry's official guide book (Crummy et al, 2014; 2015). The focus of this activity prevented direct influence on the content or design of the tapestry, except in the case of panel IT01a which the author discussed with the artist directly as it relates directly to a field of his specific historical expertise (Johnston, 2010). The division of labour across the management team is discussed in more detail in chapter three, but in essence the overall strategy, content development, contributor recruitment and physical creation of the tapestry were all driven by others. The issue of partiality and objectivity in participant observation based research is one which is understood as one of the inherent risks (Breuer, 2003), but a degree of reflexivity and a consciousness of the researcher's place within both the tapestry project and its evaluation throughout the process should have limited the scope for this thesis' evaluation to have become distorted as a result of this choice of method. It is therefore important to place beyond question that the aspects of the project which are of the greatest concern to this study were not those over which the author had direct influence or responsibility, which should alleviate any concerns regarding the partiality of this study.

In fact this degree of integrated participation was to the study's benefit as it facilitated greater access to the participants and to the data. There is of course a risk that contributors who are aware they are under observation may alter their behaviour, known as the reactive effect (Bryman, 2012). They might

speak less frankly at meetings for example, or behave either more dominantly or shyly depending on how they might wish to be perceived, or else they might otherwise attempt to influence the observer's perception and data through moderation of behaviour, manipulation or even direct approach. However, there is evidence that in fact a considerable degree of normalisation occurs over the course of time as participants become accustomed to the observer (McCall, 1984). This reduced any potential concerns about the validity or reliability of the observer's findings. Normalisation occurred swiftly in this case, as the observer-researcher was already well known to those who were most frequently under direct observation – the project team members - and was also well-established in the field context in which they were operating. There is no evidence apparent to the author that the team behaved any differently because they were being observed for the purposes of this study, or that the author's participation affected any outcomes.

In terms of the internal project team, the subjects under observation were also very familiar with one another, professionally and in some cases socially, so there were few barriers to frank speech and every opportunity for team members to identify and challenge any unusual behaviour as might indicate a reactive affect to the observation (Bryman, 2012). Even the addition of a new member to the team in the summer of 2013 did not result in an observable change in behaviour or openness. Research suggests that there are positive benefits to having this level of familiarity between team members, as it encourages cooperative information pooling (Gruenfeld et al, 1996). The balance of relations was somewhat different at external meetings. Those with government agencies and funders were more formal in their general tone and the exchanges were often noticeably more guarded, to reflect a different power relationship. It was therefore the perceived balances of power between project and funder which affected the nature of behaviour during observed meetings, rather than those between team members or their reaction to the presence of a participant observer.

In order to gain a full insight into the entire process of a tapestry panel's creation, participant observation was carried beyond simply attending the planning and strategy meetings: two full panels were stitched by the author (FR05 and IT01a) so as to share in the experience of other contributors. They were created exactly the same way as the other panels, including the liaison between stitcher and designer. This allowed a clearer understanding of the nature of the relationship between contributing volunteers, including those providing content information and those undertaking the embroidery, and the artist designer in Scotland. It also gave an appreciation of the extent of the commitment made by volunteer stitchers, the amount of time required to complete a panel, and the sense of ownership engendered simply through participation. The resulting empathy also encouraged acceptance of the participant observer into the informal community of the volunteer contributors, and although it did not

generate specific data the results of this exercise have been useful in informing interpretation of certain phases of the project and the nature of the relationships within the networks. This particular element of the participation method did not affect the potential objectivity of the research result, but provided experiential data which facilitated a deeper level of empathy with other participants in the project processes,

Observation was also undertaken at tapestry events and exhibitions as well as meetings. Each of the eight full exhibitions held in Scotland in 2014 was attended on at least two occasions, whilst the English exhibitions in Doncaster and Corby were attended on their opening days. During the European Tour of 2015, four exhibitions were visited in person in Norway, the Netherlands, and France, although it proved impractical for the author to attend the two Italian exhibitions at Barga and Picinisco. Practical restrictions, primarily relating to the costs of travel and the distances involved, also prevented any direct observation by the author at any of the Australasian and North American exhibitions, but on the tapestry's return to Britain in 2017 the author attended the Westminster, Edinburgh, Prestonpans, Crieff and Irvine exhibitions. The analysis presented in this thesis has been kept at pace with the exhibition programme and continuously updated. At the attended exhibitions it was possible to observe the ways in which visitors responded to the tapestry in natural conditions without interference.

This form of simple observation (Webb et al, 1966) made it possible to gain a basic sense of public response but did not result in the creation of an effective set of statistical data. Attendance at opening ceremonies provided an additional opportunity to gauge the responses of politicians, societies and institutions, in addition to the general public. On such occasions, conversation with and observation of visitors were deliberately kept informal and unrecorded in order to maintain an un-intrusive atmosphere. Just as the process of writing a visitors' book comment can help the audience member to formulate their opinion, it was hoped these informal conversations might also aid in the reaching of considered thoughts (Macdonald, 2005). Discussions were often spontaneous however and so they did not come from a controlled sample; early attempts to screen for visitors who might be of particular interest to the study proved impossible to implement. The results of these observations are of course more qualitative therefore than quantitative, and are considered in relation to the value of the cultural experiences being observed rather than in an attempt to infer any wider statistical trends (see Crossick & Kaszynska, 2016).

In attempt to balance this, over 1,600 visitor comments were recorded from the 2014 exhibitions in Scotland, along with additional information which was gathered by the volunteer stewards at the Paisley exhibition (focussing primarily on visitor origins). These were collected from visitors' books left at exhibitions and subsequently examined. Visitor feedback was not collected at European exhibitions as this was at the discretion of the exhibition venues, but further comments have been collected from a number of the Australian and North American venues from the 2016 tour, the visitors' books being returned to Scotland after the exhibitions, and additional comments have also been gleaned from those left at the Irvine exhibition in October 2017. Written visitor comments at exhibitions are a self-selecting sample and should not therefore be considered a wholly representative population, and the majority of comments lack sufficient depth to provide insight (Crossley, 2014). Writing comments places the burden onto the visitor, and those who are passive or disinterested are less likely to record that than those who have responded very positively. There is also an obvious but understandable tendency for visitor books to collate repetitive and often uninformative responses which simply express approval or otherwise. However, that is not always the case and the act of first reading and then contributing to a visitors' book can be shown to assist the exhibition viewer in formulating their opinion on an exhibition (Macdonald, 2005). Some comments can prove insightful, and the more expansive or unusual entries were picked out for consideration. More than anything else, the visitor books are valuable in providing data on where visitors have come from.

Textual analysis and identifying authorial voice

The participant observation, simple observation, survey instrument, and textual and documentary analysis methodologies explained above relate most relevantly to the findings presented in chapters three and seven of this thesis. Evaluating the tapestry's actual content and understanding the composition of the wider community of volunteer contributors which helped to determine it, requires different methodological approaches. The textual analysis found in chapters five and six is based largely on a statistical analysis of the panels and the countries they represent and an interpretive analysis of their visual imagery. A thematic breakdown of the panel content was provided by Dr Gordon Prestoungrange (a full explanation of the project team is provided in chapter three), who prepared a content table in 2015 to aid in the development of downloadable digital software (the "app") for exhibition visitors. This was drawn up by hand in the form of a large and unwieldy checklist for that specific purpose, but it was a useful starting point for the purposes of this study, as an initial coding table for the content of each of the individual illustrated panels. The reasoning behind some of the chosen coding decisions was unclear however, with some panels appearing to bear only slender relevance to a category they were listed under and most listed under so many categories as to

make meaningful comparative calculations difficult. As a result the Prestoungrange coding table, in both its paper and digital app forms, was used as a guide but not as a reliable statistical set. It also did not provide a coding table which addressed the historical date settings of the content, and so this was created from scratch (see appendix five). Coded breakdowns were valuable in informing an understanding of the content of the tapestry, supported by the comprehensive content summaries visible on the tapestry's website, the app, and the two editions of the official printed catalogue (Crummy et al, 2014 and 2015). This data is then contextualised in relation to historical studies of the Scottish diaspora (see chapter two) in order to highlight where there may be disparities or biases.

Taking the content analysis a stage further to examine the visual symbols used in the tapestry (chapter six) also required a coding of the panels, this time not according to their subject but according to the choice of visual representation. The coding choices for this were fairly straightforward – buildings; people; soldiers/war – these categories were then subdivided to provide a more in-depth and meaningful analysis, such as religious buildings; named individuals; women. For the full coding tree, see appendix five. The results of this content analysis were then studied for trends which relate to both geographical distribution and historical context. The value of these results must however be considered in relation to the authorial voice of the tapestry and the direction of the influences which may have affected the visual presentation. That is one of the key considerations of this study as it influences so much of our conclusions, and in order to understand it the demographics and the motivations of the contributors required analysis also. It was decided therefore to gather information from contributors around the world by means of a questionnaire.

This was a challenging exercise as the numbers of people who contributed to the tapestry are considerable. In fact, no final figure can reliably be placed on the number of people involved in this global project. The second edition of the official tapestry guide (Crummy et al, 2015), informed as it was by the database of the management team, provides the names of 1,014 known named contributors. There were certainly more, but how many more is impossible to know (see chapter three). Many of those who are listed are known by name and location only, as a smaller core of lead contacts usually handled liaison between local networks and the team in Scotland. That reduced the amount of information that could be gained from the known population. More detailed information could only be gained from those participants for whom contact details were available. This means that a reduced sample was available for contact by this study, although additional contributors were also spoken to informally at events and exhibitions and although they did not feature in the data set those discussions also helped to inform of this study.

A survey instrument was carefully drafted for distribution to as many contributors as was possible, aimed at gathering as much information as was plausible in one hit without over-burdening or discouraging the participant. It can be found as appendix two of this thesis, along with the covering letter and participant permission form. The survey instrument and the associated methodology received full ethical approval from the University of the West of Scotland in November 2014. The questionnaire itself contained thirty-eight questions over three sections, each of which reflected different areas of interest to this study. A deliberate mix of interrogative styles were used, including a mix of dichotomous, nominal and ordinal questions, in order both to facilitate swift completion of certain sections and to avoid participants settling into a response set (Johnson & Reynolds, 2012). The order of the questions was also so crafted as to encourage deeper thought about the answers as the survey progressed, culminating in an invitation to express the participants' sentiments in their own words. The expectation was that the preceding questions will have provided a sufficient guide to the intentions of the study to encourage relevant and thoughtful responses.

The first section of the questionnaire was designed to collate key demographic information on the participants, including their gender, age and nationality. Established British census conventions were used for the answer lists for age range and religion, which facilitated easy coding of the results. The questions of ethnicity and nationality were deliberately presented without predefined answers, as it was expected that there may be interest in capturing how the participants defined themselves according to these measures. This would of course be relevant in understanding their perception of their identity (see chapter four).

The questions in the second section focussed on the respondents' relationship to Scotland. Most were simple single-barrelled questions with straightforward yes or no answer options. The opening question of this section was a filter question designed to identify clearly whether participants were currently resident in Scotland, as some data sets would be analysed separately according to whether the respondent was based in Scotland or overseas in order to reveal any possible trends and variations. These answers could be cross-referenced as required to those regarding nationality, for example. The purpose of other questions in this section was to identify how connected to the homeland the respondents appeared to be, in terms of their own or family connections, ancestral connections, or basic cultural affinity. In regard to the latter, the meaning of society was deliberately left undefined when asking, 'Have you ever been a member of a Scottish society?', as it was potentially interesting to see how that might be interpreted by the respondents. If they answered that they were or had once been, they were therefore asked to specify what society that was. A small number of homeland-based

respondents interpreted this as including national cultural organisations for example, regardless of whether their activities could be classified as specifically Scottish. Most Scottish respondents correctly identified that many of the questions in this section of the survey instrument were not directly relevant to them and moved straight on to the next.

The third section was designed to elicit more specific information about the respondents' contributions to the tapestry. The options were mainly presented as scales or as lists of possibilities, to facilitate straightforward coding of results as well as enabling a simpler completion process for the respondent. There was the opportunity to enter additional options however, to ensure that respondents were not constricted by the questionnaire's expectations. Some questions were designed to address the same point but with different terminology, in order to provide the maximum opportunity to interpret the responses accurately. For example, respondents were asked who they felt was responsible for the content of their part of the tapestry and they were also asked how much influence they felt they had on that same content. Establishing authorial voice is a critical issue within this study and so it was considered important to get a clear answer from the respondents on this particular point. Some of the answer options also implied potential criticism of the project, for example if answering that the respondent would have liked more input than they felt they had, and it was felt possible that this would discourage some respondents from being honest. Reframing the question in a slightly more oblique way was intended to counter this possibility. The final question invited a longer answer to be written in the respondents' own words. This was designed to compensate at least in some measure for the study's inability to hold direct interviews with such a large number of contributors. Responses were coded for analysis based on key terms which emerged during their collation.

The questionnaire was distributed by email along with an appropriate covering letter and permission form to 311 known email addresses provided from the project participant database. The participants in the survey were therefore fully aware of the purpose and destination of their information and all respondents granted their permission for their answers to be used for this study. As most of the contributors to the tapestry already had their names and general location in the public domain, there was no real cause for or evidence of any concern regarding confidentiality. It was felt appropriate that the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry logo was featured on the questionnaire, along with a specific statement that the survey was being conducted with the support of the project management. This was expected to encourage participation in the survey, on the assumption that there was considerable goodwill towards the project from those who had contributed towards it. The survey was carried out around six months after the tapestry's launch exhibition, which meant that the contributors were still likely to be closely its activities and their memories of the process of participation were still recent and therefore

reliable. The slight delay was also intended however to ensure that the respondents had had a little time to put their participation into some perspective, and so as they did not feel over-burdened by further demands in the wake of their potentially extensive voluntary contributions to the tapestry itself.

Email was the only realistic means of contacting so a large population as this study required, particularly as there were no postal addresses available for all but a small sample of contributors (those to whom the raw materials for stitching the panels had been despatched). The reliance on email distribution does mean that the questionnaires were only sent directly to around one third of the known named contributors, although an attempt was made to mitigate this by encouraging recipients in the introductory email to share the questionnaire with anyone they knew who had contributed but who may not have received a copy. It was hoped that this method of snowball sampling might help the survey instrument to reach multiple members of groups and communities who may have all contributed to the same panel, as often only one email contact had been maintained as a liaison between that group and the project team. That often meant that participants were known by name but had no direct means of communication with either the project itself or with this study. In addition, announcements regarding this survey were made in the tapestry's email newsletter, and at meetings of the *Friends of the Prestonpans Tapestries* group which were held in Scotland. These methods helped encourage participation but were only able to reinforce the message to existing networks which were accessible by email or in person, the latter being restricted to those in Scotland.

Digital circulation necessarily meant that those without internet access were excluded from the survey's initial reach and their ability to contribute was therefore dependent on their relationships with those who were contactable. Basic computer literacy was also required if the survey was to be completed as a digital file and returned by email. A small number of respondents contacted the researcher requesting alternative file formats, which was always accommodated. At least one respondent had the form completed by a family member whilst they read out the answers, as explained in a covering email returned with the completed survey. Although the majority of completed questionnaires were returned by email, a large minority (48) arrived as hard copies despite the international postage costs that often entailed. This is indicative not only of the willingness and eagerness of respondents to contribute to the study but also of their ability to overcome any discomfort occasioned by receiving the survey instrument in digital format. In short, it was reasonable to assume that those who were contactable by email were sufficiently computer literate to open, read and complete the questionnaire if sent digitally, and to return it in either digital or paper form as

desired. Therefore the decision not to send out hard copies of the questionnaire did not reduce the population of possible respondents.

Another factor which did reduce that population was the unavoidable fact that the questionnaire was only available in the English language. This probably accounts for the low level of response from outside Western Europe and English speaking communities, although it is not unreasonable to assume that there was an existing bias towards English in the tapestry project and that the majority of contributors therefore had a working knowledge of the language. This was not always the case however for contributors in countries such as India, where the digital capacity of some contributors may also have been an inhibiting factor. There are therefore pockets of contributors which this survey was never able to reach and which therefore had no input into the results. Sometimes these circumstances are themselves relevant to our understanding of the diaspora, as will be discussed elsewhere, but it is important to acknowledge this gap in the data set. The resulting bias towards English speaking countries is borne in mind throughout the analysis of the survey's results, and whilst it prevents us making a fully global interpretation of the findings it does not reduce the significance of the findings as long as they are held within a proper context. This bias in the data has been borne in mind during its analysis.

In total 126 complete responses were received and analysed, meaning approximately 13% of the known named participants. This is clearly not comprehensive coverage, but it nevertheless represents a sufficiently large and varied sample to allow meaningful interpretation when the appropriate caveats are taken into account, as they are throughout this study, and it represents a 41% response rate in relation to the 311 email addresses used to distribute the questionnaire. This study is therefore confident that the nature and presentation of the questions asked facilitated honest and valuable responses without placing undue burden on the participants, and was timed to maximise the response rate. All participants were invited to contact the researcher should they have additional material they wished to add, information which has been incorporated as appropriate into the data sets informing this thesis. The research methodology and the sample survey instrument were submitted to the relevant ethics committee at the University of the West of Scotland in November 2014 and received unqualified ethical approval as the ethical considerations of this survey were largely limited to provisions for privacy and participant awareness.

The survey successfully generated both quantitative and qualitative data which combine with the content analysis of both the tapestry and the archive material, and the results of the observational

phases of the research, to form the effective dataset with sufficient power to answer the study's core research questions. The results of the questionnaire can be combined with the findings of the participant-observer phases of the project, and the detailed coding analysis of the content of the panels, to facilitate a comprehensive understanding of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry. It is on this research that the findings of the subsequent chapters are based, beginning with an evaluation of the composition and motivations of the project's participants.

Chapter Two:

The Literary and Theoretical Context

As a newly created artwork the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry has not been the subject of deep investigation prior to this study. There are presently only two published works about the tapestry, the most significant of which is its official accompanying guide (Crummy et al, 2014) which ran to 222 pages in its first edition but 380 pages in the updated edition released only a year later to reflect the project's expansion (Crummy et al, 2015). This guide is primarily a summary of the content of each individual panel and whilst some of this text was based on input from volunteers within the diaspora, much was prepared or edited by members of the project team in Scotland. Importantly it also includes informative supplementary chapters written by key members of the project team, which provide insights from the project's own internal viewpoint into some of the issues which will be explored in this thesis. Although these chapters were designed for the interested visitor rather than to serve as a detailed academic analysis, they are a convenient and personal articulation of the processes which this research study observed and will therefore be quoted on occasion in support of the author's interpretations.

The second work available on the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry is *The Art of Narrative Embroidery* (Farmer and Ferguson, 2015), which is a visual exploration of the stitching techniques used by contributors to this Tapestry and its predecessor project, the Prestonpans Tapestry. This book is charming, edited by two of the tapestry's stitchers, but as a thematic stitching guide its contents shed little light on the aspects of the project which are of primary interest to this study. It is nevertheless a reflection of the tapestry's appeal as a creative work, during both its participatory and exhibition phases (see Fig. 4-6).

With only these two works in publication about the tapestry, this thesis should be considered as the only comprehensive appraisal of the significance of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry, a project which acts as a window into both the historic and contemporary Scottish diaspora and its sense of identity. It nevertheless sits within a broad body of existing works which explore the nature of nationalism and national identity, both globally and in relation to Scotland, the complexities of the notion of diaspora, and the means of defining, studying and engaging with them. The original research impetus,

unsurprisingly given the author's principal discipline, arose from questions around historical interpretation aspects of the project; it appeared self-evident however that the real value of the case study lay in its wider implications. The resulting thesis is therefore cross-disciplinary and will link historiographical and sociological approaches to the subject in order to evaluate this contemporary representation of an historical narrative. It will therefore relate to literature from both disciplines. There are further avenues for analysis that lie beyond the scope of this study, from which creative and participatory arts theorists might find value, but whilst some such opportunities will be introduced it is not the purpose of the thesis to evaluate the tapestry in an artistic context; instead the focus is on the project as a process of diaspora engagement and historical interpretation.

As stated in the introduction, this study will consider the tapestry as a contemporary representation of an historical narrative, a self-asserted visualisation of the historical connections between the Scottish homeland and the host country. By examining that visualisation and understanding the composition of both its content and contributing volunteers, a greater understanding of the modern Scottish diaspora may be gleaned. To achieve this it is necessary not only to understand the project, however, but also the literary and theoretical contexts within which our analysis of it will take place. Our purpose in this chapter is therefore to identify and examine those contexts.

Theories of nations and national identity

By seeking to use the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry to consider how the modern diaspora relates to its historical connections, this study implies by its very nature that the relationship between history and identity is significant. That significance, of history both perceived and actual to the contemporary sense of national and diaspora identity, is therefore a grounding principle of this thesis. In itself this theory is not new, although the evaluation of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry as evidence of its truth certainly is. The importance of a nation or community's sense of its past has been long acknowledged as a significant aspect of contemporary national identity (Smith, 2001), although there are variations in the interpretation of that relationship in terms of the theoretical understanding of nations and nationalism. Theorists are neither in agreement over the extent or even the existence of that relationship, and it is therefore important to consider the principal schools of thought in this field before continuing.

Discourse around the nature of nations and nationalism has a long tradition dating back over two hundred years, although it is generally accepted that the theoretical study did not begin until the twentieth century. Contributions from earlier writers such as Rousseau or Kant can be considered as more philosophical than theoretical (Özkirimli, 2010), which is not to deny their importance considering their historical context in an age of nationalist revolutions in America and France in the eighteenth century and the formation of new nations such as Germany and Italy in the nineteenth. So dramatic were the changes engendered by these events, largely coinciding as they did with major socio-economic revolutions (or rather evolutions), that in their wake it was often difficult for observers to correlate the newly formed modern nation and its historical antecedents. If the nation is a purely modern entity, formed only by a co-occurrence of modern phenomena, then can pre-modern notions of identity bear any relevance to the identity of the new nation? Thus the dating of the *nation* becomes a key battleground in the theoretical analysis of it.

Özkirimli identifies the period between the ends of the First and Second World Wars as the first real phase in which nations and nationalism became the focus for academic investigation (2010). The political landscape of the early twentieth century naturally motivated a desire in the west to understand nationalism, which was spoken of as being both ‘commonplace in the modes of thought’ of contemporary politics and, simultaneously, ‘peculiar to modern times’ (Hayes, 1931). If so it had grown deep roots in a pretty short time in historical terms. It was in this environment that the modernist approach to nations developed, with Kohn articulating the idea that nationalism was simply not possible before the emergence of the strictly modern nation (1958). The changing world of the second half of the twentieth century, which saw the breakup of empires and the emergence of new states across the world, engendered further development of the modernist theory (Özkirimli, 2010), and such was the strength of this new phase of investigation into the subject that McCrone (1998) suggests the study on truly began in the 1960s. Gellner’s work is seen as particularly influential in advancing the discussion, although as the twentieth century drew to a close the modernist approach was rightly criticised for its weakness in interpreting longer-rooted historical evolutions as a part of nationalism.

For modernists the guiding principle is ever that nations and nationalism are a purely modern phenomenon (Özkirimli, 2010). The word modern is generally accepted as meaning since the late eighteenth century. Hobsbawm (1990) takes 1780 as his starting point, and Anderson (1983) agrees in associating the birth of nations with the American Revolution, going so far as to claim nationalism as an American invention. This was a period in which Enlightenment thinking on issues such as personal rights and liberties and free market capitalism combined with increasing urbanisation and

industrialisation, increasing literacy and ever more accessible media, to provide the context for a citizen-driven approach to the state which had not existed before. It is certainly possible to argue that without many of these factors transformative events such as the French Revolution *might* not have occurred. That is not to say though that they *could* not or even *did* not. The hard-fought revolutions in mid-seventeenth century Britain occurred in a primarily agrarian population, for example.

The theory that nations and nationalism are purely modern phenomena, the cornerstone of the modernists, is a fundamental challenge to the primordialist approach which is considered to be the oldest theory of nationalism (Leith, 2006). In essence this theory takes nationalism to be an essential and natural part of our social makeup. Nations and national identities are deep-rooted in the underlying pre-historic foundations of a group, directly connected to its ethnic identity and to ties of kinship and blood. Gellner, no advocate of primordialism, sums it up in its most basic form as: ‘a man must have a nationality as he must have a nose and two ears’ (1983). The formation of nations is therefore considered a purely natural process, and one far longer in the making than modernists could accept.

Strict primordialism is now less common in the debate and some consider it to have been left behind as a serious theory (Brubaker, 1996) although though Grosby and Roshwald are cited as leading something of a resurgence (Özkirimli, 2010). Primordialism as a theory lacks the flexibility to explain peaks and troughs in nationalist sentiment, and the way in which nations such as the United States of America can be forged from groups lacking pure ethnic or territorial roots. The same can be said of England, where a sense of nation can be traced even in pre-medieval times (Hastings, 1997) with its Angles, Saxons, Norsemen and Celtic Britons. Even the invading Norman political elite bought into, and became chief advocates of, their adopted nation: too strict a tie between nation and ethnicity cannot always be borne out. Primordialism does however contribute to an understanding of the sometimes intangible emotional aspects of national identity as well as the importance of a sense of continuity and legitimacy within nations and nationalist groups (Smith, 2008).

A more engaging, if occasionally confusing, discussion on primordialism centres on whether it is the case that the nation itself is created by the pre-historic bonds of its people – whether expressed in ethnic, cultural or tribal terms – or whether nations and nationalism are engendered rather by the *belief* that this is the case (culturalist primordialism). The latter course is how Smith (1998) and others interpret the works of Geertz and Shils, although Eller and Coughlan (1993) seem to disagree in their

reading and consider them strict primordialists (Özirimli, 2010). The so-called nationalist and culturalist variants of primordialism lead to quite different potential conclusions: if the nation is primordial, then the participant is passive; if people only perceive the nation to be primordial, then the participant is proactive and responding to some sort of cultural stimulus. This latter interpretation has important overlaps with the ethno-symbolist approach which emerged in turn to challenge modernism, as does the importance which must be attached to issues of ethnicity and collective historical and cultural experience.

The modernists strongly reject the primordialist assumption that nations are rooted in distant prehistory and a part of the essence of social grouping, but beyond that modernism is a broad label incorporating a range of sub-theories. Instrumentalist modernism considers nations and nationalist groups to be founded from self-interest rather than anything so ethereal as kinship. Essentially the notion is that people band together because they find benefit in the sharing of resources, safety in numbers, and a greater chance of personal prosperity as part of a larger group than as an individual (Brown, 2000). Following this theory, the nationalist revolutions of the early modern age would be a response to the inability of large concentrations of citizens to participate in or flourish under the old order. Contemporary nationalism is interpreted in turn as a response to the inability of the modern state, in an increasingly globalising political and economic context, to represent the individual's best interests (Leith, 2006).

But to emphasise self-interest and economic factors in the formation of nations and nationality is to degrade the importance of both ethnicity and cultural belonging, whilst some cite uneven development as a problem for economic models of nationalism theory. There are examples of nationalist movements developing in areas which were not culturally or economically less developed than their neighbours, including Scotland, as well as places where nationalism has failed to develop where self-interest models might suggest it should (Orridge, 1993). Rational choice models are also badly undermined by irrational action on the part of the national groups, including those which bring about conflict or contribute to the group being highlighted as a minority with the state. Such cases are not easy to reconcile with nationalism as self-interest. Perhaps a sense of a greater belonging can override the baser motivations of self-interest.

Brass (1979) extends the self-interest theory to argue that it is elites within social groups who select and manipulate symbols of national or ethnic groupings in their own interests: in order to secure or

mobilise support for their activity or authority. National identity is therefore a tool, its symbols artificial and changeable, and accordingly cannot be an inherent attribute (Özkirimli, 2010). This view therefore accepts the potential power of identity symbols associated with the nation and the sense of belonging to it, and yet fails to provide an explanation as to why a nation or group might feel a powerful attachment to those symbols. This lack of space for the emotional aspects of nationhood is an important weakness in the self-interest theory, especially when nationalist groups can be shown on occasion to act defiantly against what might be perceived as their best economic or security interests. And if the bonds binding a national group together are consciously chosen, deliberately re-defined, and remain fluid depending on where the self-interest leads, then how does one account for the apparent constancy and durability of many national identities and movements. As Leith (2006) neatly states, identity cannot be both fixed and fluid: if elements of it are fixed, as Brown (2000) concedes they can be, then national identity cannot be based purely on self-interest.

The suggestion that the symbols of national and ethnic identity are changeable and open manipulation ties into constructivist modernism, which posits that the nation and its sense of identity are artificially constructed entities. Traditions and symbols of nationhood are considered as conscious responses to major changes in the nature of the state, especially in cases during the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries involving massively increased enfranchisement in some European states. They are used to encourage stability and legitimacy, as tools for the control and manipulation of the population as well as to create an artificial sense of continuity between the present state and that which had gone before. Hobsbawm describes this process as the use of history and tradition – invented or re-invented – to legitimise activity and bind groups together (1983). It is particularly useful for the ruling elite, who naturally encourage forms of national expression which support their position by presenting contemporary political systems as having a basis in something more ancient and therefore more legitimate or palatable. This is a theory which clearly acknowledges the power of history and its symbols but denies the authenticity of their connection to the modern nation.

This assumes that the target group – the people – is susceptible, whether through vulnerability (Brown, 2000), a need to belong (Smith, 1983), ignorance or even connivance, to manipulation by the elite. The implication must therefore be that the non-elite are either unaware of the disjoint between historical truth and the symbols of their identity, or else do not care. This is hard to accept as a guiding principle. On the contrary, attempts to cynically hijack or manipulate treasured symbols are likely to result in a backlash. Some societies, Scotland included, are very sensitive about their history (both perceived and real) and its symbols, and respond with scepticism to visible attempts to interfere with them (Leith, 2011). Admittedly that sensitivity does not make manipulation impossible – some

ceremonial aspects of British royalty that were largely re-invented in modern times are widely accepted as being centuries old – but an age of mass communication makes that increasingly difficult and re-invention is very different to invention. In this regard the modernists' association of the rise of nations and nationalism both with literate and well-informed communicative societies and simultaneously with symbols and identities which are artificially constructed by the elite seems unconvincing.

The fundamental problem with modernist approaches, however, remains that core principle which leads them to deny the existence of nations and nationhood prior to the industrialisations and urbanisations of the late eighteenth and nineteenth centuries. There is of course merit in the argument that mass communication, requiring both high levels of literacy and a common language alongside widely accessible media, played a highly significant role in the emergence of nations as we know them in the past two hundred and fifty years (Deutsch, 1966). There are also clear relationships between powerful economic factors and the political inadequacies of certain regimes with the emergence of powerfully motivated nationalist movements in examples such as Revolutionary France and interwar Germany. What is far less clear is that the conditions required for the emergence of the resulting movements could only be satisfied in the modern era, or that the nations which emerged in their wake possess only artificial connections to their predecessors if any at all.

Somewhere between the primordialists and the modernists the ethnosymbolists can be found. The term applies to those who acknowledge the importance to modern nations and national groups of long-standing historical and cultural experience. This is reflected in their attachment to, sometimes reverence for, symbols and traditions which reflect the longevity of their identity. This approach also accepts that the modern nation is directly connected to its pre-modern predecessors. Whilst the nation state may have changed in the modern era, the state may have but the building-blocks of the nation need not have. This overlaps considerably with perennialist primordialism, which does not insist that nationhood is inherent in nature but does accept that nations and national identity can be documented long before the American Revolution starting point. Examples such as medieval England have already been mentioned, as particularly advocated by Hastings (1997). In Scotland, the signatories of the Declaration of Arbroath refer to themselves as a nation in 1320, and define both themselves and England in terms of their people rather than their territory. To Hastings, England forms the prototype nation which is looked-to subsequently for reference. Importantly, and probably correctly, he sees this as an evolution not a revolution.

That the modern nation is built up through a longstanding consciousness which can be seen to stretch back centuries and beyond was a key theme of Armstrong (1982). This *longue durée* approach harks back to the instinctive human need to gather together, which Armstrong suggests occurred through negative selection, collecting together to fend off those who were different or from outside the emergent community. This inherent hostility to those who do not belong to the national group is the principal criticism of nationalism. Despite his emphasis on the *longue durée*, Armstrong seems to sympathise with elements of constructivism, contesting only that the roots of the inventions lie further back in time (1995).

That the modern state has longer roots than modernists allow is also supported by Anthony Smith, who refers to the precursor of the nation (which he accepts to be a modern entity) as an *ethnie*. All nations emerge from an *ethnie*, although clearly not all *ethnies* prove capable of creating a nation. Smith grants the *ethnie* six main characteristics which should enable it to flourish: a recognised name; a common ancestry myth; shared historical experience; a common culture which sets the community apart; a homeland; and a level of internal unity (1991). The ultimate goal is the maintenance or achievement of recognition and autonomy, political and cultural. Smith also tackles the terminology, moving the definition of *nation* out of modernist hands and into a broader space which can accommodate events beyond the modern revolutionary era: effectively it is boiled down to a sense of commonality of heritage and identity, within a framework of economic and legal oneness and a defined territory. That definition is very close to the attributes of an *ethnie*, and thus we are able to see clearly the correlation between the modern nation and its roots.

The ethnosymbolist approach facilitates an exploration of the relationship between a modern nation and its historical evolution, political and cultural, emphasising elements of continuity which explain both the emotional importance attached to national symbols and the durability of nations and nationalist sentiment. By distancing itself from strict primordialism, ethnosymbolism also permits acceptance that whilst nations might form earlier than modernists accept, they are also capable of flexibility and change according to the challenges of a particular political or cultural context (Hutchinson, 2005). The challenge this presents is that it looks ever more sensible to examine nations through the eyes of their specific evolutionary experiences: otherwise assumed correlations may disguise the reality and lead to flawed generalisations. This lends support to the suggestion that no single definitive theory of nations and nationalism can be employed to account for all cases (Ozkirimli, 2010), and whilst this might imply the study is left only with descriptive analysis there is no reason why a case-by-case approach cannot provide valuable insights for cross-referencing.

It is also often difficult to determine the realities of sentiment regarding national identity in the pre-modern era, where documentary evidence can tend to lead us to a warped understanding, or where much relies on the interpretation of historians. What may have been felt by a literate elite (those who leave us the best records) may not be representative of the population. Connor (2005) is anxious that true national consciousness must come from the masses, and their views are often difficult to pinpoint with certainty. Evidence does not of course have to be written – it can be found for example in events such as the facility of recruiting military forces for specific causes – but certainly there is a considerable need for historians and social scientists to interact. An historian does not view events in isolation but as part of a process: there are very few “big bang” moments, but rather a great many contributing factors and experiences which together. The examination of how contributing factors interplay over an evolutionary course also helps to explain why not all ethnies form into or survive as nations.

The primordialist and ethnosymbolist approaches therefore share traits in regard to the incorporation of the long view into our understanding of contemporary nations their identities and politics, but there are also important differences. A nation’s roots can indeed be centuries old, but perhaps not millennia. The longevity and durability of nation sentiments need not mean a nation’s development was an inevitable natural phenomenon, or that external factors have not driven or created aspects of it. What it does mean is that a contemporary nation should not be seen as a strictly novel entity as per the modernist, occurring only within an artificially restrictive timeframe, however tempting it might be to view a set of related revolutions as distinct from the evolutionary processes which led to them.

Nor should we inherently accept that the mass communications, economic drivers and common causes which may have triggered the birth of new nations were only possible in the modern age: pre-modern communities were often capable of communication and common cause (Hastings, 1997 highlights the role of the church in this) before the printed media, and Scotland’s literacy levels were relatively high from the sixteenth century. Economic and political factors – including a sense that an identity is being challenged or overlooked, disenfranchisement, or lack of access to opportunity or prosperity – can also play a crucial role as triggers for the resurgence of nationalist sentiment and political movements, but should not be seen either as a purely modern occurrence or as the root causes of that sentiment. A root identity is required about which the community will coalesce, expressed through the symbols, traditions and cultural heritage of the root national grouping or ethnie. Whilst

these are subject to interpretation and reinterpretation, they are nonetheless grounded in a shared historical experience and only open to manipulation within bounds.

These symbols of historical continuity within a national identity are given expression in the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry by its very nature as a visual creation. The durability of those connections between the contemporary identity and its past, and the value which is often placed upon them, is evident throughout the project as this thesis will explore in detail. The levels of authentic or constructed symbolism will also be considered. Whilst there has been considerable discussion about the role of historical myth and reality in creating a Scottish national identity (Murray and Soule, 2011), the Tapestry offers a potential insight to the types of visual symbols which appear important to members of the diaspora, whether that be individuals, institutions or structures. Whether those symbols are consistent across the diaspora or differ according to the nature of the contemporary community will be of considerable interest. First however it is worth considering the context of national identity in Scotland and its diaspora.

Scotland and Nationhood

Scotland can be both interesting and challenging as a case study for the emergence of a sense of nationhood. Reaching into history as far as a primordialist might recommend reminds us that Scotland as we know it was not formed from one single ethnic community any more than England was. As well as the native Celtic Britons there were the enigmatic Picts, and the Gaels from across the Irish Sea. In the south-east especially there were Angles from the south, and later the Norsemen came and built powerful bases of influence in the north and north-west. A Norman elite was imported across the Channel from the eleventh century, adding to the complex ethnic patchwork which covered the territorial area now known as Scotland.

Before the coming of the Romans at the end of the first century AD, the land was a network of family and tribal groups, capable of confederating to resist the invader from beyond but not of long term political unity (Keppie, 2004). Later Roman sources however, bitty as they are in their references to Scotland, give the impression of increasing cohesion and consolidation. After the Romans – whose influence on the politics certainly of southern Scotland should not be ignored – abandoned their northern frontier, tribal groupings evolved into kingdoms which came to be more or less defined by

their ethnic roots: the Brittonic kingdoms of Strathclyde in the south-west and Gododdin in the south-east, the latter falling to Anglian Northumbria; Gaelic Dalriada in the north-west, highlands and islands; the Scots kingdom of Alba; and the imprecisely defined Pictland. If these can be considered to be Smith's *ethnies*, their autonomy was not destined to last. Peaceful and warlike means alike aided their gradual coalescence, although localised linguistic and cultural identities probably survived: the Lothians maintained linguistic and cultural ties to their Anglian/English neighbours – and former occupiers – into the medieval period (Johnston, 2013). The union of the Pict and Scots kingdoms is usually attributed to Kenneth MacAlpin in the ninth century (Moffat, 2005), and Scotland emerged as the dominate name.

Emerging from such a complex ethnic and cultural background, and with a history of ever-fluid borders, it is difficult to define Scotland therefore as a territorial nation so much as one defined by people: it was ruled by the King of the Scots, not of Scotland. But considering its historical makeup it is also not possible to consider it an ethnic construct. How unified the pre-medieval kingdom was in terms of a sense of nationhood is hard to know for sure, but probably not a great deal: central government, such as it was, struggled to assert itself very far from its powerbases well into the medieval period. It does however become possible to sense a developing sense of nation emerging out of the long conflicts with England which ignited in 1296. As has already been mentioned, the leadership at least identified Scotland terminologically as a nation in the Declaration of Arbroath. Protracted conflict, especially when it brings an existential threat or requires prolonged coordinated effort, can be a powerful motivator in the formation of nations. A sense of English nationhood also strengthened during this period, heightened by simultaneous war with Scotland and France (Hastings 1997).

By the middle of the fifteenth century the chronicler Walter Bower was articulating elements of what could be considered a foundation myth for Scotland as a nation. His account of a victory by the Pictish king Hungus (Angus) II over the Northumbrians at Athelstaneford in East Lothian explains how a visit from St Andrew secured their success. Other accounts of similar date describe the appearance of St Andrew's cross in the sky above their battle lines. In recognition of this divine aid, the saint was adopted as the nation's patron and his cross as its symbol (Johnston, 2013; Marshall, 2007). Most of this is more or less absurd: dates, names, and circumstances associated with the story are all awry from the historical record. But that is not nearly as important as the fact that medieval Scots were seeking to assert the antiquity and provenance of the symbols of their identity. The Battle of Athelstaneford and the birth of the saltire should be viewed in this way, but it is an embellished past not a constructed one: an obscure border raid has been distorted into a major event, perhaps

consciously but certainly with roots in an older folk memory (in this case the name of the settlement). Today Athelstaneford churchyard boasts the Flag Heritage Centre telling the story and a monument to the birthplace of the national flag, believed to be one of the oldest.

Despite the strong case that elements of a Scottish national identity can be discerned in the medieval and post-medieval kingdom, it must also be acknowledged that there are challenges to the perception that it is indeed a nation. Even into the eighteenth century Scotland was not bound by a unified culture and language (Gaelic/Scots/English), a division which exasperated political divides during the civil wars of the seventeenth century and the Jacobite wars of the eighteenth. Although these issues are not unique to Scotland – some comparable divisions can be observed for example in medieval France – with such stark divisions as that of the Highland/Lowland cultures is it really possible to consider pre-modern Scotland as a nation? Not in terms of the modernist arguments requiring mass communication and common language. Certainly Davidson (2000) argues that there was no true collective Scottish identity prior to the mid-eighteenth century, although he seems to concede a sense of ‘national consciousness’ did. This consciousness, a self-awareness of belonging to something conceptual, is surely too important a step towards nationhood to dismiss its significance.

For much of Scotland’s pre-modern history it is possible to see elements within the Highlands as posing a considerable challenge to the integrity of the evolving nation through political and cultural resistance to central or royal authority, whilst also and perhaps paradoxically sustaining proactive loyalty to the later Stuart kings and their exiled heirs. Yet it is often Gaelic/Highland elements of Scottish culture which are presented as symbols of its identity, from Highland dress to sweeping mountain vistas, and this is certainly the case for example with the tartan tourism of the contemporary capital. Admittedly Lowland Scots is now gaining increasing attention, just as Gaelic has been much promoted: the 2011 census asked citizens if they could speak Scots, and Education Scotland’s website states that ‘Scots is definitely not slang and calling it slang demeans those who speak this unique Scottish language’ (EducationScotland.gov.uk, April 2016). So it seems that both Gaelic and Scots languages are held up as symbols of Scottish cultural heritage, and therefore as a part of its identity, despite once being evidence of a cultural division. Clearly the common language element of nationhood is not as important as the ability for communities to communicate and co-relate. Contemporary Scotland considers both to be part of a shared cultural inheritance.

So Scotland can be considered to have identified itself as a nation in pre-modern times, despite the fact that there existed cultural and linguistic divisions which would prohibit many theorists from accepting it achieved true nationhood (Davidson 2000). Symbols of that process – whether it be the flag, the languages, or a reverence for the Declaration of Arbroath (whether that be true political reverence or simply the wearing of its text upon a tee-shirt) – can still be found and are still in use today. Some of that use is, in Billig's terms, banal. Every man who wears a kilt at his wedding is not a political nationalist, but he has bought into on some level an appreciation of a cultural belonging. This clearly demonstrates a connectivity between contemporary identity and the historic evolutionary process which has shaped the nation.

Whatever the extent of Scottish nationhood by the eighteenth century, the Union of 1707 brought about the country's incorporation into a larger whole with the formation of the Great Britain. In some ways, as has been suggested, this concept is not novel in the history of Scotland and elements of regional identity had proved capable of coexisting with an emerging sense of nation. There were already considerable cultural and ethnic overlaps between people in Scotland and England, and there was also a sense amongst many that union might bring some welcome prosperity despite the loss of political autonomy (on the surface at least, supportive of an instrumentalist approach). There was of course violent opposition in some quarters, especially in the Highlands where resistance to challenges to local rights was arguably a well-established practice and which provided fertile recruiting ground for opposition movements such as Jacobitism.

Scottish identity was not obliterated by union (arguably it fared better than English identity), and it found new means of expression. The fact that the terms of union preserved Scottish legal and religious institutions is extremely important in this regard (Fry, 2006) as it fostered a strong sense of civic nationalism which was perfectly capable of coexisting with identifying oneself with the new British nation. With Britain came the Empire and all its associated opportunities for enterprising Scots. Once the political threat from the Jacobites had been removed – no easy process and one which ultimately required violence and the temporary suppression of the symbols of Gaelic/Highland identity – there was no serious challenge to Britishness but also no discernible disappearance of Scottishness. The very fact that Scottish people had access to imperial opportunity (Fry, 2001) and to a growing diaspora, may have contributed to the lack of political nationalism in Scotland during the epoch most associated with it elsewhere. The populus does not appear to have felt, on the whole, that sense of alienation from power or prosperity which helped mobilise revolutionary nationalism in their contemporaries elsewhere. In this way Scotland has been considered anomalous within the theoretical debate (Leith, 2006), a late-comer to nationalism. That can only really be justified if nationalism is

taken as a political movement seeking full autonomy for the nation at any cost. Certainly, as we have seen even just in this summary discussion, Scotland was no late-comer to a sense of identity and collective belonging, nor to its right to be autonomous if it so wished.

That many symbols of Scottishness can demonstrate deep roots reaching into a shared historical experience means that they could be carried with Scottish migrants. Even if they lay dormant for periods, their reactivation can find justification in that same shared past. This becomes important for the study of Scotland's diaspora and the symbols with which it represents its kinship to Scotland. Before exploring how this is borne out by a study of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry, however, it is first necessary to consider the conceptual frameworks within which diasporas are discussed.

Definitions of the Diaspora

The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry is a visual depiction of a wide-ranging set of stories, people and incidents from the long history of Scottish migration and overseas connections. The manner in which those stories were selected for inclusion will emerge from this study, which will also consider how representative they can be considered in relation to the overall historical narrative of the Scottish Diaspora. The broader question of what might actually constitute a *diaspora*, in both historical and sociological terms, has been explored in some detail and is worthy of consideration before exploring in depth a tapestry which purports to represent one.

Etymologically, a diaspora is a scattering or dispersal. Thus it can be taken simply to mean migration or more particularly migration from a central point to several locations. The word became associated with forced dispersal after it became commonly associated with the expulsion of the Jews from Palestine (Adamson 2008; Devine 2012). The identification of diaspora with forcible migration is, as Devine correctly identifies at the outset of his *To the Ends of the Earth*, unfortunate in its relation to the Scottish experience as it risks reinforcing a common misunderstanding that hostile coercive forces were responsible for its migrations (2012). It is important therefore to recognise that the term has broadened in its usage and definition beyond that.

Safran (1991) presented an important list of characteristics which ought to be present of a true diaspora:

- i. migration from a common place of origin to more than one destination
- ii. a shared memory of the original home nation
- iii. a sense of outside-ness in the host nation
- iv. idealisation of the homeland
- v. belief in the integrity (or need for) the homeland
- vi. continuing connections to the homeland.

It is possible to detect a broad consensus in support of some of these attributes – especially the first – although there is a sense in Safran’s list that being a part of a diaspora is primarily about dislocation rather than relocation, and that longing for the homeland should effectively dominate the definition. Cohen (1996) suggests more positive angles should be emphasised, an approach which helps to provide an explanation for the durability of some diasporic identities. Certainly there ought to be a relationship on some level with the homeland or the collective memory of one, and according to Butler (2001) also a relationship between diaspora groups in different areas. In other words, there must be a self-aware diaspora identity: a diaspora must actively consider itself to be a diaspora.

The broadening of the definition of diaspora permits further breakdowns to be posited, and Cohen (2008) attempted to delineate between the principal types of diaspora: victim; labour; imperial; trade; and hybrid/de-territorial. The first, victim, harks back to that earlier definition associated with enforced migration, whether through conflict, persecution or economic factors. A labour diaspora is caused by the large-scale movement of a people to create workforces outside of their homeland, whilst an imperial diaspora is created when the soldiers or administrators of an imperial power set down roots in the empire’s territories. Trade diaspora involves migration for professional opportunity or as part of a trading network (not to be confused with the labour diaspora, which carries more negative connotations and potentially very different social compositions). The final category includes those who share a culture or identity (such as religious groups) but not necessarily a territorial homeland.

In terms of the Scottish experience, it is possible to evidence cases of three if not four of Cohen’s categories (Leith and Sim, 2014 suggest three). Those driven overseas by the more aggressive phases of Highland Clearance could constitute a victim diaspora, as could the periodic waves of political or

religious exiles and refugees, including the Jacobites of the early-mid eighteenth century. At roughly the same points in history however their countrymen are found playing prominent roles in the creation and operation of the British Empire (imperial diaspora) and making fortunes from the development of Hong Kong (trade diaspora). It is possible also to see aspects of a labour diaspora: unforced in the Australian gold rushes of the nineteenth century or the shepherds of Patagonia; forced in cases such as the shipment of Cromwellian prisoners of war to work as slaves in the colonies. Sometimes these categories can be fulfilled simultaneously by different groups of migrant Scots in different locations, whilst it is also possible to see shifting patterns and changes in the overall nature of Scotland's diaspora experience. That this is true is evidenced clearly by the tapestry, as will be explored further in the third chapter of this thesis. It does not necessarily devalue the categorisations offered by Cohen, but it does warn us against applying too simplistic a label to a diaspora – especially one created over such a long period as that of Scotland.

Time is not only a factor in understanding the creation of a diaspora, but also its sense of identity following its establishment. Butler (2001) argues that a diaspora must exist across several generations, a definition which would exclude first-generation “ex-pat” communities for example, and perhaps even some cases of imperial or trade diasporas in which lasting roots are not established by the original founders.

This perfectly reasonable suggestion does in fact raise an important issue: that of ‘legacy’ or ‘memory’ diaspora. Time might have led to the assimilation of the migrants or to their moving on, processes exemplified by the Scots merchant communities in late medieval Poland or Holland respectively (Dobson, 2000; Blom, 2003). The result is that there may no longer be a self-asserting or readily identifiable diaspora population, but still a sense of trans-cultural or trans-national connectivity. The definitions discussed above do not allow for considering the importance of these transient diasporas which might nonetheless have made important contributions to the host nation's heritage and which still form part of the identity of the broader diaspora community. This idea of a memorial diaspora – defined not by living ancestrally-linked communities but by the memory or influence of past ones – will be considered within this thesis. In this regard it should be expected then that there may be stories represented within the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry which fall short of the accepted academic definitions of diaspora. The suggestion here however is that they remain an important part of the whole, and have a resonance still in the sense of identity within the community.

The evolution of diasporic identities over time has also been widely discussed, with Radhakrishnan (2003) identifying three distinct stages in the usual process: in the immediate environment of migration, there is a suppression of overt identification with the homeland; a reassertion of homeland identity occurs in the second phase, which could be generations later; and finally this leads to the adoption of 'hyphenated' or hybrid identities, such as Scots-Americans. This recognises not only the fluidity of identities but also the influence of personal choice (Nagel, 1994), which in the context of nationalism theory poses problems for some key approaches: assimilation and hyphenation are both out of sync with the predetermined paths implied by primordialism, whilst the opting-in to ancestral identities outside of the modern host nation is a challenge to modernists, especially in cases where the attachment can be considered emotional rather than rational. Choosing to maintain a diaspora identity can both bracket the individual as belonging to a minority group whilst at the same time connecting them to a far larger external community (Burrell and Anderson, 2008).

This leads us to wondering the extent to which the reasserted identities referred to in Radhakrishnan's model can be considered as authentically rooted in a true identity rather than constructed artificially, consciously or otherwise. Hall (1990) reflects on constantly evolving diaspora identities which maintain a distant integrity but are subject to transformation over the generations, just as nations and national identities develop from an evolutionary process affected by external factors. The Scottish diaspora's maintenance of an assertive Scottishness is not always consistent in its strength of longevity, but in key areas (especially in the New World) it has proven both resilient and vibrant to the extent that perhaps ten times the current population of Scotland can identify with its diaspora (MacAskill and McLeish, 2006; Leith and Sim, 2014). But is their identity, whether reverently preserved or consciously reasserted, connected to a real or imagined sense of Scotland? Safran (1999) questions the validity of a diaspora which voluntarily maintains its distance from the homeland, but that is to overlook the emotional importance of the symbols of and belonging to an identity, however distant the reality might be. The homeland connection can often be more about longing to belong than yearning to return, and in that sense it does not strictly matter if the perception of the homeland is different to the reality. This may not be the case of course in strictly victim diasporas, especially where the homeland itself is under threat or perhaps even no longer extant. Perceived victim phases in Scottish diaspora history can still be emotive, hence Devine's anxiety about the forced-migration definition cited above, but it is not dominant in the identity's expression as this study will show. Likewise, the suggestion that a diaspora community dislocated from the homeland by both time and geography must find its identity to be rooted in an artificial or misguided perception of the homeland will not be borne out.

On a less theoretical and more practical level, and picking up on lessons from Ireland's analyses of its diaspora (Ancien, Boyle and Kitchin, 2009), the Scottish Government identifies six forms of diaspora: Reverse, Returning, New, Lived, Ancestral and Affinity (2009; 2010b). The first is distinct from the others as representing immigrant communities now living within Scotland. Returning diaspora is the community within Scotland of Scots who have returned from a period of living overseas. New Diaspora Scots are those who are *about* to leave, and are therefore targeted in relation to both the messages they will transmit within their new host countries and how they will continue to engage with and contribute to the homeland after departure. Once settled overseas these migrants join the Lived Diaspora, those who have lived in Scotland but now live, work or study overseas. They might otherwise be considered as ex-pats, although also included in this category are those from other countries who have temporarily lived in Scotland before returning elsewhere. The Lived Diaspora carries memories of contemporary Scotland and members likely maintain direct relationships within the homeland, making them useful ambassadors to a government concerned with overseas reputational messaging (2010b). The descendants of the Lived Diaspora, should they remain outside Scotland, become the Ancestral Diaspora. This is perhaps the most readily recognised form, those who have historic connections to Scotland through their families, and who form a valuable tourism market for the homeland (Visit Scotland, 2013). Affinity diaspora members are identified loosely as those with a 'direct or indirect connection', by which a purely cultural rather than ancestral connection is normally meant (Rutherford, 2009). Members of the affinity diaspora engage through choice rather than genealogical happenstance, drawn by sometimes intangible attractions and a sense of a global Scottish cultural identity (Hesse, 2014). All of these forms of diaspora are reflected in the tapestry's content with the possible exception of the so-called New Diaspora, which is by its very nature difficult to identify and engage until it becomes a Lived Diaspora.

It is evident that Scotland's diaspora fits within the broader forms of the term's academic definition, fulfilling the requirements for multiple migratory destinations, a shared consciousness of diaspora identity, and a continuing link to the homeland both in real terms and cultural. It can also be considered to belong, at various stages in its long life, to fulfil elements of victim, trade, imperial and perhaps labour diaspora types. The impact on and awareness of Scottish participation in host countries has been considerable, and it is possible to detect this even in places where thorough assimilation has occurred or the Scottish population otherwise displaced. This has been termed legacy diaspora, and will be considered more fully as a concept in subsequent chapters. The stories contained within the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry reveal the breadth and variety of Scotland's diaspora experience and its significance, and provides a clear indication as to what features of it are most cherished by its contemporary population. Before exploring it in depth however it is sensible to establish some of the literature which informs the historical discussion of the diaspora.

Scotland's Diaspora

The sheer scale of the tapestry means that it is able to cover a considerable amount of historical information from a wide range of countries, communities and individuals. Whilst it is not possible therefore to summarise all the works which might relate to its contents, a brief introduction to the key focus areas is worthwhile. The history of this migration of Scots men and women, its scale and impacts, trends and transformations, has been the subject of considerable and ongoing academic investigation and debate. Post-devolution Scotland has encouraged fresh exploration of how homeland and diaspora interact (Leith and Sim 2014), and how harnessing or developing that relationship might yield direct benefits to Scotland (Ancien, Boyle and Kitchin 2009).

In this context there has been much work done to examine the historical nature of the diaspora and its significance. Devine's *To the Ends of the Earth*, a popular and wide-ranging analysis of the evolutions and economic impacts of Scottish migration from 1750 to the present day, is set to become the starting point for many introductions to the subject (2011), and whilst its scope is vast it does perhaps suffer from a feeling of impersonality. Buelmann, Hinson and Morton (2014) cover the same extensive time period with matching global coverage, but take a thematic approach which combines elements of both historical and contemporary sociological observation. This creates a convenient complement to the strictly historical approach.

Both these works choose the mid-eighteenth century as their starting point, finding like the modernists a clear division between the types of migratory activity which had occurred before the modern age and the larger scale and better documented phases which happened alongside the development of nations as we know them today. It is also an approach which encourages correlation of the diaspora experience and the British Empire, which has been deeply explored on both national and empire-wide levels by the likes of MacKenzie and Devine (2011) and Fry (2001, 2014). The categorisation of periods of Scotland's diaspora as imperial has already been acknowledged above, and it so it need not

be surprising to note that the timelines for transformative phases of nation and nationalism development are temporally connected to imperial expansion, and that some of the best known macro-studies of the diaspora take the second half of the eighteenth century as their starting point.

This timeframe does however reduce the profile of diasporic connections between Scotland and the rest of the medieval, renaissance and baroque worlds. The historical data from these earlier phases can be sparse or of inconsistent quality, but there are clearly significant periods of Scottish overseas activity and migration which form an important part of the wider picture. This modern focus also skews the geographical reading of the diaspora, particularly in its marginalisation of connectivity with other European states. The focus is instead drawn towards those regions most commonly identified as migratory destinations for Scots of the eighteenth century onwards: first North America and later Australasia. Those earlier phases of Old World Scottish diaspora experience are culturally and economically significant, facilitating the movement of trade and ideas as well as people. They have left significant if sometimes relatively low-profile legacies and it would be negligent to allow later phases to totally overshadow them whilst a consciousness still remains (the legacy diaspora), as evidenced by their inclusion in the tapestry.

Although these early phases of diaspora activity appear side-lined in some of the macro-view analyses, they are not neglected by more focused study. Most commonly the focus is on relations with a particular country, as exemplified by Devine and Hess (2011) on Scots migration to Poland from the 1500s as well as Polish migration to Scotland in more recent times, and Fenwick (1971) on the centuries-long Auld Alliance with France. The former example makes an important point about the reciprocity of some inter-national migratory relationships: just as migrant Scots have impacted on their hosts, reverse diaspora movements have impacted upon Scotland and its culture. This is borne out in several places within the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry, as will be seen.

Explorations of the pre-modern Scottish diaspora are not solely confined to country-by-country analysis. There are also thematic treatments, ranging from the nineteenth century but still occasionally useful *The Scottish Soldier of Fortune* (Grant, 1889) to more recent assessments. Miller (2007) has brought a more modern insight into areas of the same subject as Grant, shedding light on the extraordinary and disproportionate scales of Scottish mercenary service in northern and eastern Europe, especially during the Thirty Years War. Men such as Patrick Gordon (1635-1699) not only

rose to prominent military positions in their host countries, but made important cultural contributions too: Gordon secured permission to build the first Roman Catholic church in Russia.

That the pre-modern chapters in the Scottish diaspora story can be considered to be less commonly explored than the later phases, is most likely due to the fact that the Scottish migrant populations in places such as the Netherlands, Poland or Germany historically proved either to be temporary in nature or became fully assimilated. Their legacy is less visible and vocal than is the case in, for example, Canada or the USA and their modern era migrations. The surviving echoes of the legacy diaspora can still be detected however, and are successfully articulated by Kay (2011). This work was clearly influential in the early phases of the tapestry's creation, partly for this reason (as revealed in the bibliography section of Scottishdiasporatapestry.org, accessed July 2015). A journalistic rather than academic approach can engender a more human feeling within an analysis, something which is inevitably important to a project like the tapestry. The built heritage of a diaspora community can also act as a pointer to important historical connections, and if a community can be seen to value those physical markers and what they might represent, then that legacy should still be taken into account. Examples from the pre-modern diaspora might include Veere's *Scots House* museum in the Netherlands, once home to a large Scottish merchant community, or the Scottish museum in the tiny village of Gurro in northern Italy. The legacy diaspora is not confined purely to the pre-modern: examples can also be found from the imperial phase.

There have been efforts recently to restore some geographical balance at least to an understanding of the diaspora. As contemporary political debate brings Scotland's relationship the European Union under the spotlight there is an opportunity for deeper exploration of the diaspora in Europe (Ichijo, 2004). Leith and Sim (2014) acknowledge that Scots in Europe remain a neglected aspect of diaspora studies, and they offer an investigation into contemporary phases of migration to Europe. There does not however seem to have been a discernible push for new investigation into the European pre-modern diaspora.

The global or macro-approach to the diaspora is supported by country-level studies for the modern and contemporary phases of migration as well, both historical to the sociological. The two disciplines are exemplified by the differences in approach between Calder (2006) and Sim (2011) in discussing the Scots in America. The diaspora in South Africa has received some attention (MacKenzie and Dalziel, 2012), as of course have the Scots in Australasia (Prentis, 2008; Harper, 2010; Cowan and

Henderson, 2014). Closer to home, the Scots in England have received less attention it seems than those who travelled further afield. This is perhaps in part because, apart from certain localised concentrations such as Merseyside or Corby, cultural and matrimonial assimilation often occurs so naturally within modern Britain, with roots so longstanding, that patterns are virtually invisible. There are however studies available investigating the experience of Scots in England from as far apart in timeframe as the fifteenth century (Thomson, 2000) and the Scots in Merseyside from the nineteenth century (Munro and Sim, 2001).

The broad historical narrative of the Scottish diaspora's creation and evolution, and within that the experiences of individual countries and regions, has clearly been well explored by historians as well as social scientists. Inevitably however, when considering the diaspora even on a national rather than global level, more localised and even personal stories often get lost. At the same time, a growth in the recognition of ancestral tourism accepts the potential value of facilitating personal relationships between the diaspora and the homeland: in 2012 research by tourism body Visit Scotland identified a market potential worth of £2.4 billion over five years (Visit Scotland Insight Department, 2013). Understanding and promoting the personal and local level diaspora is clearly just as important as appreciating the bigger historical trends.

The tapestry therefore fulfils an important function, and is different to many representations of the diaspora in featuring both macro and micro level content and gives an equal platform to both. Some stories relate the experiences of individual people or families, and are given weight regardless of whether they belong to a global trend. That is largely down to the content being primarily driven not by academic researchers but by individuals, groups and communities within the diaspora. This aspect of the tapestry will be explored particularly in chapters three and five. It creates an important difference in orientation to most published material, and is one of the keys to the tapestry's potential to reveal insights into how those within the diaspora perceive themselves and their connections to Scotland. With this tapestry the diaspora had an unprecedented opportunity to communicate its history and identity to a world beyond its internal audience, and the results are remarkable.

Chapter Three:

The *Scottish Diaspora Tapestry* project

“To enable Scottish tales to be told by those who are proud to be their custodians”

Gordon Prestounrange, Prestonpans, Scotland

Introduction

This chapter analyses the *Scottish Diaspora Tapestry* as an arts project, examining its conception and development, the roles of individuals and agencies in its creation, the methods by which it was brought together, and its reception in both the 2014 Year of Homecoming and in the subsequent exhibition tours. The information considered here is essential to the discussions which follow about curatorship of the information and authorship of the content and visual presentation, which in turn inform our understanding of the tapestry’s contribution to our understanding of Scottish diaspora identity.

In particular this chapter will seek to establish the dynamics which led up to and subsequently oversaw the tapestry project, both internally in terms of the core team and externally in regard to their relationship with the funding bodies and tourism agencies which were involved in facilitating the tapestry. The project was conceived and coordinated by a small independent charity but it was successful in attracting funding support from several public sources in Scotland and in mobilising considerable amounts of volunteer labour for its creation. In order to properly understand and interpret its authorial voice – the reality of whose perceptions of the diaspora we are in fact examining - the interplay between the various individuals and agencies involved in the tapestry’s creation must be evaluated. This must be done in the context of the project’s intended purposes and the associated expectations of those involved in its creation, as well as of the balance of power between sponsoring agencies and the coordinating charity.

It will be shown that whilst the overall direction of the project was determined by a small team based in Prestonpans, who maintained the ability to act as gatekeepers to the incoming content and contributions, they were nevertheless reliant on information and support from a wide and largely

un-curated range of sources from across the diaspora. To a considerable extent this was deliberate policy to ensure the content reflected grass-roots input, but it was also difficult to avoidable this reliance given the nature of the processes which had been established. There was continuing engagement between the project team and its funders throughout the formative phases of the project, and there is evidence of occasionally differing methodological preferences between the two which will be considered in more detail in section three. These related primarily to promotional strategy, but also in the approach to evaluating the project's success and longer-term potential. There is also evidence to suggest that there existed a latent potential for external partners, especially the Scottish tourism agency Visit Scotland, to directly influence the content of the tapestry during early phases of its development. This authorial influence was however limited in both its scope and effects and did not manifest itself as an intent or desire to exert curatorial control, as will be shown.

Discussion of these issues leads into consideration of the means by which the countries represented in the tapestry were selected, establishing an important understanding ahead of the analysis in chapter five. It will be shown that a small number of countries had to be dropped from the initial lists whilst others were subsequently added, and that the initial scale of the project was surpassed both in terms of the numbers of panels created and the number of countries and communities covered. This in turn necessitated an evolution of the exhibition design away from the team's original intentions.

The way those exhibitions were received during the first public displays of the tapestry will then be appraised with the support of the available evidence and feedback, including the results of passive observational study of exhibition behaviour (Webb et al, 1966). Consideration of the tapestry's reception is important in informing our understanding of its potential to generate a lasting legacy rather than it winding down as a large but essentially temporary community engagement project. It therefore lays the foundations for subsequent discussion in chapter seven. Comparison will be made between the Scottish and overseas exhibition tours of 2014-2016, particularly in terms of how the exhibitions were chosen and hosted. It will thus be shown that the overseas tours should be considered as extensions of the main project itself; in so much as they are further evidence of the same sense of diasporic identity that motivated participation in the tapestry.

Instigation and early development

The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry was not the first large-scale embroidered community arts project to be undertaken in Scotland; it was the third. The immediate inspiration for it was the *Prestonpans Tapestry* or to give its full title, the *Battle of Prestonpans Tapestry*, which was completed in 2010 after an eighteen-month project (Crummy et al, 2010). This tapestry tells the story of the military campaign which led up to the Battle of Prestonpans in September 1745, and it was stitched by over 200 volunteer embroiderers. The project originated in Prestonpans, a small town on Scotland's south-east coast situated around ten miles from Edinburgh which has been the scene of a number of community art projects over the last decade or more, including murals trails and arts festivals (Unwin, 2017). These, along with ongoing efforts to promote the town's famous Jacobite battlefield, were conceived as initiatives to boost community identity and self-confidence in a post-industrial era: a use of heritage to reinvigorate a sense of place (Johnston and Prestoungrange, 2013). Dr Gordon Prestoungrange, who had purchased the feudal barony of Prestoungrange on the western edge of Prestonpans, was a prime mover in these initiatives and illustrator Andrew Crummy was heavily involved in their implementation. Out of this process were formed both the Prestoungrange Arts Festival and the Battle of Prestonpans (1745) Heritage Trust charities, and the Prestonpans Tapestry was a collaboration between the two.

The Prestonpans Tapestry is a continuous narrative embroidery, with 104 illustrative panels designed by Crummy and stitched by volunteers recruited from across Scotland. Many came from the communities which their panel depicted or had personal connections to that part of the story (Crummy et al, 2010). The content was overseen by Prestoungrange, and two historians were deployed as historical advisors as to the narrative detail. However, as was observed by this researcher at the time, additional content was regularly added as new volunteer stitchers came forward with further suggestions, whilst all such participants were encouraged to add minor personal touches. The project was therefore more than just an historical narrative: it was about connecting a contemporary audience to its heritage and encouraging participant ownership of the completed project, as is appropriate for community arts projects (Crehan, 2013). The Prestonpans Tapestry has been exhibited regularly since its completion in 2010, including in the Bayeux Tapestry museum in France, and at the Scottish Parliament in Edinburgh in 2017. Although the vast majority of the volunteer stitchers were found in Scotland, there were several participants who contributed from overseas: including in France and the United States of America (Crummy et al, 2010).

The power of the Prestonpans Tapestry in engaging audiences was the inspiration for the creation of the *Great Tapestry of Scotland* (Mansfield and Moffat, 2013: 18). The noted author Alexander MacCall-Smith conceived the project after visiting the Prestonpans Tapestry in Edinburgh and observing the visitor response, and Andrew Crummy was soon after commissioned to design a new tapestry which used large individual panels to illustrate discrete sections of Scottish history from the Ice Age to the present day. The historical content was primarily determined by the historian Alasdair Moffat, and there was a stitch coordinator who was determined that, ‘community project or not, the quality of the stitching would be higher,’ (Mansfield and Moffat, 2013: 23). A considerable number of those who had helped to stitch the Prestonpans Tapestry also worked on the Great Tapestry, and Crummy ensured that although the design was primarily his own and Wilkie ensured the stitching standards were controlled, there was still scope for personal touches from the embroiderers (Moffat, 2013). It was launched at the Scottish Parliament in 2013. By this time the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry project was already underway, back in Prestonpans where this sudden renaissance of narrative embroidery had begun.

The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry was conceived out of discussions in Prestonpans as to how the lessons and potential of the original tapestry might be harnessed, discussions which at least partly overlapped with the Great Tapestry of Scotland’s aims. For the Prestonpans-based team a focus of opportunity was presented Scottish tourism agency Visit Scotland announced that 2014 would be designated as an official Year of Homecoming. The first such year had been held in 2009, the intention being to capitalise on overseas interest in Scotland especially amongst diaspora Scots, who were encouraged to travel to Scotland in order to visit the land of their forebears. It reflected the Scottish Government’s ‘desire to engage and mobilise the Scottish Diaspora by motivating them to reconnect with Scotland,’ (Scottish Government, 2010a). There was an emphasis on ancestral tourism initiatives and the concept of a return to the ancestral homeland, and funding packages were available for events which tied into these themes. The Battle of Prestonpans (1745) Heritage Trust received funds to hold an exhibition on the role of specific Highland clans in the battle, for example, which might be of interest to visitors interested in identifying with their ancestral clans (The Prince’s Loyal Clans, 2009). For Homecoming 2014 however, Dr Prestoungrange proposed a more ambitious project which he felt should, as he has expressed it several times in conversation, ‘turn the concept of Homecoming on its head,’ by focussing not on what diaspora Scots were missing by being away from the homeland, but rather on what they and their ancestors had/have experienced and achieved since their migration from Scotland.

The formal alignment of the project with Homecoming 2014 was facilitated by the expectation that, after contributing so much in terms of research and/or stitching hours, many of those in the diaspora

who had been involved in the tapestry's creation would then wish to visit Scotland in order to see it exhibited. This would provide a core pre-engaged audience for the first season of exhibitions. A larger audience would be found amongst the diaspora and affinity Scots who would be visiting Scotland during the Year of Homecoming and would be drawn to the tapestry by the relatability of its content to their own heritage and experiences. The potential economic as well as cultural benefits of the tapestry and the resulting exhibitions therefore made the project compatible with the Scottish Government's Diaspora Engagement Plan (2010b) and endeared it to government funding sources. The potential benefits of establishing contacts around the world and engaging them directly with Scotland as part of Homecoming preparations also presented merit, and early fundraising enquiries were sufficiently encouraging for the Prestoungrange Arts Festival (a registered Scottish charity) to press ahead with the project. By the time the coordinating team met for their first official meeting on 12 June 2012, the first pilot panels had already been stitched and the first grant had been agreed from *Creative Scotland*, the Scottish Government's creative arts agency (Strategy Group Minutes 01/12).

The project team in Prestonpans initially comprised Andrew Crummy as the artist-designer, Kristine Cunningham as public relations officer, Gillian Hart and Yvonne Murphy as diaspora liaisons and stitching coordinators, Arran Johnston (author of this paper) responsible for 'digital archive research', and Gordon Prestoungrange as chair with responsibility for financial and contractual matters (Strategy Group Minutes 01/12). Cunningham left the project for personal reasons in April 2013 (Strategy Group Minutes 05/13), and her responsibilities were devolved across the remaining team members. A year later Sharon Beck was added to the team, supporting the coordination of the exhibitions (Strategy Group Minutes 11/14). Crummy and Hart had been involved with both the Prestonpans Tapestry and the Great Tapestry of Scotland; Prestoungrange, Johnston and Cunningham had been on the Prestonpans Tapestry team; only Beck had no previous involvement with other comparable projects. The team was therefore experienced in administering such a project, at least on a national if not international scale. And whilst the experiences of the pioneering Prestonpans Tapestry had required a degree of on-the-job learning (Mansfield and Moffat, 2013), much had been learned since.

The first pilot panels were designed in conjunction with pre-existing contacts in Gothenburg, Sweden, and Barga, Italy (see Fig. 3-1). The latter is the twin town of Prestonpans, Cockenzie and Port Seton, and artistic exchanges were already well established between these communities. This connection is largely the result of artist John Bellany's migration to Barga (shown in panel IT06). Barga also claims to be the 'most Scottish town in Italy', although much of the migration traffic has been towards Scotland rather than away from it (Scotsman, 2016); several of the panel designs are therefore

reflective of a reverse diaspora relationship, focussed primarily on the twentieth century (panels IT01-05; IT07).

Fig. 3-1. Panels SE06 and IT01, two of the first panels stitched. The different stitching styles of the Swedish and Italian embroiderers create variety even as the single design hand provides consistency. The two histories being told are also very different: William Gibson of Arbroath's foundation of an important modern industrial village at Jonsered near Gothenburg; and the reverse diaspora story of plaster statue makers from Barga migrating to Scotland.

In contrast, the Gothenburg connection to Prestonpans originates in the public house in Prestonpans which is named after the Swedish city. It was established in the early twentieth century on the so-called Gothenburg Principles, by which profits above a certain percentage were to be reinvested directly into the community (Allan et al, 2006). Today the pub, restored and re-opened by Gordon Prestounrange, serves as an arts hub which provides offices and support space for community groups, including the tapestry project. It boasts a Lord Mayor's Bar named in honour of the first of several visits by the then Lord Mayor of Gothenburg, and these links were eventually stitched into panel SE10. The historic connections between Scotland and Gothenburg are however somewhat older than the Principles, reaching back to the very foundation of Gothenburg in the seventeenth century (as depicted in panel SE02). With these existing contemporary and historic links, Barga and Gothenburg were the obvious choices for pilot communities for the tapestry project, drawing on established links and contact networks with overseas communities, and representing histories which were already familiar to the project team.

Content redacted due to unpublished work without informed consent for publication. Further details can be obtained from the author.

Fig. 3-2. Dr Gordon Prestoungrange explaining the concept of the tapestry project at the official launch event at the Scottish Storytelling Centre in Edinburgh, 28 June 2012.

The first pilot panels had arrived in time to be displayed at the project's official media launch on 28 June 2012, which was held at the Scottish Storytelling Centre in Edinburgh (Fig. 3-2). Among the guests at the event were representatives of the bodies which were providing funding for the project (as detailed in the next section of this chapter); Professor Petra Wend, principal and vice-chancellor of Queen Margaret University in East Lothian; Dr Murray Leith and Dr Duncan Sim from the University of the West of Scotland; along with members of the national press and other parties with diaspora interests. The writer and journalist Billy Kay was also present, a visible statement of the importance of his book *The Scottish World* (2008) in the early days of the project, when it proved 'inspirational' to the team (Scottish Diaspora Tapestry news archive, 28/11/12). The significance of Kay's work to the project will be considered more fully in chapter five, but his journalistic rather than statistical approach to presenting the diversity of the diaspora clearly held considerable appeal as a starting point for investigating possible leads.

By the time of the launch in Edinburgh the twenty-five countries which would be represented on the tapestry had been selected. It was envisaged that there would be at least one representative community for each country, around which sets of panels would be created. The original layout of the project's website, which is no longer visible as it has since evolved, was designed to reflect this by guiding the visitor from an overall listing to a country page⁶⁰, where text summarised the general history of the diasporic relationship to Scotland, and from there to a community page exploring a specific town or

location's connection to Scotland, and thence on to the panels which narrated that history in more detail (Fig 3-3). This approach would later evolve as the uptake increased and the narratives being submitted fitted less neatly into specific localised groupings. As the project began to gain momentum after the June 2012 launch event, it was agreed that bimonthly strategy group meetings and fortnightly operations meetings would be held (Strategy Group Minutes 01/12) to oversee its development. By the end of the summer the team was undertaking its initial field visits in England and Canada. India, China, Australia, the Netherlands and Lithuania would all receive personal visits from team members as the project's reach extended, searching for stories and mobilising volunteers.

Fig. 3-3. Screenshot of the original design of a “community” page from the project website, reflecting the emphasis on presenting the diaspora in terms of representative community rather than attempting full coverage of the country-by-country diaspora narratives. Taken June 2012 (note that only panel 1 has been stitched, and the other links are shown as design drawings).

Funding and expectations

The project's initial funding was granted by the *Baron Courts of Prestoungrange and Dolphinstoun*, a local charitable body administered by Gordon Prestoungrange himself. This facilitated the initial pilot panels but alone could not provide adequate resourcing for the scale of project which was envisaged: major funding commitments from outside the local team in Prestonpan were required for the tapestry to grow beyond Barga and Gothenburg. In due course grants were received from Creative Scotland, the Scottish Government (via the International Division of the Culture, External Affairs and Constitution Directorate), and Event Scotland (the coordinating agency for Homecoming 2014), as

well as from *Bòrd na Gàidhlig* for Gaelic translation work, from the Glasgow Commonwealth Games Legacy Fund (for an event in Prestonpans in 2014 connecting specifically with Commonwealth narratives), and from the Scottish Book Trust for two specific events involving Billy Kay in November 2012 (Scottish Diaspora Tapestry news archive, 28/11/12).

The extent of the funding support through the Scottish Government (£60,000) and its agencies reveals a level of confidence in the project and awareness of its potential value. The Scottish Government is actively aware of the significance of the diaspora as a source of tourism and business investment, an awareness which led to the creation of a Diaspora Engagement Plan in 2010 (Scottish Government, 2010b). Subsequent research by Visit Scotland measured the ancestral tourism market in Scotland – the economic impact of those travelling to the country specifically because of genealogical connections – at £101 million in 2012, with a potential of around £2.4 billion over the following five years if the full diaspora market potential was engaged (Visit Scotland Insight Department, 2013). The possible lessons to be learned from Ireland’s relationship with its diaspora have also been studied on behalf of the Scottish Government, and the importance of cultural elements in diaspora identity and connectivity with the homeland has been highlighted (Ancien, Boyle and Kitchin, 2009). A report into events which specifically targeted diaspora audiences in the Year of Homecoming 2009 also identified a need to encourage awareness of the diaspora and its global influence within Scotland itself, particularly in regard to the cultural traditions and celebrated heritage of diaspora Scots. The same report emphasised the need for the relationship between diaspora and homeland to be two-way, with decentralised initiatives which were able to emerge and flourish at a local level (Scottish Government, 2010a).

The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry project provided an opportunity for the Scottish Government to further connect with that potentially significant diaspora market, producing not only tangible events and exhibitions to encourage tourism in the short term but also lasting vehicle – the tapestry itself – for continuing awareness and engagement in the longer term. It also created opportunities to further inform domestic Scottish audiences as to the global impact of Scottish migrants, a need identified by the Scottish Government through feedback after the first Homecoming year (2010a), and as a community-based arts project the tapestry would operate on a desirably local level which, although supported with central funding, was visibly free from central control. This potential was reflected in the Scottish Government’s decision to provide the project with £102,500 in funding between 2012 and 2014, along with a grant of £44,000 from Homecoming 2014 towards international promotion and the Scottish exhibitions of that year, and a further £80,000 from Creative Scotland (figures obtained from unpublished official evaluation forms).

Diaspora-related activities fall in Scotland within the brief of the Cabinet Secretary for Culture, Tourism and External Affairs. Portfolio-holder Fiona Hyslop MSP visited the tapestry twice whilst it was in progress in June and December 2013, as well as addressing the opening of the Edinburgh exhibition in August 2014 and visiting the exhibition in Paris in 2015 (Hyslop, 2015). Minister for External Affairs Hamza Yousaf MSP attended the premiere exhibition of the tapestry at Prestonpans Community Centre in May 2014 (Scottish Diaspora Tapestry news archive, 03/06/14). In addition to the grant aid provided by the Scottish Government, this level of public and visible ministerial support over at least three years represents a considerable and reasoned investment in a single project, clearly indicative of a belief in important potential of the tapestry project.

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Fig. 3-4. *Fiona Hyslop MSP (seated right) with Andrew Crummy (seated left) and some of the volunteer stitchers from Scotland, viewing panels in various stages of completion. Taken at the artist's Cockenzie studio in December 2013.*

How the Scottish Government and other agencies which supported the project thought that potential might be realised can be discerned in the detail of their grant offers, and their engagement with the project team during the development phase. The grant letter offering an initial £60,000 from the Scottish Government in March 2012, for example, details several important conditions. This funding was to be used for the hosting and development of the website – a sensible acknowledgement that the information technology is critical for global engagement (Scottish Government, 2010a; Brinkerhoff, 2009) – and for field visits to four locations. But some of the conditions attached to the funding related to the broader process of creating the tapestry, beyond the remit of the actual funds being released. The letter required that the tapestry ‘should include Scottish Government priority countries, China, India, Pakistan, USA and Canada’ (Scottish Government to Prestoungrange Arts Festival, 6

March 2012). It goes on to require that ‘connections should be made between Diaspora communities in Scotland and their home countries, as well as between overseas communities and Scotland,’ and that ‘stories should reflect contemporary as well as historic elements.’ In addition, the government was to be informed of any possible public relations opportunities associated with the project (Scottish Government to Prestoungrange Arts Festival, 6 March 2012).

These conditions reflect the Scottish Government’s interest in supporting the creation of bilateral networks between countries and communities, as recommended in their report on the 2009 diaspora events (2010a), but with particular notice paid to the reverse diaspora groups (migrants *to* Scotland, rather than *from* it). This reverse diaspora interest, and a focus on the so-called lived diaspora (those now overseas but who have themselves formerly resided in Scotland), are the principal drivers behind the requirement for a contemporary as well as historical focus. These emphases are clearly visible in the Diaspora Engagement Plan (2010b), but if overstated they run the risk of contributing to perceptions that ancestral, cultural and historical linkages are undervalued (Leith and Sim, 2016). It should also be noted that the grant letter strongly implies that the support from the Scottish Government was contingent on five specific countries being included in the tapestry, and whilst it is highly likely that those countries would have been featured nonetheless, this clearly represents an external influence on the formation of the tapestry’s narrative content.

Grant support from Homecoming 2014 (Event Scotland) was specifically identified as being for use towards the costs of hosting the actual 2014 exhibitions, including venue and transportation costs. Of the £44,000 offer, £16,000 was to be ring-fenced for marketing activities and international promotion (Event Scotland to Prestoungrange Arts Festival, 14 March 2013). The use of this latter sum was briefly a cause of contention in 2013. It had already been reported consistently at strategy meetings that attempts to centrally controlled press releases and media activity outwith Scotland was less successful than the provision of encouragement and support to the volunteer contributors operating within the diaspora (Strategy Group Minutes 05/13). After Kristine Cunninghame left the project, her responsibilities for international promotion were re-allocated amongst the other team members. The Homecoming 2014 team however preferred to propose that the ring-fenced £16,000 was used to hire a professional marketing agency to oversee activity. This was rejected by the project team in favour of maintaining support and encouragement for local on-the-ground initiative by the volunteers and stitchers, who generally proved to be eager and able agents of their own promotional activity (Strategy Group Minutes 08/13). There was also an insistence that press releases were submitted for prior approval and where possible the insertion of a ministerial quotation, which the project team suggested was impractical when encouraging local responsibility for promotion as it commonly

engendered longer lead times and increased administration which might serve as a barrier to volunteer enthusiasm (Strategy Group Minutes 07/13).

Nevertheless there was a series of communications meetings held during this time, at least in part to confirm to Event Scotland that international promotional activity was indeed continuing successfully and that the issue need not be pressed. Although some of the funding was paid out a month later than had been agreed (Strategy Group Minute 07/13), the results the project was able to report clearly provided sufficient reassurance. This difference in approach is perhaps indicative of an institutional tendency to over-centralise engagement with the diaspora, something which the 2009 report warns against (Scottish Government, 2010a) although it is nevertheless evident in the Engagement Plan (2010b) as was also noted by Leith and Sim (2016). As well as developing what turned out to be a highly effective strategy of encouraging diaspora contributors to take responsibility for their own local marketing and press releases, the project team commissioned a combination of paid advertising and editorial coverage in such publications as *The Scottish Banner* and *The Highlander*. A full list of the media coverage achieved by the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry is appended to this thesis (appendix 3).

The rest of the Homecoming funding was allocated for the actual hosting of exhibitions during the Year of Homecoming. It was received on the basis of a projected visitor turnout of 83,000 attending exhibitions of the tapestry over three years, 30% of whom were to come from the United Kingdom outside of Scotland, and 20% from overseas. In his reply to the grant offer, Dr Prestoungrange was careful to explain that these figures were no more than ‘credible expectations,’ and that the project’s success should be measured in the longer term rather than simply the counting of visitor figures during Homecoming 2014 (Prestoungrange Arts Festival to Event Scotland, 31 March 2013). This is an important point, as it demonstrates the difficulty of appropriately quantifying the value of cultural projects in any way other than the bare statistics of the number of visitors drawn within a certain time frame (Crossick and Kaszynska, 2016). At least in part, by setting the attendance target over three years, Homecoming Scotland acknowledged that the tapestry project should not just be measured in the limited window of 2014 alone, but it still neither required nor provided means of assessing longer term impacts or significance. Perhaps reflecting that agency’s different focus, Creative Scotland did request a summary of the longer-term benefits the project would bring in its End of Project Monitoring Form but, as shall be considered further in chapter 7, the conclusion of the 2014 exhibition programme drew an administrative line under the project which was wholly artificial.

Finding and engaging the Diaspora

One of the founding principles of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry was that both its content and its creation would be the product of the diaspora itself (Prestoungrange, in Crummy et al, 2014). This was the result of the environment in which the project had been conceived, taking the participatory arts movement that had developed in Prestonpans onto a global scale whilst remaining true to established practices learned through the murals trail and Prestonpans Tapestry initiatives (Johnston and Prestoungrange, 2014). The potential social value of such projects has been reported elsewhere (Roos, 2013; Crummy, 2017), but the Prestonpans Tapestry had proven a clear if unevaluated case study in the power of large scale contributory arts initiatives – bringing local heritage together with a chance to contribute to something large scale and long-lasting – to enhance a sense of personal worth and belonging.

Alexander McCall Smith and the team behind the Great Tapestry of Scotland had successfully observed the effects of these processes, and were able to harness much of the residual positivity that its predecessor project had engendered (Mansfield and Moffat, 2013), but in centralising the decisions over content and tightly controlling embroidery standards they in fact limited the scope for participation. The Prestonpans Tapestry, born more to facilitate the engagement process than to consciously create a high status artwork, was bound to an extent by narrative constraints as it told a linear story, but it nevertheless added further panels in response to demand and was defiantly open to any who wished to take part regardless of experience or skill (Crummy et al, 2010). It is a source of regret that the project was not self-aware enough at the time to ensure a more detailed contemporaneous observation and evaluation, so that although the present author was witness to the process the evidence is largely anecdotal. The best articulation is a video production undertaken for the Battle of Prestonpans (1745) Heritage Trust, *Stitches for Charlie* (Robinson, 2010). This model of deep participation – with local connectivity to a single famous narrative history (Bonnie Prince Charlie's campaign of 1745) replaced with the potentially even more powerful motivator of personal or ancestral connectivity to a global identity – that formed the basis of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry.

Such an ambition could only be achieved therefore by successfully engaging diaspora Scots around the world, in 25 countries no less. Prestoungrange writes that without the internet the task of finding willing contributors would have been 'daunting', although perhaps it would have been nearer the truth to consider it impossible (Crummy et al, 2014: vii). The importance of the internet for communicating

with the contemporary diaspora is clearly acknowledged by the Scottish Government in its commitment to ‘develop and utilise the Gatekeeper Database,’ which it defines as a database of around 6,000 key organisations and individuals for the purpose of disseminating information into the diaspora (2010a). The Diaspora Engagement Plan also notes the importance of a centralised website, social media facilitation, and the maintenance of contact networks (2010b). The project team clearly hoped that the general global accessibility of the internet (accepting nonetheless that this introduces some barriers to participation) could be combined with the existing networks of the Scottish Government and tourism agency Visit Scotland to facilitate engagement from the diaspora (Crummy et al, 2014; Strategy Group Minutes 01/12). Hart and Murphy were to trace ‘extant Visit Scotland and Scottish Government linkages and on the ground media contacts’ prior to site visits, and the Saltire Society was also identified as potential source of contacts (Strategy Group Minutes 01/12). From starting with these larger networks, they worked down through ‘countless Scottish associations all over the world.’ (Hart and Murphy, in Crummy et al, 2015: 207). Reverse diaspora groups in Scotland were also contacted, with early mention in meetings of cooperation from Italian, Swedish and Pakistani organisations based (Strategy Group Minutes 02/12).

Before continuing in the analysis of how engagement was achieved, it is worth pausing for a further comment on the importance of technology in facilitating that engagement globally. The value of the internet for diaspora communities, both for general information sharing, identity maintenance, and for achieving purposive objectives (of which the tapestry might stand example), has been demonstrated by Brinkerhoff (2009). In its most basic form, as a tool for information exchange, digital promotion, and email connectivity, the internet played an irreplaceable role in the success of the project. In the years since the project’s completion, social media (particularly Facebook, where the tapestry page has over 1,600 active followers) has been increasingly effective for the promotion of exhibitions and sharing news of the tapestry’s international exploits, facilitating continuing engagement from existing as well as new audiences. The tapestry website continues to serve as the project’s main outward face, attracting between 16,000-19,000 unique visits per month throughout 2017 (data recorded by the webhosts and accessible to the author). However much of this digital engagement is passive, and this has largely been the experience throughout. The tapestry website was in fact designed to incorporate both public and password protected blogging areas for participating groups/communities, in part for archival reasons but mainly to encourage three-way discussion between diaspora locations and the homeland team. The importance of this multi-directional relationship was highlighted by the Scottish Government’s report on diaspora events in its first Year of Homecoming (2010a), but not a single participant engaged with the online blogs of the tapestry website and the facility was eventually removed. It was discovered that several contributing groups, one in Maine, USA for example, setup private groups for their members to communicate with each and share progress reports and inspiration

instead. Perhaps this is further evidence of the desire for decentralised engagement; a sense that the process was locally controlled even if the resulting contribution was globally available. In most cases however, digital engagement was simply not as desirable as community workshops and local meetings (Scottish Diaspora Tapestry news archive, 13/11/13).

In the early stages of the project, as a means of helping to interpret the exhibitions as well as combining traditional materials with current technology, funding was sought to incorporate QR coded tags onto the panels (Strategy Group Minutes 03/12). The funding was not secured however, despite some press interest in the juxtaposition, and only one group of pioneering stitchers made use of the idea (panel IT01). QR codes are however used on the current exhibition labels, linking to information in the digital application (“app”) which has become the principal means of onsite interpretation, although printed materials are still regularly requested. These experiences with the limitations of technology in engaging participants demonstrate how, whilst networks and cyber-communities can be important in some contexts they can still be rejected in favour of more personal methods of engagement. Blinkerhoff also notes that interpersonal communication remains important even in the digital sphere, in the form of chatrooms for example (2009). Certainly in the case of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry project, direct communication with a known individual was by far the most desirable method of communication for the majority of participants.

This inevitably places strain on those at the receiving end of the communications – in this case Hart and Murphy – creating large volumes of e-correspondence on top of the necessary research work and, in due course, the creation and distribution of the panel kits. As a result an additional tier of contact points evolved in many instances, whereby a liaison would emerge or be selected for each panel or group of panels being created. This limited the amount of direct communication required, as many participants could receive their information from the designated source rather than the small project team in Scotland. This had the further benefit of further engendering a sense of localness and focus, although it also created the potential for a disproportionate influence between participants over the content and design, which may explain why some participants were unsure who was responsible for informing those aspects of their panels (see chapter four). A further effect of this process was that the true number of contributors to the tapestry becomes harder to ascertain, as only those whose names were known and passed on to the project team could be recorded and the project team did not have contact information for many of those named. When seeking to disseminate questionnaires to inform this thesis, for example, there was often only one liaison address associated with a list of many contributors. Yet there is little evidence that a reduced level of vertical contact to the team in Scotland reduced the sense of engagement in the project, so long as there remained the horizontal levels of

communication to foster a sense of involvement at a more local level. The latter remained very important, as the exception to the general experience demonstrated: one stitcher who worked on a panel alone reported to the author a sense of loneliness and regretted that she had no means of engaging a wider group of likeminded people (survey responses).

The combination of the Scottish Government and Visit Scotland contact networks and target countries, inspiration from published works such as Kay (2008), and the accessibility of diaspora associations and institutions on the internet, came together to provide the basis for global communication with the diaspora. It remained however, as could be understood for a project which ultimately required a considerable outlay of voluntary effort, a case of finding the right individuals in the right places. This meant that initial contacts were often only loosely targeted, and leads followed as they emerged. This perhaps reduced the potential for strictly proportionate coverage (see chapter five), but it bore fruit in creating diversity and interest. It is important to note, although pre-empting the analysis in the following chapter, that only 11% of survey respondents heard about the tapestry through diaspora organisations such as Caledonian societies (see Fig 4-1). None reported having heard via direct messaging from Visit Scotland, despite the size of the Gatekeeper Database. As suggested by the failure of the blogs to attract engagement, representing a more centralised vertical form of communication rooted in Scotland and the project team, the value of the local networks in supporting and encouraging engagement must not be overlooked in attempts to mobilise contemporary diaspora communities.

Fig. 3-5. *Simplified model illustrating the project team's routes towards its target audience for engagement. Further work on such modelling could aid future projects in identifying the best use of resources to achieve engagement.*

The sketch above presents an attempt to visualise this model of engagement process as demonstrated by the tapestry project, highlighting the importance of the horizontal layers of communication and the challenges in reaching directly to members of the wider diaspora community, whose levels of active engagement with their diaspora identity or at least outward manifestations of it might vary considerably. Whilst both Visit Scotland and the wide range of Scottish associations etc. can be useful connection points, they themselves face similar problems to the project team in reaching the grass-roots. This flow-chart also reflects the project's use of local contacts and enthusiasm to generate media coverage within communities, which in turn aim to support further engagement from audiences that vertical contact from the project team or intermediaries has failed to reach. It is the tiers of grass-roots diaspora members which need to be mobilised for the full economic potential of the diaspora to be realised (Visit Scotland Insight Department, 2013), to say nothing of the importance of massaging and supporting the sense of diaspora identity and cultural commonality. No doubt the model sketched out above is one which can be further refined, but it is a useful starting point for interpreting the routes which might lead the tapestry team in Prestonpans to a stitcher in Nova Scotia or New Zealand.

The original intention of the project to tell stories from selected representative communities, as piloted by Gothenburg in Sweden and Barga in Italy, and then carried forward with panel sets from Veere in the Netherlands, Kedainiai in Lithuania, Prince Edward Island in Canada and others, did not long survive contact with the wider diaspora. The author first noticed the direction of travel when attempting to allocate the putative Australia panels to a specific town or region: the spread was simply too broad for such interpretative constraints. The result was increased representation of differing narratives and wider participation, and the cost was a structural one in terms of the neatness of community groupings. As the project expanded the amount of panels that could be allocated to a single community reduced, and so it is important to acknowledge that the amount of space granted to a story does not necessarily represent its importance or even the amount of volunteer support it received, but rather the timing of its creation. Thus the city of Guelph in Canada has a single very busy panel, whilst the town of Kedainiai in Lithuania boasts three panels relating similar themes.

Homecoming 2014 and beyond

One of the effects of the project's move away from a model of representative communities was that another of its intentions, that of linking diaspora communities and histories directly back to identified

homeland communities, became much more difficult. Without the sort of direct linkages as existed for example between Prestonpans and Barga, the project in fact found engaging homeland communities other than reverse diaspora groups to be challenging. The only truly successful manifestation of this ambition was in connecting to the Arisaig Highland Games 2013, ahead of which the Boisdale Prize arts competition for young people was focussed on designing a tapestry panel. This was however facilitated using existing contacts and linkages rather than by the creation of new ones.

On the advice of Scottish Government officers, universities were invited to a workshop in December 2013 to determine whether a student placement could undertake the project of establishing connections between homeland and diaspora communities (Strategy Group Minutes 07/13). Although there was some interest from Queen Margaret University, the most local to the project base, the student who was nominated subsequently became unavailable. The 'Homeland Communities' page was removed from the project website, although the team maintained a commitment to hold small sample exhibitions in homeland communities prior to the full exhibitions programme. These initial exhibitions were limited in scope and effect, but helped to build a sense of anticipation ahead of the main launch. The so-called Homeland exhibitions were held in April-May 2014 at: Dunbar, East Lothian (birthplace of John Muir, whose features on four USA panels); at the meeting place of Nari Kallyan Shango, a South Asian women's charity in Edinburgh whose members contributed panels; at Culross Palace in Fife, which has trading connections to Veere in the Netherlands and features in panel NL07; and at the Prestoungrange Gothenburg in Prestonpans (Homelands 2014, Scottish Diaspora Tapestry website). Another was held in Musselburgh, East Lothian in December 2014.

The project did not therefore effectively fulfil its secondary ambitions of creating tangible linkages between diaspora and homeland communities, partly because of its international engagement model moving away from the strictly community-by-community presentation, but also potentially due to a widespread lack of awareness in Scotland about the diaspora outside of reverse diaspora groups of pre-engaged institutions (such as the John Muir Birthplace Museum in Dunbar, where one Homeland exhibition was held). Prestoungrange, when compiling the final project report to the Scottish Government, acknowledge this shortfall and attributed it to an inability to secure proactive engagement with the project from Education Scotland, the government's education agency (Scottish Diaspora Tapestry team, 2014b). This despite the fact that the perceived lack of domestic awareness as to the diaspora's heritage and value had previously been highlighted in the government's own reports (2010a). The long term value of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry in this regard is considered in chapter seven. Nevertheless, a small grant from the Scottish Book Trust was put towards a school workshop and a public presentation in Prestonpans by the author Billy Kay. Activities themed on

local links to Commonwealth countries were also undertaken by school pupils in Prestonpans with the support of Lottery funds associated with the Glasgow Commonwealth Games legacy programme. These local pilots demonstrate the sorts of informative engagement which might have been undertaken more widely had greater buy-in from homeland communities proved possible.

However, the lack of homeland engagement in terms of newly established community linkages during the creation phases should not be overstated, as there was in fact a considerable amount of homeland participation facilitated by the embroidery side of the projects (see chapter four). Not only were a considerable number of panels researched and stitched in Scotland by resident Scots (outside of reverse diaspora groups), but there was also an important team of volunteers who supported Gillian Hart and Yvonne Murphy in the preparation of the completed panels for exhibition. Each panel underwent a process of stretching and backing, with hanging strips and identity tags applied. All this work was undertaken by volunteers based in the team's temporary studio at Cockenzie House (the one in East Lothian, not Australia). The process is described by Hart and Murphy as a 'vital part of the creation' process, and one which required an important degree of volunteer commitment in Scotland (Crummy et al, 2015: 212).

Content redacted due to unpublished work without informed consent for publication. Further details can be obtained from the author.

Fig. 3-6. The opening night of the (first) world premiere exhibition, Prestonpans Community Centre, May 2014. Dr Gordon Prestoungrange addresses the 200 guests, most of whom are stitchers, research contributors or funders.

When the first full exhibition of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry opened on 31 May 2014 at Prestonpans Community Centre – a choice in itself representing the self-assuredly community arts ethos behind the project – there were over 165 panels on display (Scottish Diaspora Tapestry news archive, 03/06/14). This was already in excess of the project’s target of 150, and in fact over 270 panels had been ‘identified for eventual inclusion’ by March that year (Strategy Group Minutes, 10/14), and the tapestry’s website was still asking “what are we missing?” just a few weeks before the launch (Scottish Diaspora Tapestry news archive, 13/05/14). The number of panels would continue to rise during the course of the Homecoming 2014 exhibition tour, and a second world premiere – not an achievement regularly witnessed – would be held in the Netherlands in 2015, when all of the planned panels were finally displayed together (see chapter 7). In fact, there was one outstanding panel which was not added to the exhibition until it arrived in London in 2017.

Panels which were not ready in time for the Prestonpans premiere in 2014 were appended to exhibitions under the curious title of ‘apocrypha’, and they were frequently displayed in groups in ‘accumulator exhibitions’ in Prestonpans until the main exhibition moved to a new venue and thus provided the opportunity for integration. The project team had endeavoured to collate panels within their country groups in a chronological ordering, to ensure interpretative sense at exhibitions, and it was this that informed the numbering of the panels rather than the order in which panels were made. Some panels changed number several times in the early phases of the project, but late-comers were incorporated into the chronology by adding ordinal letters to their code. For example, panels AU10a-AU10e are displayed in the Australia set in between panels AU10 and AU11. In theory AU10 comes before AU10a, but this system does not work. For example, the Italian panel IT01a must be displayed *before* IT01 otherwise it both breaks the chronology and interrupts the sequence of panels from Barga with a single panel about Rome. Such issues do not generally matter to the average exhibition visitor, but they are important to bear in mind when conducting an analysis of the content. Panel codes ending with a letter are always indicative of panels created later in the process.

The project team’s internal calculations estimated 31,000 visitors attended the tapestry’s Homecoming 2014 exhibitions, which were held at Prestonpans, Stirling, Edinburgh, Paisley, Inverness and Wick (split exhibition) and Helmsdale (Scottish Diaspora Tapestry team, 2014b). These venues gave the tapestry good national coverage, exhibiting in east and west as well as in the north and the central belt. There was no display in the western Highlands, although attempts were made to link in with the Arisaig Highland Games 2014, but there were difficulties securing appropriate venues in more rural communities for such a large exhibition. It was felt important to exhibit in Stirling during June 2014 as it was expected that this would be a major focus for the Year of Homecoming,

since it was mooted as the location for a major Gathering event as well as other events such as the 700th anniversary of the Battle of Bannockburn (Moffet, 2014). However the plans for a Gathering similar to that held in Edinburgh in 2009 were considerably scaled back and then integrated into the Bannockburn event, limiting the opportunity for the tapestry to benefit from a concentration of diaspora tourists. Criticism over this issue was articulated at meetings of clan associations at which the author was present, and was evident in the feedback on Homecoming 2014 collated by Leith and Sim (2016). The exhibition at Edinburgh's St Mary's Episcopal Cathedral saw the church festooned with flags from each of the countries represented on the tapestry, and was opened by the culture minister Fiona Hyslop MSP. Running throughout the Edinburgh Festival period, this was the exhibition which drew the largest crowds although the nature of the building and the fact that the exhibition, as with all others, was both free and un-ticketed, means that precise visitor data was impossible to record.

This leaves us largely reliant on qualitative data to assess the tapestry's success in its first period of exhibitions. Although comments left in visitor comments books are by nature a self-selecting sample, it has been argued that the opportunity to leave comments at exhibitions actively assists in facilitating the formulation of an opinion on the work (Macdonald, 2005). If this holds then that reason ought to be a reasoned one. What is immediately clear from the available comments left at Homecoming 2014 exhibitions of the tapestry, of which over 1,600 have been collated from 2014 – is that the response was almost universally positive. There are very few negative comments, in fact only two which focus on design elements rather than content and were clearly written in conjunction. Another bemoaned the absence of Wales from amongst the other home nations of the British Isles, but as no Welsh panels ever appear to have been proposed this is clearly and accidental rather than deliberate oversight. The vast majority of the exhibition feedback was therefore positive, and often expressed in extremes.

The superlatives are soon exhausted of originality, but many of the comments recorded express a sense of sheer amazement, at the scale – both of the exhibition and of the historical narrative – and at the beauty of the stitched contributions. Heather Smith of Innellan in Argyll was not alone in being “overwhelmed by the enormity of the project,” and many comments demonstrate a desire and a need for repeat visits. Some visitors were clearly moved by the experience, speaking of fond memories of friends and travels, and there are frequent references to feelings of pride: “we Scots are brilliant!” says M. Watt of Bishopton. Catherine Cassidy of Paisley found her visit “an emotional journey,” whilst Ann Boland of Ayr was moved to record that “never has an exhibition taken my breath away like this one.” Christine Piper of Stirling mused that “wherever you are in the world, you are never far from Scotland,” a sentiment which could sum up the entire project. A Cumbrian visitor to the Paisley

exhibition saw the tapestry through political eyes: “Superb!! If this doesn’t convince you to vote “Yes” nothing will!” Ian and Margaret Anderson however felt that the exhibition provided a “welcome relief from Referendum fever!” Considering the political backdrop to the Paisley exhibition in particular, which ran during the Scottish independence referendum, it is perhaps surprising that there weren’t more such comments. Noticeable in the comments is a regular use of “we” and “our”, demonstrating a sense of communality of ownership over the heritage being portrayed. The same was reported by participants: “it ‘belonged’ to me and my family – I am a part of that story,” a stitcher recalled. When A. E. Rooney of Glasgow and Toronto wrote in the comments book in Paisley they may have been thinking specifically about the panels’ embroidery or about the long history of Scottish migration, as the sentiment is surely applicable to both: “what talent lies within us!”

Of the visitors who left comments at the Stirling exhibition, 75% were resident in Scotland whilst Australia, the USA and England each accounted for another 6%. In Edinburgh the proportions shifted a little, the Scottish total reducing to 67%, with 11% from England, 5% from the USA and only 1% from Australia. The remaining percentage was made up of a much larger number of countries than was the case in Stirling, probably reflecting the diversity of the international audience available in the capital during the festival period. These figures tally approximately with the project team’s assessment – for which this data was not available – that around 8% of the visitors were from the UK outside Scotland and 20% from overseas (Scottish Diaspora Tapestry team, 2014b). In Paisley the Scottish proportion was higher at 91%, with England on 3% and Australian and the USA each contributing just 2%. This is indicative of a different audience reach in Paisley, which lacked the supporting tourism opportunities present during both the Stirling and Edinburgh exhibitions, although it should be noted that the Paisley visitors were considerably more likely to leave comments in the books than any other. This possibly reflects the proactive staffing of the community heritage group volunteers who manned the exhibition, and who also encouraged visitors to place stickers on maps to identify the spread of where they all came from. There was a considerably diversity, and clearly more overseas visitors than the dominance of Scottish comments in the visitor book might initially suggest.

Immediately following the Homecoming 2014 exhibitions in Scotland the tapestry crossed the Border and visited the two communities which accounted for most of its English panels: Doncaster and Corby. Both were relatively short exhibitions, accounting for just three weeks of display days between them, but they were significant as they were the first exhibitions to be held outside Scotland. Both were organised at shorter notice and with fewer advertising resources than the Scottish exhibitions they followed, but the visitor comments are virtually undistinguishable. There is still talk of pride, especially from visitors who had clearly taken part in the project, including Harriet Brammer of

Conisbrough who wrote that panel “GBE08 was worked on by four generations of my family: including myself, my dad, grandma and 3 year old niece – simply amazing!” Sonia Matheson in Corby found the tapestry “unexpectedly emotional,” whilst Elaine Bruce wrote: “inspiring, moving, beautiful, thank you x.” The highest praise however came from Frank Williams, who felt that he had seen ‘the ninth wonder of the World.’ The positivity of feedback in England was a good harbinger for the international tour on which the tapestry would soon embark.

Conclusion

The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry was born from what might be considered the precocious community arts context of Prestonpans in East Lothian, as a direct successor to the Prestonpans Tapestry project and, rather more tangentially and certainly less consciously, the Great Tapestry of Scotland. Without the Prestonpans Tapestry, the arts festival and the murals trail which came before it, it is unlikely that the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry would have been conceived at all; the scale of both the artwork and the ambition would have been overly daunting, and the track record required to persuade funding bodies of its value and viability would not have existed. These community roots are extremely important to the understanding of the project team’s aspirations and processes: the tapestry remained committed to its founding ethos throughout, as evidenced by its inability to say no to contributors even after the official deadlines for inclusion in 2014 had passed. Community art is usually focussed on finding relevancies and output impacts with a very local focus or benefit (Crehan, 2013; Crummy, 2017). To take those same principles and attempt to globalise them in the way this project did is highly unusual, although making community global through a celebration of common heritage and identity, rooted nevertheless in the local and personal, is no less surprising than the notion that Scotland’s Year of Homecoming should be a celebration of the diaspora rather than the homeland (Prestoungrange, in Crummy et al, 2014).

The Scottish Government’s decision to hold a second Homecoming themed year in 2014, building on the lessons and opportunities created and revealed in 2009, provided a timely focus for the emergent concept of the diaspora tapestry. It also provided the opportunity to collate the necessary financial and networking resources required to undertake such an ambitious global project out of such a small-base organisation. The Scottish Government had already invested energy and resources in assessing how it might successfully engage with its diaspora (2010a), formulate a strategy to further these intentions (2010b), and undertaken comparative studies of other countries seeking similar goals (Ancien, Boyle

and Kitchin, 2009). It had also acknowledged at least in principle the potential desirability of encouraging decentralised approaches and initiatives (Rutherford, 2009). The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry provided an opportunity for all of this to be put into practice by supporting with grants, advice and contacts an independently conceived and coordinated project in pursuit of overlapping goals. As a cultural project with grass-roots relevance and participation, the tapestry also addressed the perception that the government's approach to the diaspora was both too centralist and too economically focussed (Leith and Sim, 2016). The extent of the support given, both financially and in terms of visible ministerial interest, was reflective of this coming together of opportunity.

In due course the tapestry project showed itself adept and reaching down to the grass-roots members of the diaspora, or at least to receptive sectors within it, perhaps more so than the Scottish Government is commonly able to achieve directly. Reaching those who might not otherwise have engaged with diaspora organisations, the project was able to make a positive contribution to Scotland's global community by encouraging that sense of communal belonging, as will be explored in more detail in subsequent chapters. Although there were occasions when the centralising tendencies of government agencies surfaced, the project team was both sufficiently self-assured and demonstrably capable to ensure that editorial and operational independence was totally maintained throughout the project. Thus it was able to benefit from the *auctoritas* of Scottish Government support whilst maintaining the *familiaritas* of an independent community group.

Despite its successes beyond Scotland's borders, the project team was noticeably less successful in establishing engaged community linkages inside the homeland itself. This was not the major thrust of the project operations so inevitably never gained the same weight of resourcing or attention, but it is possible that this shortcoming is also indicative of either an apathy towards or ignorance of the diaspora and its legacy amongst Scottish citizens. This is certainly something which diaspora Scots are apparently conscious of (Leith and Sim, 2016; Scottish Government, 2010a), and the tapestry team clearly felt that the lack of agency support from Education Scotland weakened their ability to generate homeland linkages (Strategy Group Minutes 02/12). Successful school and community workshops held locally in Prestonpans with small grants from elsewhere (including the Scottish Books Trust) are demonstrative of the sort of activities which might have been possible to achieve more widely, but it is likely in the wake of the tapestry's completion that the task of informing Scottish audiences as to the diaspora's history, influence and contemporary significance will be largely borne by domestic exhibitions of the tapestry itself.

By the end of Scotland's Year of Homecoming 2014 the small project team in Prestonpans had succeeded in mobilising well in excess of a thousand diaspora and homeland Scots, each committing countless hours of skilled voluntary labour with an estimated market value of around £600,000 (Scottish Diaspora Tapestry team, 2014b). It was a considerable achievement; a level of engagement worthy of note for both its geographical spread and the short time frame within which it was gathered. This chapter has introduced some of the means by which the project sought to find and engage those contributors; the following one will explore exactly who it was that responded and what motivated them to invest so much of their knowledge, passion and skill into the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry.

Chapter Four:

The Stitchers and Volunteers

“To participate in this project was a highlight of my life.”

Helen Clare Chapman, Brisbane, Australia

Introduction

Before embarking upon a detailed content analysis of the tapestry’s narratives and the potential significances of its imagery, it is essential to investigate exactly who it was that contributed to the creation of the embroidered panels. The makeup of the primary project team in Scotland has already been discussed in the previous chapter, so the focus here is the composition and motivation of the very large body of volunteers working around the world to make the tapestry a reality. This is important for a number of reasons. Firstly, it facilitates an understanding of which parts of the Scottish diaspora population were mobilised for the project, which necessarily has a bearing on how representative of the wider population our study can be considered to be. We must also consider, expanding some of the ideas mentioned previously, the processes by which that population of contributors was reached and whether the methods or inherent nature of the project restricted or enlarged the potential reach. Secondly, understanding the makeup of the contributory population allows us to better understand the true authorial voice of the tapestry, which is essential for the analysis in the two subsequent chapters of this thesis.

The contributors to the tapestry who were not part of the project team itself fall into two principal categories: the researchers or facilitators; and the embroiderers or “stitchers” who actually created the physical artworks. There is a considerable overlap between the two, and it will be shown that many of the stitchers contributed directly to the content and design, although there were also a number of facilitators whose roles were limited to providing information and expertise on a specific subject or story, to directing the project team towards those who might be able to assist in the stitching, to recruiting and coordinating other volunteers in their area or community, or any combination of these roles. The stitchers themselves formed a far larger group, the final extent of which is virtually impossible to discern with any certainty, but which numbered at least 1,014 people. There is also another possible division: homeland and diaspora. A sizeable minority of the tapestry was in fact

made in Scotland by contributors living in the homeland, and it is important to properly explore that division and the differences which emerge in terms of how the project was perceived by the participants and what motivated their contributions.

This chapter is based primarily on the findings of the survey which was distributed around the network of known contributors in 2015. A copy of the survey instrument is appended to this thesis (appendix two), whilst information on the rationale behind its creation and detail on how it has been interpreted has already been presented (see chapter one). Initially the present chapter will explore the methods by which the networks of contributors were identified and mobilised, followed by an analysis of the division of contribution between countries and the homeland so as to identify the extent of the project's global reach. This second section will also consider the extent to which the participants may have already been engaged in diaspora activities. The demographical details of the sample population covered by the survey will then be examined, revealing that there is an unsurprisingly heavy bias in the project towards mature female contributors both in Scotland and abroad. The chapter will then explore the crucial insights that have been gained into the motivations which drove individuals and groups to participate in this project, revealing some differences between homeland and diaspora contributors as well as hinting at some important insights into a contemporary globalized perception of what diaspora identity really means.

Locating and building networks

Before analysing the population of participants which the project engaged it is necessary to consider the means by which they were drawn together. Some of this has been touched upon in chapter three, but here the focus is specifically the ways in which the contributors were identified.

Fig. 4-1. Chart showing percentage distribution of survey responses to question 29: "how did you hear about the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry project?"

The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry team began by targeting two known communities in which they had pre-existing contacts and a history of active exchange. These formed the pilot to the project and were initiated even before the official project launch in June 2012 (Scottish Diaspora Tapestry news archive, 02/07/12). The first of these was Gothenburg in Sweden (initially panels SE01-SE08, with a further panel SE10 being added later to commemorate the Gothenburg Principles). As the panels relate, the Gothenburg region has strong historical links to Scotland dating back at least to the seventeenth century, but it is the fact that the principal public house in Prestonpans is named The Gothenburg which provides the pertinent connection in this instance. Like a number of others in the south of Scotland, mainly in mining communities, the Prestoungrange Gothenburg was established in the early twentieth century according to a system initiated in Sweden by which a percentage of the profits were to be reinvested in the local community: the Gothenburg Principles (Allan et al, 2006). When the pub was restored by Gordon Prestoungrange much was made of the Swedish connection and a twinning link was established which saw the Lord Mayor of Gothenburg and friends making repeated trips to Prestonpans over the years thereafter. It was these links which Dr Prestoungrange and the team tapped into in 2012, and Andrew Crummy travelled to the city to gather stories from the former Lord Mayor and his network (Crummy et al 2015: 368).

A second pilot set was initiated at the same time for Barga in Tuscany, known - although not unanimously accepted - as the most Scottish town in Italy (IT01-IT05). Barga is the official twin town of the connected communities of Prestonpans, Cockenzie and Port Seton, largely because the famous local artist John Bellamy had latterly chosen Barga as his home (portrayed in IT06; Hartley and Moffat, 2012). The existing twinning connection was leant additional support in 2012 by the fact that Vice Chancellor of Queen Margaret University in Musselburgh, Professor Petra Wend, was known personally to Gordon Prestoungrange and 'had "volunteered" to assist in Barga during her family holiday there, holding a press conference and nudging the artwork along' (Crummy et al, 2015: 378). Professor Wend's endeavours built upon the results of a visit by Gillian Hart and Yvonne Murphy to collate stories and recruit stitchers, the latter cause being supported by a local journalist. She would support the exhibition of the entire completed tapestry in Barga in August 2015. Most of the Barga panels reflect the bilateral relationship between that community Scotland, and along with a later addition to the tapestry from the town of Picinisco can be considered as reverse diaspora content as they address the influence of Italian communities within Scotland (Colpi, 1991). Thus the Italian half of the pilot panels satisfied the Scottish Government's emphasis on encouraging reverse diaspora engagement, largely on account of the economic potential of fostering direct bilateral linkages (2010b, 2016).

Both the Barga and the Gothenburg pilot schemes, although building on existing networks, were primarily driven by personal connections and direct contact from members of the tapestry team. They were very successful, leading to an interestingly diverse set of panels and a strong initial set of engaged overseas contributors. Personal visits to diaspora communities generally proved highly effective on the whole, allowing relationships to form between individuals whilst facilitating presentations to wider groups as well as giving the opportunity for face-to-face explanations and demonstrations. Crummy, Hart and Murphy also visited communities in Canada, Lithuania, the Netherlands, China, India, the USA, and Australia, whilst Prestoungrange visited Corby in Northamptonshire, England, which became the home to thousands of Scottish steel workers in the twentieth century (Harper, 2013). Those visits, incorporating as they do some of the largest cluster sets in the tapestry, were extremely significant in mobilising contributors. They also helped emphasise the community arts nature of the project, as distinct from more centralised initiatives of which grass-roots participants might be more wary (Ancien, Boyle and Kitchin, 2009). Hart and Murphy recalled that they had visited 'almost 40 groups and individuals in ten countries' in the space of just nine months (Crummy et al, 2015: 368). Combined with the use of the internet to target and contact

appropriate groups and individuals, these visits account for the large numbers in the survey reporting that they heard of the project through direct contact from Scotland.

Since the personal contacts on the ground which were enjoyed in Gothenburg and Barga could not be replicated in every country and community, the team needed of course to identify appropriate destinations for their trips. Nor could they visit every location in all of the twenty-five countries (later thirty-three, excluding Scotland itself) featured in the tapestry. To identify and mobilise contributors there was therefore considerable recourse to the internet search engine: 'St Andrew's and Caledonian societies, Burns clubs, museums, historical groups, blogs and academic institutions' were the obvious target points (Hart and Murphy, in Crummy et al, 2015: 368). Fig. 4-1 shows that Scottish clubs and societies, as well as genealogical societies such as clan associations, did indeed facilitate the recruitment of contributors although they were by no means the only, or even always the best, route to grass-roots levels of the diaspora membership. It is likely that the strong showing in Fig. 4-1 of direct contact in the stitchers' survey is at least partially a result of the fact that the survey could most easily reach those volunteers whose contact details were held on file by the project team, mainly those who acted as liaisons for others. More contributors may have been engaged through other networks than is initially apparent, but the engagement flow chart of Fig. 3-5 appears to hold true. Certainly Scottish/diaspora associations played their part in the recruitment of contributors and dissemination of information, but that role appears to have been limited. They should certainly not be considered the only route to the diaspora audience. The importance of this will be considered further in chapter seven.

It is also clear from the survey results that the media did not play a major role in encouraging contributors to come forward to engage. This is in spite of the fact that the project was promoted in major Scottish newspapers in North America and Australia, including *The Highlander* and *Scottish Banner* (see appendix three). The minutes of the strategy group reveal initial optimism for global media promotion and international contact books were purchased as part of the media strategy (Strategy Group Minutes 01/12), but it soon became clear that this was not the means to promote the project as it was exceptionally difficult to coordinate from Scotland without existing enthusiasm on the ground. As was outlined in the previous chapter, the strategy shifted to encouraging the contributors to undertake their own local promotional work, a strategy which resulted in considerable success (appendix three). In effect this was a realignment of policy to reflect existing realities, as this type of local promotional activity was already beginning to blossom organically. Naturally this approach to promotion required the volunteers undertaking it to have already committed to the tapestry, and so it should not be surprising that media coverage was not therefore reported as a major

contributor to recruitment. The recruitment must already have occurred before much of the diaspora-based press coverage could be facilitated.

What perhaps seems more surprising is that not a single respondent to the survey had found out about the tapestry directly through the work of Visit Scotland or Homecoming Scotland. As has already been shown in chapter three, these agencies contributed to the selection of the initial twenty-five target countries based on their own data and experience and had access to a Gatekeeper Database which should have facilitated direct routes of communication into sectors of the diaspora audience (Scottish Government, 2010a). In June 2012 the project team was recording continuing discussions with these agencies in terms of locating contact points overseas (Strategy Group Minutes 02/12), and there were specific tie-ins made into a number of existing pre-planned marketing activities and ministerial visits to diaspora countries. Nevertheless it was soon apparent to the project team that the Scottish tourism industry did not in fact possess a wide-reaching network of specific named contacts which it was able to mobilise, and so the project team's own researches were the critical determiner of where the message fell. Perhaps there is too strong an economic rather than cultural focus to the Gatekeeper Database. This correlates with the findings of Leith and Sim (2016) in relation to Scottish Government's approach to diaspora engagement, which highlights the continued one-directional and overtly economic attitude and the potential this has to miss or even deter some diaspora Scots. They are seen as a market rather than a connected community; a lighter touch might bring additional dividends (Ancien, Boyle and Kitchin, 2009).

Clearly a number of participants in the tapestry project were engaged either as a result of existing artistic/crafts contacts, embroidery guilds being an important and internationally active example, whilst others learned of the project through their involvement in or awareness of the preceding Scottish tapestry projects. In terms of the latter group, which were primarily homeland stitchers, their primary motivation for participation may have been artistic rather than diasporic: this will be discussed in more detail in the section on motivations below. The same need not be said of those who found out about the project through craft networks. The survey responses suggest that a number of embroidery groups were directly contacted by others within their community to provide the stitchers for panels they had been liaising with Scotland about. Some of this process is reflected in the numbers who heard about through direct contact from *within* the diaspora as well as those who specifically identified their stitching networks as the source.

It should also be acknowledged that reverse diaspora organisations played an important role in directing the project team towards appropriate stories, contact points and networks. In some cases they also provided stitchers as well as research contributors. Italian, Polish, Lithuanian, Russian and Asian groups based in Scotland were amongst those involved, often providing invaluable leads. They also of course facilitated the inclusion of a small number of reverse diaspora panels into the tapestry (see chapter five), and they also provided a network for encouraging promotion and visits to the exhibitions once the tapestry was completed.

The most striking result shown in Fig. 4-1 is the critical importance of interpersonal communication; the horizontal communications expressed in the previous chapter (as modelled in Fig. 3-5). Well over a thousand contributors were recruited for this project and it should be no surprise to discover that four or five individuals in Prestonpans were not directly responsible for identifying and engaging them all individually. Rather, the project relied on information seeping out into communities through both formal and informal networks from the contact points the team established, most of whom can be considered as pre-engaged. By this it should be understood that they were either already stitchers and therefore likely to hear of the project through arts/craft networks, or active participants in diaspora research, activities or organisations and so more exposed to the messaging emanating from Scotland. Pre-engaged participants were more likely to take on leadership or liaison roles within their community's contributions to the tapestry.

The project's ability and willingness to deal directly with the pre-engaged and grass-roots audience, and to allow local initiative to flourish organically once engagement was made, meant that the tapestry's reach went far deeper into the diaspora population than would have been possible by simply working through clan associations or Caledonian clubs. It also meant that the project team had a lesser degree of control over how far the information travelled and who came forward, which was in fact to the benefit of a project such as this which after all aimed to capture a genuine sense of community engagement. The fact that personal contacts and word of mouth were responsible for so much of the engagement achieved by the project, triggered by direct contact from Scotland at appropriate or even fortuitous points, should highlight for those who wish to mobilise diaspora networks that whilst the obvious starting points are the formal institutions and organisations, they may not in fact be the best access points to wider diaspora society. An inclusive approach using different access points is necessary, and if the offering is sufficiently appealing then the vibrations should reach the informal networks which are virtually invisible from Scotland.

In Guelph, Canada, the project team's initial search for engagement via an institution failed to result in any interest coming forward. Members of the team travelled to Guelph in person and presented at the university, which boasts a Centre for Scottish Studies which is referenced on the Scottish Government's Diaspora Engagement Plan (2010b), but the tapestry panel showing the founding of Guelph by Ayrshire-born John Galt (CA15) only came about because a branch of the Canadian Embroiderers Guild heard about the project online (in this case it was through Visit Scotland marketing materials) and passed information through to its members. These volunteers had been missed in the initial search for engagement and found out about the project several months later, as was reported in their local newspaper (Scottish Diaspora Tapestry news archive, 22/11/13).

The example of Guelph demonstrates the need for projects to make use of multiple access points into the diaspora, not relying on a small number of institutions or organisations to act as gatekeepers. It also shows the importance of local networks in facilitating mobilisation and engagement, which in turn supports the need for appropriate opportunity structures with the host country to permit unrestrained information exchange between diaspora members as a prerequisite of engagement in diaspora activity (Brinkerhoff, 2009). A further lesson is that engagement is made easier when members of a diaspora are able to coalesce into communities, historic or contemporary, real or digital, so that there is a sense of shared identity which prevents embarrassment or isolation as well as facilitating information flow and cooperative engagement. Not all migrants of diaspora members have this experience, and their ability to engage and nourish a positive diaspora identity is accordingly reduced (Cohen, 2008), although the internet is now able to play a role in replicating some of the opportunity structures provided by diaspora communities (Brinkerhoff, 2009).

In many cases of course, especially in North America and Australasia, Scottish migrants historically did coalesce into diaspora communities in both a narrow and broad sense of the word: they were by no means insular but they commonly maintain some of the trappings of the home culture and continue to value them (Buelmann et al, 2013; Scottish Government, 2010a). For contemporary Scottish migrants or ex-patriates the opportunity structures for engagement are already in place in countries across the globe (Leith and Sim, 2014). But the importance of the sense of communality and community amongst diaspora members goes beyond simply facilitating the types of local network into which homeland initiatives can reach or exploit, however. Such networks also provide a nurturing environment for diaspora identity within the host community, a sense of normalness to the resulting duality of identity for subsequent generations, and The Scottish Government's own report on diaspora activities during Homecoming 2009 specifically mentions the importance of permitting local initiatives to develop within the diaspora (2010a), and this was one of the innate advantages of the

tapestry engagement process. Its success in achieving engagement by encouraging locally-rooted activity, control and ownership suggests that contemporary diaspora identity is being embraced by individuals within the context of more localised identities; the homeland's voice does not assume automatic authority when calling for engagement. As Buelmann, Hinton and Morton put it: 'diaspora, simply, is another layer of hybridity' (2013). Direct engagement with the homeland need not therefore be an essential element within it, and Scotland-based initiatives or organisations should be wary of presenting it as some form of privilege.

The division of contribution

The objective of the team behind the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry was, simply but ambitiously, to 'capture the widest possible volunteering of embroiderers and their communities' (Crummy et al, 2015: viii). The resulting network of contributors was therefore global in its nature by deliberate design. The fact that the stories and communities represented in the tapestry's 304 panels relate to thirty-four countries (Scotland included) which are spread right across the globe might lead us to assume that all of the stitching took place in those countries, but is that in fact the case? It is important to consider this question at an early stage of our analysis in order to be sure that any interpretations we make of the tapestry's content are understood in relation to their true voice, and so that we have an appropriate understanding of whose perspective on the diaspora we are seeing. To what extent does it reflect the understanding of those in the homeland rather than those in the diaspora itself, and do those who have contributed from within Scotland have different motivations than those who are actually overseas?

When the information on each tapestry panel was being collated by the editorial team working on the tapestry's official guide (Crummy et al, 2015), information which was distributed to the lead contributors for verification, amongst the details was a note identifying the location(s) in which the panel was created. A simple count of this data allows us to see how the total stitching contribution was divided between the diaspora and the homeland. This confirms that, whilst the vast majority of the actual embroidery work was performed overseas, a significant minority took place in Scotland. Of the 304 individual panels which make up the tapestry, 62.8% were stitched overseas (191 panels), 33.6% in Scotland (102 panels), and the remaining 3.6% were created jointly in Scottish and overseas locations (11 panels). This distribution is presented in Fig. 4-2 below. Many panels were stitched in more than one location of course, as groups of volunteers passed the tapestry around each other's

homes and communities; that is not reflected in these figures unless one of the locations was in Scotland. Interestingly, approximately 32% of the respondents to the questionnaire stated that they currently live in Scotland, which means that the sample population is proportionate in this aspect to the wider picture across the whole tapestry.

The same dataset also reveals examples where no stitching actually occurred in a country which is represented in the tapestry, although this is limited to a very small number of countries and those which can be expected to have only relatively small or hard to contact diaspora populations. Examples include Ethiopia, Taiwan and Sri Lanka. We should not be surprised that there were no stitchers working away on panel AQ01 whilst actually present in Antarctica. Of the four Africa countries which are represented on the tapestry, South Africa produced all of eight of its panels itself and one panel was stitched in Zimbabwe. The remaining four of the African panels were stitched in Scotland. In fact, apart from South Africa every country in the tapestry has at least one panel in its set which was stitched or partially stitched in Scotland. Germany, Russia and Poland are amongst the small group of countries for which the majority of their panels were actually stitched in Scotland. This is likely to be a reflection of the nature of the historical connection, although there was no similar disparity in the Netherlands which leads to some potentially significant considerations which will be explored in chapter five.

Fig 4-2. Chart showing the distribution of contribution between Scotland and other countries, according to the location registered for each panel's stitchwork.

It is important however to also recognise that some of those panels which were stitched in Scotland were created there for good reason. Of the four Lithuanian panels, three were stitched in Kedainiai and depict the Scottish connections to that region in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries (LT01-

LT03), whilst the fourth (LT04) represents the Lithuanians who migrated to Scotland in the late nineteenth and early twentieth century (Millar, 1998). That this panel was stitched in Scotland is therefore appropriate. The same reverse diaspora significance explains the propriety of other panels being stitched in the homeland also, such as PK03 and PK04 in the set from Pakistan for example. It has already been seen that Pakistan was considered a priority country for the Scottish Government (Scottish Government, 2016). The stitchers' survey results also reveal that a number of those who were stitching in Scotland had origins and connections from further afield, further demonstrating the bilateral nature of some of the relationships reflected in the tapestry.

It is therefore important for us to interpret the distribution of the contribution fairly: 202 panels were stitched or partially stitched overseas, and of the remaining 102 that were stitched in Scotland at least some of these were stitched by individuals or groups who either represent reverse diaspora connections or those with specific connections to the stories being portrayed, such as the *Nari Kallyan Shangho* South Asian women's group and the *Edinburgh Malawi Mafia & Friends*. It is not appropriate therefore to conclude that those panels stitched in Scotland are in any way less significant to the present study.

What is important, however, is that when analysing the panels the location of the contributor is borne in mind in case it holds potential bearing. Is a stitcher working in Scotland for example less likely to be connected to the story they are telling and therefore less able, likely or inclined to influence its content and design? Probably not, on the whole: 64% of respondents who were based in Scotland stated that they had either a personal, family or community connection to the story told in their panel. The same figure for overseas respondents is only two percentage points higher.

Age and gender proportions

There was no minimum requirement of skill or experience set for those wishing to contribute to the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry, and the basic skills needed to physically complete a panel are possible to learn very quickly and without a great deal of tuition. The researcher was able to demonstrate this by creating two panels despite no prior experience of embroidery. Completion of FR05 took around five weeks' worth of long evenings to achieve, and whilst IT01a took two weeks longer the hours spent on its creation were less concentrated and the design a little more ambitious. Although this in itself is not

a particularly scientific assessment, at least two panels are referred to by survey respondents as being completed within six weeks (a feat described as a challenge). Some panels of course took much longer than this, but it was also possible of course for a volunteer to only work on only a part of a panel: 16 survey respondents reported that their panels had been completed by between eight and fifteen people, and some panels have long lists of names associated with them. It is therefore possible to assert that a person's technical competence at embroidery need not have been a prohibiting factor in participation beyond the idea that the task might initially seem a little intimidating. Assuming that you were able to find out about the project through those channels discussed earlier in this chapter, the essential prerequisites for participation were therefore the time and the will to do so.

It may well be this time commitment which influenced the age range of the contributors. Only three respondents were aged below 44 years, and the largest group of volunteers by a considerable margin were over 65. This suggests that the vast majority of the work on the tapestry was carried out by those approaching or beyond retirement age. This latter point may well be a contributing factor to the imbalance: older people may simply have more time available to undertake voluntary craft projects or the sort of genealogical research which might encourage diaspora engagement in this form. There is also evidence from some of the stitchers' survey responses that some became involved through activities such as membership of an Embroidery Guild or the Womens' Institute, places which can also be expected to draw in an older demographic (Lane, 2003).

Fig 4-3. *Distribution of stitchers' ages according to the survey responses.*

The age-range appears to be even more limited amongst those who contributed from within the homeland. It is possible however that, given the relatively small numbers of younger stitchers who seem to be involved, that the sample is too small to draw that distinction with confidence. It is also

possible that, if we accept that time constraints (such as work and family) might prevent many younger participants from taking on a panel, those same restrictions might reduce the likelihood of those who did manage to do so of responding to a questionnaire.

There are however a number of younger contributors who are not picked up during the survey, those who were not responsible for panels by themselves but who nevertheless participated even if only to put in a few finishing stitches. Often in conversation a stitcher would relate that a child or grandchild had made a small contribution to the panel so as to be involved. For example, the Prime Ministers panel (GBE21) is credited to the whole Lindsay family as the main stitcher's husband and son "added a few stitches". The Portuguese panel on the Scots' role in the port industry was taken into the Luís de Camões primary school (PT03). We do not know the names or even the total number of the pupils who put in a stitch, and if we did and had included them in our results the age distribution might have looked very different! It is important here also to note panel CA09, designed by Lachie Robinson at Mallaig High School when he was thirteen years old as part of a twinning between his school and one in Nova Scotia. The content of this panel will be considered in more detail in subsequent chapters.

These contributions by younger participants, often invisible in the actual artwork and of course in survey statistics, must not be dismissed or overlooked as the very act of bringing them into the process of the creation may yield a legacy in the longer term (see chapter seven). Nevertheless, in real terms we should accept that the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry project's contributors were not drawn at all evenly from across the age spectrum and this study is therefore analysing the engagement of a mature generation of diaspora constituents, a point which should be borne in mind.

It is also clear that there is a significant gender imbalance in the contributing population; perhaps something which should not surprise us as the craft of embroidery is traditionally - if not always fairly - seen as a female one (Barrett, 2008). That this is largely the case has been observed by the researcher by attendance at the International Stitching and Knitting Show at the Alexandra Palace in London, the audience for which is predominantly female, and was also observed in the volunteers who rallied to create the Prestonpans Tapestry in 2009-10 (Crummy et al, 2010). In terms of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry, of the 1,014 named stitchers 93% are women. These proportions are conveniently reflected in the survey sample – 94% of respondents were female – so in terms of both gender and geography, two aspects for which we have a comparative dataset, the sample closely mirrors the bigger picture.

Of the individual panels, only eight out of the 304 can be shown to be the work solely of male hands so the majority of male stitchers shared their contributions with women. Two of the panels which were solely executed by men were stitched by the researcher (FR05 and IT01a), which would probably have been the case regardless of this study and so they need not be discounted. Two of the five Jamaican panels were stitched in Scotland by Professor Geoff Palmer, which is the largest proportion of male contribution for any country set and a reflection of the considerable contribution the Jamaica-born professor made to the project in terms of research and inspiration. The panel which celebrates his own achievements as Scotland's first black professor was stitched by his daughter in Glasgow, and taken together these panels wonderfully reflect the two-way migration relationship between Jamaica and Scotland over the centuries.

Considering the extremity of the gender imbalance amongst the stitching population, should we therefore view the tapestry as a female perspective of the diaspora? Do the proportions of the stitchers' genders affect the nature and presentation of the content in the same way that potentially the homeland/overseas distribution of stitchers might? The answer is almost certainly not. Hesse proposes that 'the Scottish dreamscape is gendered; the Scottish dreamscape is male,' relegating female participation to something passive (2014: 9), and whilst that may be observable in the relation to pipe bands and military re-enactment, it is not the case for the tapestry in either participation or content. Of the panels which were coded as containing people as their primary focus, 40 illustrated women, but although this appears low compared to the 146 panels showing named individuals, the imbalance is likely to be an historical one rather than a flaw in the contemporary project. For the 59 stitchers who felt their panel content had been determined by themselves or fellow stitchers, 69 felt that theirs had been determined by either local academics and societies or the project team in Scotland (see 'Direct and Indirect Influence', chapter six). The latter has already been shown to have had an equal gender balance of three men and three women, and as the male designer was in the strongest position to exert any conscious or subconscious influence. In terms of those research contributors (those labelled in the survey instrument as local academics or societies), a name analysis on the database used by the project team it is possible to demonstrate an even gender balance here also.

Fig 4-4: Approximate gender proportions of stitchers compared to the research-only contributors.

It can therefore be concluded that the gender imbalance in the stitching population is there offset in terms of its ability to have a significant bearing on the perspective of the content, by both the project team in Scotland as a potential filter and by the even balance amongst the research contributors and facilitators. Where the female influence was strongest was in the technical styles of the tapestry's actual embroidery, the stitching techniques, which are varied and impressive: 'they were encouraged to embroider as they felt the images called them' (Farmer and Ferguson, 2015: 4). Those techniques do not have a considerable bearing on the actual content or presentation in and of themselves, however. The artist Andrew Crummy has himself noted that the community arts movement in Scotland since the 1970s has a tradition of female leadership (Crummy, 2017). Although there is potentially interesting work to be done then in assessing both the role of women in driving community arts projects, and the potential for different gender perspectives amongst diaspora constituents, the tapestry does not appear to be the best vehicle for doing so, and so gender will not be a primary focus for this thesis.

Nationality and ethnicity

It has been established earlier in this chapter that approximately one third of the project's contributors stitched within Scotland and that this proportion is reflected in the proportions of the questionnaire respondents. The survey instrument asked both for the contributor's country of birth and their current place of residence; the results are shown in Fig 4-5. This chart shows that the survey was able to reach people in Scotland and fourteen different diaspora countries (including England and the rest of the UK as two distinct locations). It also shows that there is a clear bias in the data towards English-speaking countries and northern Europe (where the likelihood of respondents being able to read and understand

English is high). This bias was addressed in chapter one, and reflects the researcher’s inability to conduct this study in a language other than English, and although it is a fair assumption that most of those involved in the project must have had a working knowledge of English in order to take part in the first place, this need not always have been the case as only one person need act as a liaison between the project team and the stitchers. There are therefore countries which are featured in the tapestry but which do not have any representation in the survey dataset, including the whole of the Asian cluster.

The graph does not tell the whole story of course: there are stitchers in Scotland who created panels with overseas narratives, so in fact some of those countries’ panels are represented in the data even if not by somebody of that particular nationality. It must also be acknowledged that the chart can be misleading if taken at face value: the twenty-two respondents who were born in Canada are not in fact exactly the same twenty-two people who currently reside there. There is clear two-way global traffic amongst the sample, mainly to and from Scotland and England but occasionally between other countries: one German-born respondent now lives in the Netherlands for example, and that migration has left a trace in the chart.

Fig 4-5. *Distribution of survey respondents’ places of birth, alongside current places of residence.*

This evidence of migratory behaviour is further revealed by the answers to Questions 6 and 16 in the survey instrument. Forty-seven instances of temporary overseas residence were recorded in the

responses, spread over at least twenty-three different countries. These include places not covered by the tapestry such as Nigeria, Saudi Arabia and Japan. Of the respondents who stated that they did not currently live in Scotland, 27% said that they had lived there at some point in their lives. When asked in Question 16 if the respondent had family connections to other diaspora countries, 107 instances were recorded which again demonstrates the international nature of the volunteers' families and experiences. A considerable proportion of these overseas family connections (43%) were claimed by those who stitched their panels in Scotland, a fact which we should again bear in mind when considering Fig 4-2: just because a stitcher was working in Scotland does not mean they lacked a connection to the diaspora. The biggest single group of connections were to England, Wales and Northern Ireland, which when taken together accounted for over 22% of the total number. Perhaps this evidence hints at the interconnectedness of the British nations in the contemporary Scottish diaspora context.

This latter thought leads to a consideration of the contributors' nationalities. The survey instrument asked both 'what is your nationality?' and 'how do you define your ethnic group?' (questions 7 and 8). Reinforcing the point introduced above, there were 29 respondents who considered themselves British as opposed to only 9 who identified themselves specifically as Scottish. A further three categorised their nationality as British/Scottish, but nobody stated their nationality as English. Meanwhile six people defined their ethnicity as Scottish or White Scottish, and another six as English; two defined themselves as both Scottish and English and nine thought their ethnicity was British or White British. Perceptions of national identity are of course of considerable interest in Scotland at present, as debate about the potential survival or breakup of the United Kingdom continues. The admittedly small sample of respondents under our spotlight seems to indicate that, even though this project is a tribute to the specifically *Scottish* diaspora, nevertheless a sizeable majority of its Scottish participants identified their nationality as British rather than exclusively Scottish. Even fewer tied their Scottish nationality to a perceived Scottish ethnicity. If this is indeed the case then it is revealing that a majority are comfortable with the ideal of a two-tier identity which can celebrate its special Scottishness whilst still identifying itself within a broader Britishness. The two need not be mutually exclusive.

Altogether there were twenty-two different nationalities registered by the respondents to the survey. Some of these were so specific as to peculiar only to one individual but most were fairly straightforwardly tied to a country of origin and/or residence. Significantly, fourteen respondents gave themselves nationalities which can be categorised as hyphenated identities, such as Anglo-Australian, Canadian-British or English/Italian. In the same way that the British identity can be seen to happily

coexist with the Scottish, so too can we see evidence of diaspora constituents identifying with more than one perceived or legal nationality. Surprisingly however result of the nationality question is that the hyphenated identities listed do not include such definitions as Scottish-American or Scots-Canadian as might have been expected. The vast majority of Canadian contributors see themselves as just that, Canadian. So whilst the participants do indeed show a comfort with multiple identities or even dual nationalities, their perceptions of their nationality are in fact firmly rooted in the “host” countries. Any deep sense of diaspora identity is therefore being reflected in their activities rather than their perception of nationality.

The picture is rather more confused when considered in terms of ethnicity. This was deliberately left as an open question on the survey instrument so as not to restrain respondents within orthodox categories. The result was some fairly unique definitions, although it is also worth noting that the third most common category is those who chose not to answer the question. Perhaps ethnicity is a more sensitive means of defining oneself than nationality; perhaps the lack of options to select put some respondents off. The largest numbers identified themselves as either white or Caucasian, each of which represents over 18% of the total responses, or white European. There were a number of mixed ethnicities: Caucasian and Anglo-Indian; Anglo-Irish; White/Native American; Pakeha of Scottish ancestry, and even the fairly comprehensive French/English/Canadian/Scottish/Polish. These examples again demonstrate an awareness and comfort with the idea of a hyphenated identity.

Some do still identify their ethnicity with their country rather than what might strictly be considered an ethnic grouping (the Scottish and English examples have already been mentioned), and thus we can find one stitcher in Norway identifying themselves as Norwegian and another as Scandinavian. A surprising number identified their ethnicity with a more distant past: there were two mentions of Celtic and six to Anglo-Saxon. It is just possible that these reflect an ethnic identification reaching so far back into the past that they offer an echo for ethnosymbolist (or even primordialist) theories that we still consciously or otherwise align ourselves with our ancient tribal roots (Smith, 1986). In contrast there was one respondent who specifically stated that they did not identify themselves ethnically, explaining further on that they have ‘a powerful distrust of the concept of Blood and Belonging’. Yet another respondent provided a thoughtful answer which nevertheless stands as a clear a lesson in question framing: when asked how they define their ethnic group, the answer was ‘hard working and creative’.

Motivation factors

Whilst it is possible to make a statistical analysis of the contributors to the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry, that can only advance our understanding so far. It is necessary to achieve an insight into the factors which motivated their participation, the factors which determined their willingness to engage with an arts project commemorating an historic diaspora. The importance of this area of investigation meant of course that the question was included in the survey instrument. To simplify coding of the responses five possible answers were offered, as well as an invitation to supply additional reasons if required: a personal or ancestral connection to Scotland; a connection between Scotland and the contributor's own community; a general love of Scottish culture; an enjoyment of embroidery; and a chance to participate in a global project. The distribution of the responses is shown in Fig 4.5 below. It should be noted that an additional answer has been included on the chart, reflecting its recurrence several times as a contributor's response.

The chart clearly shows the three most important factors determining participation were, in descending order: the enjoyment of embroidery (25%); the chance to participate in a global project (24%); a personal or ancestral link (22%). It must be noted that considerable numbers of respondents chose all three of these options without prioritising their order, which no doubt explains the close spacing of the proportions. At first glance the results are nevertheless a little surprising. The implication appears to be that the chance to undertake an embroidery challenge was a more important motivator than the opportunity to commemorate or share personal diaspora narratives.

It is perhaps a fairer reading of the data however if personal/ancestral connections are combined with the results for community connections, a reinterpretation which better reflects the sense of connectivity between contributor and content, and which gives that combined field 30% - the largest response. Considering the fact that 65% of all respondents claimed in the answer to other questions that they had either a personal or community connection to their panel's content, it would be expected that this was a major factor in encouraging participation in the project, as indeed appears to be the case. This is particularly so for the diaspora-based stitchers, a far higher percentage of whom cited personal/ancestral links as a key motivator as compared to their Scottish counterparts (Fig 4-7). The importance of these connections is further emphasised in the results from question 36, which asked the respondents to answer in their own words. The responses were coded according to themes that emerged during analysis, and the findings can be seen in Fig 4-7. These are of course qualitative

assessments and so less straightforward to compare statistically, but nevertheless there is a clear importance attached to personal and local connections, to honouring ancestors, and to acknowledging descent from Scots or Scottish migrants. This is of course exactly what we would expect: the majority of contributors chose to give up their time and apply their skills in order to record or celebrate some form of direct connection between themselves or their community and Scotland. It is the very essence of what the tapestry set out to achieve.

Fig. 4-6. Chart showing the percentage distribution of motivations for participating in the tapestry project as selected by survey respondents.

Fig. 4-7. Chart showing the percentage distribution of motivations selected by survey respondents currently resident in Scotland as compared to those who were based overseas.

It is nevertheless important to acknowledge the fact that the nature of the project, the fact that it was an embroidery-based activity, played a very considerable part in motivating participation. In some cases this was in fact the primary motivator, one respondent stating categorically that she was ‘in it for the embroidery’. This goes deeper than simply meaning that the participant enjoys physically stitching onto linen: it speaks of the quiet power of the craft in creating and enhancing social experiences and relationships. A number of respondents suggested that they had stitched to support friends or fellow club members who may themselves have had connections, and there were also a considerable number who spoke of the importance of the social side to the stitching. This can be seen in Fig. 4-8, coded as Social Stitching. New relationships were created or existing ones reinforced as a result of the stitching process, one respondent praising it as a ‘meaningful opportunity to bond three people... it was a profound experience.’ One stitcher, an unfortunate exception it seems to the general rule, lamented that they were not able to hook into a new community of stitchers having become involved quite late, leaving her feeling ‘isolated’ by the experience. The social significance of contributing is revealed as both a motivating factor and a result. There were also creative as well as social explanations for the high prominence of embroidery as a motivator (again visible in Fig. 4-8), as some participants saw in this project a chance to enhance their existing skills or to develop new ones.

We are also seeing at least in part the legacy of the previous Scottish tapestry projects, the Prestonpans Tapestry and the Great Tapestry of Scotland, which since 2009 had been building an appetite and experience of such projects in Scotland, especially in the area around the Prestonpans hub (as explained in chapter three). A number of stitchers were directly recruited from amongst those existing networks, as has already been referred to elsewhere in this chapter. A glance at the fourteen panels of the Global cluster shows that the vast majority were stitched in a small geographical area around Edinburgh and East Lothian, which is indicative of pre-existing connections being mobilised. This does not of course reduce the importance of the contribution, but it does go some way to explaining the numbers of panels produced by people who had no discernible connection to the content: 35% of respondents to this survey.

Yet more of those panels are explained by the 15% of respondents who were motivated by a general love of Scotland and Scottish culture. This is also shown in some of the answers to question 36, where a general sense of affiliation or affection towards Scotland, rather than a specific connection to a particular content, was also detected. Those who wished to help share the overall story of the diaspora could also be included in this group, including also the small number whose own stories were not able to be included but who were nevertheless offered panels. All this is indicative of a broad goodwill towards Scotland and its legacy which might again explain the fairly large numbers of panels stitched by people with no actual link to their content. At the launch of the first exhibition of the tapestry in Prestonpans in May 2014, one French contributor summed this up when asked by the researcher why she had done her panel: “what *wouldn't* we do for Scotland?” A survey respondent summed up her motivations even more succinctly: “SCOTLAND! Love of!”

This level of affiliation can be born from positive personal experiences of visiting or working in Scotland, as is the case with the Regensburg stitcher who saw the panel as a representation of ‘the friendship I feel to Scotland,’ but it can also manifest itself almost subconsciously. A stitcher in Winnipeg claimed ‘I have no special ties to Scotland’, and yet she had designed two tartan sets within her community, one for her local embroidery guild and another for a nursing school graduation class. So whilst the individual might not feel a personal connection, aspects of Scottish culture – tartan being a particularly visual and visible manifestation – are deeply rooted in this diaspora community. This absorption of Scottish symbols into host cultures has been observed elsewhere, including the USA (Sim, 2011).

A very significant motivating factor for participants was the opportunity to participate in a major international project. The very scope of the tapestry in terms of both project and content made it appealing. A Canadian stitcher spoke of her ‘desire to be part of an international project’; the word international was underlined for emphasis. Another volunteer was proud to be ‘part of a world-wide scheme’. For the remote community of Tristan da Cunha this was a particularly significant factor. Although the logistics of transportation to and from the island prevented the stitch-work being done there, panel TDC01 was nevertheless stitched by a former islander who was able to share some of the embroidery with her mother when the latter left the island for a visit to Cape Town. For a community which often seems disconnected from the rest of the world, representation in the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry goes some way to bridging the gulf: ‘Tristan da Cunha is the most isolated community in the world and it is wonderful that they can be part of such a global project’.

Fig 4-8. Coded responses to the final question of the survey, asking participants describe what participation in the tapestry meant to them.

That the tapestry was able to harness or facilitate this desire to connect to something bigger is important. What it suggests is a common yearning for a sense of connectivity or belonging, an acceptance on a larger field than that of one's own community. One stitcher considered the tapestry to be a 'great way to unite so many countries', whilst a Canadian embroidery group were 'determined' to make sure their region was represented. This is a two-way street between the diaspora and the homeland. 'It gave me a sense of "belonging" to something,' recalled a stitcher in Renfrewshire, Scotland. She had neither a personal nor community connection to the content of her panel, only a general affection for Scottish culture and a willingness to volunteer. The tapestry here is acting as a mirror for a broader significance of diaspora identity: it is providing a sense of belonging and a means of connectivity, familiarity and acceptance within a global network.

There is a hint within these results that this yearning exists amongst those outwith the diaspora constituency as well as the expected population within, and that collaborative and community-based projects like the tapestry can in fact help fulfil that longing in and of themselves, hence its ability to draw in participants without strong connections to the diaspora itself. Project-based connectivity of course is only really live for the duration of the task at hand, unless the resultant networks are nurtured and supported beyond the immediate aims (see chapter seven for more discussion on these themes), whereas identification with a diaspora provides longevity. It is perhaps this appeal as much as any innate charms belonging to Scottish culture and its symbols which lies behind some diaspora engagement, the same factors causing both the general affection towards Scotland already expressed above and also to the emergence of so-called affinity diaspora groups, adopting those symbols regardless of having any personal or historical claim to them (Hesse, 2014; Rutherford, 2009).

In the present case however, it seems that it is the international nature of the Scottish diaspora, its very scale, which give it continuing appeal in a modern globalised society. That implies a case for a contemporary view of diaspora identity as a broad belonging but one which is not so dependent on the concept of the homeland as it might once have been perceived (Tölölyan, 2005 quoted in Cohen, 2008). In the context of this study's other results it would be too far to advance this case to the extent of demonstrating a 'decoupling' of diaspora from homeland (Cohen, 2008: 8), the social constructivist approach, but there is here a hint of Brah's 'homing desire' superseding the territorial or nationalistic core of the identity (1996: 180). If the importance of the homeland as a territorial concept is therefore not *the* critical factor in diaspora engagement, as appears to be the case for some of the tapestry's participants, then perhaps that shows a maturing of the diaspora identity in keeping with the increasingly globalised society in which it now sits. Considering the high average age of our sample, this maturing is probably not new. The content analysis of the panels and their stories will shed more

light on this important area of consideration, which reaches to the root of what belonging to the diaspora really means to contemporary constituents (chapters five and six).

Conclusion

The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry has proven itself to be a highly successful attempt to mobilise members of the diaspora, both ancestral and affinity, and as such provides insights into both how to reach and engage diaspora constituents and what factors might motivate that engagement. In terms of the former, it has been shown that a broad-brush approach through media channels, both in terms of local press and the more targeted “Scottish” overseas publications, was not the most effective means of mobilising contributors even if it contributed to raising awareness. If anything this was more effective in the later stages of the project in terms of supporting the exhibitions or reporting and promoting work already undertaken by local volunteers.

Nor was an institution-based approach universally successful, although formal societies and clubs providing the readiest available entry points into the diaspora. Both of these approaches were the ones recommended by Scottish Government agencies (as discussed in chapter three). Targeted approaches to museums and heritage groups with a specific focus on Scottish connections could be affective, as evidenced in places such as Prince Edward Island Scottish Settlers Historical Society, Veere in the Netherlands, and the Kolkata Scottish Heritage Trust in India. However it was direct contact with individuals, supported where possible by personal visits as well as regular correspondence which really triggered the initial engagement. Once appropriate buy-in had been achieved, the project was promoted through informal networks centred on friendship and kinship, as well as common interests such as embroidery, and through this grass-roots process did the majority of contributors emerge. The craft and stitching networks were as important as the genealogical, all of which comes together to suggest that project-based activities, especially with artistic outputs requiring physical contributions, working towards a larger whole or specific objective, hold significant potential as a method of mobilising diaspora engagement.

This is supported by some of the motivational factors reported as the reasons behind the participants’ contributions to the tapestry. Some did so simply because of family or friends requesting support, or because their craft groups wished to be involved, although considerably more were motivated by an

awareness of their own or their community's diaspora links. This latter factor was to be expected, but there was also a strong desire amongst participants to view their diaspora connectivity in global terms, or at the very least to have it represented on a global stage. Does this hint at a maturing of the diaspora identity, one which sees itself as international rather than just bilateral and anchored in yearning for the homeland? Possibly so, and the contributors' tendency, with notable exceptions, to express their nationality and ethnicity in simple terms without a clear trend towards identification with an ancestral homeland appears to support that possibility.

It has further been established, in order to aid contextualisation of the analysis of subsequent chapters, that approximately two thirds of the contributors were based overseas in the diaspora itself, whilst a significant proportion of those who were based in Scotland still had important personal or community rooted motivations for being involved. The contributing population does represent a fairly restricted age band, the majority of participants being over 65 years old, although we also know that school aged children were involved in some panels. The embroidery work itself is very much the work of female hands, with a very small number of exceptions, whereas the research contributors were drawn from a much more natural gender distribution; sufficiently so that there is no requirement to consider the content of the tapestry in a specifically gender-orientated perspective.

What is also clear is that the large majority of participants appear to have had either a personal, ancestral or community connection to the content of the panels to which they contributed. That is the case both for the Scottish and overseas stitchers, and that fact provides sufficient need for this investigation to move its focus onto the actual content of those panels.

Chapter Five:

The Stories

“Glory, passion, warts and all.”

Marion Richardson, Kelvinhead, Scotland

Introduction

It has already been shown that the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry sought contributions from twenty-five different countries, rising to thirty-four by the time the project was completed. It has also been shown that some of these countries had been identified by both the project team and the Scottish Government as key target countries on account of their importance to the contemporary Scottish tourism economy, including the United States of America, Canada, and China. Others are known to have been included because of existing bilateral cultural relationships between specific communities and Prestonpans: Barga, Italy and Gothenburg, Sweden. Others emerged unexpectedly as volunteers connected with the project, such as Chile and Ethiopia, and are represented in the tapestry primarily because enthusiastic individuals drove their inclusion. As a result it is important for us to consider the stories that are related in the tapestry panels – the narrative content – in terms of the historical understanding of the Scottish diaspora. In other words, is the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry appropriately representative of the historical narrative, or does its content bias towards particular countries, regions or time periods?

The previous chapter identified that there were barriers to participation in the project for those who did not speak English or lacked regular access to the internet, and so we must consider whether this has led to Anglophone countries dominating the tapestry in a disproportionate manner. The extent to which historical distance – the length of time that has passed since the original Scottish connection – affects representation in the tapestry must also be considered. If more ancient ties are less represented, is that indicative of a diluted enthusiasm amongst diaspora communities today? This is particularly important for communities where the genealogical connection between host and homeland may not be so strong or so visible, or where there has been a distinct “Scottish period” in the host region’s history which did not prove to be permanent. How these connections fare in the tapestry compared to those of more visible diaspora identities such as Scots in America or Australia will also be considered.

After considering the spread and proportionality of the tapestry's narrative content, both in geographical and chronological terms, we will then consider it in regard to the narrative themes. This will include an evaluation of the parity given both to famous diaspora names (John Muir and Andrew Carnegie for example) and less well-known and much more personal stories. The narrative themes of the panels will be broken down based on the findings of a coding exercise, to reveal the relative importance of, for example, military or religious themes. This will lead to a discussion of the Scottish diaspora, as it is represented by the tapestry, in relation to the theoretical understanding of diaspora as presented in particular by Cohen (2008). Combined, these findings will demonstrate how the historical narrative of the Scottish diaspora can be broken down into distinct phases, each with varying characteristics, and with those variations come differences in the perception or extent of diaspora identity today. This returns to the original considerations of the project's relative successes in mobilising diaspora engagement in the tapestry and its subsequent activities.

Emerging out of this analysis are two important issues which will be singled out for consideration in the final sections of this chapter. The first is the concept of a *memorial* or *legacy* diaspora, as evidenced particularly by the panels from Veere in the Netherlands. This addresses a possible gap in our understanding of diaspora, which falls somewhere between the traditionally understood ancestral or migrant diaspora and the much looser affinity diaspora, and can be used to consider the sense of historic connectivity between people or cultures where the influence of migrants has been transitory or temporary and yet has left a legacy which is still visible or valued. Understanding such legacies could be just as important for encouraging contemporary engagement with the homeland as those connections which are rooted in genealogy are, for example, for Scottish tourism (Basu, 2007).

The final issue to be considered in this chapter will be the importance of diaspora identities in the forming of new nations away from the homeland. Definitions of diaspora often focus on a continuing belief in the homeland as a concept, real or aspirational, which harks back to the early focus of diaspora studies on the Jewish diaspora for example. There is evidence in the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry however which shows the importance of diaspora identities in the forming of new countries, in this case particularly Australia, Canada and the United States of America, both as a means of giving depth to the emerging new identities and a sense of collective association to countries founded to a large extent on immigrant populations and endeavours. This is important both in encouraging us to accept that the concept of diaspora need not in fact require a longing or aspiration to one day return to

an ancestral homeland (Cohen, 2008), and in demonstrating that diaspora identity can constructively coexist with, and can in fact strengthen, national identity based in the host country.

Geographical distribution

It was identified in Chapter Three that many treatments of the Scottish diaspora either focus on specific countries (Calder, 2003 on Canada, for example) or else choose to begin in the middle of the eighteenth century (Devine, 2011; Bueltmann et al, 2013). The result is often either that the overall global context becomes less clear in the first case, or that the earlier historical phases of migration are given too little attention in the latter. In particular this means Scotland's Old World diaspora is less popularly understood than the higher-profile and better documented New World migration in later centuries: Kay (2008) calls it the forgotten diaspora. Descendants from the earlier historical phases of Scottish migration into European countries are hard to trace, although there are recent databases of migrants' names drawn from manuscript sources (Dobson, 2000) which are useful references if not contextual analyses, but even the contemporary diaspora in Europe is under-studied (Leith and Sim, 2014). But the story of Scottish migration inevitably begins with encounters with Scotland's nearest neighbours, initially elsewhere in the British Isles and then into northern Europe, Scandinavia and the Baltic (Dobson, 2000); the story extends to North America from the seventeenth century, with gathering momentum into the eighteenth, especially in the second half of that century; and then it booms through the nineteenth as the opportunities spread further across Asia, Africa and Australasia (Devine, 2011). The result is that Scotland's diaspora is truly a global affair.

Looking at the diaspora through the lens of the tapestry provides a good sense of that global reach: the project surpassed its original intention of encompassing twenty-five countries and reached thirty-three. For clarity, that count excludes Scotland and counts England, Northern Ireland and Ireland separately, and Palestine/Israel together (from which no political conclusion should be drawn). The count also includes Antarctica. As has been explained, these countries are grouped for the purposes of exhibitions in regional "clusters", the titles of which became increasingly disconnected from strict geography as the number of countries grew. After opening the exhibition in Bergen, Norway in March 2015, the mayor of Hordaland county Tom-Christer Nilsen asked with a smile: "how long has Bergen been on the Baltic?" Nevertheless, the cluster titles alone give a sense of the tapestry's – and therefore the diaspora's – global reach: the Baltic; the British Isles; Western Europe; Canada; the Americas; Southern Asia; and Africa and Australasia. Another cluster, the Global Panels, is non-geographic.

RANKING	COUNTRY	No of PANELS
1	Australia	41
2	Canada	37
3	USA	26
4	India	24
5	England	21
6=	France	12
6=	Netherlands	12
7	New Zealand	11
8=	China	10
8=	Sweden	10
9=	Italy	8
9=	South Africa	8
10	Ireland	7
11	Russia	6
12=	Jamaica	5
12=	Argentina	5
12=	Pakistan	5
12=	Northern Ireland	5
12=	Norway	5
13=	Germany	4
13=	Lithuania	4
14=	Portugal	3
14=	Brazil	3
14=	Malawi	3
14=	Poland	3
15=	Chile	2
15=	Zimbabwe	2
15=	Palestine/Israel	2
15=	Sri Lanka	2
16=	Taiwan	1
16=	Ethiopia	1
16=	Tristan da Cunha	1
16=	Antarctica	1

Fig. 5-1. *Countries represented on the tapestry, ranked in descending order by number of panels.*

But to what extent is the tapestry a reliable reflection of the true nature of the historical or contemporary Scottish diaspora? The table above (Fig 5.1) ranks the countries represented in order according to the number of panels associated with them. The top three, Australia, Canada and the

USA are perhaps not surprising: 1,792,622 people in Australia claimed Scottish ancestry in the 2011 census (Australian Bureau of Statistics, accessed March 2017), and 4,719,850 Canadians in 2006 (Statistics Canada, accessed March 2017), and an estimated 12,190,000 in America (Basu, 2007). These three countries between them represent by far the largest populations of contemporary diaspora Scots actively identifying with their ancestry, and therefore the most fertile recruiting ground for engagement with the tapestry: together they account for over a third of the entire tapestry.

Two of these countries, Canada and the USA, were also on the Scottish Government's top five priority countries to be involved in the project, as discussed in chapter three (Scottish Government to Prestoungrange Arts Festival, 6 March 2012). The absence of Australia from the Scottish Government's list is therefore striking, especially as Australia was ranked fourth for overseas tourist spend in Scotland in 2016 after falling from third place in 2015 (Visit Scotland: Research and Statistics, accessed August 2017). Perhaps its inclusion was so obvious as to go without saying. The other countries which the Scottish Government prioritised for the project team were India (which has the fourth largest number of panels in the tapestry), China (joint eighth for number of panels), and Pakistan (joint twelfth). India and China together represented only 3% of the tourism market share by spend in 2016, compared to 41% between Canada, Australia and the USA. They are however listed as markets of interest by Visit Scotland on their website (Visit Scotland: Research and Statistics), and taken in conjunction with the Scottish Government's requirement for reverse diaspora stories to be included in the tapestry it should be accepted that their inclusion in the priority list was motivated by a desire to mobilise the reverse diaspora communities within Scotland and encourage increased tourism from their home countries.

England takes fifth place in the tapestry's rankings, which is also unsurprising considering that Scots have been crossing their porous southern border in countless numbers for many centuries (Thomson, 2000). Visitor spend from England is not ranked in the same league tables as the overseas visitors, but the 2015 visitor spend by the English of £2,086 million, 41% of all tourism in Scotland, this is by far the biggest market (Visit Scotland Insight Department, 2016). It is worth noting that Norway is also noted by Visit Scotland as a market of interest, matching Sweden's £43 million tourist spend in Scotland in 2016 (Visit Scotland: Research and Statistics, accessed August 2017), and although both are included in the tapestry with 15 panels between them, there was no formal pressure for the Government or Visit Scotland to engage those markets. In summary, every country in the top ten rankings – and indeed the top twelve if England and Northern Ireland are included in the rankings, as they are in the tapestry (Visit Scotland Insight Department, 2016) – although the next largest existing

market by tourist spend is Spain and this is one of the few countries where the tapestry did not succeed in achieving engagement (Visit Scotland: Research and Statistics).

The question at hand however is whether the distribution of panels is proportionate; or in other words, whether the tapestry presents a false perception of the scales of Scottish migration or influence to certain countries over the centuries. Although migration figures can be ascertained for some countries in later periods, they can only be estimated for others (Buelmann et al 2013). Without reliable statistics for the numbers of Scots who migrated to each country, however, it is impossible to answer the question fully. So instead of statistical proportionality, we must rely on a sense of proportional fairness – a scientifically unsatisfactory and inevitably subjective measure. For example, are the three panels dedicated to the Scottish pedlars, soldiers and merchants in seventeenth century Poland (PL01, PL02, PL03), which may represent a Scottish population in that country of around 40,000 people (Smout et al 1994), in proportion with the same number of panels exploring Scotland's links with Malawi (MW01, MW02, MW03)? The famous conservationist John Muir (1838-1914) has four panels dedicated solely to his life and legacy (US19-22), the same number as reflects the centuries of connectivity between Scotland and Lithuania (LT01-04). There are six panels commemorating Barga as the most Scottish town in Italy (IT01-06), but only one (GBNI01) to represent the many thousands of Scots who settled in Ulster since the beginning of the sixteenth century (Bardon, 2012). When viewed in this way of course, the tapestry cannot be viewed as being proportionate in representation to the actual historical narrative except in the very broadest sense: that the largest and most continuous flows of Scottish migration occurred to New World countries (Devine, 2011).

But the apparent disproportionality in the tapestry's geographical weighting should neither surprise nor disappoint us. Firstly, it has already been shown that the tapestry team consciously avoided over-curation of the content, so the numbers of panels are as much a reflection of the bias of the volunteers as they are a result of the diaspora's historical processes (see chapter three). It has further been shown that there was a strong leaning amongst the overseas volunteers towards anglophone New World countries, and that there were barriers to participation in some countries where English was not commonly spoken or where internet-based outreach could not be effective (see chapter four). As the project was essentially reactive in its search for content, at least once the initial calls had gone out, timing could also be a factor in determining the number of panels a story or community received. Those communities which were proposed in the earliest phases of development – Barga, Gothenburg, Prince Edward Island, Corby and Kedainiai, for example – were generally represented by a set of related panels, whereas those who joined later tended to be condensed into smaller sets or even a single panel. Valparaiso in Chile, for example, has a single panel depicting at least three different

connections (CL01, Fig. 5-2): Thomas Cochrane's involvement in Chilean Independence in 1818; the founding of the Mackay School in 1857; and the Casa Riddell department store in 1870 (Dobson, 2003). These factors also affect aspects of the design, as will be discussed in chapter six.

Fig. 5-2. Panel CL01: Valparaiso, stitched by Mary Richardson in Tranent, Scotland.

The Chilean example leads to another important point: the phasing of the project and the openness of its team to new contributions facilitated an increased geographical spread. Chile was not featured in the original list of countries featured in the tapestry by the time of its launch exhibition in June 2014. Neither were Taiwan, Sri Lanka, Palestine/Israel, Antarctica, Ethiopia, Zimbabwe or Tristan da Cunha. It is no accident that these so-called Benchmark II countries account for those with the lowest number of panels, as they were added in response to enquiries which came in too late for inclusion in the initial sets. Had each received a more statistically proportionate number of panels then the scale of the tapestry would have become virtually unexhibitable. So although they do not aid the proportionality of the representation, they do add to the geographical spread and therefore present a broader picture of the diaspora's extent.

Fig. 5-3. Percentage of the total tapestry belonging to each Cluster grouping, demonstrating the dominance of Australasia.

Chronological distribution

Geography and chronology are closely related in the study of the Scottish diaspora, as there are periodic shifts in the focus of migration. The starkest is the westward shift away from Europe, Scandinavia and the Baltic, in favour of North America. This begins in the seventeenth century as colonial opportunities emerge in the New World, but gathers most of its impetus in the decades which follow the Act of Union in 1707, opening up new territories to Scottish traders and migrants (Devine, 2011). Further phases were affected by the fluctuations in push and pull factors, from population pressures in Scotland (Buelmann et al, 2013) to opportunities for enrichment through imperial service, civil or military (Devine, 2011), and even the proactive recruitment of Scottish workers and migrants. The recruitment of Caithness shepherds for Patagonia (AR02) and the ten-pound passage to Australia (AU21) stand as examples of the latter. The geography of the tapestry content is therefore closely connected to the chronology, and so having explored the former it is important to consider the latter.

A simple coding analysis of the tapestry panels allows us to see where the chronological focus lies, and whether any patterns are visible (see appendix five). The results have been tabulated below (Fig. 5.4), and for clarity the table has been subdivided into cluster groups. Each panel had its content matched to a principal time period. Anything dating to before the year 1000 was designated as ‘early’, and anything from 1000-1499 as ‘medieval’. The sixteenth and seventeenth centuries were each designated as a category, whilst the eighteenth century was divided in half to reflect the tendency to begin studies of the later diaspora around 1750 (for example Devine, 2011). The nineteenth century has also been divided, to allow for the changes between the Georgian and Victorian periods, which saw considerable changes on the global stage and the increase in Scottish involvement in Africa and India (Fry, 2001). The next category was reserved for panels directly relating to the First World War (WWI), followed by an interwar category and then the Second World War (WWII). The final two categories covered anything relating to the post-war to modern period, and panels specifically referencing content which is live in the present day. These divisions were designed to allow the data to reflect any significant changes in focus, without being so broad as to dilute the numbers and therefore disguise the possible patterns.

BALTIC	Early	Med.	C16th	C17th	1700-1750	1750-1800	1800-1850	1850-1914	WWI	1918-39	WWII	1950-2000	Present
Norway	1	1	1	1				1			1		
Sweden				2	1	2	2	2					1
Russia		1		1		1	1				2		
Lithuania				3					1				
Poland				3									
TOTAL	1	2	1	10	1	3	3	3	1	0	3	0	0

BRITISH ISLES	Early	Med.	C16th	C17th	1700-1750	1750-1800	1800-1850	1850-1914	WWI	1918-39	WWII	1950-2000	Present
England		1			1	1	4	3	1	2	1	4	
N Ireland				3		1	1						
Ireland	2	2				1		2		1			
TOTAL	2	3	0	3	1	3	5	5	1	3	1	4	0

EUROPE	Early	Med.	C16th	C17th	1700-1750	1750-1800	1800-1850	1850-1914	WWI	1918-39	WWII	1950-2000	Present
France		2	2		3		1	3	1	1			
Italy					1			2		1	1	1	2
Germany			1	1	1		1				1		
Netherlands		1	3	4	1	2					1	1	
Portugal		1				1	1						
TOTAL	0	4	6	5	6	3	3	5	1	2	3	2	2

[continued]

CANADA	Early	Med.	C16th	C17th	1700-1750	1750-1800	1800-1850	1850-1914	WWI	1918-39	WWII	1950-2000	Present
Canada	0	0	0	2	1	11	13	8	1	0	0	2	0

AMERICAS	Early	Med.	C16th	C17th	1700-1750	1750-1800	1800-1850	1850-1914	WWI	1918-39	WWII	1950-2000	Present
USA				3	1	3	5	8		2			2
Jamaica					1	2		1				1	
Chile							1			1			
Brazil							1	1				1	
Argentina								4		1			
Antarctica										1		1	
TOTAL	0	0	0	3	2	5	7	14	0	5	0	3	0

ASIA	Early	Med.	C16th	C17th	1700-1750	1750-1800	1800-1850	1850-1914	WWI	1918-39	WWII	1950-2000	Present
Palestine/Israel								2					
China					1	1	3	3		1	1		1
India				1		2	8	9		2		1	3
Sri Lanka								2					
Pakistan								1		1		2	1
Taiwan								1					
Palestine/Israel								2					
TOTAL	0	0	0	1	1	3	11	20	0	4	1	3	5

AFRICA/ AUSTRAL	Early	Med.	C16th	C17th	1700-1750	1750-1800	1800-1850	1850-1914	WWI	1918-39	WWII	1950-2000	Present
Ethiopia						1							
Tristan da Cunha							1						
South Africa							2	5		1			
Malawi								3					
Zimbabwe							1	1					
Ethiopia						1							
Tristan da Cunha							1						
Australia						3	9	20		6		3	
New Zealand						1	2	9					
TOTAL	0	0	0	0	0	6	16	38	0	7	0	3	0

[continued]

TOTALS	Early	Med.	C16th	C17th	1700-1750	1750-1800	1800-1850	1850-1914	WWI	1918-39	WWII	1950-2000	Present
Overall TOTAL	3	9	7	24	12	34	58	93	4	21	8	17	7

Fig. 5-4. Set of tables showing the chronological spread of the tapestry content, divided according to exhibition cluster.

The results of this analysis show that the earlier the date of the content, the lighter the representation in the tapestry. By far the heaviest weighting of the tapestry's content is focussed on the nineteenth century into the first decade of the twentieth. This trend correlates with the marked increase in Scottish migration at that time, in the era Devine (2011) identifies as the Great Migration. It was a time when improved transport and new technologies were opening up vast territories and all the associated opportunities for exploration, settlement and endeavour, whilst gold rushes and the continuing reach and economic power of the British empire encouraged migration and entrepreneurship at a time of steadily rising populations at home (Buelmann et al, 2013). This dominance. This weighting is driven by the New World clusters, especially Africa and Australasia.

By contrast, the Baltic and Western European clusters are weighted towards the earlier periods. Of particular note is the concentration of seventeenth century content in the Scandinavian and Baltic clusters. It has already been seen that this important phase of migration may perhaps be proportionally under-represented in the tapestry, but within the Old World clusters the pattern is important and reflective. The British Isles cluster is also noteworthy, as it demonstrates a level of continuous and continuing interaction stretching back to the medieval but continuing through to the modern age to create a large and engaged diaspora population with close associations with the homeland (Mycock, in Leith & Sim 2014). The Ireland set features the oldest content, representing the ancient kinship between the peoples of Scotland and Ireland (IE01), and the cultural overlap bridging the Irish Sea is represented by the famous Book of Kells (IE02) (Meehan, 1995).

These results are not on the whole surprising: the chronological weighting of the tapestry favours the nineteenth century, and this correlates with the geographical distribution which is weighted towards the New World and, in particular, North America and Australia. This in turn correlates with, as has already been demonstrated, the profile of the survey respondents (Fig 4.4), the vast majority of the overseas responses coming from Canada, the USA or Australia. These are also amongst the countries

most associated with Scottish diaspora activity, are anglophone and therefore accessible for engagement projects, and also actively engaged in tourism to Scotland.

However, coding the chronology of the narrative also reveals that the weighting of the tapestry does not strongly favour contemporary stories, with just seven panels identifiable as being present-day and only 17 covering the years from 1950-2000. This means that most contributors were not primarily interested in telling their own stories or those of the immediately preceding generation. They might however depict the first generation of their family to undertake the migration. These trends are reflected in the survey responses enquiring whether contributors had a personal/family connection to the content of their panel, or whether the story depicted was connected to the community or place where they live (Fig 5.5). Overseas contributors were more likely to be stitching a story connecting their community to Scotland (56%) than their own family (34%), which is likely to indicate narrative content placed further back in time than their family’s recent experiences. This trend is reversed amongst the contributors who were living in Scotland when they took part in the project: more were stitching panels connected to family experiences (49%) than community (33%). This reflects the panels which feature reverse diaspora content, for example, which are also more likely to reflect twentieth century or contemporary narratives.

Fig. 5-5. Percentage distribution of survey responses to Question 23 and Question 24 of the contributors’ survey, with side-by-side comparisons of those who were based in Scotland and those who were overseas.

The narrative content of the tapestry is therefore proving consistent with the findings of the contributors' questionnaire, reflecting an unsurprising bias towards the phases of migration which occurred in the nineteenth century into the early twentieth, particularly focussing on anglophone countries in North America and Australasia. Whilst this in part is a reflection of the relative accessibilities of communities in these regions to a Scotland-based project team, the correlation of this with the geographical and chronological phases of Scotland's migratory experience suggests that this weighting is neither surprising nor in fact heavily disproportionate. The tapestry is not only reflecting the historical phases of the Scottish diaspora: from early British Isles and Northern European destinations into Baltic and Scandinavian countries in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, which in turn declines in relation to North America-bound migration into the eighteenth century. In the nineteenth century new destinations and opportunities emerged in Africa and India (Fry, 2001), and especially in Australia and New Zealand. Places such as Lithuania and Poland, destinations for Scots in previous centuries, saw the flow reversed in the twentieth century and the creation of their own diaspora communities within Scotland. All of this is reflected in the panels of the tapestry, and although there will certainly be communities, connections and perhaps even countries that have been missed, the main geographical and chronological trends of the diaspora are clearly represented.

Dominant Themes in relation to theoretical frameworks

The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry makes no claim to be a comprehensive narrative of the history of the Scottish diaspora, at least not 'in any deliberate way', and instead provides is a 'snapshot' of the historical and contemporary diaspora (Prestoungrange in Crummy et al, 2016). By accepting that this is the case, the tapestry's broadly representative distribution of content over time and space as considered above appears to satisfy that it reflects many of the key phases of the Scottish migratory narrative. We have also seen that there is a correlation between the stage of that history and the geographical focus, with earlier periods focussing on Europe and the Baltic, and later periods with North America and Australasia, for example. Developing this analysis further, it is possible to show that the tapestry details several different *types* of diaspora narrative, and that these also often follow the patterns identified above in geographical and chronological contexts.

These considerations reflect back to the discussion introduced in Chapter Two regarding the definition of diaspora and the various distinct types into which they can be categorised. Cohen (2008) identifies five ideal types of diaspora in order to identify the dominant characteristics of a diaspora over and

above the definitions which apply to all (Safran, 1991). Cohen identifies the following categories: victim; labour; imperial; trade; and de-territorialised. The content of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry will now be set against these ideal types in turn, in order to test the applicability of such categorisation to the Scottish experience.

Victim diaspora

The idea of a victim diaspora harkens back to the classical use of the term diaspora to apply primarily to the Jewish experience. As the discussion of diaspora broadened in the mid-twentieth century the term nevertheless maintained its negative connotations and the Jewish diaspora remained a key comparator for other examples to be measured against (Cohen, 2008). The discussion has expanded considerably since, but the notion of victim diaspora remains powerful and relevant. But is it an appropriate lens for considering the Scottish experience? Victim diaspora requires a specific agency which triggers migration, expulsion or exile of a native people in sufficient numbers and to sufficiently diverse destinations as to establish a diaspora community (Safran, 1991).

The tapestry certainly features examples which could be identified in those terms. Exiles and fugitives from the failed Jacobite Risings of the early-mid eighteenth century feature in panels from Sweden, France, Italy, Jamaica and America. In fact, Charles Edward Stuart (the famous *Bonnie Prince Charlie*) appears more frequently in the tapestry than any other named individual, a symbol of the fates of hundreds of political and religious exiles over several generations. There is also a panel recording the transportation of Scottish prisoners from the battles of Dunbar and Worcester to the New England, Maine and Massachusetts (US02). The Scots are depicted with heads bowed and hands bound (see chapter six). There are also depictions of Scots being driven overseas by the notorious Highland Clearances in the second half of the eighteenth century, particularly in the Canadian set where panels from Prince Edward Island and Ontario depict a sense of melancholy and homesickness alongside the physical hardships of carving out a new life in the untamed lands of North America (CA03, CA06, CA10 being fine examples). Certainly there were considerable push factors at work in Scotland during this period, with economic and population pressures contributing to a large increase in Scottish emigration (Devine, 2011), and that narrative clearly resonates with diaspora communities in eastern Canada still.

The majority of instances represented in the tapestry which could be categorised as victim diaspora experiences are therefore relating to the eighteenth century, particularly the second half, which correlates with the historical shift from Old World to New World migratory focus (Devine 2010). There are examples outside this range, such as the military career of Patrick Gordon in Eastern Europe and Russia after leaving Scotland to avoid persecution on account of his Catholic faith (RU02). The forced migration of Scots to the Australian penal colonies in the late eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries could also perhaps be considered as creating a victim diaspora (AU02), although the experience was not based on Scottishness but on criminal convictions and was not therefore exceptional alongside the identical experiences of, for example, English convicts. And although the migration itself was forced, the focus of the tapestry narrative does not rest on a sense of victimisation (see chapter six for a discussion of the imagery in panel AU05).

Fig. 5-6. Panel CA09, the imagery of victim diaspora.

So there is content within the tapestry which would identify with the concept of victim diaspora, but it is a minority of the content and it is concentrated primarily in the eighteenth century, particularly along the Jacobite and Clearances themes. This is no great surprise in itself: the Jacobites are a major focus of historical interest in both Scotland and the North American diaspora, as evidenced by Scottish tourism initiatives in 2017 promoting Jacobite heritage sites, for example, and the large number of respondents to public petitions for the protection of Culloden and Prestonpans battlefields in 2014 and 2016 which came from North America (author's observations, April 2017). Popular perceptions of the failure of the 1745 Rising and the aftermath of the Battle of Culloden often bleed into those of the Highland Clearances (Prebble, 1963) and certainly the latter feature largely in

perceptions of the Scottish diaspora inside Scotland itself, forming a ‘popular myth’ (Devine 2011: xiv). In July 2017 for example, a BBC documentary about the voyage of the *Hector* (depicted in panel CA03) came under fierce criticism on social media for supposedly underplaying the forced nature of the exodus. The BBC’s use of the word ‘migration’ rather than ‘clearances’ in an advertisement provided the initial trigger. In relation to the prisoners of the slightly earlier Dunbar and Worcester battles of 1650 and 1651, there are networks for research and DNA profiling led by the descendants of prisoners with an active interest in engaging with their heritage: in September 2016 enough of them were willing to travel to Dunbar in East Lothian for a re-enactment of the battle that a symposium on the fate of the prisoners was added to the itinerary (information provided by the Scottish Battlefields Trust).

The identification of the Scottish experience as a victim diaspora will therefore be recognisable to many, including audiences within Scotland: at the tapestry’s exhibition in Westminster Hall, a Scottish Member of Parliament (Scottish National Party) looked out across the exhibition and lamented that the tale told in the tapestry was ‘sad’ narrative of a country which had seen the potential of its people diminished as so many were driven overseas. That is not borne out by a serious reading of the tapestry, but rather exposes a preconceived interpretation of the Scottish diaspora as primarily victim in nature, to the detriment of the homeland. But whilst this narrative might resonate in some communities both in Scotland and abroad, its comparatively low level of representation in the overall tapestry suggests that the Scottish diaspora experience cannot be defined solely as a victim diaspora.

Labour and Trade diaspora

Cohen states that ‘instead of arising from a traumatic dispersal [ie. victim diaspora], a diaspora could be generated by emigration in search of work, to further colonial ambitions, or in pursuit of trade’ (2008: 61). This follows his amendments to the list of core diaspora characteristics created by Safran (1991), which allowed for acceptance of positive characteristics, introducing the categories of labour, imperial and trade diasporas. The lines dividing these categories can sometimes be blurred: labour and trade opportunities can be intertwined, whilst trading connections could lead to colonisation and in turn perhaps to new employment opportunities. Cohen aids distinction by separating less or un-skilled migrants seeking work from, for example, the clerks and administrators of empire and the international trade tycoons. He points to the related classification by Armstrong (1976) of a ‘proletarian diaspora’ to sharpen the distinction.

Does this labour diaspora type apply to the Scottish case, however? Leith & Sim do not suggest so, fitting the Scottish case into only three of Cohen's five categories (2014), but there are examples within the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry which might indeed meet the criteria. One example would be the Scottish steelworkers who migrated to Corby in England from the 1930s, increasing its population from 1,300 to 18,000 in just twenty years (Crummy et al, 2016). Corby contributed six panels to the tapestry, has hosted exhibitions of both the Prestonpans and Scottish Diaspora tapestries, maintains a Grampian Club and boasts two Church of Scotland churches. These migrants could not perhaps be described as unskilled, but they are certainly migrating purely for employment. Another example could be the shepherds and farm workers who travelled to Patagonia in the later nineteenth century, many from Caithness (AR02). The Argentinian government proactively recruited from Scotland, and although many such workers were on limited contracts for five years, many also settled (AR01). The tapestry also features labour diaspora panels relating to Scotland's reverse diaspora, including Irish workers (IE05), and the plaster statute makers or 'fish and chip men' from Italy (IT01, IT02).

Although the Scottish shepherds in Patagonia can perhaps be no more considered as unskilled than the steelworkers of Corby – after all, they were being hired because of their specific perceived qualities – they are certainly not part of an imperial diaspora as they are seeking employment outside the boundaries of the British Empire. Should the large numbers of Scottish soldiers involved in European warfare in the seventeenth century also be considered in this category (SE01, PL02; see Miller 2007)? The potential for a labour diaspora to prove transitional, as new-found opportunities permit migrants to break out of their initial circumstances or temporary employment engagements expire and they return home, perhaps means that in the Scottish case at least the labour diaspora should be considered as a stage of the experience rather than a defining classification. In Corby or the shipyards of Merseyside (Munro and Sim 2001), however, that diaspora is still very much visible and the identification viable.

Trade diaspora can be transitory too, as the trends of history shift: panels relating to Scotland's Baltic timber trade (NO03) and the great Scottish merchant houses in Lithuania (LT01), Poland (PL03) and the Netherlands (NL02) all relate to periods of considerable economic connectivity which faded after the opening up of New World markets. Its impacts and legacy can however be long-lasting and ongoing. The Scots' involvement of the port wine industry in Portugal is a later period example of trade diaspora content in Europe (PT02, PT03), for example, whilst the three panels stitched in Hong Kong show the evolution from the East India Company trading post at Canton (CN02) through the

establishment of Jardine Matheson & Co in the mid-nineteenth century (CN03), to the skyscrapers of modern Hong Kong (CN10). The Southern Asia cluster of the tapestry is in fact largely dominated by trade diaspora panels, including the great tea clipper races of the nineteenth century and the famous Clyde built *Cutty Sark* (CN05), and the great commercial tea plantations of India which helped British companies break the trade out of Chinese control. Some of these trade links endure, but others are so entwined with the imperial diaspora that they share the fortunes of the empire (see the following subsection for more discussion on this issue).

Imperial diaspora

Imperial diaspora therefore overlaps with trade, in that most large eighteenth and nineteenth century European nations maintained overseas empires and colonies, with varying degrees of success, and trade was a critical motivating factor. The Scots were heavily involved in the creation, maintenance, administration and finance of the British Empire (Devine, 2003), and this is reflected in the tapestry. Colin Campbell's presidency of the Swedish East India Company, depicted in panel SE04, shows that they were involved in others too. The presentation of that imperial diaspora in the tapestry is however interesting: in India it is reflected primarily through content relating to trade, tea plantations, and botany; in Africa it is through missionaries such as David Livingstone (MW01) and Robert Moffat (ZW01); in both Africa and Australia, as well as in some North America panels, there is content commemorating individuals connecting to anti-slavery campaigning or building relationships with indigenous peoples.

In contrast, there is relatively little recognition of the considerable role of Scots in the Atlantic slave trade in the eighteenth century. Minutes of the project team record no deliberate intention to ignore these issues, and the researcher recalls this darker side of the diaspora being raised several times by Crummy who was anxious not to be accused of over-sanitising the history. But the tapestry's acknowledgement of Scotland's involvement in black slavery is largely due to the contributions of Professor Sir Geoff Palmer, an active researcher in this area. He personally stitched the Jamaica panel JM02 illustrating the influence of Scots in the sugar, coffee and tobacco plantations, whilst his daughter stitched a panel celebrating her father becoming Scotland's first black university professor (JM05). Slavery is also referenced in JM03, which tells the story of the Wedderburns who rebuilt their fortunes through the plantations after losing everything after the last Jacobite Rising (see chapter 6). So this aspect of the negative side of Scotland's imperial diaspora is indeed shown in the tapestry.

Many Scots remain unaware or perhaps even in denial about the extent to which places such as Glasgow benefitted from black slavery, as expressed in the book 'It Wisnae us' by Mullen (2009). And although this is not a dominant feature of the tapestry, its presence there has at least re-raised the issue within the diaspora discussion.

Similarly, although perhaps not so recognisably, there are challenging panels in the USA set reflecting negative engagement relations with native peoples in North America. Chief William McIntosh (1775-1825) of the Creek Nation is commemorated in a panel explaining the name of the McIntosh Trail through Georgia and Alabama, and the central figure is depicted dressed in a combination of native and western fashions (US12). McIntosh was assassinated by his people after he had signed away a large part of their country to the US government. Through such deals many native peoples were displaced, but although this is mentioned in the tapestry's interpretation (Crummy et al, 2015: 208) it is not referenced in the panel itself. In contrast, Chief John Ross of the Cherokee (1790-1866) is depicted in two panels (US13, US14) commemorating his unsuccessful resistance to the displacement of the native Americans and the devastating impact of their forced removal along the so-called Trail of Tears (Smith, 2011). In this case the Scottish influence is in trying to stay the repressing hand, rather than supporting it as is arguably the case with McIntosh. These examples are of an imperial diaspora type, although relating to US expansion rather than the British Empire, and as a trio of panels US12-14 do introduce the Scots involvement on both sides of those issues. The negative aspects of that direct involvement are less clearly portrayed, however, and are only explained in the supporting materials.

Although it can therefore be shown that potentially controversial aspects of the diaspora history are indeed addressed, even if relatively lightly, it is significant that there are no illustrations of Scottish military involvement in the expansion and maintenance of the British Empire. The role of Scots in these areas was considerable, so much so that Fry's *The Scottish Empire* features Scottish soldiers fighting in the British army prominently on its front cover (2001), but this is not evident in the tapestry. Hesse (2014: 158) identifies that 'the kilted soldier is at the heart of the Scottish dreamscape,' and that the image of the Highland regiments is an enduring symbol. And yet, for the core historical period during which this symbol was most globally active, it does not appear in the tapestry. This suggests that this is not a side of the historical narrative that either the contemporary diaspora or the Scotland-based project team felt it was appropriate or desirable to illustrate. In fact, Lachlan Macquarie (1762-1824) and the two soldiers depicted beside him in panel AU03 are the last military images until the First World War, a gap of around a century during which Scottish soldiers were active across the globe. Despite there being a range of panels in the total tapestry referencing

military themes or events, there are none from the mid-late nineteenth century (see chapter six). Clearly that side of the historical narrative found no champion to press for its inclusion, not in any of the countries for which it might have been relevant.

Perhaps the Kolkata Scottish Cemetery panel (IN16, Fig. 6-5) is the clearest acknowledgement of how Scots permeated through all the layers of the imperial administration in India. It is discussed in more detail in both the subsection below and in chapter six. It may be relevant that only six of the twenty Indian panels were in fact stitched in India, which perhaps emphasises the temporary or transitory nature of imperial diaspora in countries such as India, in contrast to the more demographically lasting legacies of colonial settlement in Australasia, South Africa and of course North America. However it has also been suggested by historiographers that India has played a part in the down-playing of not only the darker sides of its own history but also the complexities of their historical relationship with Britain (and therefore Scotland). The latter contains both the negatives attributes of empire and the benefits of reintroducing India to the wider world and even to their own heritage (Bose, M. in Furtado, 2017). So perhaps the avoidance of the more difficult imagery of the Scots' involvement in nineteenth century India is symptomatic of both Indian and Scottish sensitivities towards the era.

The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry has so far been shown to identify with four of Cohen's five ideal types of diaspora. The fifth classification is more complex: de-territorialised diaspora. This is Cohen's response to a perceived need to address 'mobile and multi-located cultures' created by multiple phases of migration affecting the same diaspora population over time, or the less unidirectional nature of migration for the purposes of study, temporary work or tourism (2008: 124). These processes can lead to large networks of international connections which might not fit comfortably with classical notions of diaspora groups as migrant populations yearning for a return to a single homeland. This classification can also be used to apply to communities which share a common culture but not perhaps a common homeland, such as the Roma people. But it also has some validity in relation to Scotland too, as identified by the Scottish Government's interest in 'lived' diaspora members who may have had only transient engagement with the homeland, and affinity diaspora members who may have a purely cultural affiliation rather than a real territorial or ancestral connection (Rutherford, 2009).

The results of the stitchers' survey presented in chapter four clearly identify that only 30% of contributors took part because of a personal or community connection to the panel they stitched. The desire to be a part of something global (24%) and a broad sense of affection or identification with

Scottish culture (15%) were powerful motivating factors for participation. These findings imply that those engaged in the tapestry project were connecting to a cultural diaspora rather than a strictly territorial one, and whilst Scotland is of course the heartland of that culture it is not its sole source for contemporary communities or members: panels celebrating Caledonian societies, New York's Tartan Day and Burns Suppers demonstrate that. That many such themes are represented in a separate 'Global' cluster of tapestry panels, which show cultural exports such as music and dance as well as Scotch whisky, should be seen as an acknowledgement that a yearning for the homeland need not be an essential part of the Scottish diaspora experience as its culture is accessible in recognisable forms right across the world.

This has been identified elsewhere, and has led some to broadening diaspora discourse away from the homeland-based models to something constructionist (Cohen, 2008). This correlates with the observation by Hesse (2014) that for large sectors of the diaspora it is the culture and history of Scotland which mobilises engagement rather than ancestral or personal connections. Ancestral or lived connections are simply not necessary in order to feel – or be – a part of it (Hesse, 2014). Belonging to the diaspora therefore becomes a conscious choice rather than a result of historic or contemporary circumstance, and not necessarily based on an authentic vision of the homeland or its culture. The tapestry also suggests however that there is a middle ground, where connectivity is based on historic roots between communities rather than individuals, discussed in the following chapter in the section on *memorial diaspora*.

The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry therefore stands testament to the fact that there is no single formula for categorising the Scottish migratory experience: it has shown characteristics of all of Cohen's defined categories, although not always simultaneously or consistently across either time or geography. When the tapestry panels were coded by the project team as part of the preparation for the mobile media application (app), however, it was into themes such as Botany, Farming, Exploration, and Engineering. It is not the *type* of diaspora that the tapestry set out to express, but its achievements and legacy. In both regards it is remarkable for its breadth and variety.

Diaspora identity as a support for national identity

One of the content themes identified in the tapestry app is Politics, and although the term is used very broadly (including content such as the Bendigo gold rush and forest conservation in India) there are a number of panels with clearly political themes. One of these commemorates the British prime ministers of Scottish birth or descent (GBE21). Others show James Connolly's involvement in the Easter Rising of 1916 (IE06), dynastic royal marriages (FR03, FR04, NL01, NO04), or the founder of the Scottish National Party's time in Argentina (AR04). Analysis of others leads to potentially significant conclusions relating to the connectivity of diaspora and national identity in the context of the host country. The content of some panels provides evidence that, rather than diluting a sense of belonging to the host country the homeland identity, its culture and heritage, can be used by diaspora Scots to strengthen their sense of national identity. The co-existence of diaspora and national identity in host countries is well attested, and is probably most recognisable in the form of so-called hyphenated identities such as Ulster-Scots, Italian-Americans, Scots-Americans (Sim, 2011). But co-existence or dual-identity is not actually what some of the tapestry panels are in fact revealing: they show diaspora identity as an important facet of the formation of new national identities.

Of the panels categorised as political in their content, a considerable proportion relate to what can be considered as "new" nations. The United States of America, Canada, Australia and New Zealand together comprise around 38% of the total content. Significantly, in each of these cases the tapestry overtly celebrates the role of Scots in the process of their foundation. Panel US09 depicts John Witherspoon, the Scots minister from East Lothian who went on to become principal of the College of New Jersey (later Princeton University) and a signatory of the American Declaration of Independence in 1776 (Wilson 2006). That declaration came during a war in which Culloden veteran Hugh Mercer served as a brigadier-general for George Washington's forces; the landmark tree which marks the site of his death in battle is the centrepiece of panel US07. US24 shows that great symbol of America, the Statue of Liberty, swathed in tartan in tribute to National Tartan Day (Sim, 2011). In Canada meanwhile Panel CA08 commemorates the Confederation of Canada and the Scots who were its leading advocates, whilst CA18 features a large red maple leaf to proudly proclaim that Glasgow-born Sir John A MacDonal became Canada's first prime minister, and that it was Lesmahagow-born Alexander Muir who penned the popular anthem 'Maple Leaf Forever'. In Australia, Panel AU01 depicts Captain James Cook, son of a Scots Borderer, and Alexander Dalrymple who was a key proponent of Cook's expedition in search of the unknown southern continent (Fry, 2013). The First Fleet, on which travelled the first British settlers, is shown on AU02. Two panels (AU03 and AU04) show Lachlan Macquarie and his wife Elizabeth, identifying the former as the 'Father of Australia'.

The famous song ‘Waltzing Matilda’, so strongly recognisable as an Australian anthem, is the subject of Panel AU11 on account of its lyrics being written by Banjo Paterson, son of a migrant from Lanarkshire, who set the words to an old Scots tune recalled for him by Christina Macpherson.

The significance of these examples is the extent to which they overtly identify Scots and their descendants with founding political moments or important cultural markers such as anthems and songs. It is possible to discern in this the importance of diaspora identity in the formation of new national identities during the creation and evolution of new nation-states. The role of migrants, specifically Scottish migrants in this case, in the foundation narratives of America, Canada and Australia is therefore significant, and the importance of that role in the contemporary diaspora’s psyche is being reflected in these panels. This should be interpreted as evidence that national identities, consciously or otherwise, search for historical roots on which they can rest (Smith 1983). The role of Thomas Cochrane in the liberation of Brazil and Chile (BR01, CL01) is also commemorated in the tapestry, further identifying the importance of foundation narratives to national identities.

All this corresponds with an ethnosymbolist interpretation of identity, as indeed does a study of some of the visual symbols deployed in the tapestry which will follow in chapter six. Unlike identities which could be based upon ancient territorial possession or the tribal *ethnies* described by Smith (1986), new nations based on migratory settlers instead create identities based on their migrants’ roots. This can be done through a deliberate promotion of continuing immigration as a cornerstone of the national identity, the ‘melting pot’ model which is perhaps best represented in the tapestry by the cultural mash-up of Gung Haggis Fat Choy (CA31; Crummy et al, 2015: 185). Or it can be done by reaching into the past, using the vehicle of diaspora identity and the accompanying heritage which has travelled with the migrants and been preserved by their descendants, through which the citizens of the new nation are able to draw upon an inherited legitimacy. The value of that sense of legitimacy is accepted by constructivist modernists, who might perceive such symbols as Tartan Day (now Scotland Week) in the USA as a conscious method of strengthening internal identity (Hobsbawn, 1983). The great St Patrick’s Day parades would serve the same purpose for America’s Irish diaspora populations, drawing the diaspora and national identities together by providing spectacular platforms for the demonstration of shared roots. But however elites might find it useful to harness it and create vehicles for it (Hobsbawn, 1983), the need to belong is a grass-roots reality (Smith, 1983).

What we are seeing in the tapestry panels identified above then is how diaspora identity acts as (and is used as) a strengthening agent in the national identity of settler-based new countries, giving it a lasting sense of cultural legitimacy and satisfying citizens' need for a sense of belonging which has heritage and roots, rather than a more recent and politically constructed identity (Brah, 1996). Scottish diaspora identity is therefore not only coexisting with national identities, it is supporting them positively. This appears to be supported by the results of the questionnaire discussed in chapter four, which show that contributors to the tapestry might define their ethnicity based on genealogical roots but identify their nationality clearly with the host country: 10 defined themselves as Canadian compared to 3 Canadian-British and none as Scots-Canadian, for example (see chapter four). So whilst Americans 'have always thought of themselves as a new people,' free from the baggage of an established history (Onuf, P. in Furtado, 2017), they can yet draw strength and cultural legitimacy from their European heritage. This goes some way to understanding how, in a nation so assertive proud of the symbols of its national identity (Marshall, 2017) the symbols of diaspora identity can also be so fully embraced: the latter does not challenge or override the former.

These observations are largely confined to the New World countries which were formed in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, in the area that modernists would consider as the beginning of nationalism (Anderson, 1983). Diaspora identity does not appear to play a similar role in the national identities of other "new" nations emerging during this period in Europe, such as Italy or Germany. It appears to be clear therefore that the diaspora identity survives strongest and most meaningfully as a collective identity in countries which were forged almost completely through colonial settlement (Canada, USA, Australia, New Zealand), rather than in places where there were existing or developing identities into which the migrants could be subsumed. In Poland, for example, the Scottish communities were eventually assimilated despite their attempts to maintain discreet institutions (Kay 2006).

With that in mind it is important to view the formation of new settler-based nations in the context of their relationships with indigenous peoples. Indigenous cultures are capable of providing territorial legitimacy to new nations in a way that diaspora heritage cannot. The tapestry reveals something of this tension within the American national identity through its depiction of the Trail of Tears, the forcible removal of the Cherokee in 1838 (US14). On the whole however the tapestry portrays a positive image of the engagement between Scottish immigrants and native peoples: panels US12, US13 and US15A present stories of intermarriage, as do CA11 and CA19 in Canada, the latter explicitly commemorating the First Nations wives of Scottish employees of the Hudson's Bay Company. Panel CA22 shows how the Métis community was formed through the intermarriage of

immigrant traders (including Scots), developing a distinct culture with a clearly Gaelic flavour which still has an influence in Manitoba. The positive relationship between Lord Selkirk and Chief Peguis in the early eighteenth century is commemorated in CA24.

In Australia however, relations with indigenous populations are not discussed in the tapestry until panel AU25 which commemorates Francis Dunbar Warren, son of a Scottish migrant, who established a mission station which also encouraged traditional aboriginal ways of life. AU31 depicts Charles Duguid, an aboriginal rights campaigner. But these are both twentieth century stories: earlier tales of Scottish involvement in clearing Aboriginal populations are not featured, although they are part of the academic discourse (McCarthy and MacKenzie, 2016). MacIntyre suggests that it is only relatively recently that Australians have begun to consider their country's history as predating 1788 (Furtado, 2017: 184-5). This move towards reconnection with Aboriginal heritage and culture, effectively the coming together of historic homeland and host-country identities, may be in part reflected in those few panels listed above, whilst the overwhelming predominance of white imagery reflects both the lingering tradition of Australia as a “new” country with an imported cultural identity.

Of course it would be surprising to see many negative narratives appearing in the tapestry, but as has been shown with the slave plantations in Jamaica it would not have been impossible if there had been someone pressing for it. But a representation of a positive role in racial relations is evidently important to some, including project team member Yvonne Murphy from South Africa (now living in Scotland), who stitched a panel on Moors at the court of King James IV (GE03A). This panel was added to the list in the later round of designs, and was entered into the Global section of the tapestry. The evidence of the tapestry suggests there is a perception amongst diaspora Scots that, or else that the diaspora is keen to present a narrative that, Scots made a positive contribution to relations with indigenous peoples and have a tradition of promoting tolerance and diversity. In this way the diaspora identity is able both to provide the host national identity with an established cultural heritage for its immigrant population and also act as a bridge to the cultures which can provide the territorial legitimacy which would otherwise be missing. There is perhaps more work which can be done on this relationship between diaspora and indigenous identities and their relationship with national identity in New World countries. It is best summed up on the tapestry by panel US11, designed and stitched in Florida by members of the Native Nations Museum: ‘We are all related’.

Conclusion

The narrative content of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry is extraordinary in its breadth and variety. Like the sample of contributors reached by our questionnaire, the content is dominated by panels relating to English-speaking communities in New World countries, a reflection of both the contemporary Scottish diaspora and some of the unavoidable limitations of the project's reach. In a broad sense, the tapestry succeeds in representing the geographical spread of Scottish migration and overseas influence since the late medieval period (there are a few earlier examples in the Irish set). Earlier phases of migration, particularly pre-eighteenth century, tend however to be represented by fewer panels than the numbers of migrants involved might fairly deserve, with two or three panels often representing the experiences of tens of thousands of people. The geographic and chronological proportions of the tapestry are largely in alignment in that the earlier phases are focussed primarily on Europe until the opening up of North America, Australasia and Southern Asia to large numbers of migrants in various stages from the eighteenth century onwards.

The breadth of content themes presented in the panels reflects the diversity of experience Scottish migrants have had over the centuries, and the variety of fields in which they have had influence. They range from the military and political to agriculture, industry, medicine and exploration. The legacy of this engagement is primarily portrayed as positive, including in racial contexts and in regard to the foundation narratives of new national identities. There are a few acknowledgements that the Scottish international narrative is not exclusively positive, however, but whilst involvement with slave plantations is represented there is no depiction of overtly imperial activity such as military conquest and the portrayal of relations with indigenous peoples seems somewhat sanitised – a reflection of contemporary sensibilities rather than universal historical reality.

The breadth of the content portrayed in the tapestry helps us to take an overview of the Scottish diaspora which can then be judged against theoretical frameworks. In particular it has been shown how the Scottish experience relates to Cohen's classifications of diaspora as being either victim, labour, trade, imperial or de-territorial (2008). It has been demonstrated that in fact the Scottish diaspora fits each of these classifications at different times and in different locations, suggesting that no single classification is applicable to the whole history of the diaspora. Just as it can be argued that there is no perfect model for the development of nations and national identities and that each must be assessed case-by-case (Özirimli, 2010), so too it seems for diasporas. Cohen's categories,

particularly trade and imperial but also victim and labour, are not mutually exclusive and can be interdependent or even undistinguishable, especially in a case as varied and wide-ranging as Scotland's diaspora. The conclusion therefore is that whilst the broad classifications may hold for comparing some diasporas they can only be applied to specific phases of Scottish migration and sometimes to specific geographical locations. This in turn supports the subdivision of the Scottish diaspora, perhaps most obviously into Old World and New World, a division followed by many publications (for example Devine, 2011; Bueltmann et al, 2013) which begin their focus from around 1750.

A number of panels have been identified which relate to the foundation myths/narratives of countries within the diaspora. Although these include Brazil and Chile, the most important appear to be Canada, the USA and Australia, where the importance of Scots in the foundation and development of the new countries encourages us to look at diaspora identity's connectivity with national identity in these places. The tapestry appears to indicate diaspora identity plays an important supporting role in the new identity, not only coexisting in harmony but in fact actively strengthening the legitimacy of the national identity by providing access to a cultural and ancestral heritage which cannot otherwise be provided by constructed nations. This connects to existing research on hyphenated identities but also prompts further work on how immigrant diaspora identity connects with those of indigenous peoples in the context of the creation and evolution of an overarching national identity accessible to all.

These considerations appear to support the theory that a need to belong and a search for heritage roots are important facets of identity formation and management. Even in a modern constructed nation, these needs have to be satisfied for the citizens and in the absence of true territorial legitimacy a new nation may well make use of its inherited immigrant identities. This supports both the ethnosymbolist approach, which accepts the importance of heritage roots, cultural traditions and their symbols, and a more constructivist approach which suggests that need is encouraged and manipulated to strengthen the new identity. It is therefore necessary to consider these issues further, for which an examination of the visual symbolism within the tapestry becomes illuminating.

Chapter Six:

The Designs

“Oh the artistry! Oh the history!”

Donna Forray, Manitoba, Canada

Introduction

It has now been established that the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry provides a powerful and engaging overview of hundreds of years of Scottish migratory history. It was stitched by over a thousand hands and reveals much both about the history of the Scottish diaspora and about how it is perceived by its members. It has also been seen that, just as the diaspora conforms to no one single type, there is no simple formula to explain how each panel came into being. Instead each of the 305 pieces is the result of research, discussion, inspiration, and often the serendipities of proactivity from either the project team in Scotland or individual agents around the world. Some panels had individual champions or committed interest groups who drove their content and design, others emerged from specific researches or publications. The tapestry is a community artwork, a reflection of the many minds and hands behind it.

But it is an artwork nonetheless, and as the largest visual representation of the Scottish diaspora it must be considered in the context of its illustrative power as well as its narrative content. Illustrators have the capacity to include multiple layers of messaging and meaning in a single image (Brazell and Davies, 2013), and through those messages the audience is stimulated into further thought and the construction of narratives beyond the immediate content (Kafalenos, 2001). The tapestry must therefore be viewed as an artwork as well as a record of historical events, as only that combined analysis enables a full picture to emerge as to how the diaspora is being presented. Examining the visual content of the tapestry, especially once the relative levels of influences have been understood and the authorial voices identified, helps us to understand the importance of specific types of symbols to the diaspora identity. In some cases these are purely aesthetic, but in others they are significant in leading to conclusions about the diaspora's sense of itself and of Scotland.

This chapter will develop ideas introduced and discussed previously relating to the levels of influence contributors had over content and, in particular here, design. This will allow us to understand whose perceptions of the diaspora the tapestry is really representing. Those panels which stand out as being particularly clearly designed by those other than the artist Andrew Crummy will be highlighted and examined for their significance. The analysis will then move on to consider common symbols which recur in the designs which may be important to our reading of the tapestry, which will be related to our existing understanding of Scottish identity symbols. Further discussion will then emerge about the relative balance of positive and negative imagery, demonstrating the overwhelmingly positive messaging of the tapestry, particularly in the way negative imagery is used. By natural progression this will in turn lead to consideration of the balance between the depiction of people and of places, which leads to important conclusions about the importance of built heritage and to the introduction of the concept of memorial diaspora communities.

Direct and indirect influence

The panels of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry were, with a few notable exceptions, all designed by the hand of Scottish artist Andrew Crummy. He had previously designed the *Prestonpans Tapestry* and was in the final stages of designing the *Great Tapestry of Scotland* when the diaspora project began. In the years following the completion of the project, Crummy would also go on to design the *Mount Felix Tapestry* in Walton-on-Thames, England, and several smaller tapestry projects in Scotland. Creating so many bespoke illustrations for a single project would have been challenge enough, but the brief for this tapestry was deliberately collaborative in its approach. Crummy summed it up in the tapestry's official guide: 'the brief was to listen to the voices of those in other stories and try and tell their story in a visual format' (Crummy et al, 2015: 365). This reaches to the heart of the project, the objective of creating an authentic representation of the diaspora's own interpretation of its heritage.

Such collaboration in contemporary illustration is not unique, and there are artists and designers who seek to engage audiences in the processes of the illustration rather than focussing purely on the output (Vormittag, 2014). In order for Crummy to achieve the objective of engaging diaspora communities, which could be simultaneously subject, contributor and audience, he had to interpret large amounts of information and imagery from all around the world. Timetables were tight, distances great, and so direct communication with the artist was often filtered through nominated contact points in each diaspora community (Strategy Group Minutes, 03/12) and then on to project team members. Research

was being undertaken by the artist himself, other members of the project team, unquantified numbers of academics and amateur researchers, and of course the stitchers themselves. Understandably the minutes of the project team meetings make regular reference to the need to avoid the building of a backlog of panels, as any delays in design would create difficulties for the volunteer stitchers (Strategy Group Minutes, 01/12).

In this ‘organic approach’ to the design, information was usually passed to Crummy at least at the first stage through Hart and Murphy, ‘sometimes edited, sometimes not’ (Crummy et al, 2015: 366). They were therefore the initial gatekeepers, as expressed in chapter three, although there is no evidence that they turned down viable proposals. Andrew designed an initial black and white drawing, based on a grid system which he created for the purpose, translating the content he had received into an illustration. This, he says, was designed to then be changed after review by the contributors in the diaspora: ‘I would do a drawing then the stitcher or local historian would sketch over that drawing, sometimes making radical changes’ (Crummy et al, 2015: 366). If a contributor’s first opportunity to influence the tapestry was in the proposal of content, the second comes at this stage, where there is a direct opportunity to affect the visual messaging of the illustration.

Some contributors clearly took this opportunity to influence the designs whilst others did not. The survey undertaken for this study sought to discover the extent to which the panels were influenced by those who stitched. In response to question 28, which asked who the respondent thought determined the subject of their panel, the results were split exactly 50/50 between those who believed it was the tapestry team in Scotland and those who believed it was themselves or fellow stitchers, others in their community or local academics. This may reflect the fact that some contributors were removed from the decision-making processes and therefore did not know where the project team had sourced its stories. In contrast, 58% of respondents felt that they had lots of influence or moderate influence over the subject and content of their panels (question 29). These results suggest that the project was successful to a large degree in building a true sense of collaboration over the content. Just 4.5% of respondents to this question wished they could have had more influence. Surprisingly however just 48% felt that having a direct influence was either very important or quite important, a figure that rises to 64.5% if the panels stitched in Scotland are considered in isolation.

The fact that some panel designs required or received very little amendment when sent out to the contributors for review should be seen as a tribute to Andrew Crummy’s skills in interpreting the

information he received. As one survey respondent stated, he ‘discerned what was truly the most emotional part of our story, he requested some pertinent pictures,’ and came up with a design which was accepted. Another confirmed that whilst Crummy had based a design on information they had provided for him, on receipt of the sketch she ‘added a few extra bits’, whilst a New Zealand based contributor found the project team ‘wonderfully open to my suggestions’. When Crummy sent the first sketch of IT01A to the researcher, in order to gauge how responsive the artist was able to be even at an advanced stage of the project, an overhaul of the initial scheme was proposed. After requests for additional information and images, a completely redesigned image was returned within days. This is a process therefore which led to the presentation of final designs which were acceptable to the contributors who had proposed the content and/or were volunteering to stitch them. This level of influence over design limited Crummy’s artistic hand to an extent, but increased the authenticity of the output.

Fig. 6-1. Panel CA07, the design of which was clearly determined directly by the contributors. The original sketch design was more complex and did not show the buildings and monument. This demonstrates the importance of built heritage to identity maintenance.

A small number of panels can readily be identified as being particularly heavily influenced by other hands than Crummy’s in their design. From Prince Edward Island in Canada, panel CA07 stands out as being stylistically distinct from all other panels in the cluster (Fig. 6-1). Although it retains the compass point and circle motif of many of the panels, the main illustrative content is a selection of people and places drawn discretely from another, not bound by a central coordinating focus. Less obviously designed by another as its denser imagery and central focus makes for easier association with its neighbours, panel CA09 was based on the winning entry from a design competition at Mallaig

High School, Lachie Robinson. He was thirteen years old at the time, and although Andrew Crummy modified some aspects to ensure the design was suitable for embroidery, the substantive elements are all Robinson's. The most obviously distinct panel is US11 from Florida, which is also stitched onto slightly different fabric to the other panels and to a slightly smaller size. As with CA09 (Fig. 5-6) the images within show several discrete features without a single focus, although still bound within the circular outline of Andrew Crummy's grid mechanism. The same is true of a recently added panel commemorating American presidents with Scottish roots, a panel designed by one of the stitchers in England in 2017 and not officially enrolled in the exhibition. The core building blocks Crummy's grid system provided for each panel are therefore important in creating sufficient uniformity across the whole exhibition for it to retain an aesthetic unity. The imagery of panels CA07, CA09 and US11 will all be discussed further within this chapter.

It is therefore to be understood that the tapestry, although with only a few exceptions drawn by the hand of a single artist, the influences upon that artist's final design were varied. Contributors across the diaspora had the opportunity at the very least to authorise the final designs, and if they wished even to go so far as to redraft them directly. Less directly, Crummy's design choices were influenced by the imagery of the photographs and other source images that were sent to him by contributors and researchers, and the nature of the content being submitted. So whilst it is not possible to apply a single model to every panel in terms of who determined what aspects of the illustration, it is possible to conclude that the authorial voice of the panels is sufficiently rooted in the diaspora itself to be accepted as an authentic representation of those who were engaged in the project. The symbolism of how they have chosen to present their stories, or at least that they have authorised the artist to make use of in presenting them, are therefore potentially revealing as to how the contemporary diaspora engages with its heritage and identity.

Positive and negative imagery

'A visual representation of a single scene is not a narrative', but is powerful enough to trigger in the viewer the creation of further mental imagery and a perception of a background narrative spreading wider than the individual snapshot shown (Kafalenos, 2001: 138). This is in many respects the key to successful illustration, layering meanings and messages which can be interpreted by the audience and generate the desired response. The panels of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry are no different: unlike those of the Prestonpans Tapestry the panels do not form part of a continuous narrative sequence, and

single images must convey wider significances. This is an interpretative challenge, which is why the project team provided first guide leaflets and then a downloadable app so that visitors to the exhibitions can be aided in their reading of the illustrations. It is also why the imagery of illustrations is so revealing, as reading the symbols helps to invite deeper perception of, in this case, how the Scottish diaspora is being presented by the project's contributors.

In this context it is important therefore to understand the balance within the design of the tapestry between positive and negative imagery, as this has the capacity to affect the viewer's perception not only of the artwork but the story behind it. If, for example, the overriding impression of the tapestry was of burdened souls, persecuted and driven from their homeland, would put the narrative of the tapestry at odds with current research suggesting that the majority in fact emigrated in favour of the positive new opportunities (McCarthy & MacKenzie, 2016). To do otherwise however might be at odds instead with popular preconception that the Scottish diaspora experience is predominantly routed in the Clearances (Devine, 2011). These waters are not without trouble: the pro-independence Scottish newspaper *The National* reported complaints on 21 July 2017 over an exhibition on the Isle of Arran which contextualised the local Clearances as part of a wider movement towards agricultural reform. Despite having been in place for a decade, this presentation has now been described as misleading and sanitised. The balance of positive versus negative imagery within the tapestry might therefore go some way to revealing how the diaspora views its position within this tension over perceptions.

The project team was certainly conscious that there are negative narratives associated with aspects of the Scottish diaspora, not just in terms of the victim diaspora narratives of the Clearances, but also in terms of Scots' relations with indigenous peoples (McCarthy & MacKenzie, 2016), their active and important role in the conquest and management of the imperial projects (Fry, 2001), and their involvement in and profit-making from black slavery (Devine, 2003). As Andrew Crummy himself put it, 'like all nations we were and are a mixed bunch and there as a positive side to our diaspora and a darker side too' (Crummy et al, 2015: 365). It has already been remarked that there is an absence of military imagery covering much of the imperial period between the end of the Napoleonic Wars and the start of the First World War. In total only 18 panels show soldiers or warriors armed or dressed for battle; another four show uniformed military officers serving in a civic capacity. Of these few relate to anything from 1815 onwards. Un-uniformed combatants face-off at the Battle of Seven Oaks, a shoot-out over trade rivalries in 1816 Canada (CA23), and uniformed soldiers accompany Lachlan Macquarie, himself in scarlet uniform, as Governor of New South Wales from 1810-21, but these are exceptions to the overall trend. There is clearly no overall reticence in displaying soldiers and warriors in the tapestry from earlier periods, as they take centre stage on panels in Sweden (SE01),

Poland (PL02), Russia (RU01, RU02), France (FR02), and Portugal (PT01), Ireland (IE03, IE04) and England (GBE08). All these examples relate to pre-eighteenth century events or personalities, and all to Old World contexts. Does the service of tens of thousands of Scots in foreign service in the seventeenth century (Miller, 2012) offend contemporary sensitivities less than the service of Scottish regiments in British imperial conflicts in the nineteenth (Fry, 2001)? Possibly so, not least as it avoids discussion about imperial heritage which can be found embarrassing or uncomfortable in contemporary society (Johnson, 2003). Evidently nineteenth century military themes did not find champions when the tapestry content was being collated, indicating an area of the diaspora narrative which is not actively embraced. The legacy is visible nonetheless: bagpipe making in Sialkot, Pakistan, for example, traces its origins to the supply demands of Scottish regiments (PK01).

Later era military themes are generally presented to provoke feelings of collective loss the hardship of war, rather than military adventurism or glory. This is done in CA45 with a plethora of poppies and bowed heads and raised hands, the panel commemorating Lt-Colonel John McCrae who wrote the poem *In Flanders Fields*. Tangles of barbed wire surmount the trenches at the very bottom of the panel, evocative and recognisable images of the First World War. These same symbols appear again in GBE17, commemorating the Liverpool Scottish Regiment. The horrors of war are discretely implied by the barbed wire and muddy ground, a striking contrast to the tall upright soldier in his dress uniform. A roll-call of evocative place-names surrounds the pane, including Passchendaele and the Somme. The design is simple, the background far emptier than most panels, which makes it all the power potent. Elsewhere, the nurses of the Scottish Women's Medical Unit aid the wounded servicemen under the medieval arches of Royaumont Abbey (FR09), all heads solemnly bowed just as most are in the panel commemorating Confederate Army nurse Kate Cumming, although the sense of this American Civil War panel is a little more chaotic (US15). The bowed heads of these military-themed panels evoke a sense of sorrow, and are a symbol which recurs elsewhere within the tapestry.

This includes panels tackling Scotland's relationship with slavery, another aspect of the diaspora narrative which invites controversy, potential embarrassment or even denial (Mullen, 2009). Unlike imperial warfare, however, it has already been shown that in Professor Sir Geoff Palmer this face of the diaspora did find a champion. Not only were slave plantations included in the tapestry in order to show that the project was not ignoring these complex issues, but Palmer was also invited to speak at several gatherings and exhibitions of the tapestry in order to contextualise the content and stimulate further discussion. The design of panel JM02 (Fig. 6-2) is straightforward and the colour palette muted: an African slave bends his back under a heavy burden of cut cane that bears the names of plantations with Scottish names; his clothes are covering in the names of plantation owners, and the

circle around him record Scottish surnames which can still be found on Jamaica. The message is clear: the Scottish involvement in slave-run plantations was considerable.

Fig. 6-2. Panel JM02, recording the role of Scots in Jamaican plantations.

In panel JM03, slave women carrying their master's children are seated with heads bowed, whilst the black abolitionist Robert Wedderburn holds out the sixpence with which he was dismissed from his father's door at Inveresk Lodge. Flanking plantation owner James Wedderburn is the grim sight of his hanging father, whose execution as a Jacobite in 1746 propelled Wedderburn into seeking a means to revive his fortunes overseas. The hanging figure seems to invoke a sense of irony as to how those escaping persecution themselves could go on to repress others. The imagery of these panels is powerful and clear, even though JM03 juxtaposes rather colourful landscape design behind the key messaging. This somehow serves to prevent the image appearing overtly judgemental, whilst its very presence faces up to the more challenging sides of the diaspora's history. At least one visitor to the tapestry exhibition was left confused however: 'several exhibits seem to celebrate the Scots role in slavery!' (Comments Books, 23/08/14).

Slavery features in several African panels also, but here the imagery is rather different. In ZA03 we find the story of 217 Galla children who were being shipped from Ethiopia to Arabian slave markets in 1888 when their transports were stopped by the British navy. The children were taken to the Scottish mission at Lovedale where they received accommodation and education. The panel shows two of them in the foreground, heads bowed in misery with chained hands. Behind them, two others

raise their heads high, their shackles broken and hanging loose and books placed in their hands. Broken chains are also depicted beneath the label 'abolitionist' around the portrait of David Livingstone in the first Malawi panel (MW01). Here the message is simpler than the earlier slavery-related panels in Jamaica, the negative imagery of slavery transcended by the positive messages of Scots' roles in opposing it in Africa.

Similar imagery of bound hands and bowed heads appears in panel US02, which depicts the transportation of Scottish prisoners of war to New England in the early 1650s. A Cromwellian soldier drives them over the sea at the point of his pike, emphasising the enforced nature of these Scots' migration after their defeats at the battles of Dunbar and Worcester. Many of those who were sold off as indentured servants went on however to secure their liberty and make new lives for themselves. But in the tapestry the imagery is of ragged clothes and misfortune, an unpromising beginning to a new life.

The portrayal of forcible eviction of Scots from their homeland is found not only in the Dunbar/Worcester panel, but as expected it also appears in relation to the Highland Clearances over a century later. In the early Canadian panels there are also images of heads bowed in melancholy and hands clasped in quiet prayer (CA03), and ships to symbolise the departure from home, including the famous *Hector*. The unloading of chests (CA05) emphasises the starting of a new life, whilst the small log cabin surrounded by immense trees, the new settler gazing upon them with a small hand axe, evoke a sense of the difficulties migrants here faced in carving out a new life (CA06). But the panel which uses the most negative imagery in its presentation of this phase of the migration is that which was designed in Scotland by competition winner Lachie Robinson (CA09, Fig 5-6). The Clearances are presented with striking effectiveness: flames lapping around the old crofts on one side of the panel, whilst great flocks of woolly sheep are moved in on the right to replace their former inhabitants. In the centre, beneath a brooding sunset over a turbulent sea, a woman waves farewell to her kin as they rose their boat towards a waiting ship. It is a scene of loss and forced migration, and it therefore sits well with panel CA10, 'the Settlers' Lament', with its bowed heads and melancholic lament. The music, symbolised by the fiddle, is however the device which binds the old life to the new; a symbol of the importance of cultural continuity to the migrant communities in Canada. Panel CA08 is a striking contrast to these two panels: a bright red maple leaf frames an image of Province House, a far cry from any log cabin, flanked by some of the well-dressed diaspora Scots who helped give birth to Canadian Confederation. This serves as a useful snapshot of the general pattern of the tapestry: the negative imagery when it appears can be very powerful, but it is generally overpowered by the positives which surround it.

The same can be said for the way in which Scots' relationships with indigenous peoples are portrayed. It is interesting that many Indian panels do not depict people at all, and Scots and Indians do not appear together except in panels illustrating the establishment of religious and educational institutions (IN16A, IN17A), and the celebration of the meeting of Patrick Geddes and Rabindranath Tagore in 1917 (IN17; Fraser, 2008). This is clearly not a complete picture of the interaction between Scots in India and the local population, but it is one which avoids controversy and focusses on the positive work of missionaries and educationalists. The same patterns are visible in the smaller sets relating to African countries.

Relations with indigenous peoples in North America are much more directly addressed, but as was noted in the previous chapter the negative face of the relationship is underplayed. Chief William McIntosh is portrayed in a combination of European and Native American dress (US12) symbolism evoking messages of cultural interconnectivity which disguise the fact that McIntosh was torn between two nations with incompatible goals (Chapman, 2005). Chief John Ross however is shown on two occasions in purely European dress (US13, US14), and on the second occasion is clearly displayed as a defender of the native Cherokee. The latter are huddled together and shrouded, the foremost among them with the now expected display of a bowed head, whilst a uniformed American soldier stands uncomfortably behind them to enforce their removal. In front of the Cherokee John Ross leans forward with his head high and his hand raised in a vain but determined attempt to halt the removal of his people. In Canada there are several panels recording interrelationships between Scots immigrants and native nations, but it is the simple handshake between Lord Selkirk and Chief Peguis which stands out (CA24), the hands joined by the words 'a steady friend'. A simple Christian cross behind them symbolises Peguis' conversion to Christianity in 1838. The message is clearly one of mutual respect and amity.

There are no aboriginal peoples depicted at all in the New Zealand panels, and they appear in only two of the forty Australian panels. The first of these was stitched in Matcham, New South Wales, and shows the boy who accompanied William Turnbull's 500 mile cattle-drive in 1847 (AU07). The other is AU25, showing Francis Dunbar Warren, with his de-facto wife (mixed marriages not being legal at the time) Laura Buralda and their seven children. The message here is a positive one, about a second-generation diaspora Scot cutting against the prejudices of his time and encouraging traditional ways of life. Aboriginal rights campaigner Charles Duguid is depicted in AU31, but his portrait is the dominant feature of this relative simple design, the man and the Christian cross delivering their

message alone. There are no panels portraying the negative role of some Scots and their descendants in relation to native peoples, however important the impacts of those activities on, for example, the original occupants of Queensland (McCarthy and MacKenzie, 2016).

The dominance of positive messaging in the designs of the tapestry is striking, moving, and perhaps misleading. Although conscious effort has been made in several cases to broach controversial aspects of the diaspora narrative, it is clear that there is a bias in the tapestry's content away from difficult areas such as involvement in imperial warfare, occupation and administration, and negative cases of engagement with other races and indigenous peoples. But identity can be self-selecting in its symbols, especially a diaspora identity in which members have a degree of choice regarding the extent of their engagement and its proportionality against alternative identities, and it is not surprising therefore that the tapestry was not viewed as an appropriate vehicle for presenting a deliberately challenging and provocative narrative. As a result it would not be unfair to consider its presentation of the historical experience as somewhat sanitised.

The symbols of Scottishness

There are a large number of common symbols which occur as common tropes identified with either Scotland or Scottish-ness. The most obvious are tartan and Highland dress, thistles, the St Andrew's Cross (saltire), bagpipes, Highland games and Scotch whisky (Bhandari, 2014). The poetry of Robert Burns and the ancient Scottish clans qualify too (Bhandari, 2014). And whilst some of these symbols are often perceived as twee, stereotyped, or disconnected from contemporary Scottish culture, they are also universally recognisable and readily embraced by the Scottish tourist industry (Bhandari, 2014). They are also important part of Scottish cultural identity abroad, as evidenced by the immensely popular Highland games events in North America for example, and the growing importance of ancestral tourism (Visit Scotland, 2013). When the tapestry was touring Canada in 2016, there was sufficient demand to justify the exhibition manager preparing a list of which panels featured particular surnames.

In the early stages of the tapestry's development there was some anxiety amongst the project team that so many of these universal symbols of Scottish-ness would be proposed as content for panels that considerable discussion took place on how to present them. In October 2012 the team proposed to

‘avoid repetition of the universal components of diaspora’ (Strategy Group Minutes, 03/12). Instead there would be a specific set of panels made to address these themes, which would be stitched locally around Prestonpans and be displayed in between exhibition clusters ‘to sustain interest for visitors’ (Strategy Group Minutes, 03/12). The themes of these universal panels were already identified as including Burns Nights, Highland games, dancing, golf and whisky. Discussions continued into April the following year, when it was decided that there should be an introduction panel and, at the exhibition’s end, a panel depicting the international renown of the song of parting, *Auld Lang Syne* (Strategy Group Minutes, 05/13). This process led to the creation of the Global cluster, the smallest of the discrete sets. In fifteen panels such themes as ceilidh and country dancing, Burns suppers, whisky, sport, music and St Andrew’s societies are all covered, along with the more surprising inclusions of Moors at the Court of King James IV (GE03A) and the abstractly depicted Ancient Trade Routes (GE03), the latter being stitched in Dublin. Tartan appears on eight of the fifteen panels; bagpipes, whisky and thistles each appear on two. By contrast, the *Auld Lang Syne* panel features nothing overtly Scottish at all, just a circle of people diverse in age, sex and ethnicity, linking hands to the familiar tune (GE02).

The Global cluster represents a pre-emptive strike by the project team against a simplistic expectation of how some diaspora communities would wish to express themselves. By creating a discrete space for celebrating all Highland games, there would be no case for including individual panels for specific events however well attended they might. However as Crummy admitted, ‘initial simplistic perceptions were quickly dispelled’ (Crummy et al, 2015: 365). In truth, some of these panels reveal more about the way that Scotland perceives its diaspora than vice versa, as the reality of the project was that these overt symbols of Scottish-ness were not the way in which most diaspora Scots or communities wanted to be portrayed. Instead they wished to tell narratives, to demonstrate personal connections or important local stories which demonstrated the authenticity of their heritage. This is largely supported by the contributors’ survey: 62% of those who answered question 18 were not currently members of a Scottish society (such as St Andrew’s society or clan association), but 67% who answered the previous question *had* researched their own ancestral roots. This suggests that many of those engaging in the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry project saw their diaspora identity as something personal or familial, and that the big noise aspects of diaspora identity either did not appeal or did not truly represent their own perceptions of it.

This does not mean however that overt symbols of Scottishness do not appear in the tapestry outside of the Global cluster. The Corby Highland Games do enjoy a panel (GBE06), whilst tartan kilts, skirts or plaids and Scots bonnets appear in six of New Zealand’s eleven panels. Australia is largely

immune, with just one appearance of tartan in its entire vast set, as are the African countries. In Chile, Victorian department store owner Robert Riddell is beautifully depicted in full Highland dress (CL01, Fig. 5-2), and a saltire flutters on the San Andres golf course in Argentina (AR02A). The first Campbell to arrive on Jamaica does so in JM01 wearing a muted plaid about his waist, whilst in the USA shoulder-plaids are worn by two iconic females, Flora Macdonald (US10) and the Statue of Liberty (US24). No fewer than seven saltires appear in US25, the panel depicting the mountain climber John Milligan who always carries one on his climbs. He worked on the panel himself. There is a piper in Highland dress in Rotterdam (NL11) and mercenaries march in plaids in both Poland and Sweden (PL02, SE01), but otherwise there is little overtly Scottish symbolism in the European and Baltic clusters. A striking tartan doublet and matching bonnet in Lithuania, with a thistle added for good measure, make a notable exception in panel LT01.

Fig. 6-3. Panel CA05 from Prince Edward Island, showing 18th century migrants unloading their kist on arrival in Canada. Note the distinctively Highland dress.

Overtly Scottish symbols are most common in the Canadian set however, where tartan shawls make a number of appearances, often on forlorn looking women in a clear attempt to emphasise of their displacement from the Scottish Highlands. In March 2013 Tanja Buelmann, one of the many research contributors involved in providing advice on the Canadian panels queried the historical veracity of depicting migrants in their Highland dress (CA05, above) and cautioning against over-emphasising the sense of lamentation on arrival at St John's Island (now Prince Edward Island). After this discussion the design for panel CA06 was altered to give a male figure trousers rather than a plaid. There is nevertheless an unusual concentration of tartan, kilts and bonnets and the Gaelic language, as well as reference to musical traditions; all symbols of a particularly Highland form of diaspora identity which remains strong in eastern Canada.

Perhaps the boldest example of the use of Scottish symbols in a panel is IN21, which features Baron Sirdar Iqbal Singh. Here we see tartan, thistles, and Robert Burns and his poetry, all brought together in a beautifully embroidered panel stitched in North Berwick. The design reflects the interests of Baron Singh himself, who attended the official launch of the tapestry wearing the very tartan jacket in which he is depicted. Importantly, this is a reverse diaspora panel: Singh is a migrant *into* Scotland rather than out. The symbols of Scotland which he has adopted within his identity are not so strongly concentrated as here in any other single image in the tapestry.

In the preceding panel however (IN20), tartan, whisky and haggis are nearly contrasted with the banana leaf and traditional Indian delicacies which might be served upon one during a celebration. Saltires also form subtle backdrops to three Indian panels (IN16A, IN17A, IN18), each of which commemorate the establishment of schools or colleges. This may have been an attempt to associate their content therefore, especially as two of the panels were added in the later wave of panels. Mention must also here be made of panel PK01, which opens the Pakistan set. Here the relatively simple design focusses attention on a set of tartan bagpipes. But here the symbols of Scotland are somewhat subverted: Sialkot in Pakistan is a renowned manufacturing centre for pipes and Highland dress, home of the first company which exported bagpipes *into* Scotland!

The tapestry does therefore include many of the visual symbols most readily and popularly associated with Scotland and Scottish-ness, but their use on the whole is subtle and usually relevant to specific content. Rarely does the use of tartan appear gratuitous or the symbolism appear overly contrived. Although it is possible that this is due to the success of the Global cluster in concentrating much of that symbolism in a specific set of illustrations, but actually the nature of the content being proposed for the tapestry suggests such overt Scottish-ness was never likely to be dominant. Flags are not a prominent feature of the tapestry, despite its international nature, perhaps because although they are powerful symbols they are so fundamental to the sense of national identity that they are difficult to correlate with the global nature of a diaspora one (Marshall, 2007). Perhaps tartan should be considered as a surrogate for the saltire, equally identifiable but free from geographical or political boundaries. It also offers a challenge for embroiderers, which some volunteers would relish and therefore encourage in design. Overall however there is a lightness of touch to the overtly Scottish symbolism in the tapestry when viewed as a whole, and this is indicative of a more personal approach to diaspora identity which searches for legitimacy rather than show. The symbols which should be

looked for in the tapestry are not therefore the overt and instantly recognisable ones but the more meaningful ones; not the universal, but the specific.

People and Places

The vast majority of panels, over 82%, feature images of people. Of the remainder, a small number are abstract or design-orientated illustrations, including for example the Book of Kells panel (IE02) stitched in Dublin in Ireland and Port Seton in Scotland. In this panel it is the style of design which best illustrates the cultural connectivity of the Celtic lands, the elements of the Celtic cross forming the centrepiece. Most other non-people focussed panels are dominated by features such as: ships, as with the clipper *City of Adelaide* in AU27; landscapes, as with AQ01 which also commemorates Scots-built ships, this time research vessels in the Antarctic; or animals, as with the sheep and collies commemorated in panel AU17. But these examples stand out as exceptions, and one of the most striking commonalities of most panels is their depiction of people. This in itself should not be surprising, as the story of migration is inevitably one of human experience, but that does not make the observation unimportant. It supports the notion suggested above that diaspora ultimately is about personal connectivity into a wider whole.

This leads to consideration of the types of people who are being depicted, particularly the relationship between famous names and those who are simply representatives of hundreds or thousands of similar experiences. Of course fame is a subjective concept and people might be well-known in their communities or even countries whilst still being utterly unfamiliar to contemporaries in Scotland or other diaspora nations. Some of those who appear in the tapestry certainly have a high historical profile globally however, and the sample is worth exploring. Wilson's *Scots Who Made America* profiles 22 of 'America's Great Scots' (2006), but of these only three appear in the tapestry. They are not surprising choices. John Witherspoon (1723-94), signatory of the Declaration of Independence, leaps from the pages of a book in panel US09, stitched in Princeton where once he was college president. Panel US18 shows the head of Andrew Carnegie (1835-1919), the symbols of his steelworks surrounded by shelves of library books which represent so much of his legacy. Conservationist John Muir (1838-1914) becomes increasingly abstracted in his portraits over panels US19, US20 and US21, becoming one with the landscapes he fought so hard to protect. He does not appear personally in US22, a Californian panel which instead depicts his home in Martinez, now an historic site. Wilson also lists 22 Scots who have influenced America without making it their home.

Of these only two make it into the tapestry, both literary figures and neither featuring in the American set: Robert Burns and Robert Louis Stevenson.

Famous names and what might be termed celebrity diaspora Scots do not in fact feature heavily in the tapestry overall, as this crude experiment comparing Wilson's list supports. That is not to say they do not feature at all. Charles Rennie Mackintosh appears in France (FR08), but it is to tell a side of his story which is perhaps not so well known as his architectural and design achievements in Glasgow. The Italian-Scots singer Paolo Nutini makes a modest appearance in the periphery of panel IT05, an example of contemporary reverse diaspora from Barga, and a raft of famous names adorn the panel of Liverpool Football Club, the 'team of the Macs' (GBE18). David Livingstone and his legacy dominate the Malawi set, as would be expected (Thompson, 2007), surrounded in panel MW01 by the symbols of his mission (compasses, the Bible, broken shackles) but also by colours and designs reflecting African artistic styles. In MW02 the Livingstonia Mission dedicated in his name is surrounded by tribal drums and shields and the flora and fauna of the region, in striking contrast to the mission's European architecture.

The two people who appear most frequently in the tapestry are John Muir, with four panels in the USA set, and Charles Edward Stuart (Bonnie Prince Charlie), who appears in five panels in France, Italy and, more surprisingly, Sweden and the USA. The Jacobite prince (1720-88), like with his ancestor Mary, Queen of Scots (FR04), is one of Scottish history's most famous international characters. He and his cause are important to the Scottish tourism industry – a fact particular evident in 2017, with a large promotional campaign led by Visit Scotland promoting Jacobite heritage sites and exhibitions – and his defeat at Culloden ties into perceptions of the causes of the Highland Clearances. It is perhaps not surprising therefore that Bonnie Prince Charlie appears frequently, especially as the project team in Prestonpans were inevitably tuned in to stories of his connections. After all, he won his first battle at there and is the hero of the *Prestonpans Tapestry* (Johnston, 2013). His father, James Francis Stuart, is depicted in FR05 wearing a coat adorned with oak leaves, a long-established symbol of the Royal Stuarts (Pittock, 2013). Around the exiled Stuarts there existed a diaspora of elites, as well as a wider diaspora of soldiers, clerics and others driven into exile for their support for the dynasty (Cruikshanks and Corp, 1995). Although there were foci in France and Rome, these spread further afield too. The Stuart court in exile lasted for three generations and few of the Jacobite exiles returned home. Although John Muir's story is very different to that of Charles Edward Stuart, they share the fact that they are well known in both Scotland and overseas and are important tourism drivers today. Two of the Jacobite panels and one of the Muir panels were stitched in Scotland.

But these famous names remain the exceptions rather than the rule, and the diaspora is certainly not telling its story wholly through the commemoration of famous names. Some panels depict people who are well known in their particular field, but many more are reflective of ordinary people with extraordinary stories and experiences. In total 146 panels show named individuals, famous or otherwise (it is so subjective a term that it is very difficult to distinguish in some cases), whilst 58 panels show unidentified people who can be deemed to be representative of a wider experience. The message of the latter is also made by the visualisation of family groups (22 panels), which act as powerful symbols of the diaspora's continuity and the shared experience of migration. In Prince Edward Island, a husband and wife face the challenges of forging a new life together, their side-by-side profiles and tartan shawl overlain with the image of the big *Alexander* bearing the Glenalladale Settlers (CA04). Similar imagery is evoked on CA10, although here the faces look in different directions as if from the old life to the new, flanking the fiddle which plays "the Settlers' Lament". Excited children disembark at Waipu in New Zealand, led by their parents to a new life (NZ04), and the Polsons mourn together the loss of their twin babies in 1869. The simple grave beneath the willow tree and the single tear of their mother stand tribute in this muted pastoral panel to some of the hardships experienced by those struggling to carve those new lives out of the frozen earth (NZ06B). In contrast, a century later, the Skedds disembark in 1960s Australia with an air of gentle satisfaction (AU21). At their feet is a ship with the caption '200,000 families': the experience of these three people represents that of so many others who accepted the ten-pound passage incentives (Lunn, 2007). With just 18 panels depicting politicians or royal figures, the emphasis of the tapestry on the ordinary migrants' experience is clear. The same trend is suggested by examples of huts, log cabins, and private dwellings which suggest a focus on the common rather than the exceptional.

Buildings are of great importance in the tapestry and often occupy important positions within the designs. At least 97 panels were coded as containing buildings or cityscapes as key elements of their design. In Rotterdam, church architectures dominates two panels (NL09, NL11), and the Chateau de Saint-Germain-en-Laye stands behind King James VIII in FR05. Over three panels we see, as if through a window, the evolving cityscape of Hong Kong as it develops from its East India Company roots at Canton to the city we might recognise today, by which point no Chinese imagery is visible but the saltire, thistle and bagpipes are (CN10). In most such examples, the representation of specific buildings and recognisable landmarks – the Sydney Harbour Bridge for example (AU09) – helps to root both the audience and the subject in a known landscape. There are at least 21 panels which can be considered as using buildings or constructed landmarks in this way. Sometimes the illustration of particular architectural styles makes a deliberate statement, as in the Malawi example referenced

above which shows a building which is clearly contrasted with the African symbols surrounding it. The baronial style of Robert Dunsmuir's Craigdarroch Castle in British Columbia is deliberately reflective of stone castles in Scotland, a symbol of the coal baron's roots (CA33). Elsewhere in Canada the church architecture, the simple façade and slender steeple, provides a sense of continuity through panels CA25 in Manitoba, CA17 in Montreal, CA02 in Nova Scotia. Religious buildings dominate 15 panels across the tapestry: as a symbol they provide a unity and comfort to the tapestry visitor just as they did to the communities of migrants they served.

Thus the use of buildings can in fact be considered as being more important than simply acting as illustrative way-markers as the visitor crosses the diaspora. There are countless examples of buildings, named specific buildings, being illustrated for deeper reasons than simply to aid orientation or provide interesting features in the design. Some, like NZ06A which depicts three buildings associated with the Melbourne "child-rescuer" Selina Sutherland, or the Canadian panel CA09 which depicts a St Andrew's Church, St Andrew's College and the Scotsfort Monument on Prince Edward Island, are clearly illustrating specific buildings with the community which are important testaments to the influence of diaspora Scots. The way they sit in the design often suggests the influence of hands other than Crummy's in such arrangements, which is indicative further of the importance these buildings clearly play. This is significant in that it supports the belief that communities have a sense of attachment to their built heritage, which plays an important role in their sense of identity. The government of New South Wales, where the Elizabeth Farm depicted in panel AU10 can still be visited as an historic estate, describes on the website of its Office of the Environment and Heritage, that 'built heritage describes our origins and informs our understandings of who we are today. It helps to define a sense of place, an identity for a community. It can contribute to feelings of connectedness and community pride and confidence' (accessed May 2017). As tangible connections to the past, and therefore to the people of the past, buildings and monuments become important visual symbols of our identity even if their origins. In total, 16 panels were coded as carrying illustrations of civic buildings (government buildings, schools, universities) and 29 showing the historic built heritage of a community (including landmark structures, properties now operating as museums, and monuments).

This way of interpreting the portrayal of built heritage in the tapestry is best considered in the context of a particular case study, that of Veere in the Netherlands, where the physical reminders of the town's Scottish connections are powerful symbols of its community identity. The fact that these symbols remain potent even without the presence of personal ancestral connectivity to Scotland encourages identification of a discrete classification of diaspora community, memorial diaspora.

Memorial diaspora

The relationship between Scotland and the town of Veere in Zeeland can be traced back at least as far as the marriage in 1444 of the Lord of Veere to the daughter of King James I of Scotland. The happy couple are depicted on panel NL01, hands joined, whilst behind them the brilliant white fleeces are delivered to Veere to symbolise its profitable status from 1541 as the staple port for Scottish trade in Europe. This trade flourished throughout the later medieval period and beyond. From Scotland came wool, salmon, butter, leather and coal; to Scotland came linen and pan tiles (Blom, 2003). This two-way trade is shown in NL02, but the panel is dominated by an illustration of the vast stone well-house where fleeces could be washed. This impressive structure still stands today. The Scottish merchants in Veere were successful enough to construct fine properties in prominent positions along the quayside, as illustrated in NL03, the beautiful architecture reflecting just how important the Scottish trade was to the town. The merchants enjoyed special privileges and formed a largely autonomous community within Veere, led by their own Conservator of Scottish Privileges in the Low Countries. The Conservator's recently rediscovered badge of office, featuring a thistle and the distinctively Scottish motto *Nemo Me Impune Lacessit*, is beautifully embroidered as the centrepiece of panel NL04. An aisle of Veere's massive church was set aside for the use of the Scots, becoming the first Scots Presbyterian congregation in Europe in 1613. The four communion cups commissioned for the kirk a few years later are shown in panel NL05, flanked by images of the first and last Scottish clergymen to preach there in 1614 and 1799 respectively. Along the bottom of each of these panels are stitched the names, rendered in Dutch, of the Scottish communities with which Veere built trading links.

The importance of this set of panels lies in the fact that after a French invasion of 1799 most of the Scots remaining in Veere returned home, and the link with Scotland was effectively broken. Most merchants had not settled permanently, and so there was in fact no diaspora community forged through during several centuries of very close connection. This is not unusual, and the transient nature of some trade diasporas has already been discussed in chapter five (Cohen, 2008). The same can be said about other communities which feature in the tapestry too, including some of those associated with imperial phases of the diaspora such as India, many diaspora communities leaving along with the apparatus of the empire. What is particularly striking about the Veere panel set is that despite this the community was one of the earliest to engage with the project, produced six complex panels, and demonstrated significant enthusiasm and ownership thereafter even to the extent of hosting a major exhibition of the completed tapestry. Other communities did the same, but almost all others demonstrating that level of engagement could draw upon more recent or more direct diaspora connections.

Fig. 6-4. Panel NL02, showing the stone well in Veere where fleeces could be washed, a symbol today of the importance of the medieval wool trade between Veere and Scotland.

Veere's panels are also interesting in terms of their choice of symbols. Four of the panels centre heavily on the surviving tangible evidences of the historical connection: the stone well, the Scots merchant's houses on the quayside which now form the Scots House Museum, the badge of the Conservator of Scottish Privileges, and the communion cups. Acting as a Scottish counterpoint is the distinctive orange of Culross Palace in Fife, Scotland, said to have been built with materials brought in from the Netherlands and clearly showing Dutch influences in its design. The building features in the top corner of NL06, which commemorates the Scottish regiments which helped liberate Zeeland in the Second World War, and has a panel all of its own which was stitched in the nearby village of Dalgety Bay (NL07). These panels all focus on physical objects, buildings and monuments, the communion cups standing in place of the Scots kirk which has not survived. This ties in with the preceding discussion of the importance of tangible and built heritage in connecting contemporary communities with the past. This appears particularly to be the case in examples like Veere, where the historical connectivity to Scotland is represented by a shared historical experience rather than ancestral roots.

The community in Veere was sufficiently engaged with the project to commit to hosting the first ever exhibition of the complete tapestry in 2015 (incorporating all those panels which had arrived after the official premiere at Prestonpans the previous year. The researcher accompanied the tapestry to the Netherlands and was struck by the depth of the engagement. Saltires hung not only from the Scots

House Museum – in its own right an important symbol of the importance of the community’s historic links with Scotland – but also from the bell tower of the town hall. The clock chimed Scottish folk tunes each hour through the exhibitions duration. The official Veere tartan was worn by the stitchers and volunteers, pipes were played in the centre of town, and walking tours identified the key monuments and the former location of the Scots kirk. In the museum’s permanent exhibition, a mannequin of a sixteenth century merchant stands implausibly swathed in tartan. At the opening of the tapestry exhibition, the Conservator’s badge of office was officially handed over to the museum after being rediscovered in Scotland, and the current Conservator (a Scottish businessman now living in the region) appeared in his kilt: it has been revived as a ceremonial role. Veere stitchers attended the tapestry’s launch in Prestonpans in 2014 and returned to Britain to see it in Westminster Hall in 2017.

When one of the Veere panels (NL05) was stolen from the homecoming exhibition in May 2017, the stitchers stoically volunteered to recreate it. One wrote to the researcher explaining that the theft had created ‘a renewed consciousness of the great values’ the tapestry project represented. Fortunately the panel was returned and further effort was not required of the Veere stitchers; all the more important considering the fact that they were already prepared to remake one of the panels so that they can keep their own copy at the Scots House Museum. The Scottish connection is an important part of Veere’s contemporary identity, despite centuries passing since the principal historical connection was broken.

Veere is not unique – Bergen in Norway also demonstrates similar characteristics, as does Gothenburg in Sweden. In Bergen the strength of the connection was such that the Bergen Scottish Society was determined to hold an exhibition of the tapestry, the first outside the British Isles, despite the fact that none of the Norwegian panels had been stitched in the city. Pipe bands were mobilised and whisky procured, whilst the mayor spoke of the important connections between Norway and Scotland. Veere and Bergen are examples of memorial diaspora communities: a place or group which values and identifies with Scotland not because of ancestral or migratory roots, but because of an important if temporary historical connection which has left a discernible legacy or influence which is cultural or architectural (perhaps even archaeological) rather than ancestral. Memorial diaspora is distinct from affinity diaspora, which shares the lack of an ancestral link, because the latter is essentially a free-choice cultural identity whereas memorial diaspora communities are tied to Scotland by an historical connection. Buildings and monuments are particularly important symbols of that connectivity, the foci for the shared experiences of the past. This leads to potentially important implications for heritage and tourism policy, both regarding the conservation of built heritage and the importance of taking a wider view of where engaged audiences might be found. A strict definition of diaspora which relies on

ancestral or current ‘lived’ connectivity would have missed Veere out entirely, one of the project’s most proactively engaged audiences. Memorial diaspora communities might also act as access points for engagement with the homeland for contemporary diaspora Scots in Europe for example. In particular, those whose settlement for work or study might prove transitory, but might wish to maintain a sense of their roots without engaging in more overt forms of diaspora identification or who feel they ill-at-ease or unrepresented by “Scottish” organisations (Leith and Sim, 2014). Further study on this potential might prove insightful.

Fig. 6-5. Panel IN16, showing the work to restore the former Scottish Cemetery in Kolkata, India.

Panel IN16 (above) becomes relevant here: it shows the old Scottish cemetery in Kolkata, where over 2,000 lie buried. It was established in 1820 and those laid to rest there include people from a wide variety of trades, many of which are listed around the edge of the panel. After Indian independence, with the Scottish community largely gone, the cemetery was abandoned and fell into disrepair. But since 2008 a collaborative project led by the Kolkata Scottish Heritage Trust has been working to conserve it, and the tapestry panel illustrates this. One man with a scythe cuts back the overgrowth, whilst another works with his mason’s tools at restoring stonework. A Celtic cross emerges from behind the leaves. In this case the cemetery is the tangible reminder of a shared historical engagement, and the restoration project is resulting in renewed connections and shared opportunities. It is the historical connectivity, symbolised by surviving built heritage, which is facilitating that process. Memorial diaspora can therefore be revived and harnessed as well as surviving organically by itself. It may not fulfil the requirements of diaspora as identified by Safran (1991) and others, but it does

represent a form of potent connectivity between Scotland and the world, more authentically rooted than affinity diaspora (Rutherford, 2009) but more flexible than one based solely on ancestral connections. Whilst communities like Veere might sit on the fringes of academic interpretations of diaspora, there is no doubt in their own mind that they belong.

Conclusion

By advancing the discussion of the tapestry's content to incorporate discussion of its design and imagery, the conclusions of the previous chapter have been strengthened and further contextualised. It is clear that the tapestry, despite the breadth and diversity of its content, does not reflect all the faces of the diaspora experience. It is overwhelmingly positive in its imagery, but it maintains a convincing level of authenticity by viewing Scotland's migratory history through the experiences of real people, rich and poor, the names of many of whom would never appear in the history books. The positivity of much of the imagery and content does not obscure the realities of times when the experience was painful or arduous, and there are instances of sadness and loss as well as those of great fortunes and discoveries being made.

As the designer Andrew Crummy was reliant on the imagery provided to him by contributors to shape the form of the illustrations he created, and there was considerable opportunity for those within the diaspora to influence those forms during the creative process. Whether or not those opportunities were seized to the full, the final designs had still been based on the photographs and sources submitted to the project team or encountered by them on their field visits, and the very act of the stitching the panel was an act of verification of its content. The symbols found within the panels can therefore be considered to reflect more than just a single artist's stylistic choices, meaning that they can provide insight in the contributing community's means of self-identification.

By concentrating most of the overt Scottish-ness of the illustration into a set of globally relevant panels, the project attempted to prevent repetitive design themes and subject matters recurring throughout the exhibition. Experience soon showed that this was unlikely to have occurred, as the majority of those who engaged with the project wished to present their diaspora identity not through single cultural events such as a local Highland Games or the depiction a regional tartan, but rather through the experiences or achievements of individuals, families and communities. Understanding this

leads to a deeper reading of the tapestry's symbols, one which emphasises the significance of images to a particular community or individual. Contributors have chosen to share those symbols most meaningful to them in their own context, such as a church or landmark.

The importance of structure symbols as a means of visually presenting historical connections demonstrates the importance of the archaeological and architectural remnants of those connections. Built heritage is therefore important both to maintaining a sense of identity and engagement with historical roots, as well as to tourism. This becomes particularly important in locations where the memory of shared historical experiences has outlived the presence of an ancestry-based diaspora community, which can be termed memorial diaspora communities. The level of engagement with the Scottish connection might be proactive or perhaps dormant, but the historical linkages provide continuing opportunities for bilateral activity.

Chapter Seven:

The Tapestry's Legacy

*“A splendid way to draw the attention of my grandchildren
and future generations to their heritage.”*

Anne Adams, Ontario, Canada

Introduction

Armed with a fulsome understanding of both the hands that shaped the tapestry and its illustrative and historical messaging, it is possible to formulate an assessment of the project's value and potential in the longer term. At the end of 2014 the Scottish Diaspora Team was required to submit a series of final reports to its main funders, the Scottish Government, Creative Scotland and Homecoming Scotland. Once these had been filed the project was, in the official eyes of these agencies at least, complete. The required data on financial expenditure, basic visitor numbers and breakdowns, and media coverage (see appendix three) were all collated by means of standard reporting forms. Needless to say, however, the life of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry was far from over: it had in fact barely begun. The tapestry had been created to a high standard (although there were still panels in development and its scale was still growing as outcome reports were being compiled); it had engaged large numbers of people, and it had delivered the promised series of exhibitions in Scotland during the Year of Homecoming. These facts alone satisfied the Scottish Government and its cultural agencies, which were therefore assessing it only by a part measure. What they were not apparently considering was its long term potential, despite the fact that their own report into the benefits and challenges of diaspora engagement clearly advises that such initiatives should be assessed by long-term monitoring (2009).

It is that longer term potential – the ongoing legacy of the processes of 2012-2014 – which concerns this chapter. It will be considered in two key areas: the educational role of the tapestry, particularly in the homeland context; and the legacy in terms of bilateral engagement between Scotland and its diaspora. Much of this analysis has been informed by observation of the tapestry's post-Homecoming activities, including both its world tour and its return to Scotland in 2017. It will be shown that the

tapestry's potential to play a positive role both as an agent for reinforcing diaspora identity and in encouraging direct engagement from within the diaspora, strengthening both the appeal and the understanding of the globalness of the Scottish diaspora identity. Crucially, it also has an important role to play – one already begun – in the continuing education of homeland audiences as to this diaspora heritage and its contemporary resonance and importance, something which has been shown to be lacking (Scottish Government, 2010a). It will also be suggested that an important opportunity has already been missed by the Scottish Government and Visit Scotland, in that they did not attempt to support or conserve the networks of diaspora Scots engaged by the tapestry project. The project team also lacked the structures or resources to do so, and the result is that some of the engagement the tapestry facilitated will prove temporary. Whilst it may be possible to re-energise that potential in the future, the opportunity to prepare for that when engagement levels were at their height has been missed.

This leads to further consideration as to the lasting legacy of the tapestry and what form it might take as its life enters a new phase. It has now completed the natural stages of creation, initial exhibition, global touring, and return. The current plans of the tapestry's operating team, which has itself evolved since 2014, for the future of the artwork will be considered in this context. By its very nature the discussion in this chapter will work its way to the limits of the existing evidence base, but even with little by way of direct comparators available for reference (as will be shown), the possible nature, extent and significance of the tapestry's forward legacy can be predicted. Only after so doing can it be considered that we have reached a true understanding of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry, and through that an understanding of the diaspora itself.

Exhibitions beyond 2014

It lies outside the scope of this study to examine the academic theory behind exhibitions and artwork as cultural devices, since the relative virtues of alternative methodologies are rendered largely irrelevant by the fact that the project team neither considered alternative methods of interpreting the diaspora nor maintained a particular ideological message to promulgate; but it is nevertheless important to consider opportunities which the project has created for itself in pursuing this path. The decision of the project team to continue exhibiting the tapestry beyond the end of 2014 should not be considered as surprising, but nor was it inevitable. Although the Prestonpans Tapestry has continued travelling to temporary exhibitions every year since its completion in 2010, the more recently

completed Great Tapestry of Scotland slowed down its exhibition programming just a few years after completion and now most commonly displays only sections of the whole as it moves towards securing a permanent exhibition space (Great Tapestry of Scotland website). The end of Homecoming 2014 also marked an end to the accompanying funding streams, and no resources from the 2012-14 grants had been allocated for funding beyond this point. But as the tapestry was still adding panels there was an evident need and appetite for exhibitions, and there amongst the project team there was also a sense that international exhibitions were not only appropriate but deserved. Several stitchers commented in conversation on the mixed emotions of investing so many hours of skill into a panel only to then send it to the other side of the world: the chance to see their panel again in the company of the whole tapestry would surely be welcome. Prestoungrange recalls the effectiveness in 2010 of touring the Prestonpans Tapestry to communities where the stitchers had themselves been based, and this same principle was envisaged for the diaspora (Crummy et al, 2015: ix). There was also the overhanging commitment to achieving a visitor figure of 83,000 over three years – the nearest Homecoming Scotland came to committing the project to a life beyond 2014 – of which 31,000 had been achieved by the end of the year (Scottish Diaspora Tapestry team 2014a).

The lure of international touring after the Year of Homecoming can therefore be clearly understood, but so too can the potential challenges. Long lead times were required to ensure appropriate arrangements, and that meant it was not possible to wait to evaluate the success of the 2014 tour before planning the events of 2015. There was also a need to strike whilst the core audience – the contributors and their networks – were still sufficiently engaged with the project and accessible to the team. Commitments had to be made, but resourcing even the basics of an international tour was a daunting task: safe transportation of the tapestry; the means to hang the exhibition; the hiring of exhibition spaces; the marketing and promotion; and then the same requirements for each subsequent venue. The problem was the extent of funding the project had already received: the Scottish Government had already increased its initial contribution, with a further £30,000 being allocated to support the additional task of extending the project past the expected and budgeted 150 panels (Scottish Diaspora Tapestry team, 2014b). Without this support the project would have had to turn away participants on a large scale, which the team felt would be ‘artificial and inappropriate – artistically and motivationally’ (Strategy Group Minutes, 06/13). This increase however brought the total government commitment to £102,500 between 2012 and 2014. Culture minister Fiona Hyslop MSP made it quite plain in her speech of August 2015, delivered at the opening of the tapestry exhibition in St Mary’s Cathedral, that this was the limit.

The project team remained committed to their course however and agreed to a programme of European exhibitions where it was felt that the anticipated on-the-ground support could help alleviate some of the resourcing constraints: including Barga in Italy, with a track record of exchange events, and Veere in the Netherlands which had proven itself to be highly engaged and logistically capable. To go further afield, especially the significant target regions of Australasia and North America, would require an estimated £45,000 in additional grant aid however (Scottish Diaspora Tapestry team, 2014b). Requests for exhibitions in Canada and Australia proved irresistible however, and the strategy group minutes record that as early as July 2014 an application had been submitted to Creative Scotland for the facilitation of international touring (13/14). This was unsuccessful, but the project team was sufficiently encouraged by the feedback to apply again once a new funding round opened in October that year. This had been tabled by January (Strategy Group Minutes, 17/15), but so too had the first putative Australia exhibition dates and following the previous application's failure discussions were also now being held with the airline Qantas in the hope that a form of transportation sponsorship might be agreed given the airline's Scottish roots (featured on panel AU16). Neither initiative was successful, nor was a further application to Creative Scotland tabled in May 2015 (Strategy Group Minutes, 20/15) or a more modest one for support of the Westminster display in 2017. By then the tapestry was on its way home, having somehow completed 23 overseas exhibitions as far apart as Bergen and Tasmania (see appendix four).

In some ways the global tour of 2015/16 is almost as impressive an achievement as the completion of the tapestry itself, considering the distances the tapestry travelled in the space of just two years. No additional funding was secured and the shortfalls were made up by the Baron Courts of Prestoungrange and Dolphinstoun and the revenues that had been generated from merchandising. There was little opportunity for the latter at exhibitions outside of Europe, as the freight costs of shipping guide books beyond the reach of the project team and their van was prohibitive (Strategy Group Minutes, 18/15). The tour was facilitated by trimming down the expense to the barest minimum wherever possible. This meant passing much of the burden back to the host community in the diaspora, particularly in regard to finding and booking the exhibition venues and arranging the volunteers to staff the displays (Scottish Diaspora Tapestry team, 2014b).

The Tapestry itself was passed from place to place in a giant global relay with each host group responsible for organising onward travel for the tapestry – which outside of Europe had to be transported without the exhibition stands and supporting materials which had been used in the British exhibitions. To get things started, two eager volunteers from the north of Scotland agreed to drive the tapestry overland through northern Europe and into Norway in March 2015. It was no small

undertaking! Nor was the return journey back to the Netherlands, undertaken by three more stitchers from the Prestonpans area who took to calling themselves “the Golden Girls” on this grand adventure. At the end of October, as the author helped load the display stands into a van for their return to Scotland, a courier collected the seven boxes of tapestry panels and whisked them off to the airport and their flight – partly delayed by a customs strike – to Australia. It was a visibly humble enterprise, unlike the transportation of most major artworks.

It was the very humility of the touring project however which makes it so important. Everywhere it went it was the sole responsibility of its hosts, who became its guardians until it arrived at the next destination. This was the case even after the volunteer Jenny Bruce became a semi-permanent fixture of the tour. From Wick, Bruce had coordinated the stitching efforts on one of the Australia panels connected to Caithness and was able to make herself available for accompanying the tapestry’s travels in Australia and most of Canada in an advisory capacity. She was housed and hosted on the goodwill of the communities running the exhibitions. At almost all the exhibitions along the route there was a tangible sense of local ownership of the tapestry: Sharon Beck reported that the volunteers in Wisconsin simply could not wait for her arrival to open the boxes, and had almost completed setting up before Beck reached them. The researcher found the same in Boussy-Saint-Antoine, France when he travelled to meet the exhibition and aid in its installation, only to discover a fully installed exhibit. There was a slightly different atmosphere in Bergen, Norway, where the author observed an unusual dynamic as the hosts of the exhibition (the Bergen Scottish Society) had not themselves been involved with the creation of the panels (as related in chapter six). Nevertheless, they were sufficiently energised by the results of the project to arrange and man the tapestry’s only Norwegian exhibition in the Bergen’s council building. What this wealth of anecdotal evidence reveals is the importance of that sense of local responsibility. This is evidenced by the way the stitchers coalesced into groups during the tapestry’s creation (see chapter three), coordinated themselves into organisational instruments to facilitate exhibitions, and then staffed and supported those exhibitions with great pride. It is the same advice found in the Scottish Governments report on diaspora-focussed events in Homecoming 2009: ‘Initiatives outside Scotland encouraged to develop at a local level; not led from Scotland’ (2010a).

The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry believes it received its 100,000th visitor whilst in Ottawa in January 2017, surpassing the original estimate given to Homecoming Scotland. The news was reported back home in Prestonpans (East Lothian Courier, 05/01/17), where it helped maintain interest ahead of the tapestry’s return to Great Britain a few months ahead. The level of engagement achieved by the touring exhibition, where audiences could only be mobilised through local (horizontal) networks or by

locally resourced promotional activity, was considerable. It more than matched the achievement of the homeland exhibitions of 2014, which were centrally organised. The model of encouraging local ownership, from the choice of venue to the hanging methods, layout and supporting activities, and of a focussed and motivated team being able to dedicate themselves to a single exhibition, was demonstrably effective. It is also the approach recommended by Paul (2015) for overcoming barriers to diaspora engagement. It is important therefore that the exhibitions programme beyond Homecoming is acknowledged as being a significant extension of the engagement achieved by the creative phase of the tapestry project, requiring further levels of proactive commitment and sustained interest.

This last point is important in that it acknowledges not only that the overseas tours represent an extension of engagement, a further demonstration of a depth of commitment to sharing expression of a common diaspora heritage, but also that it was the very possibility of hosting/supporting those exhibitions which facilitated the continued engagement. Just as the creation of panels served as a focus, so working towards an exhibition created a vehicle for activity which had a tangible result and measurable outcome. Although both stages of engagement required considerable commitment from the volunteers involved, neither required that commitment to run indefinitely. The implication of these considerations is twofold: firstly, creative participatory focussed projects have demonstrable potential to mobilise both individuals and communities, some of which might not otherwise have been reached (as will be discussed shortly); secondly, that the focussed nature of such projects presents challenges in maintaining similar levels of engagement over the longer term. Whilst the core project team is able to maintain the organisational memory of the successful processes of engagement, added to the declarative knowledge gained in relation to the diaspora heritage it has become an advocate for (Morman and Miner, 1998), it also loses many of the resources required to put them into practice over a consistent and sustained future. Only continued exhibitions provide the focus for that unless, as occurred after the creation of the Prestonpans Tapestry, it finds outlets in new projects. For the participants and those who were engaged, there remains a new appreciation of both heritage and personal/community potential but its focus is unlikely to remain the tapestry once the stitching or the hosting of an exhibition has passed. Perhaps the promise of more overseas touring offers a potential remedy, perhaps coinciding with or paving the way for future Years of Homecoming.

This experience was observable in the wake of the Prestonpans Tapestry project and is partly responsible for the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry's conception, as both the organisational team and many of those who had participated – and even those who had not but now saw the potential or opportunities – retained an appetite for activity. But subsequent activity did not re-engage all those

involved in the first tapestry, and informal networks which had grown organically during the project's duration soon dispersed without common focus. This is likely to be true of the diaspora networks which were mobilised to create the panels and facilitate the international touring, if an alternative of supporting focus is not provided. No formal mechanism was established by neither the tapestry team nor the Scottish Government or agencies which supported them, to turn the engagement into a database of skilled, creative and participation-inclined diaspora members, which might have supported future comparable engagement exercises. The opportunity to do so has already passed, as even by the time of this research the sharing of the participant's questionnaire relied on centrally invisible networks and the personal goodwill of individuals to share information beyond the known contacts. A number of email addresses on the stitchers' database were already out of use. This transiency is a risk with a project-based approach to engagement, but one which the tapestry may yet be able to at least partially counter on account of the fact that the physical artwork itself survives the temporary nature of the project. So too does the memory of participation: "I hope my children and grandchildren – and beyond! – will see my work on display and feel the same pride".

The feedback left in the visitor comments books during the overseas exhibitions has an added poignancy to it when compared to those collected in Scotland. The overwhelming positivity and approval is the same, as are superlatives and the expressions of pride, but there is sometimes a subtle but discernible difference in tone which is perhaps best heard in the words of Eleanor and Eddy in Albury, New South Wales: "more than ever, my heart is in Scotland." Some were eager to share in the diaspora identity the exhibition cultivates: "mother's maiden name was Campbell," one visitor in Winnipeg comments; "a proud Scottish descendant," boasts another in Wangaratta; "my heritage!" writes Heather Cameron Gabrioloa in Victoria. The qualitative evidence is all very clear: the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry is beautiful, inspiring, and evokes feelings of pride, relatability and fraternity. Ralph and Gina Blasbalg of British Columbia put it rather well when they called it, "a display of family, community and belonging."

The Tapestry returned to Scotland via a last-minute exhibition in Iceland and a much anticipated one at Westminster Hall in London. This prestigious venue at the Houses of Parliament was secured on the initiative of the volunteers of the Crown Court Church, a Scottish Presbyterian church near Covent Garden which had originally been founded to provide for the courtiers of King James VI of Scotland and I of England (panel GBE20). The planned fanfare – with ambassadors' receptions and stitchers' reunions – became in fact rather muted; the opening days of the exhibition coincided with the tragedy of a terrorist incident occurring just beyond the doors. Nevertheless the exhibition was a success and brought the tapestry, and with it the diaspora, into the heart of the British Government. Some months

later, when East Lothian's Member of Parliament Martin Whitfield addressed a parliamentary meeting on the effects of art on health, he was able to refer to the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry in the comfort that many of his fellow members could not have helped but to have seen it as they had gone about their daily business in the spring. Using the tapestry project as an example, Mr Whitfield stated that art 'is not about money, it's about society, it's about empathy, and it's about the people' (Whitfield, 2017). These words reflect the principles of community art, and are just as applicable to diaspora engagement. It also reveals the foresight of an anonymous visitor to the exhibition in Sydney, Australia, who wrote in the visitors' book: "what an amazing lesson for our politicians".

The return of the tapestry to Scotland was celebrated with a special exhibition in St Giles' Cathedral on the Royal Mile in Edinburgh, the second of the capital's three cathedrals to host the tapestry. This did not save the tapestry from thieving hands, and one of the Veere panels was stolen a few days into the exhibition. The Dutch stitchers, although disappointed, remained sufficiently engaged to be prepared to re-stitch the panel if required, as has already been related in chapter six. Fortunately it was returned anonymously to police a few weeks later. The St Giles exhibition marked a return to the more centralised model by which the display was coordinated by the project team rather than a community host, although stitchers were nonetheless willing to volunteer as stewards. The exhibition mounted in Crieff, Perthshire two months later operated on a model much more familiar to the overseas ones, except that it was the volunteers of the local community arts festival who resourced, hosted and stewarded the exhibition. The same was true of the Helmsdale and Irvine exhibitions of September and October 2017, and each has proven successful. This is a model which both addresses the manpower and resource limitations of the project team, and maximises the emphasis on local initiative and enthusiasm to generate footfall and engagement. It is a model which is potentially sustainable.

Of course there are drawbacks to the model which, out of necessity as much as design, the tapestry team have developed and adopted. In the first place it is essentially reactive, which places limitations on the spread of engagement. Communities which lack the internal cohesion to fundraise or manage an exhibition then risk being unable to participate, creating barriers to inclusion in the wider global project. As Brinkerhoff (2009) identifies, opportunity structures are required to facilitate a full diaspora engagement, and with a tangible real-world project such as the tapestry it is difficult to bypass any deficiencies locally by digital means. This then is where the diaspora associations and societies can again become significant, not in their usual capacity as outward manifestations of identity but as opportunity structures to facilitate a different form of diaspora engagement: a regional clan association or even highland dancing group could potentially provide the structural or

administrative nexus around which those not normally engaged with them might be able to back-engage with the tapestry in terms of exhibition mounting. Without the project team driving the exhibitions programme, diaspora communities must find these localised structures or the leadership to form new ones. With this in mind, it should be acknowledged that the lack of an exhibition in a community is not a reflection of a lack of engagement but of a lack of the opportunity structures – whether finance, leadership, or sufficient concentration of active diaspora networks – to facilitate the planning and execution of what was a considerable responsibility. In no way should the fact that there was only one exhibition in the United States but two in Italy be perceived as evidence that the Italian Scots are twice as engaged with diaspora identity as the American Scots. It can however suggest that they are more concentrated, and that their pre-existing local networks were able to mobilise quicker when the initial opportunity for exhibitions presented itself.

Educational potential

The reality of the logistics behind touring the tapestry would suggest strongly that the majority of its upcoming exhibitions for the short and medium term will be held in Scotland or, since there are putative expeditions in Carlisle and Merseyside, elsewhere in the British Isles. On the assumption, which there is no current evidence to contradict, that the project team is unlikely to possess adequate resources to maintain a proactive marketing presence in the diaspora itself, the role of the tapestry is now moving away from the Homecoming 2014 model which saw it as a draw for diaspora tourism. Perhaps that role will be revived in future Homecoming years which might come to pass, when the environment is right for well-resourced targeted marketing and specially designed engagement activities harnessing the lessons of the original project. A permanent home base would also re-energise that potential (see next section). Otherwise, and this is the situation at present, the principle role of the tapestry is now becoming one of encouraging homeland engagement with diaspora heritage. This is an important shift in positioning and should be reflected both in how it is managed at present and how its potential is assessed going forwards.

The latent educational value of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry was first addressed by this author and museum education professional Fiona Johnston back at the time of exhibition's launch (Johnston and Johnston, in Crummy et al, 2014; 2015). The tapestry was identified as 'a valuable cross-curricular learning resource,' with the potential in formal educational settings for 'creating dynamic and interdisciplinary lessons' (2014: 214). This is undoubtedly the case, although there is little evidence to

suggest that it has yet been harnessed in this way. No doubt, from the perspective of Scottish schools at least, this is in part due to the fact that the tapestry has spent over half of its lifetime overseas and out of direct reach. The difficulties in aligning touring exhibition dates with the optimum moments in school terms has previously been observed during involvement with the Prestonpans Tapestry, although an experiment in hosting a specific schools week based at Loretto School in Musselburgh was a great success in 2010 (Prestonpans Tapestry website, 2013).

The Scottish Diaspora is taught in Scottish schools studying the ‘Migration and Empire’ module of the National 5 secondary senior qualification (Scottish Qualifications Authority, 2016). The course looks at both immigration and emigration from the 1830s onwards. It has already been shown in Fig. 5-3 that the majority of the content in the tapestry relates to this era, and with its breadth and diversity of coverage this makes the tapestry a potentially valuable teaching resource for secondary school pupils. As Baines identifies, ‘adding relevant visual stimuli to a lesson helps students learn more effectively’ (2008: 33). Nor does the content of the lesson necessarily have to be the diaspora itself: themes of transport, industry, medicine, warfare, botany, geography are just a representative sample of those which could be studied using the tapestry as a prism, not to mention craft, art and design. The classroom applications of the tapestry are therefore significant, and represent a currently untapped potential.

A demonstration of this potential was provided by a schools project run by Sharon Beck on the project team in 2016-17. Five schools saw the project through, researching, designing and then stitching their own panel representing local diaspora connections relevant to their school or community. The finished panels, unveiled at St Giles’ Cathedral as part of the tapestry’s ‘coming home’ celebrations, reflect themes as disparate as ancient cultural connectivity, cattle droving routes, and American airbases. The ethos of the project was to encourage different departments within the school to inter-relate their activities: history classes for research and art classes for design, for example. It was a successful pilot, and the verbal feedback from participants at the St Giles’ event suggests that the resulting engagement was very rewarding for the pupils, who were of mixed ages and abilities. The official report on this project is yet to be released, but it will no doubt demonstrate the latent potential and the value of encouraging a more widespread promotion of the tapestry as an educational tool.

This activity, and the potential for greatly expanding it, is significant for the development of improved bilateral relationships between Scotland and its diaspora. In revealing ‘the common threads linking

different communities, celebrating commonality but also diversity,' the tapestry is a powerful starting point for the encouragement of international partnerships or twinnings, whether between schools or whole communities (Johnston and Johnston, in Crummy et al, 2014: 216). Exhibitions can serve the same purpose but towards a different, generally more mature audience. The comments books reflect a level of surprise at the histories revealed by the panels, sometimes implied but occasionally explicit: "who knew?!" Both Scotland and diaspora based respondents to the participants questionnaire (appendix three) felt that participating in the tapestry project had enhanced their awareness of the wider diaspora: 61% of homeland based and 50% of diaspora based contributors felt this was very much the case (Fig. 7-1). This is a pre-engaged population compared to the casual exhibition visitor, and if the project was enhancing *their* understanding to such an extent then the effect must be replicated or even enhanced amongst exhibition viewers.

Fig. 7-1. Chart showing how much more aware of the Scottish Diaspora survey respondents felt the tapestry project had made them.

This educational potential, both in its school learning applications and in its more passive educational outcomes as an art exhibition, is highly significant in light of the perception in sectors of the diaspora that its members and heritage are not fully understood by homeland audiences. The Scottish Government has itself identified 'a need to educate people in Scotland' about the diaspora, and 'to encourage understanding that the Scottish heritage celebrated by Scotland's Diaspora has an intrinsic value' (2010a). This learning does not appear however to have transferred itself into the Diaspora Engagement Plan (2010b), which speaks to a commonality of identity and heritage but does not outline an intention to proactively nurture that feeling within the homeland. It focusses on promoting

Scotland's 'place in the world' as a contemporary nation, but not on the contemporary diaspora's place in Scotland (2010b). The Engagement Plan is not alone in failing to spot the importance of a diaspora education strategy in Scotland: Paul's research on how to engage the next generation of diaspora Scots identifies homeland attitudes as a barrier but does not then address this in the recommendations for overcoming those barriers (Paul, 2015). Perhaps it is the search for more immediate solutions that obscures the longer term vision, although meaningful diaspora engagement strategies need to accept a long lead time for results (Rutherford, 2009). A receptive homeland is an important facilitator of flourishing diaspora identities (Brinkerhoff, 2008), and the only way that the forms of bilateral relationship diaspora communities appear to favour (see chapter three) can be properly nurtured in the long term. Currently the lack of understanding of the diaspora within Scotland is a barrier to developing meaningful engagements, as some diaspora Scots still feel they are dismissed as outsiders or 'wannabes' (Leith and Sim, 2016; Paul, 2015).

The research evidence clearly points to a need for increased education in the homeland as to the diaspora's history and contemporary relevance, although the Engagement Plan a process which in time will facilitate a more welcoming atmosphere for direct diaspora engagement and the opportunity for more truly bilateral relationships. It may therefore be as simple a fact as that the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry was asking the diaspora to tell its own story, rather to receive a Scottish version of it that facilitated the levels of engagement witnessed. It is a vindication of the project team's decentralised approach to determining the tapestry's content. This makes it all the more remarkable that the minutes of the project's strategy meetings are repeatedly remark upon an inability to engage Education Scotland with the tapestry. Meetings were held but despite apparent initial interest discussions never came close to creating a proactive partnership, without which the project team lacked the resources to reach schools outwith the immediate vicinity of Prestonpans. The project team's final Report to the Scottish Government uses a somewhat loaded expression to summarise the experience: 'back word was given and we were unable to connect to EducationScotland' (2014b: 2).

It took a request for ministerial intervention in 2015 to bring the agency back to the table in order to consider involvement in the putative schools project described above (Strategy Group Minutes, 19/15). The engagement thereafter was more positive, but it was limited to internal promotional support for the project and low-key advisory engagement during the formation and rollout of the project. No formal resources of financial support were made available, but it was nevertheless felt that even the ability to promote the project as supported by Education Scotland – however limited the reality of that support – was important in giving schools reassurance that the project was viable and potentially worthwhile. A longer-term and more engaged relationship between the Scottish Diaspora

Tapestry and Education Scotland would clearly be of considerable benefit in facilitating an opening up of the tapestry's educational potential, which in turn would be to the long-term benefit of both Scotland and its diaspora (Scottish Government, 2010a).

A lasting legacy?

What then is the lasting legacy of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry? The latent educational potential of exhibitions has been established, but so has the fact that the project team seems to have been left to its own devices in trying to realise it. This, combined with the inability of the project to secure funding support for any of its exhibitions outwith Scotland, is indicative of a wider sense amongst diaspora projects that self-reliance is essential as support from the centre often feels inadequate (Leith and Sim, 2016). The project has already gone through several evolutions, from conception to creation, from Homecoming 2015 to international touring, and now to a potentially more stable but less dynamic phases of domestic homeland exhibitions. The reactive model for securing exhibition venues and host communities is viable so long as interest in the project is sustained, but it should not be forgotten that the tapestry is very large exhibition and despite its organisational flexibility the spaces for which it is suited are limited.

The recent strategic planning of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry team is harder to evidence except through the author's experiences as a participant observer who has remained closely engaged with the project throughout its life to date. The last minuted strategy group meeting took place on 14 May 2015 (Strategy Group Minutes, 20/15), from which point on they became more informal as the tapestry was by then overseas and largely in the hands of its hosts. Beyond this point Gillian Hart and Yvonne Murphy became increasingly passive agents, as indeed did Andrew Crummy, reflective the shift away from design and on to exhibition. Without the focus of a creative project and the resources for continued use of a studio space, these team members necessarily took up other projects. The Prestoungrange Arts Festival has effectively been wound down as a proactive group, and in early 2017 ownership of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry was officially transferred to the Battle of Prestonpans (1745) Heritage Trust, on which all the remaining team members already sat and which is the owner-operated of the Prestonpans Tapestry (Battle of Prestonpans (1745) Heritage Trust minutes, 85/17). The change has not affected the tapestry operationally, but it does potentially tie its long-term future to that of its predecessor project. The Trust is actively seeking to build a permanent home base

for the Prestonpans Tapestry, and its current intent is that such a facility would also serve as a base for the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry's long-term conservation, storage and display.

What that long term display strategy might look like has not been officially articulated, although it is important to recall the model of the Great Tapestry of Scotland – also in the process of awaiting a permanent home, in this case in the Scottish Borders – by which segments of the tapestry remain on display whilst others are in storage. The entirety of the diaspora tapestry is visible online and on a free mobile “app”, but with a textile artwork the digital experience is wholly inadequate without the capacity to see the original. It is noteworthy however that the app has also attempted to subdivide the panel content into thematic segmentations which could potentially form the basis of future sectional exhibitions: botany; gold rush; music; sport; culture; farming; military; social; exploration; medical; religion; transport; education; engineers and industry; Jacobites; politics; trade. Some of these segmentations would still result in very large exhibitions, and the current allocation of some panels (many of which appear under several categories of course) is occasionally contestable. Nevertheless, it should be expected that thematic exhibitions start to appear should there appear to be no full exhibitions scheduled for an extended period of time. With a number of putative and now confirmed dates emerging for 2018 and into 2019, however, the appetite for the exhibition appears currently undiminished amongst venues: the key legacy question is whether that is matched amongst audiences. The experience of the Prestonpans Tapestry suggests there need be no immediate cause for concern. It should also be noted that the project has not yet reached out once again to reverse diaspora groups and organisations within Scotland, which have the capacity to provide additional interpretative opportunities and audiences. In 2015 Gordon Prestoungrange predicted a continuing legacy when the revised second edition of the official guide to the tapestry was published: ‘we confidently expect to see the images we have been gifted sparking and sustaining a deep interest and understanding of the nation’s emigrant history’ (in Crummy et al, 2015: 380). There is no current evidence that this will not be the case.

The tapestry’s legacy therefore goes beyond that which can be measured by visitor statistics and the number of exhibition bookings. It is better, if more difficultly measured in terms of ongoing engagement with the history it reports, and continuing use of the tapestry as a source of both information and inspiration. The tapestry’s website has been linked on the Scottish Government’s website as a diaspora resource, and their liaison officer to the project team during 2012-14 informed the author that it was likely that the tapestry and its website would be used in the future as an information gateway by government officers and their ministers, providing as it does a convenient set

of short country-by-country summaries of Scotland's historic connections. This aspect of the tapestry's legacy might not be measurable or even visible, but it is important nonetheless.

The website also continues to collate stories that are submitted to the project which have arrived too late to be made into panels. This further gives additional life and growth to the website, which serves both as an important window between Scotland and its world, a first point of contact for exploring the breadth and diversity of the diaspora, but also as an important archive of the project itself. Its news archive has been an important reference point for this study, even though the author was present at many of the events described. How much more valuable will it prove to be for future students of the project and its development who seek to build upon the present work. There are and will be challenges in keeping the website up to date, as it is a large and none too streamlined site, but it attracts comments and enquiries as well as diaspora researchers who wish to share their interests or seek advice. There is a more physical legacy of the tapestry too, for although the official tapestry project no longer accepts new panels, it does not deter those who wish to create their own based on the original model: a panel on US presidents with Scottish ancestry has been created in England; a set of five panels is being created in Iceland; and there is talk of others too, in the Netherlands and even further afield. Like the Prestonpans Tapestry before it the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry has proven what can be achieved, but the modest scale of its individual panels makes the diaspora model a realistic one for communities to emulate independently. If the stitching continues around the world, however localised, then the process of sustaining heritage and the associated sense of identity also continues.

The stitching of new panels, or even the commissioning of whole new tapestries, is a continuing legacy which is both physical and social, and it leads us back to consideration of the tapestry's success in engaging over a thousand named individuals from so many different countries. The hows and the whys of this process have been much discussed already, but it is worth returning to the survey data once again as we consider a further lesson from the tapestry project. The questionnaire asked the contributors whether they had ever been a member of a Scottish society or association (appendix three, question 18). Of the diaspora respondents to this question: 38% were members at the time of writing; 8% had been a member once but no longer were; and 54% said had never been a member of a Scottish society. If this proportion is representative of the whole contributing population, these figures would suggest that 62% of participants would not have heard about the tapestry if the messaging had come only via those types of organisations. In fact, Fig. 4-1 has already shown that only 19% of respondents had found out about the tapestry through Scottish diaspora associations, Scottish international newspapers, and genealogical societies combined. This despite the fact that twice as many contributors said they had researched their ancestry than said they had not (question 17). This

suggests that many are doing so independently of formal organisations, something facilitated both by family oral histories and by the power of internet-based tools and resources (Basu, 2007). Of even further interest, whilst around 53% of respondents were already aware that 2014 would be a designated Year of Homecoming in Scotland, one third did not know this until they engaged with the tapestry.

What these figures suggest is that the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry was successfully engaging participants who might not have been engaging in formalised diaspora activities without it. Not only did the project help extend the penetration of the Homecoming 2014 messaging, but it exposed a potentially new audience to awareness of the diaspora’s global heritage, the international commonality that it represents, and the rewards of engagement on both “horizontal” networks within their communities or the wider diaspora, and bilateral “vertical” projects connecting back to Scotland (see Fig. 3-5). The results are born in out in the answers to question 36: do you feel participating has strengthened your connection to Scotland (see Fig. 7-2 below). The homeland responses have been separated from the diaspora ones, as they show different trends. The great majority of Scottish respondents identified a pre-existing level of engagement. It is hard to read much into this as the question’s meaning to a participant already residing in Scotland is ambiguous, but nevertheless the result does not suggest that the participants were unaffected by their engagement. It still reflects a beneficial outcome in terms of their connection to their country: the tapestry acted as not only an expression but an enhancer of a form of national identity. This matches the experience of visitors to the Scottish exhibitions who spoke of experiencing feelings of pride on visiting the exhibition, as discussed in chapter three.

Fig. 7-2. Chart showing percentage of survey respondents who felt that taking part in the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry project had strengthened their connection with Scotland.

Of the diaspora based participants, 30% felt the same way: they had a pre-existing sense of connection but the experience of participation strengthened it. Yet 52% were unequivocal in declaring their connection to Scotland – their sense of diaspora identity – strengthened by involvement with the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry. Only 18% did not report a positive change, although the options available did not allow for a division of this which might inform whether that was because they were already so connected that this could not have been further enhanced, or simply that the project's local significance was more important than the link to the homeland. The important result however is that 82% of diaspora-based respondents were felt more engaged with the homeland after their participation in the project than they had been before. If that proportion is indeed representative of all those who participated in the project, this is a significant legacy.

Conclusion

The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry did not end with the Hogmanay fireworks of 2014. Even before the year had ended its exhibitions programme had spilled over the Border, beyond the scope of the original Year of Homecoming ambitions, and a European tour for 2015 was already committed. The project team determinedly stayed true to its incautious promises to tour the tapestry to as many diaspora communities as could manage to host it, and the result was an impressively ambitious international tour taking in Norway, the Netherlands, Italy, France, Australia, New Zealand, Canada, the USA and Iceland (appendix four). The tour was undertaken without central funding support, a fact which perhaps identifies a tendency at governmental level to perceive cultural engagement projects on too short a term, but the constraints this imposed were in fact transitioned in advantages by creating a second phase of deep diaspora engagement.

The focus provided by the touring programme, with much of the control, curation and risk delegated to host-country communities, organisations or individuals, was both the facilitator and a demonstrator of the degree of mobilisation the tapestry had achieved. This should be measured not just in terms of the numbers of visitors engaged – 100,000 by January 2017 – but in the depth of the contributions made in both time and skill by all the participants. Evidence from the survey of contributors undertaken for this thesis suggests that many of these participants lay beyond the immediate reach of the tradition gatekeepers between the Scottish Government and the diaspora population, which makes the case for other participatory cultural projects which produce tangible outcomes which can be

shared between communities. The measure for successful diaspora engagement should not be limited to short-term tourism or investment goals, and should take account of long term effects (Rutherford, 2009). The challenge is to find ways to sustain engagement once the initial foci of project-based activity has passed, something towards which a longer-term touring strategy for the tapestry might be able to contribute.

The Tapestry's success in mobilising both pre-engaged diaspora members and those who might be termed dormant engagers is evident both in the scale and quality of the finished artwork and in the overwhelmingly positive reception it has won at exhibition. As a global engagement project it was an important success from which lessons for future projects can be gleaned, for which very purpose this evaluation has been undertaken. However the tapestry has also now shifted into a new phase of its life, primarily focussed on homeland exhibitions. This encourages a continuation of the arms-length curation model developed during the overseas tours, but potentially leaves the project as reactive rather than proactive. In this new phase the educational potential of the tapestry to audiences of all ages must be taken seriously, not least because diaspora Scots are self-conscious in the face of homeland audiences who do not appear to understand or fully appreciate the diaspora heritage and the importance of the global Scottish identity (Leith and Sim, 2016; Scottish Government, 2010a). If the tapestry is able to enhance understanding within Scottish communities and even act as a catalyst for the creation or re-energising of bilateral linkages, then its lasting legacy can be highly significant to both Scotland and the diaspora. It is a bridge between the homeland and the host country, which can be harnessed on the personal, community or intra-national level. In fact it can become a tangible opportunity structure in and of itself, as well as helping to create the receptive homeland environment which allows diaspora identity to flourish (Brinkerhoff, 2009).

The Tapestry's legacy is therefore manifold. Firstly, it has the physical legacy of having created a spectacular and inspiring artwork which will last for generations, and which represents not only a major engagement project but also a lasting testament and record of the diversity and nature of the historic diaspora as perceived by its contemporary members. Just as Sim and McIntosh note a 'conflation' of the contemporary and historical in the minds of their diaspora interviewees (2007: 88), so too the tapestry. Secondly, there is a legacy of engagement. The project achieved a breadth and depth of mobilisation which belied the smallness of the core team, the scatter approach to participant identification, and lightness of touch in its approach to local promotion. The resulting engagement was sufficiently strong to facilitate the burden of research, stitching, and exhibition hosting on diaspora communities and individuals. This ethos appears to have been a two-way success, however, as decentralised projects are believed to hold wider appeal in some diaspora communities (2010a).

This engagement was sustained successfully for almost five years, at least in Western Europe and in the English speaking New World. Serious attempts to sustain engagement in Asia or Africa beyond the completion of the panels have not been observed to date, perhaps because of the absence of strong or proactive opportunity structures (Brinkerhoff, 2009). The third legacy is educational, both in terms of its potential to increase awareness of diaspora heritage amongst homeland audiences and in contextualising diaspora members and communities within the global historical experience and contemporary identity. The tapestry's latent educational potential is ripe for immediate and long-term exploitation. The final legacy appears to be instructive, identifying the broad-sweep appeal of fresh, creative and participatory project-based exercises in reaching potentially under-engaged sectors of the diaspora community and re-energising those already engaged with exciting foci for contribution. Projects calling for direct input, in both skills and knowledge, which are truly and visible bilateral in their interests and outputs, possess considerable potential as a model for expressing, and harnessing, the contemporary diaspora.

Chapter Eight:

Conclusions

“You may be a Scot, have connections to Scotland, visited as part of a family holiday or just have an interest! Whatever your connection, I’m confident the tapestry will impress.”

Fiona Hylsop, MSP

The three hundred and five embroidered panels of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry are the product of thousands of hands, innumerable hours, and unquantifiable skill. Its images touch upon the histories of thirty-four countries and seven continents, over more than a millennium. From the remote island of Tristan da Cunha to the metropolis of New York; from the Norwegian fjords to the Australian desert; and from the Nile to the Fraser; the breadth and reach of the tapestry’s content is marvellous to behold. Its contributors range from childhood to maturity; they live and have lived on all sides of the globe. But its heart, the common thread that binds all that wealth of human experience and endeavour together, is the Scots. This thesis set out to examine the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry during all the definable phases of its lifetime to date, from its conception in 2012 and through the experiences of creation and exhibition up to the present day. Its intention was to expose the artwork as a two-way mirror, through which we can both read the history of a diaspora’s past and understand the faces of its present. In that it has been successful, identifying the tapestry’s value as a case study in how a contemporary global diaspora engages with the historic identity it has both inherited and created.

The project

The tapestry was not the result of a spontaneous combustion but was rather an ambitious evolution from an existing community arts context. It is the successor to the Prestonpans Tapestry of 2008-2010, a project itself deserving of study as a heritage-conscious participatory project taking the principles of community art onto a national scale, progenitor of a new generation of embroidered public artwork in Scotland (Mansfield and Moffat, 2013). Out of the residual enthusiasm created by the Prestonpans Tapestry, which had proven the potential for contributory creative art on a large scale to result in widespread engagement in a single heritage, the Prestoungrange Arts Festival conceived of a project which could harness learned lessons and make an even broader impact. The alignment of this need, this longing for ambitious project-based activity in a community rediscovering its self-esteem in

the post-industrial age (Johnston and Prestoungrange, 2013), with the Scottish Government's strategy for engaging its international diaspora (Rutherford, 2009), provided the opportunity and a catalyst in the form of a focussed Year of Homecoming in 2014.

The guiding principles of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry project were therefore inherited directly from its predecessor, from which it also borrowed much of its core management team. The combination of Andrew Crummy, an artist rooted in the traditions of Scottish community art (Crummy, 2017), and the visionary Gordon Prestoungrange, created an environment which encouraged not only engagement and participation but also direct contributor influence in the creative processes. It was Prestoungrange who insisted the project should turn the very concept of Homecoming onto its head to promote diaspora narratives rather than homeland. The core of the project remained true to the essence of community art, seeking out and harnessing local and personal relevancies (Crehan, 2013), but then contextualising them as part of a wider representation of common experience. Key to all was the fact that the content was determined at roots level as well as the physical stitching: it was to be the diaspora telling its own story. This local focus helped to play to the small project team's organisational memory (Moorman and Miner, 1998), whilst encouraging diaspora engagement as research had previously identified the desirability of decentralised initiatives in mobilising the membership (Scottish Government, 2010a).

The project began with pilot panels in Sweden and Italy, in communities where existing connections could be harnessed. These early successes, combined with the demonstrable success of the Prestonpan Tapestry, provided sufficient comfort to the Scottish Government that the team in Prestonpan was capable of executing its grand ambition to create 150 panels, a target they more than doubled by 2016. Although the Scottish Government has been criticised for favouring a centralised and investment-focussed approach to engaging its diaspora (Leith and Sim 2016; Scottish Government, 2010b), it successfully identified the potential of the tapestry project to fulfil many of the requirements identified for diaspora engagement as learned from the experiences of Homecoming 2009: localised approach; cultural focus; reciprocity; and homeland education (Scottish Government, 2010a). In addition, the project had the potential to support the mobilisation of the ancestral tourism market for the benefit of the Scottish economy (Visit Scotland Insight Department, 2013), especially as it aimed to engage almost all of the tourist board's main markets of interest.

The result of this alignment of objectives and potential was considerable financial support, the majority of which was provided directly from the Scottish Government, its cultural agency Creative Scotland, and its dedicated tourism/events agency for 2014, Homecoming Scotland. The project team maintained creative and editorial independence, and whilst the funders made support conditional on the inclusion of several named countries and of reverse diaspora groups, these requirements neither distorted nor diminished the project's content and in fact helped to ensure a breadth of coverage. Resisting the centralising impulse of Homecoming Scotland with regard to communications and media, the project team delegated promotional activity to local activists and contributors in their home communities and achieved considerable international coverage (see appendix three). This is yet further evidence of the importance of localised initiative in maximising engagement, and of the importance of horizontal networks in creating message-reach rather than relying on top-down messaging dependent on gatekeepers or direct marketing.

Armed with these resources, the tapestry project succeeded in mobilising over a thousand known individuals who committed their skills and their stories to the creation of the embroideries. Their voluntary contribution, based on 200 hours of skilled work being required for each tapestry panel, was quantified at £600,000 (Scottish Diaspora Tapestry team, 2014b). The resulting exhibitions, in Great Britain in 2014, Europe in 2015, Australia and North America in 2016, have been visited by in excess of 100,000 people; indications from the Scottish exhibitions of summer 2017 suggest the visitor appeal remains strong. This level of engagement surpassed expectations and the key performance indicators on which the central funding streams were based.

Discovering exactly who this project engaged and how it managed to do so was one of the key objectives of this research, and through a combination of documentary analysis, participant observation and survey a sound understanding of the contributing population has been possible. It has been identified that those whose contributions were restricted to research and content proposal were a gender balanced population, whilst that which undertook the stitching was overwhelming female and mature in age. It has also been established that two-thirds of the stitching did indeed occur within the diaspora, the remainder being made in Scotland itself. The latter were more likely to be amongst the 25% of survey respondents who were drawn to the project by the opportunity to participate in an embroidery project – a legacy of the Prestonpans Tapestry and Great Tapestry of Scotland projects – as opposed to by direct connection to content. Others however reported that they were specifically motivated by a personal or ancestral connection to the content of the panels (22%). A further 15% engaged because of their general love of Scottish culture, whilst 8% were motivated by a community

link to the content. These are reflective of the project's success in engaging ancestral, affinity and memorial diaspora groups.

The means of engaging these participants was not particularly targeted, as an essential facet of the project remained its openness to contribution and its determination to be driven by diaspora suggestions. That does not mean it was entirely reactive however, as it was necessary to mobilise the populations which might provide the required input to get panels underway. A combination of avenues was exploited: gatekeeper databases and Scottish associations/societies were contacted; reverse diaspora groups were approached; published researchers and academics in relevant fields were invited to help; "Scottish" overseas publications published advertisements and editorial; and visits were made to potentially warm communities by members of the project team. Most of this work was performed by Gillian Hart and Yvonne Murphy, an immense undertaking which required considerable logistical and communication skills. The broad-brush media approaches were less successful in their results than the establishment or exploitation of personal contacts with pre-engaged diaspora members, who then mobilised their own internal horizontal networks – either diasporic or creative – to extend the message-reach beyond was achievable vertically from the centre.

The lesson observable in these processes is that there are multiple routes into diaspora population which can be used to encourage engagement, but that the obvious direct vertical channels – clan societies, Caledonian Clubs, genealogy groups – reach only a segment of the potentially-engaged audience. Of the volunteers who responded to the questionnaire on their contributions, 62% were not current members of a "Scottish" society: many of the obvious information channels would simply have missed them. To reach out beyond the pre-engaged a project needs to have local relevance or appeal, and needs to be sufficiently creative of ambitious to generate enthusiasm within horizontal networks. This is where the tapestry was so successful: it used multiple approach mechanisms; developed bilateral relationships; and possessed the creativity, uniqueness, and ambition to generate excitement. Its decentralised focus – its genuine desire to reflect participant input rather than a top-down perception – appealed to both individuals and communities and encouraged engagement. There were few barriers to those who wished to participate, as evidenced by the projects exponential growth.

Scale was also important. Almost a quarter of survey respondents said that they were primarily motivated to participate in the project by the opportunity to participate in a global project, and this touches upon an important aspect of the diaspora identity. Despite the demonstrable importance of

local networks and relevancies in facilitating and sustaining engagement, being a member of the Scottish diaspora is about belonging to a global network bound by universal symbols and a perceived commonality of historic experience. It is possible to interpret this as evidence that the Scottish diaspora identity is maturing into one which emphasis its own inherent internationality, an identity which might even flourish without direct connectivity to the homeland. This may be reflecting the third phase of diaspora integration identified by Radhakrishnan (2003), a settling into a hybrid identity which can provide both a sense of belonging to a local minority and a global network simultaneously (Burrell and Anderson, 2008). The results of the stitchers survey, which does not reflect a strong preference for hyphenated identity in statements of nationality, might support this interpretation. Scottish diaspora identity can here be seen as strengthening personal identity, without undermining national identity.

The Content

Analysis of the tapestry's narrative content and visual imagery lends further support to this interpretation. As was the case with the contributing population, the content of the tapestry is dominated by narratives relating to English-speaking New World communities. This is partly a reflection of the inherent difficulties of engaging other populations in contributory projects with on-the-ground teams to aid facilitation, but also of the historical weighting of the diaspora narrative. This latter is further reflected by the bias towards storylines which date from the later eighteenth century onwards, the beginning of a major increase in Scottish migration to the New World (Devine, 2011). In contrast, the historic diaspora populations in Europe have either returned to Scotland, as exemplified by Veere in the Netherlands (Blom, 2003) or integrated into their host population, as in Poland (Dobson, 2000). The result of these historical trends is that the earlier phases of Scotland's migration history tend to be told in smaller panel sets which reflect the lower populations of self-identifying ancestral diaspora in Old World countries rather than the numbers involved in the historical experience. In Europe the engagement achieved was therefore based less on ancestral diaspora identity but on the lived diaspora – those who have lived worked or studied in Scotland – and the memorial and affinity diaspora. In France, for example, the Edinburgh University alumni association provided a crucial network for the creation of tapestry panels (see Leith and Sim, 2017 for a consideration of the modern Scottish diaspora in France).

In content from the “new” countries of North America and Australasia the diaspora is found to be at its most assertive and most confident. Together they provide almost 38% of the total tapestry content by country, although it is perhaps surprising given the reputation of the diaspora in the USA that it only produced 26 panels; half as many as Australia and New Zealand. Only one American community mobilised successfully to host an exhibition compared to seven in Canada. The reasons are unclear as it is not a reflection of a lack of engagement with the diaspora identity (Sim, 2011). Perhaps there are so many existing opportunities to manifest Scottish identity in the USA that the marketplace was too crowded for the tapestry project to make an impression, or perhaps the horizontal networks were less strong as a result of less concentrated diaspora populations. Nevertheless it is the third largest set in the tapestry.

In the context of these new countries, it has been shown that some of the panels appear to be indicative of diaspora identity being used in support of national identity, expressing for example the role of Scots in the political formation of the host nation and in defending its freedoms and its citizens. This again challenges assumptions that an active diaspora identity must necessarily be tied to political affinity to the homeland or proactive desire to return, or a sense of other-ness within the host (Safran, 1991): national and diaspora identity are speaking to different parts of the sense of self. These panels also demonstrate however that the need to belong and to possess a sense of heritage (Smith, 1983) remains important even in a constructed state like the new nations of the USA and Canada for example. The new state and its citizens make use of inherited cultural identities to provide legitimacy even in the absence of the territorial form on which older nations can form (Smith, 2008). These findings suggest an ethnosymbolist understanding of identity which acknowledges the importance of an overt sense of heritage, even in an environment which lends itself to constructivist interpretations of how new national identities are formed. The apparent paradox of a self-consciously new nation deliberately designing itself to be distinct from its Old World comparators is summed up by Onuf: ‘American historylessness is a myth. By denying the claims of the past, Americans have made history central to their self-understanding’ (Furtado, 2017: 174). That is all the more so when the demonstrable importance of roots is weighed against this sense of American exceptionalism. Perhaps because they achieved autonomy over time and without revolution, this dichotomy is not so stark in the Canadian or Australian contexts.

Whilst some elements of Safran’s defining characteristics of a diaspora are not therefore being fulfilled, Cohen’s classifications are diaspora types certainly are (2008). The tapestry content demonstrates that the historical experience of Scottish migrants can, at different times and in different locations, be either victim, labour, imperial or trade, and that some of these classes are interdependent.

If the earlier suggestion that Scottish diaspora identity is maturing away from a dependency on homeland – a theory which the continued importance of roots tourism admittedly weakens (Basu, 2007) – then the sense of commonality and globalness to the Scottish diaspora identity can also satisfy elements of Cohen’s de-territorial classification. In its ability to reflect all of Cohen’s diaspora types the Scottish experience undermines the value of such classifications when assessed as a whole, but they remain effective when the historical narrative is subdivided by either time or place. This assessment supports the historiographical tradition of assessing the diaspora in segments, although recent high-profile historical studies such as Devine (2011) and McCarthy and MacKenzie (2016) have tended to reinforce the suggestion that the main division is between Old World and New, a transition which occurs in the seventeenth century but speeds up in the second half of the eighteenth.

It is apparent however that there is occasionally a gulf between academic understandings of aspects of the Scottish migratory experience and popular conceptions, what Furtado calls a ‘disjunction between the history of the academy and that of the people’ (2017: 11). It is particularly apparent in dominance of the Clearances in the popular interpretation of the historic diaspora, visible in Scottish attitudes which commonly appear not to have developed beyond Prebble’s emotive and influential account (1963). It is seen in the tapestry in particular with the Canadian set, tied to Gaelic traditions as well as to the sense of pioneering spirit in the face of adversity. Many of these panels speak of courage and determination but there is an air of lamentation, of what is lost and left behind. It is the tapestry’s strongest representation of that longing for the homeland which some diaspora definitions see as so critical (Safran, 1991), but it is counterbalanced by the overtly Canadian imagery of maple leaves and civic buildings which represent a sense of place within the host country. The contemporary diaspora may share the memory of that homing desire, but it is rarely a proactive or realistic ambition (see Sim and McIntosh, 2007).

This disjunction suggests a need for increased homeland education as to the history and nature of the Scottish diaspora. The tapestry has considerable potential to contribute to that process now that it is entering a longer-term phase of homeland exhibitions. The potential to act as a visual learning tool and as a stimulus for further research from primary schools to academic levels, is self-evident. However it must also be acknowledged that despite its remarkable breadth and diversity of narrative the tapestry is not fully comprehensive. It was of course never intended to be, but that need not be the perception of the everyday visitor. This study has found important gaps in the storytelling, particularly in terms of the tapestry’s engagement with the imperial diaspora narrative: the Scots’ role in the creation, expansion, administration and defence of the British Empire is arguably sanitised into presentations of botanical gardens, international trade and the foundation of missions and schools (see

Fry, 2001). This despite that fact that the tapestry does not shy away from Caribbean slavery, which suggests that there was nobody who particularly sought to press for the imperial narrative to be explored more fully in places such as India or Ethiopia, in the way that Professor Sir Geoff Palmer influenced the content for the Jamaica panels. It must be born in mind therefore, especially when the tapestry is being promoted in an educational context, that in places its emphasis reflects contemporary sensibilities rather than historical realities, especially in what is *not* shown. Consciously or otherwise then, parts of the Scottish diaspora are willing to be perceived as victims, but not as dominators (benign or otherwise).

The increased education of homeland audiences is also required for the diaspora itself to feel that its members and their contributions are valued and understood by the homeland population, as identified in Scottish Government research papers (2010a). That the diaspora seeks a sense of reciprocal value again suggests that the power dynamic between homeland and diaspora is less straightforward than traditional definitions of diaspora allow: there is no automatic authority attributed to the homeland, and engagement must be earned. Cultural links should be as actively fostered by the homeland as the diaspora (Ancien, Boyle and Kitchin, 2009). The Scottish diaspora is a mature one, and whilst connectivity with the homeland remains desirable it is possible to access the cultural assets of the identity without dependency. We return therefore to a sense of the global diaspora identity, the recognisability and accessibility of it across the globe. Its trappings – whether manifested as tartan, bagpipes, music, sport, or clan affiliation – are not in the gift of the homeland alone. Hence an affinity diaspora can emerge regardless of the lack of ancestral connections (Hesse, 2014). All these symbols of Scottishness can be found in the panels of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry, especially tartan.

Yet the content analysis of the tapestry panels reveals that it is not these overt symbols of universal Scottishness which are presented as the most important manifestations of diaspora identity. The importance of structures, buildings and monuments stands out far more than that of flags or Highland Games events. The importance to some communities of events such as Games is perhaps in part obscured by the mechanism of the Global Panels cluster, which sought to prevent repetitive imagery across the tapestry's exhibition, but there is little evidence to suggest that there was a demand for such once the contributions began flowing in. Much more important to individuals and communities expressing themselves through this project was the visual representation of their built heritage and heritage landmarks which helps to anchor their sense of diaspora identity into their physical environment. This ranges from Canadian churches (both Presbyterian and Catholic), to the homes of diaspora Scots which have now become museums in Australia; from botanical gardens in India, to a landmark oak tree on Princeton Battlefield in the USA. The importance of these locations shows the

significance of finding physical manifestations of diaspora identity within host communities, giving a sense of nearness to the otherwise distant. The apparent conflict between diaspora identity and national heritage identified by Ang (2011) need not be considered as such in the case of the “new” countries in which the diaspora heritage has played a key role in the creation of the national identity. Following these lessons to their conclusions suggests firstly that as well as appropriate conservation and promotion of heritage sites to facilitate engagement and sustenance of identity and sense of place, transnational heritage initiatives could also play a role in the long-term process of engaging and maintaining diaspora. Ang (2011) cites the African Diaspora Heritage Trail as an example, although the representation in the tapestry of the bilateral initiative to restore the Scottish Cemetery in Kolkata could serve as another. Taken further, the decision by UNESCO to connect the frontiers of the ancient Roman Empire in Britain and Germany together as a single World Heritage Site demonstrates the capacity for heritage to be approached from beyond the limits of national boundaries, and to cultivate a sense of transnational commonality.

The importance of physical heritage locations is particularly keen for memorial diaspora communities, where the engagement is born of transient historical linkages which did not give birth to residual ancestral diaspora populations. The Scots House Museum in Veere is the most striking example to emerge from the tapestry project; the levels of engagement from this community were exceptional and enduring, perhaps precisely because there was a museum site to provide a natural focus and facilitate a general degree of local awareness of historic connection (Blom, 2003). A similar experience in Bergen, Norway, where the castle was said to have been built by Scots craftsmen, found expression in pipe bands and associations as well as a determination to host the tapestry exhibition in the heart of the civic centre. There are other such communities which, whilst not engaged in the tapestry project, find expression for their memorial diaspora heritage: Aubigny-sur-Nere in France is one such example. Perhaps there are other communities, particularly in Europe and the Baltic, where memorial diaspora linkages can be nurtured directly through targeted campaigns and bilateral heritage initiatives, generating new audiences or providing existing affinity groups with more tangible linkages. Such connections might also serve as access points for first-generation Scottish migrants who might otherwise be sceptical of affinity diaspora organisations (Leith and Sim, 2014).

But although built heritage, religious buildings and historic landmarks are highly significant, the imagery of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry makes a very powerful statement about the diaspora’s true nature: above all else, it is about people. This might seem an obvious conclusion, but it is a significant one. Understanding the history of the diaspora is not really about analysing the global trends of Scottish migration, it is about empathising with the hundreds of thousands of individual and family

experiences which make up the complex international whole. Some of the most powerful imagery in the tapestry is found in the gentle subtlety of families standing side by side as they face new lives in new environments, or as they mourn together, reminisce together, build together. The key messages of the tapestry are about renewal and discovery, opening up new worlds and opportunities regardless of the push factors which set these Scots upon their course. The panels speak of achievement, whether modest or grand, the embracing of opportunity and the coming good rather than any lasting sense of a maudlin longing for land lost. There are exceptions of course, but the imagery of the tapestry is overwhelmingly positive, and overwhelmingly about people. This is one of its key lessons, and it goes a long way to explaining why for example decentralised models of engagement are so effective: the connection is locally rooted, in individuals, families or sometimes wider communities, and so it is at a local level that initiatives will be most meaningful. That personal connection or self-identification with diaspora identity then passes upstream through communities, sometimes but not always through formalised diaspora identity structures such as societies, pipe bands or clan associations, and thence back towards the homeland culture. But the tapestry – and the diaspora it represents – is about Scots rather than Scotland.

Contemporary Scotland and its diaspora

The homeland of course retains a privileged role in the Scottish diaspora identity but it is not central to it, or at least the contemporary homeland is not. What some call the dreamscape of the homeland retains considerable emotive power (Hesse, 2014) and this is evidenced by the roots tourism industry (Basu, 2007; Visit Scotland Insight Department, 2013). But dreamscape and contemporary Scotland are not one and the same, and the diaspora is well aware of this: Scotland cannot take the diaspora for granted or treat it solely as an investment vehicle (Leith and Sim, 2016). The latter is a deterrent to meaningful engagement and the long-term sustenance of connectivity, whilst cultural exchange and the promotion of a sense of global Scottish identity are likely to bear sweeter fruit (Ancien, Boyle and Kitchin, 2009). As Sim and McIntosh identified, diaspora Scots interviewed for their research were ‘well aware of Scotland as a modern West European country, but [their] prime interest, nevertheless, was in heritage and family history’ (2007: 86). Thus the support of the Scottish Government and its agencies was able to give the tapestry project credibility internationally, but it was the decentralised methodology and the harnessing of the local which determined the extent and effectiveness of its engagement. In short, the saltire is not the symbol of the Scottish diaspora; the people are.

What does this mean for the way in which Scotland engages with its diaspora, and vice versa? At the very least it means that the relationship is bilateral: it is not about what Scotland has given its diaspora, or even what the diaspora should give in return. Instead it is about forming meaningful partnerships based on a common cultural identity. After all, contemporary Scots have inherited their identity just as members of the diaspora have. The emotional, cultural and historical symbols of Scottish diaspora communities and the native population of Scotland share common roots, and are valued by both in their understanding of who they are today (Smith, 2001; 2008). They are represented by their common expression in distinctive music, song, dress and even language, but also in the shared passion for landmark heritage as evidenced in the panels of the tapestry. Buildings are as much a symbol of Scottish identity as bagpipes, even if their significance is most readily understood in local rather than global contexts. This encourages an ethnosymbolist interpretation of the formation of the Scottish diaspora identity, but that should not imply it is a static constant. The relationship between diaspora and homeland has matured and, perhaps due to the disparity in numbers between the two, the homeland's position should be seen as one of privilege rather than assumed leadership. Diaspora Scots have been so successful in maintaining their sense of identity overseas, particularly in English-speaking countries, that engagement with the homeland is a matter of choice rather than necessity. Our understanding of identity must accept the resulting flexibility and optionality of how it is perceived and manifested (Nagel, 1994).

It therefore follows that, as has been observed throughout this thesis, effective engagement requires a policy of fanning flames rather attempting to control the conflagration. To continue the metaphor, the resulting direction of engagement may be unpredictable but the spread will likely be wider. This reflects back to observations about the need to tap into horizontal networks within communities in order to reach audiences which may have a latent potential which is untapped by the existing opportunity structures of, for example, St Andrew's societies. However those horizontal networks are harder to reach from outside of their own environment, which encourages homeland initiatives to focus on a smaller set of gatekeepers when attempting to reach out (Scottish Government, 2010b). The lesson of the tapestry project is therefore that engagement initiatives need to be not only cultural but also creative, imaginative, and if possible participatory. They also need an output focus, although this in turn raises challenges in terms of longer-term maintenance of the temporary or informal networks formed for the duration of a project.

In the context of homeland-based initiatives this approach requires a decentralised facilitation structure – such as the tapestry project team – and an appreciation of the true nature of the diaspora to inform it. Diaspora populations which remains sceptical of how they are perceived by homeland

audiences or wary of cynical economic motivations (Leith and Sim, 2016; Scottish Government, 2010a), will not engage with full effectiveness and ultimately the bond between homeland and diaspora will weaken. The dreamscape would likely survive in the mind of the diaspora but that reciprocal relationship – which could benefit contemporary Scotland so much deeper than simply in terms of visitor spends – might not. This returns thought to the importance of education and the medium- to long-term potential the tapestry holds in supporting or facilitating increased homeland understanding of the historic diaspora and its contemporary resonances. The fact that the tapestry project's weakest areas of achievement were in mobilising community-based homeland engagement in 2014, and in creating an effective linkage with Education Scotland, suggest that there is some distance yet to travel in this regard. Those education projects which were mounted – the local school engagements in Prestonpans facilitated by Scottish Books Trust and the Commonwealth Games Legacy support, and the 2016-7 school panels project – demonstrate what might yet be achievable.

This thesis opened with an assessment of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry is ‘a remarkable and heart-felt homage to the determination, courage and achievement of Scottish migrants and their descendants across the centuries.’ That it is remarkable is self-evidence from the levels of engagement achieved, the responses of international and homeland audiences to the exhibitions, and the very need for this investigation. That it is heart-felt is clear from the scale of the commitment it required from its contributors and the sentiments of those who were met or surveyed by the author along the tapestry's long journey from conception to the present. They speak of pride, of love, of emotional association and a sense of ownership of their heritage and identity. The tapestry is the physical manifestation of that pride, of an awareness of a global community to which diaspora members – whether ancestral, affinity or other – all equally belong. The determination, courage and achievement of Scottish migrants and their descendants is indeed reflected throughout the tapestry's narrative, with a representative if not exhaustive spread of content and a geographical and chronological weighting proportionate at least to the contemporary diaspora if not necessarily always to the historical populations. The tapestry does not shun difficult subjects but nor does it dwell upon them: as the visual expression of the diaspora's sense of self it is not surprising that this is so. What is perhaps more surprising, at least to some homeland observers, is that it is so overwhelmingly positive in its understanding of its achievements and legacies. Pull factors are just as important as push, perhaps more so, and what matters ultimately is what the Scots did when they arrived not the reasons for their departure. The Scottish diaspora defies simple classification, is remarkable in its breadth and diversity, and in its continued spirit. Most importantly, it is a community of people; each with their own story, their own sense of identity, and their own motivations. What binds them together is not only a common cultural, ancestral or historical connectivity to Scotland, but the conscious choice to value and express it.

Bibliography

- Abrams, L., Gordon, E., Simonton, D. and Janes Yeo, E. (eds.) (2006) Gender in Scottish History since 1700, Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.
- Adamson, F. (2008) Constructing the Diaspora: Diaspora Identity Politics and Transnational Social Movements. Available:
https://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/7071339/diasp_identity_politics_isa08_proceeding_251176.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAIWOWYYGZ2Y53UL3A&Expires=1507939584&Signature=66vfoMUrLhPTn3GFMomSRd2rThU%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DConstructing_the_diaspora_diaspora_ident.pdf [accessed August 2017].
- Allan, A. (2006) Prestonpans: an Economic and Social History across 1000 years. Prestonpans: Prestounrange University Press.
- Ancien, D., Boyle, M., and Kitchin, R. (2009) The Scottish Diaspora and Diaspora Strategy: Insights and Lessons from Ireland. Edinburgh: Scottish Government Social Research.
- Anderson, B. (2006) Imagined Communities. Revised ed. London: Verso.
- Ang, I. (2011) 'Unsettling the National: Heritage and Diaspora', in Anheir, H. K., and Yudhishtir, I. (eds.) Heritage Memory and Diaspora. London: Sage.
- Armstrong, J. A. (1982) Nations before Nationalism. Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press.
- Armstrong, J. A. (1995) 'Toward a Theory of Nationalism: Consensus and Dissensus', in Periwal, S. (ed.) Notions of Nationalism. Budapest: Central European University Press, pp 34-43.
- Australian Bureau of Statistics. Census of Australia 2006. [Online]
http://www.censusdata.abs.gov.au/census_services/getproduct/census/2011 [accessed March 2017]
- Baines, L. (2008) A Teachers' Guide to Multisensory Learning. ASCD: Alexandria.
- Bardon, J. (2012) The Plantation of Ulster: British Colonisation of the North of Ireland in the Seventeenth Century. Dublin: Gill & Macmillan
- Barrett, A. (2008) 'A Stitch in Time: New Embroidery, Old Fabric, Changing Values', Textile Society of America Symposium Proceedings No. 79. Available:
<http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1079&context=tsaconf> [accessed May 2017].

- Basu, P. (2007) Highland Homecomings: Genealogy and Heritage Tourism in the Scottish Diaspora. Abingdon: Routledge.
- Battle of Prestonpans (1745) Heritage Trust (2017) Minutes of the 85th Meeting of the Trustees (85/17) 6th April 2017. Unpublished.
- Bhandari, K. (2014) Tourism and National Identity: Heritage and Nationhood in Scotland. Bristol: Channel View.
- Billig, M. (1995) Banal Nationalism. London: Sage.
- Blom, P. (2003) Scots Girn about Grits, Gruel and Greens: Four Centuries of Scots Life in Veere. Veere: Stichting Veere-Schotland.
- Brah, A. (1996) Cartographies of Diaspora: Contesting Identities. London: Routledge.
- Brass, P. R. (1979) 'Elite Groups, Symbol Manipulation and Ethnic Identity among the Muslims of South Asia', Taylor, D. and Yapp, M (eds.) Political Identity in South Asia. London: Curzon Press, pp 35-78.
- Brazell, D. and Davies, J. (2013) Understanding Illustration. London: Bloomsbury.
- Breuer, F (2003). 'Subjectivity and Reflexivity in the Social Sciences: Epistemic Windows and Methodical Consequences', Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung / Forum: Qualitative Social Research, Vol. 4 No.2.
- Brinkerhoff, J. (2009) Digital Diasporas: Identity and Transnational Engagement. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Brooks, S. and Eckstein, E. (1989) Operation Overlord: History of D-Day and the Overlord Embroidery. Leatherhead: Ashford, Buchan & Enright.
- Brown, D. (2000) Contemporary Nationalism: Civic, Ethnocultural and Multicultural Politics. London: Routledge.
- Brubaker, R. (1996) Nationalism Reframed: Nationhood and the National Question in the New Europe. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Bryman, A. (2016) Social Research Methods (Fifth Edition). 5th ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Bueltmann, T., Hinson, A. and Morton, G. (2013) The Scottish Diaspora. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.

- Burrell, J. and Anderson, K. (2008) “‘I have Great Desires to Look beyond my World’”: Trajectories of Information and Communication Technology use among Ghanaians living Abroad’, New Media and Society, Vol. 10, No. 2. pp203-224.
- Butler, K. D. (2001) ‘Defining Diaspora: Refining a Discourse’, Diaspora Vol. 10, No. 2. pp 189-219.
- Calder, J. (2004) Scots in Canada. Edinburgh: Luath.
- Calder, J. (2006) Scots in the USA. Edinburgh: Luath.
- Cameron, E. (2010) Impaled upon a Thistle: Scotland since 1880. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University press.
- Chapman, G. (2005) Chief William McIntosh: a Man of Two Worlds. Cary: Cherokee Publishing Company.
- Christou, A. and Mavdouri, E. (eds) (2016) Dismantling Diasporas: Rethinking the Geographies of Diasporic Identity, Connection and Development. Abingdon: Routledge.
- Coakley, J. (2012) Nationalism, Ethnicity & the State: Making and Breaking Nations. London: Sage.
- Cohen, R. (1996) ‘Diasporas and the Nation State: from Victims to Challengers’, International Affairs, Vol. 72, No. 3. pp 507-20.
- Cohen, R. (2008) Global Diasporas: an Introduction. 2nd ed. Abingdon: Routledge.
- Colpi, T. (1991) The Italian Factor: the Italian Community in Great Britain. Edinburgh: Mainstream.
- Connor, W. (2005) ‘The Dawning of Nations’, in Ichijo, A. and Uzelac, G. (eds.) When is the Nation? London: Routledge, pp 40-46.
- Cowan, E. and Henderson, L. (2014) ‘Scots in Australia: the gaze from Auld Scotia’, For Auld Lang Syne: Images of Scottish Australia from First Fleet to Federation. pp. 18-27.
- Crehan, K. (2013) Community Art: an Anthropological Perspective. London: Bloomsbury.
- Crossick, G. and Kaszynska, P. (2016) Understanding the Value of Arts and Culture: the AHRC Cultural Value Project. Swindon: Arts and Humanities Research Council.
- Crossley, L. ‘Consult Non-Visitors as well as Visitors,’ Museums Journal, Vol. 114, No. 12. p.14.
- Cruickshanks, E. and Corp, E. (eds.) (1995) The Stuart Court in Exile and the Jacobites. London: Continuum

- Crummy, A. (2017) 'Craigmillar Festival, the Scottish Community Arts Movement of the 1970s and 1980s, and its Impact: a View from Scotland', in Jeffers, A. and Moriarty, G. Culture, Democracy and the Right to Make Art: the British Community Arts. London: Bloomsbury.
- Crummy, A., Hart, G., Johnston, A. Mhoireasdan, B., Murphy, Y. and Prestoungrange, G. (2014) The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry: Your Official Guide with Commentaries. Prestonpans: Prestoungrange University Press.
- Crummy, A., Hart, G., Johnston, A. Mhoireasdan, B., Murphy, Y. and Prestoungrange, G. (2015) The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry: Your Official Guide with Commentaries. 2nd ed. Prestonpans: Prestoungrange University Press.
- Crummy, A., Wilkie, D., Hart, G., and Prestoungrange, G. (2010) The Prestonpans Tapestry. Prestonpans: Prestoungrange University Press.
- Davidson, N (2000) The Origins of Scottish Nationhood. London: Pluto Press.
- Deutsch, K. W. (1966) Nationalism and Social Communication: an Inquiry into the Foundations of Nationalism. 2nd ed. Cambridge: MIT Press.
- Devine, T. (2011) To the Ends of the Earth: Scotland's Global Diaspora. London: Allen Lane.
- Devine, T. M. (2003) Scotland's Empire 1600-1815. London: Allen Lane.
- Devine, T. M. and Hess, D. (eds.) (2011) Scotland and Poland: Historical Encounters 1500-2010. Edinburgh: John Donald.
- Dobson, D. (2000) Scots in Poland, Russia and the Baltic States. Baltimore: Clearfield.
- Education Scotland, Curriculum of Excellence: Knowledge of Language Resource Pages. [Online] <http://www.educationscotland.gov.uk/knowledgeoflanguage/scots> [accessed April 2016].
- Eller, J. D. and Coughlan, R. M. (1993) 'The Poverty of Primordialism: the Demystification of Ethnic Attachments', Ethnic and Racial Studies Vol. 16, No. 2. pp 183-201.
- Farmer, R. and Ferguson, M. (2015) The Art of Narrative Embroidery. Prestonpans: Prestoungrange University Press.
- Fenwick, H. (1971) The Auld Alliance. Kineton: Roundwood Press.
- Flick, U. (2015) Introducing Research Methodology. 2nd ed. London: Sage.
- Fraser, B. (ed) (2008). A Meeting of Two Minds: Geddes Tagore Letters. 3rd ed. Edinburgh: Word Power Books.

- Fry, H. (2013) Alexander Dalrymple and the Expansion of British Trade. London: Routledge.
- Fry, M. (2001) The Scottish Empire. Edinburgh: Birlinn.
- Fry, M. (2006) The Union: England, Scotland and the Treaty of 1707. Edinburgh: Birlinn.
- Furtado, P. (ed.) (2017) Histories of Nations: How their Identities were Forged. London: Thames & Hudson.
- Gellner, E. (1983) Nations and Nationalism. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Grant, J. (1889) The Scottish Soldier of Fortune: their Adventures and Achievements in the Armies of Europe. [Online] <http://www.electricscotland.com/history/scotreg/fortune/index.htm> [accessed February 2015].
- Great Tapestry of Scotland Website. [Online] <http://scotlandstapestry.com> [accessed September 2017].
- Gruenfeld, D. H., Mannix, E. A., Williams, K. Y., Neale, M. A. (1996) 'Group Composition and Decision Making: How Member Familiarity and Information Distribution Affect Process and Performance,' Organizational Behaviour and Human Decision Processes, Vol. 67, No. 1, pp 1-15.
- Hall, S. (1990) 'Cultural Identity and Diaspora' in Rutherford, J. (ed.) Identity: Community, Culture and Difference. London: Lawrence and Wishart, pp 262-81.
- Harrison, H., Birks, M., Franklin, R. and Mills, J. (2017) 'Case Study Research: Foundations and Methodological Orientations'. Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung / Forum: Qualitative Social Research Vol. 18, No.1.
- Harper, M. (2004) Adventurers and Exiles: the Great Scottish Exodus. London: Profile Books.
- Harper, M. (2010) 'The Persuaders: Recruiting Scots for New Zealand', History Scotland, Vol. 10, No. 4, p. 15.
- Harper, M. (2013) "'Come to Corby": a Scottish Steel Town in the Heart of England', Immigrants and Minorities, Vol. 31, No. 1, pp 27-47.
- Hartley, K. and Moffat, A. (2012) John Bellany. Edinburgh: National Galleries of Scotland.
- Hastings, A. (1997) The Construction of Nationhood: Ethnicity, Religion and Nationalism. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Hayes, C. (1931) The Historical Evolution of Modern Nationalism. New York: Macmillan.

- Hesse, D. (2014) Warrior Dreams: Playing Scotsmen in Mainland Europe. Manchester: Manchester University Press.
- Hicks, C. (2007) The Bayeux Tapestry: the Life Story of a Masterpiece. London: Vintage.
- Hobsbawm, E. (1993) Nations and Nationalism since 1780. 2nd ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Hutchinson, J. (2005) Nations as Zones of Conflict. London: Sage.
- Ichijo, A. (2004) Scottish Nationalism and the Idea of Europe: Concepts of Europe and the Nation. London: Routledge.
- Johansson, R. (2003) Key note speech at the international conference "*Methodologies in Housing Research*," Royal Institute of Technology & International Association of People–Environment Studies, Stockholm, September 22-24, 2003. Available: http://www.psyking.net/htmlobj-3839/case_study_methodology-_rolf_johansson_ver_2.pdf [Accessed July 2018].
- Johnson, J. and Reynolds, H. (2012) Political Science and Research Methods. 7th ed. Los Angeles: CQ Press.
- Johnson, R. (2003) British Imperialism. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Johnston, A. P. & Prestoungrange, G. (2013) 'History in the Making: Community Self-Esteem in Post-Industrial Prestonpans', Transactions of the East Lothian Antiquarian and Field Naturalists' Society Vol. 29. pp126-144. Available: <http://www.prestoungrange.org/arts-festival/documents/Transactionspages126to144.pdf> [accessed June 2016]
- Johnston, A. P. (2010) Valour Does Not Wait: the Rise and Fall of Charles Edward Stuart. Prestonpans: Prestoungrange University Press.
- Johnston, A. P. (2013) Blood Stain'd Fields: the Battles of East Lothian. Prestonpans: Prestoungrange and Cuthill Press.
- Kafalenos, E. (2001) 'Reading Visual Art: Making – and Forgetting – Fabulas', Narrative, Vol. 9, No. 2. pp 138-145.
- Kay, B. (2008) The Scottish World: a Journey into the Scottish Diaspora. Edinburgh: Mainstream.
- Keppie, L. (2004) The Legacy of Rome: Scotland's Roman Remains. Edinburgh: John Donald.
- Kohn H. (1958) The Idea of Nationalism: a Study in its Origins and Background. New York: Macmillan.

- Labarge, M. W. (1999) 'Stitches in Time: Medieval Embroidery and its Social Setting', Florilegium, Vol. 16, pp77-96.
- Lane, M. (2003) 'Is the WI ready for Bridget Jones?', BBC News. [Online] <http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/magazine/3035124.stm> [accessed March 2016].
- Leith, M. and Soule, D. (2012) Political Discourse and National Identity in Scotland. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.
- Leith, M. S. (2006) Nationalism and National Identity in Scottish Politics. PhD thesis, University of Glasgow. Available: <http://theses.gla.ac.uk/2924/> [accessed November 2014].
- Leith, M. S. and Sim, D. (2017) 'Les Écossais en France: a modern diaspora?', Social Identities: Journal for the Study of Race, Nation and Culture, Vol. 23, No. 2, pp 179-194.
- Leith, M. S. and Sim, D. (eds.) (2014) The Modern Scottish Diaspora: Contemporary Debates and Perspectives. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.
- Leith, M., & Sim, D. (2016) 'Scotland's Diaspora Strategy: The View from the Current American Diaspora', Scottish Affairs, Vol. 25, No. 2, pp 186-208.
- Lunn, G. (2007) And the Crew Went Too: the £10 Assisted Passage. Stroud: Tempus.
- MacAskill, K. and McLeish, H. (2005) Global Scots: Voices from Afar. Edinburgh: Luath.
- Macdonald, S. (2005) 'Accessing Audiences: Visiting Visitor Books', Museum and Society, Vol. 3, No. 3, pp 119-36.
- MacKenzie, J. M. and Dalziel, N. R. (2012) Scots in South Africa: Ethnicity, Identity, Gender and Race 1772-1914. Manchester: Manchester University Press.
- MacKenzie, J. M. and Devine, T. M. (eds.) (2011) Scotland and the British Empire. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Mansfield, S. and Moffat, A. (2013) The Great Tapestry of Scotland: the Making of a Masterpiece. Edinburgh: Birlinn.
- Marshall, T. (2017) Worth Dying For: the Power and Politics of Flags. London: Elliott & Thompson.
- McCall, M. J. (1984) 'Structured Field Observation', Annual Review of Sociology, Vol. 5, pp263-82.
- McCarthy, A. and MacKenzie, J. M. (eds.) (2016) Global Migrations: the Scottish Diaspora since 1600. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.

- McCrone, D. (1995) Scotland the Brand: The Making of Scottish Heritage. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.
- McCrone, D. (1998) The Sociology of Nationalism. London: Routledge.
- Meehan, B. (1995) The Book of Kells. London: Thames and Hudson.
- Merriam, S.B. (2009) Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Millar, J. (1998) The Scots in Lithuania: a Personal View. Colonsay: House of Lochar.
- Miller, A. (2017). Harnessing the Pioneer Spirit: an Exploration of Possibilities and Potentials. Creative Learning Series.
- Miller, J. (2007) Swords for Hire: the Scottish Mercenary. Edinburgh: Birlinn.
- Moffat, A. (2005) Before Scotland: the Story of Scotland before History. London: Thames and Hudson.
- Moffat, A. (2013) The Great Tapestry of Scotland. Edinburgh: Birlinn.
- Moffet, R. (2014) Bannockburn Live Press Launch. [Online]
<http://www.clans2014.com/bannockburn-live-press-launch/> [accessed July 2017].
- Moorman, C. and Miner, A. S. (1998) 'Organizational Improvisation and Organizational Memory', Academy of Management Review, Vol. 27, No. 4. pp 698-723.
- Mullen, S. (2009) It Wisnae us: the Truth about Glasgow and Slavery. Edinburgh: Royal Incorporation of Architects in Scotland.
- Munro, A. and Sim, D. (2001) The Merseyside Scots: a Study of an Expatriate Community. Birkenhead: Liver Press.
- Nagel, J. (1994) 'Constructing Ethnicity: Creating and Recreating Ethnic Identity and Culture', Social Problems, Vol. 41, pp 1001-26.
- Paul, T. (2015) Engaging the Scottish Diaspora: the Next Generation. Edinburgh: Scottish Government.
- Pittock, M. (2013) Material Culture and Sedition 1688-1760: Treasured Objects, Secret Places. New York: Springer
- Prebble, J. (1963) The Highland Clearances. London: Penguin.

- Prentis, M. D. (2008) The Scots in Australia. Sydney: UNSW Press.
- Prestonpan Tapestry website. (2013) Pinkie House-Loretto Goes Tapestry Crazy! [Online] http://www.prestonpanstapestry.org/tapestry/html/news/show_news.aspx?newsid=3250 [accessed September 2017].
- Prestonpan Tapestry website. [Online] <http://www.prestonpanstapestry.org>. [accessed September 2017].
- Prince's Loyal Clans (The) – Homecoming Exhibition. (2009) [Online] Available: http://www.battleofprestonpan1745.org/prestoungrange/html/news/show_news.asp?newsid=2556&search=loyal+clans
- Radhakrishnan, R. (2003) 'Ethnicity in the Age of Diaspora', in Braziel, J. and Mannur, A (eds.) Theorizing Diaspora: a Reader. Oxford: Blackwell, pp 119-31.
- Robinson, E. (dir.) (2010) Stitches for Charlie. [DVD] s.l.: Battle of Prestonpan (1745) Heritage Trust. 27 mins.
- Rooke, A. (2013) Curating Community? The Relational and Agonistic Value of Participatory Arts in Superdiverse Localities. Swindon: Arts and Humanities Research Council.
- Rutherford, A. (2009), Engaging with the Scottish Diaspora: Rationale, Benefits and Challenges. Edinburgh: Scottish Government.
- Safran, W. (1991) 'Diasporas in Modern Societies: Myths of Homeland and Return', Diaspora, Vol. 1, No. 1. pp 83-99.
- Safran, W. (1999) 'Comparing Diasporas: a Review Essay', Diaspora, Vol. 8, No. 3. pp 255-91.
- Saldana, J. (2016) The Coding Manual for Qualitative Research. 3rd ed. London: Sage.
- Scotsman Newspaper (The) (2016) Welcome to Barga, the Most Scottish Town in Italy. [Online] Available: <http://www.scotsman.com/lifestyle/travel/welcome-to-barga-the-most-scottish-town-in-italy-1-4238742> [accessed October 2016]
- Scottish Diaspora Tapestry team (2012-17) News Archive. [Online] <http://www.scottishdiasporatapestry.org/news> [accessed September 2017].
- Scottish Diaspora Tapestry team (2012-2015) Strategy Group Minutes. Unpublished.
- Scottish Diaspora Tapestry team (2014a) Homecoming Scotland 2014: Outcome report. Unpublished.
- Scottish Diaspora Tapestry team (2014b) Final Report to Scottish Government. Unpublished.

Scottish Diaspora Tapestry website. [Online] <http://www.scottishdiasporatapestry.org>. [accessed October 2017].

Scottish Government (2010a) Analysis Report of Homecoming 2009 Diaspora Events. [Online] <http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2010/09/14081057/0> [accessed April 2017].

Scottish Government (2010b) Diaspora Engagement Plan: Reaching out to Scotland's International Family. [Online] <http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2010/09/14081131/1> [accessed January 2017].

Scottish Government (2016) Scotland's International Framework: Pakistan Engagement Strategy. Available: <http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2016/03/5305/0> [accessed March 2017].

Scottish Qualifications Authority (2016) National 5 History Course Support Notes. Available: https://www.sqa.org.uk/files_ccc/CfE_CourseUnitSupportNotes_N5_SocialStudies_History.pdf [accessed September 2017].

Sim, D. (2011) American Scots: the Scottish Diaspora and the USA. Edinburgh: Dunedin.

Sim, D. and McIntosh, I. (2007) 'Connecting with the Scottish Diaspora', Scottish Affairs, Vol. 58, No. 1, pp 78-95.

Smith, A. D. (1983) Theories of Nationalism. 2nd ed. London: Duckworth.

Smith, A. D. (1991) National Identity. London: Penguin.

Smith, A. D. (2001) Nationalism: Theory, Ideology, History. Cambridge: Polity.

Smith, A. D. (2008) The Cultural Foundations of Nations. Oxford: Blackwell.

Smith, A. D. (2014) The Nation in History: Historiographical Debates about Ethnicity and Nationalism. Cambridge: Polity.

Smith, D. B. (2013) An American Betrayal: Cherokee Patriots and the Trail of Tears. New York: Henry Holt & Co.

Statistics Canada. Census of Canada 2006. [Online] <http://www12.statcan.gc.ca/census-recensement/2006/dp-pd/index-eng.cfm> [accessed March 2017].

Tapestry's Tour Packs in Punters. (5 January 2017). Haddington: East Lothian Courier.

Thompson, J. (2007) Ngoni, Xhosa and Scot: Religion and Cultural Interactions in Malawi. Zomba: Kachere Series.

Thomson, J. A. F. (2000) 'Scots in England in the Fifteenth Century', Scottish Historical Review, Vol. 79, No. 1, pp 1-16.

Tölölyan, K. (2005) 'Restoring the Logic of the Sedentary to Diaspora Studies', in Anteby-Yemini, L. Berthomiere, W. and Sheffer, G. Les Diasporas: 2000 ans d'Histoire. Rennes: Presse Universitaires de Rennes, pp 137-48.

UNESCO (n. d.) Memory of the World Register: the Bayeux Tapestry. [Online]
<http://www.unesco.org/new/en/communication-and-information/memory-of-the-world/register/full-list-of-registered-heritage/registered-heritage-page-1/bayeux-tapestry/> [accessed March 2016].

Unwin, J. (ed.) (2017) The Murals Trail and Art Treasures of Prestonpans. 2nd Ed. Prestonpans: Prestoungrange University Press.

Visit Scotland (n. d.) Research and Statistics: International Markets. [Online]
http://www.visitscotland.org/research_and_statistics/visitor_research/visitor_research_international.aspx [accessed August 2017].

Visit Scotland Insight Department (2013) Summary of Ancestral Research 2012. [Online]
http://www.visitscotland.org/pdf/Ancestral%20Research%2016%20Jan%20vs.org_pptx.pdf [accessed May 2017].

Visit Scotland Insight Department (2016) Scotland: Key facts on Tourism in 2015. [Online]
<http://www.visitscotland.org/pdf/Tourism%20in%20Scotland%20Factsheet%202015.pdf> [accessed August 2017].

Vormittag, L. (2014) 'Making (the) Subject Matter: Illustration as Interactive, Collaborative Practice', Journal of Illustration, Vol.1, No. 1, pp 41-67.

Webb, E. J., Campbell, D. T., Schwartz, R. D., and Sechrest, L. (1966) Unobstructive Measures: Nonreactive Measures in the Social Sciences. Chicago: Rand McNally.

Whitfield, M. (2017) Effects of the Arts on Health. Westminster Hall debate: 11 October 2017.
Available: <http://parliamentlive.tv/event/index/434e3907-d2f7-4af0-bc45-212c426192b8?in=18:14:57&out=18:17:55> [accessed October 2017].

Wilson, R. (2006) Scots who Made America. Edinburgh: Birlinn.

Özkirimli, U. (2010) Theories of Nationalism: a Critical Introduction. 2nd ed. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.

APPENDICES

APPENDIX ONE

List of tapestry panels, arranged by cluster and country.

CLUSTER and COUNTRY	PANEL NUMBER	PANEL TITLE
Global Cluster		
	GE01	The Logo Panel
	GE02	Auld Lang Syne
	GE03	Ancient Trade Routes
	GE03a	Moors at the Court of King James IV
	GE04	Birth of Scottish Clubs & Societies
	GE05	Music
	GE06	Whisky
	GE07	Burns Supper
	GE08	Highland Dancing
	GE09	Highland Games
	GE10	Sport
	GE11	Ceilidh Dancing
	GE12	Scottish Country Dance
	GE13	St Andrews societies: Big Cities
	GE14	Selkirk Colonial Society and Common Riding
Baltic		
Norway	NO01	Travel by Longship
	NO02	The Maid of Norway
	NO03	Skottehandelen
	NO04	Edvard Grieg
	NO05	Shetland Bus
Sweden	SE01	Warriors
	SE02	The Birth of Gothenburg
	SE03	William Chalmers
	SE04	Colin Campbell and the Jacobites
	SE05	Royal Bachelors Club
	SE06	William Gibson: Jonsered
	SE07	Alexander Keiller
	SE08	Association Football
	SE09	Cockenzie Boat Disaster
	SE10	Gothenburgs in Scotland
Lithuania	LT01	Scots Church
	LT02	The Scots are still arriving
	LT03	Scots Traders
	LT04	Lithuanians of Scotland
Russia	RU01	Norman and Walter Leslie
	RU02	Patrick Gordon
	RU03	Catherine the Great & Scottish Doctors
	RU04	Thomas the Rhymer
	RU05	Arctic Convoys: PQ17 & HMS Ulster Queen
	RU06	Arctic Convoys II
Poland	PL01	Puir Pedlars
	PL02	Soldiers
	PL03	Merchants
Western Europe		
Germany	DE01	Abbey of St James
	DE02	Regensburg Schottenportal
	DE03	The Scholars of Ratisbon
	DE04	A German Love Story
Netherlands	NL01	Princess Mary

	NL02	Special Privileges
	NL03	The Scots House
	NL04	The Conservator
	NL05	The Kirk
	NL06	Lions from the Sea
	NL07	Trading with Veere
	NL08	Rotterdam Schotse Kerk 1643
	NL09	Schotse Kerk Vasteland 1685
	NL10	Reverend Robert Walker
	NL11	Rotterdam Scots Church 1952
	NL12	Universiteit Leiden
France	FR01	The Auld Alliance
	FR02	The Garde Ecossaise
	FR03	Mary of Guise
	FR04	Mary, Queen of Scots
	FR05	The Stuarts in Exile
	FR05a	John Law
	FR05b	Bonnie Prince Charlie
	FR06	James Young Simpson
	FR07	Robert Louis Stevenson in the Cevennes
	FR08	Charles Rennie Mackintosh in Roussillon
	FR09	Dr Elsie Inglis & Scottish Women's Medical Unit, Royaumont
	FR10	Golf and Arnaud Massy
Portugal	PT01	John the Scot: John Drummond
	PT02	George Sandeman
	PT03	The Port Trade
Italy	IT01	The Plaster Statue Makers
	IT01a	The Stuart Court in Rome
	IT02	The Sons of Fish and Chip Men
	IT03	They took the Low Road
	IT04	World War 2 and the Arandora Star
	IT05	The Most Scottish Town in Italy
	IT06	John Bellany
	IT07	Picinisco
Southern Asia		
Palestine/Israel	PL/IS01	Scots in Palestine/Israel
	PL/IS02	Tabeetha School, Jaffa
Pakistan	PK01	Sialkot Bagpipes
	PK02	Kinnaird College for Women
	PK03	New Bride
	PK04	NHS: Doctors and Nurses
	PK05	Truck Art
India	IN01	King James & Jahangir
	IN02	Robert Kyd (1741-1793)
	IN03	William Roxburgh (1751-1815)
	IN04	Scottish Surgeons
	IN05	Robert Wight (1796-1872)
	IN06	Forest Conservation
	IN07	William Graham McIvor (1824-1876)
	IN08	Scottish Gardeners
	IN09	Dr Robert Bruce – Assam Tea
	IN10	Darjeeling Tea Company
	IN11	Kashmir Weavers

	IN12	The First Shawl
	IN13	Vale of Leven Turkey Red
	IN14	Jute: Bangladesh & Dundee
	IN15	Mills around the World
	IN16	Kolkata Scottish Cemetery
	IN16a	Alexander Duff 1806-78
	IN17	Geddes & Tagore
	IN17a	Scots in Kalimpong
	IN18	Honorable Mary Scott
	IN18a	Alastair Robin McGlashan
	IN19	Indian Wedding: Bride
	IN20	Traditions and Celebrations
	IN21	Baron Singh
Sri Lanka	LK01	David Sime Cargill (Burmah Oil)
	LK02	Sir Thomas Lipton
China	CN01	John Bell - Rhubarb
	CN02	East India Company
	CN03	Jardine and Matheson
	CN04	Tea: Andrew Melrose
	CN05	Cutty Sark Tea Clipper
	CN06	The Great Tea Race of 1866
	CN07	Chinese students in Scotland
	CN08	Eric Liddell: Missionary
	CN09	Eric Liddell: Athlete
	CN10	Hong Kong
Taiwan	TW01	Sir Patrick Manson
Canada		
Canada	CA01	Royal Charter of Nova Scotia
	CA02	Nova Scotia Gaels
	CA03	<i>The Hector</i>
	CA04	The Glenalladale Settlers
	CA05	The Landing
	CA06	Pioneers First House
	CA07	Keep the Faith
	CA08	Birth of Confederation
	CA09	Fuadach nan Gàidheal
	CA10	The Settlers' Lament
	CA11	John Norton, War of 1812
	CA12	From Croft to Clearing
	CA13	Scarborough Logging Bee
	CA14	Bees, Frolics and Building Barns
	CA15	The City of Guelph
	CA16	Mary Irwin, 17 th century nun
	CA17	St Andrew's Society of Montreal
	CA18	The Maple Leaf Forever
	CA19	Fur Trade/First Nations Wives
	CA20	York Boat
	CA21	Lord Selkirk's Settlers
	CA22	Métis Community
	CA23	Battle of Seven Oaks
	CA24	Chief Peguis
	CA25	Settlement Churches
	CA26	Sandford Fleming

	CA27	Alexander Mackenzie
	CA28	John Rae
	CA29	Simon Fraser
	CA30	Agnes Dean Cameron
	CA31	Gung Haggis Fat Choy
	CA32	Sir James Douglas: Father of BC
	CA33	Coal Baron Robert Dunsmuir
	CA33a	Campbell of the Yukon
	CA34	The Megantic Outlaw
	CA35	Lt-Colonel John McCrae
	CA36	The Wilson Family
The Americas		
United States	US01	Robert Barclay
	US02	Battles of Dunbar and Worcester
	US03	Merrymeeting Bay: Ulster Scots' Arrival
	US04	Crown of Maine
	US05	District of Maine (unfinished)
	US06	Colonel Ninian Beall
	US07	Hugh Mercer
	US08	Tobacco Factors
	US09	John Knox Witherspoon
	US10	Flora MacDonald
	US11	We are all Related
	US12	Chief William McIntosh
	US13	Chief John Ross
	US14	The Trail of Tears
	US15	Kate Cumming: Confederate Nurse
	US15a	Last Princess of Hawaii
	US16	Roderick Mackenzie
	US17	Montello Granite Company
	US18	Andrew Carnegie
	US19	John Muir: Dunbar
	US20	John Muir: Marquette County
	US21	John Muir: Sierra Nevada
	US22	John Muir: John of the Mountains
	US23	Donaldina Cameron (Mackenzie)
	US24	National Tartan Day
	US25	John Milligan: Mountain Climber
Jamaica	JM01	First Campbell on Jamaica
	JM02	Scots and Plantations
	JM03	James and Robert Wedderburn
	JM04	Mary Seacole
	JM05	Geoff Palmer: a Jamaican Immigrant
Brazil	BR01	Thomas Cochrane
	BR02	Football in Brazil
	BR03	Carlos Drummond de Andrade
Argentina	AR01	Nueva Escocia
	AR02	Caithness Settlers
	AR02a	Mungo & Grace Park
	AR03	Alexander Hutton
	AR04	Robert Bontine Cunninghame Graham
Chile	CL01	Valparaiso
	CL02	William Mann Somerville

Antarctica	AQ01	RRS <i>Discovery II</i>
Africa & Australasia		
Ethiopia	ET01	James Bruce
Tristan da Cunha	TDC01	Edinburgh of the Seven Seas
Malawi	MW01	David Livingstone
	MW02	Livingstonia Mission
	MW03	Blantyre Mission
Zimbabwe	ZW01	Robert Moffat
	ZW02	Thomas Meikle: the Whisky Trail
South Africa	ZA01	Lovedale Missionary Institute
	ZA01a	Thomas Pringle
	ZA02	Tiyo Soga & Janet Burnside
	ZA03	Galla Slaves
	ZA04	Robert Moffat
	ZA04a	Andrew Geddes Bain
	ZA05	Dundee Mining
	ZA06	Kruger Park
Australia	AU01	Botany Bay
	AU02	First Fleet
	AU02a	Alexander Muir and the Scottish Martyrs
	AU03	Lachlan Macquarie
	AU04	Elizabeth Macquarie
	AU05	William Scott: Convict and Horsebreeder
	AU06	Robert Campbell
	AU07	William Turnbull
	AU08	Shipping firm of McIlwraith McEacharn
	AU09	Thomas Tait: Sydney Harbour Bridge
	AU10	John MacArthur
	AU10a	Eliza Furlonge
	AU10b	Three Macphersons
	AU10c	Rankine Family of Strathalbyn
	AU10d	Clan MacNicol of Scorrybreac
	AU10e	William Wilson Gordon
	AU11	Waltzing Mathilda
	AU12	Dorothea Mackellar 1885-1968
	AU13	Andrew Petrie
	AU14	Rev John Dunmore Lang
	AU15	Royal Flying Doctor Service
	AU16	Qantas
	AU17	Rutherford Collies
	AU18	Discovery of Gold at Poverty Point
	AU19	Bendigo Gold Rush
	AU20	Bendigo Pottery
	AU21	Ten Pound Passage
	AU22	Captain Cadell
	AU23	Cockenzie Captains
	AU24	Little Scotland
	AU25	Laura Buralda & Francis Dunbar Warren
	AU26	John McDouall Stuart
	AU27	Clipper Ship <i>City of Adelaide</i>
	AU28	Sir Thomas Elder: pastoralist
	AU29	Peter Waite

	AU30	Catherine Helen Spence: Grand Old Woman of Australia
	AU31	Charles Duguid
	AU32	Eric Bogle AOM
	AU33	James Drummond
	AU34	Saint Mary MacKillop
	AU35	The Longest Cattle Drive
New Zealand	NZ01	HMS <i>Endeavour</i> and Sydney Parkinson
	NZ02	Whalers
	NZ03	Rev Norman McLeod
	NZ04	Families
	NZ05	Otago Settlement
	NZ05a	Dunedin
	NZ05b	Spinning Tales from Applecross
	NZ06	Gabriel's Gully
	NZ06a	Selina Sutherland
	NZ06b	Polson's Hut
	NZ07	Charles Nicholson
British Isles		
Northern Ireland	GBNI01	The Plantation of Ulster
	GBNI02	Elizabeth Shaw and the Linen Trade
	GBNI03	Bessie Bell & Mary Gray
	GBNI04	William Ritchie
	GBNI05	The Linen Thread Co.
Republic of Ireland	IE01	Republic of Ireland
	IE02	The Book of Kells
	IE03	The Gallowglass
	IE04	The High King of Ireland
	IE05	Irish Migrant Workers
	IE06	James Connolly and the Easter Rising
	IE07	The Burns Connection
England	GBE01	It's Corby for Me!
	GBE02	Home and a Job
	GBE03	PLUTO
	GBE04	St Andrew's Church
	GBE05	New Town home
	GBE06	The Grampian Club
	GBE07	Earl Henry
	GBE08	Ivanhoe
	GBE09	Nigel Gresley: Doncaster Works
	GBE10	Jock Kane
	GBE11	Thomas Telford
	GBE12	William & John Laird
	GBE13	Cammell Laird
	GBE14	Louisa Birt: Liverpool Sheltering Homes
	GBE15	Dr James Currie
	GBE16	William Henry Duncan
	GBE17	Liverpool Scottish
	GBE18	Liverpool FC
	GBE19	Federation of Scottish Societies
	GBE20	Crown Court Church of Scotland
	GBE21	Scottish Prime Ministers

APPENDIX TWO:

Participant Questionnaire

including information sheet and certificate of consent

Participants' Information Sheet

Introduction

The *Scottish Diaspora Tapestry* is a unique visualisation of the story of the Scottish Diaspora across the globe and across the centuries. In order to evaluate its significance we would like to hear from all those who have participated in its creation. This study is being undertaken as part of a PhD dissertation by Arran Johnston at the *University of the West of Scotland*, with the support of the *Scottish Diaspora Tapestry* team.

Taking part in this survey is optional and you have two months to respond if you wish to do so, so there is plenty of time for you to consider whether you wish to be involved.

This sheet should answer most of your questions, but if you have any further queries or concerns then please do not hesitate to get in touch.

Contact

Arran Paul Johnston

Room L238, School of Social Sciences

University of the West of Scotland

Paisley Campus

Paisley

Scotland

PA1 2BE

Personal details redacted.

Purpose of the research

This survey will help us to understand who participated in the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry and why they chose to do so. We believe this will provide a greater understanding of how important this artwork may be in revealing how Scotland's Diaspora sees itself and its connection to Scotland. The results might be very different from country to country. The results of this survey are expected to play an important role in defining how we appreciate the Tapestry, and allow us to record for posterity the motivations of those involved.

Participant selection

All the stitchers and contributors whose names and details are known to the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry team will be invited to participate. Naturally the more responses received, the better our understanding of the project.

Voluntary participation

Participation in this survey is optional. If you do not wish to participate then there is no requirement to do so.

How to take part

This research consists of a simple questionnaire. It will begin with some straightforward questions covering gender, nationality etc, which will help us gain a sense of the spectrum of people the project attracted. Then there will be some more open questions inviting your thoughts on your participation.

If there are any particularly unusual or intriguing results, we might wish to follow up with additional questions for individual participants. Participation in this additional stage would also be optional.

You do not have to complete all the questions in the survey if you do not wish to answer any. It is expected that the survey will take less than thirty minutes to complete.

Once completed you can return the questionnaire to the contact address above, by email or by post. You can return your questionnaire at any time within eight weeks.

Confidentiality

Correspondence outside of the questionnaire will be treated as strictly confidential and will only be seen by the researcher and the supervisory team.

Some information from the completed questionnaires may be shared with the trustees of the *Scottish Diaspora Tapestry (Prestoungrange Arts Festival)* for internal evaluation of the project. We will not share any of your data or contact details with any other party. Hard copies of responses will be stored in locked cabinets and digital files will be password protected.

Analysis of the data collected from this survey will be published, and your name may be identified along with the pieces of the Tapestry you were involved in.

Sharing the Results

Participants in this survey will be contacted by email to advise where the results of this research can be accessed and read. Publication of the research is expected to occur in the first half of 2016.

Right to Withdraw

Participation is optional, and if you choose to withdraw your responses from this research please do not hesitate to contact us.

This Participants' Information Sheet has been reviewed by the University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee.

Certificate of Consent

Please complete this form and return it along with your completed questionnaire to:

Personal details redacted.

Arran Paul Johnston

Room L238, School of Social Sciences

University of the West of Scotland

Paisley Campus

Paisley

Scotland

PA1 2BE

I hereby consent to participate in the survey of stitchers and volunteers for the above research project.

I have been provided with and read a participants' information sheet, and voluntarily consent to be a participant in this study

I understand that my answers may be cited in published research.

Name of Participant _____

Signature of Participant _____

(a digital signature is permitted for email responses)

Date _____

Statement by the researcher/person taking consent

I confirm that the participant was provided the information sheet and given opportunity to ask questions about the study or to refuse participation. I confirm that the individual has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

Signature of Researcher _____

Date _____

Questionnaire

Thank you for agreeing to share your experiences of participating in the *Scottish Diaspora Tapestry* project. Your contributions will contribute significantly to our understanding of the significance of this remarkable artwork.

You can find all the information you need about your participation on the Information Sheet provided. If you have any further questions please do not hesitate to contact me.

Please remember to complete the Consent Form and to return it with this questionnaire.

PART I

About you

These questions help us to understand the breadth and diversity of the people involved in this project.

Q1.	First name (s)	
	Surname	
	Maiden name (where applicable)	
Q2.	Gender	Male
		Female
Q3.	Age	Under 18 18-24 25-34 35-44 45-54 55-64 65+
Q4.	In what country were you born?	
	In which city/ province/state where you born?	
Q5.	In which country do you live now?	
	In which city/ province/state do you live?	
Q6.	Have you ever lived in any other countries? If so, please specify.	
Q7.	What is your nationality?	

Q8.	How do you define your ethnic group?	
Q9.	What is your religion?	No religion Church of Scotland Other Presbyterian Roman Catholic Anglican Other Christian Buddhist Hindu Jewish Muslim Sikh Other:

PART II

Your relationship with Scotland

Q10.	Do you currently live in Scotland?	Yes No
Q11.	Have you ever lived in Scotland?	Yes No
Q12.	If you live/have ever lived in Scotland, how long did you live there?	Less than 6 months 1 year 1-2 years 2-5 years 5-10 years More than 10 years Please specify:
Q13.	Do you have family living in Scotland?	Yes No
Q14.	Have you ever visited Scotland?	Yes No
	If so, what was the purpose of your visit?	Business Holiday/vacation Genealogy/Ancestry research Visiting friends or family Study Other
Q15.	Do you hope to visit Scotland in the future?	Yes No

Q16.	Do you have ancestral or family roots in Scotland?	Yes No Think so Never thought about it
	Do you have family or ancestral links to other Diaspora countries (other than Scotland)	Yes (please specify) No
Q17.	Have you ever researched your family tree?	Yes No
Q18.	Have you ever been a member of a Scottish society?	Yes, I am presently Never Have been but not any more If so, please specify:
Q19.	Did you know that 2014 was Scotland's <i>Year of Homecoming</i> ?	Yes No Not before I heard about the Tapestry

PART III

Your part in the *Scottish Diaspora Tapestry*

Q20.	Did you stitch part of the Tapestry?	Yes – a full panel Yes – part of a panel Yes – a few stitches No
Q21.	If you did, which panel was it?	
Q22.	Did you help suggest or research the content of a panel?	Yes No
Q23.	If you did, which panel was it?	
Q24.	Were you involved in any other way? Please tell us how.	
Q25.	Does the panel you were involved in tell a story directly relating to you personally, or your family?	Yes (please explain how) No

Q26. Does the panel you were involved in relate directly to the community where you live?	Yes No
Q27. How many other people worked on your panel?	
Q28. Who do you think determined the content of your panel?	You Other stitchers Others in your community Local academic or society The Diaspora Tapestry team in Scotland Don't know Other (please specify)
Q29. How much influence do you feel you/your group had on the subject and content of your panel?	Lots Moderate Would have liked more None Any additional comments:
Q30. How important was it to you that you/your group/community had an influence over the content of the panels?	Very important Quite important Not very important Irrelevant
Q31. How did you hear about the Tapestry project	The Tapestry Website "Scottish" Newspaper or Magazine Local newspaper Direct contact from Scotland <i>Visit Scotland</i> information Other (please specify)

Q32.	What was the main reason(s) you participated in the Tapestry?	Personal or ancestral connection to Scotland Community connection to Scotland A love of Scottish culture Enjoyment of embroidery Chance to participate in a global project Other (please specify)
Q33.	Did you travel to Scotland to see the completed Tapestry?	Yes No If Yes, please specify where you saw it:
Q34.	Would you consider travelling to Scotland in order to see the Tapestry?	Yes No
Q35.	Would you like the Tapestry to be displayed in your local area?	Yes, I would go and see it Yes, I would help make it happen No, I'm not interested
Q36.	Do you feel participating in the Tapestry has strengthened your connection to Scotland?	Yes Yes, although I was already No Other
Q37.	Has participating in the Tapestry made you more aware of the Scottish Diaspora and your place within in?	Very much so Yes, a little I was already very aware No
Q38.	Finally, can you please describe in your own words why you participated in the Tapestry and what it means to you/your group/your community:	

Thank you for taking the time to complete the questionnaire.

APPENDIX THREE:

List of media coverage for the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry project

From the archive maintained by Dr Gordon Prestoungrange.

Listed by publication/outlet in chronological order of appearance.

Up to date as of September 2015.

Waterloo Record, Guelph, Ontario (Canada): Tapestry celebrates Scottish influence around the world.
22 November 2013

Association de Jumelage (France): La broderie de l'amite Franco-Ecossaise. [n. d.]

Bungendore-Braidwood local news, New South Wales (Australia): Settlers celebrated in Scottish
Diaspora Tapestry. [n. d.]

Scottish Banner (Australasia and North America editions): Tales for the 2014 Homecoming. October
2013.

Scottish Banner (Australasia and North America editions): half-page advertisements. October,
November and December 2013.

Scottish Banner (Australasia and North America editions): half-page advertisements with editorial.
February, March and April 2014.

Commonwealth Games Celebrate newsletter (Scotland): £10K boost for Tapestry. [n.d.].

John o'Groat Journal (Scotland): Tapestry project to explore links to Patagonia. [n.d.].

Scots Heritage Magazine: A stitch in time. [n.d.].

Hyslop, F. MSP (Scotland): Scotland's rich tapestry revealed by stitchers: first glimpse by Scots.
[n.d.].

Acquire Media/ BusinessWeek: Diaspora Tapestry panels unveiled. [n.d.].

Craft Scotland (Scotland): First panels of Scottish diaspora tapestry unveiled [n.d.].

Douglas local newspaper: Sew far Sew good from Sweden. [n.d.].

Scots Canadian: The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry. Summer 2013.

Corby local newspaper (England): Corby Scots picked to tell tales on tapestry. [n.d.].

BBC Radio Northampton (England): Corby Scots picked to tell tales on tapestry. [n.d.].

The Scotsman newspaper (Scotland): Preston pans to the World - Global Vision. [n.d.].

Corby Council (England): Scotland wants to hear Corby's story. [n.d.].

East Lothian Council (Scotland): Latest tapestry to be made in 25 different countries. [n.d.].

Arisaig Highland Games news (Scotland): Warp and weft. [n.d.].

Northamptonshire Telegraph (England): Pipers, a pipeline and porridge for Corby tapestry panels. [n.d.].

Northampton Herald & Post (England): Tapestry coming to Corby. [n.d.].

Scots International Church Rotterdam (Netherlands): Scottish Tapestry Project. [n.d.].

Douglas: So that's how you picture Scots history. [n.d.].

East Lothian Courier (Scotland): First panels due to arrive from Sweden; First tapestry panels arrive. [n.d.].

Kvibergs-Staden (Sweden): De syr ihop historien... from Utby to New York. [n.d.].

Scottish Studies Society: The Scots Canadian. Spring 2013.

'Cruachan' Clan Campbell Society of Australia newsletter (Australia): Scottish Diaspora Tapestry under way. No. 119, Spring 2013.

'Cruachan' Clan Campbell Society of Australia newsletter (Australia): Busy recruiting Campbell support. No. 120, Summer 2013.

Provinciale Zeeuwse Courant (Netherlands): Veere borduurt aan enorm Schots wandtapijt. [n.d.].

Kedainiy garsas (Lithuania): Siuvinetame gobelene – Kedainiu skotu bendruomenes istorija. [n.d.].

BrazilMag (Brazil): Brazil's Scots invited to lend a hand to historical tapestry project. [n.d.].

Paisley Thread Mills Museum news (Scotland): Diaspora Paisley Threads around the World. 18 October 2013.

Sao Paulo news outlet (Brazi): Projeto da Tapeçaria Historica. 26 November 2013.

Brantwood Times (New South Wales, Australia): Looking forward to 2014. 20 November 2013.

Clan Macpherson Association (Australia) Newsletter: November 2013.

Commonwealth Games Celebrate newsletter (Scotland): A stitch in time. 6 December 2013.

The Scotsman newspaper: International tapestry collaboration has dates booked for Nationwide Tour. 30 December 2013.

American Society of Sao Paulo Forum (Brazil): Brazil's Scots and Scots Americans Invited to Lend a Hand. December 2013.

Visit Scotland (International): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry and Events Programme](#). 31 December 2013.

Scottish Government News (Scotland): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry and Events Programme](#). December 31 2013. Available: <http://news.scotland.gov.uk/News/Scotland-s-Diaspora-Tapestry-7f8.aspx>

Buzz PEI (Canada): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry](#). 2 January 2014.

CBC Island Morning radio (Canada): [Adding to a Worldwide Tapestry: interview with Mary Gallant](#). 3 January 2014.

East Lothian Courier (Scotland): [Minister's Visit to see artist](#). 10 January 2014.

Daily Bulldog – Franklin County's News (USA): [Tapestry project connects Maine to Scotland](#). January 16 2014.

Toun Cryer Magazine (Scotland): [Hand made in East Lothian](#). February 2014.

Hillstyle (Australia): [Clipper 'City of Adelaide' Returns](#). 6 February 2014.

Harrogate Advertiser (England): [Scot involved with tapestry](#). 6 February 2014.

The Guardian: Community (Canada): [Panels from the Past: PEI Groups create historic pieces for Scottish Tapestry project](#). 13 February 2014.

AOL Alabama Community News (USA): [Scottish Society of Mobile stitches panels for Diaspora Tapestry](#). 14 February 2014.

BBC Radio Scotland (Scotland): [Scots around the world celebrate heritage in tapestry](#). 15 February 2014.

The One Show, BBC One (United Kingdom): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry on Claudia Winkleman's Sewing Bee, with live link to stitchers in the Netherlands](#). 20 February 2014.

Bream Bay News, Waipu (New Zealand): [Hard at work on the Great Scottish Tapestry](#). 27 February 2014.

East Lothian Life (Scotland): [Scotland's Diaspora telling its Tales to The Pans](#). Spring 2014.

Scottish Banner (Australasia and North America editions): [We're Looking & Listening in Scotland as the Tales Unfold](#). March 2014.

Gairloch and District Times (Scotland): March 2014.

Scotland Now (United Kingdom): [Expats sew their personal stories across the globe to create Scottish Diaspora Tapestry](#). 11 March 2014.

Morrison, J. in Sunday Mail (United Kingdom): Threads of Scotland that wrap around the world. 9 March 2014.

The Highlander (North America): Scottish Diaspora Tapestry – telling tales to Scotland, plus full colour advertisement. Spring 2014.

Fisher, M. in Overseas – Royal Overseas League magazine (international): United by the Past - Scotland's Homecoming. March-May 2014.

Feeling Stitchy (international): 'Ola! This week I bring a beautiful story from Scotland ... Stitches with Portuguese Soul. 13 March 2014.

BBC Radio Sheffield (England): Left Field for Doncaster, including interviews with Charles Kelham, Ruth Taylor and Andrew Crummy. 25 March 2014.

Lewis, C. and Smith, F. in World of Cross Stitching (United Kingdom): Out & About. March-April 2014.

Nairnshire Telegraph (Scotland): Scottish tapestry on a Russian theme. 25 March 2014.

Inverness Courier (Scotland): Tapestry celebrates contribution made by Scots around the world. 25 March 2014.

Doncaster Star (England): Sew Up a Place in Scottish History. 26 March 2014.

Feeling Stitchy (international): Portuguese Panels - Ola!. 27 March 2014.

Doncaster Star (England): Frae Donny Scotland as town stars in artwork. 27 March 2014.

R. Black in The Scotsman newspaper (Scotland): The Battle of Prestonpans is being fought all over again over Gaelic. 1 April 2014.

Doncaster Free Press (England): Sewing Up a Piece of Scottish History. 3 April 2014.

East Lothian Courier (Scotland): Marilyn helped stitch a tribute to John Muir. 18 April 2014.

3 Harbours Festival Programme, (Scotland): centre spread and editorial. April-May 2014.

Sedgefield Edge (South Africa): The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry. 23 April 2014.

Sarkar, S. in The Telegraph, Kolkata (India): Scottish Cemetery Tapestry on world tour. 24 April 2014.

Times Colonist BC (Canada): Our Community Embroiderers honour local Scots. 11 May 2014.

British Genes Blog (international): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry Exhibitions](#). 12 May 2014.

American Women's Club of Central Scotland (Scotland): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry Project](#). May 2014.

East Lothian News Online (Scotland): [How to Make a Scottish Tapestry – demonstrated by East Lothian Volunteers](#). 15 May 2014.

John O'Groat Journal (Scotland): [Caithness stitchers get \[Patagonia\] tapestry all sewn up](#). 16 May 2014.

St Andrew's Church, Scarborough (Canada): [The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry](#). 15 May 2014.

East Lothian News (Scotland): [Community Art of a Global Scale](#). inc full page colour advertisement. 30 May 2014.

Porteus, T. in East Lothian Courier (Scotland): [Threads of Our Past: Weaving Family Tales](#). 30 May 2014.

Scottish Government Social Media: [Humza Yousaf MSP and Caroline Packman at Community Centre](#). 30 May 2014.

East Lothian Courier (Scotland): [Scottish Diaspora's World Premiere in Prestonpans](#). inc full page colour advertisement. 30 May 2014.

East Lothian Courier (Scotland): [Touching War Romance Tale Immortalised](#). 6 June 2014.

East Lothian Courier (Scotland): [Tapestry is Launched – former Lord Mayor of Gothenburg....](#) 6 June 2014.

East Lothian News (Scotland): [Sewing the Seeds of World Friendship in Prestonpans](#). inc full page colour advertisement. 6 June 2014.

DRB Women's History Group (Scotland): [Should auld acquaintance be forgot](#). 12 June 2014.

Lewis, C. in World of Cross Stitching (United Kingdom): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry – History in Stitches](#). No. 218, June 2014.

Scottish Field, Homecoming Supplement (Scotland): 'A Stitch Back in Time', June-August 2014.

The Southern Cross – Journal of Clan MacNeacail in ANZ (Australasia): [Welcome to the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry; the official opening](#). Vol. 22, No. 3, 2014.

CBC Radio Quebec (Canada): Eastern Townships represented on Scottish Diaspora Tapestry: interview with Jane Loiselle & Gordon Prestoungrange. 15 August 2014.

Paisley Daily Express (Scotland): Anchor Mill shows the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry. 3 September 2014.

Arts Caithness Org (Scotland): Diaspora Tapestry at Helmsdale. 4 November 2014.

Rogers, S. in Landscape Magazine: 2014.

Doncaster Star (England): Tapestry will celebrate Doncaster's Scottish Links. 12 November 2014.

Doncaster Star (England): A colourful tapestry to celebrate Scottish history has arrived for a week-long stay in Doncaster. [plus online video] 15 November 2014.

Yorkshire Post (England): Scottish Diaspora tapestry arrives in Doncaster. 15 November 2014.

South Yorkshire Times (England): Scottish Tapestry Goes on Show in Doncaster. [plus online video] 15 November 2014.

Thorne & District Gazette (England): Scottish Tapestry on show in Doncaster. [plus online video] 15 November 2014.

Northamptonshire Telegraph (England): Telling town's Scottish heritage stitch by stitch. 20 November 2014.

Corby Radio (England): daily announcements, 25 November-4 December 2014.

East Lothian News Musselburgh Edition (Scotland): Musselburgh to host tapestry. 6 December 2014.

CTV News at Six (Canada): Winnipeg's contribution to Scotland's Diaspora Tapestry. 17 December 2014.

CBC Radio with Heather Ferguson (Canada): Embroidered Tapestry for Scottish Heritage. 17 December 2014.

East Lothian News (Scotland): Burgh's Links to Slavery recalled. 26 December 2014.

East Lothian Courier (Scotland): Sir Geoff Welcomes the Tapestry. 26 December 2014.

East Lothian Courier (Scotland): Sneak Preview of new Tapestry panels. 6 March 2015.

East Lothian News (Scotland): Gradual Return for panels. 6 March 2015.

Bergen Commune (Norway): Viser skotsk historie I broderte bilder. March 2015.

BA Bergen Savisen (Norway): En spesiell historiefortelling. 24 March 2015.

Lifelivetfles (Norway): A Scot in Norway – Diaspora. 28 March 2015.

East Lothian Courier (Scotland): Taking Tapestry across Europe. 30 April 2015.

Histoire HZG (Netherlands): WereldPremiere in Veere – Schots wandtapijt van 164 metres. May 2015.

Selkirk Weekend Advertiser (Scotland): Souters stitch up Colonials cast for diaspora tapestry. 25 May 2015.

Middelburgse & Veerse BODE (Netherlands): Wereldpremiere wandtapijt in Veere. 27 May 2015.

Zeeland PZC (Netherlands): Wereldreis in borduursteke. 29 May 2015.

Z - Omrep Zeeland (Netherlands): 164 meter lang wandtapijt in Veere. 30 May 2015.

Dutch News (Netherlands): Zeeland town of Veere shows off Scottish roots with 164-metre tapestry. 3 June 2015.

Seanchas Ur: Newsletter of Scottish Gaelic Society of Victoria (Canada): Scottish Diaspora Tapestry/ Warm Welcome in Veere. *an Geambradh 2015*, No. 8.

Zeeland PZC (Netherlands): Veere brengt wandtapijt naar Italie. 1 August 2015.

Barga Estate Eventi (Italy): Barga e la Scozia unite dal “Tapestry”. Summer 2015.

GiornalediBarga.it (Italy): Scottish Diaspora Tapestry Opens. 10 August 2015.

BargaNews.com (Italy): The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry – an unqualified masterpiece. 11 August 2015.

Duratorre, E. in RTG Telegolfo.com (Italy): “La Scottish Diaspora Tapestry” sbarca a Picinisco. 31 August 2015.

Agenda Boussy (France): Exposition Internationale de la Tapisserie de la Diaspora Ecossoise. September 2015.

www.ville-boussy (France): The Scottish Diaspora Ecossoise. 3 October 2015.

Scottish Banner (Australasia Edition): advertisement. October 2015.

Frequence Decouvrir (France): La Culture Celtique – La Tapisserie de la Diaspora Ecossoise. No. 289. 25 October 2015.

Victor Harbor Times (Australia): [Scottish Diaspora Art-on-Show: Goolwa Hosts International Diaspora Tapestry Exhibition](#). 18 November 2015.

The Southern Argus (Australia): [Rankin Family History](#). 17 November 2015.

The Southern Argus (Australia): [Scottish History comes to Goolwa](#). 18 November 2015.

The Southern Argus (Australia): [Goolwa Walk with Roly](#). 19 November 2015.

Scottish Banner (Australasia edition): [Scottish History comes to Australia](#). November 2015.

East Lothian Courier (Scotland): [Strike Delays unveiling of tapestry](#). 19 November 2015.

TASCAL Newsletter (Australia): [The Scottish Diaspora is in Australia!](#). December 2015.

John McDougall Stuart Inc. (Australia): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry at Burnside Civic Centre](#). No. 146, December 2015.

Alexandrina Library: History Room News (Australia): [The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry in Goolwa](#). No. 137, December 2015.

Mercury, Tasmania (Australia): [Uncommon Thread to Scottish Stories](#). 19 January 2016.

The Border Mail, Albury (Australia): [Joining Together Threads of Rich History](#). 16 February 2016.

Review – Embroiderers Guild of South Australia (Australia): [Did you get to see the Display?](#) No. 516. February 2016.

East Lothian Courier (Scotland): [Tapestry's visit is extended Down Under to Wangaratta](#). 26 February 2016.

Wangaratta Chronicle (Australia): [Bonnie Tapestries](#). 29 February 2016.

North Shore Times, Sydney (Australia): [Tapestry a Reminder of Scotland](#). 23 March 2016.

North Shore Times, Sydney (Australia): [Scotland's rich tapestry is revealed](#). 25 March 2016.

Scoop Independent News (New Zealand): [It's Storytelling with a Difference](#). 5 April 2016.

Stitch – with the Embroiderers' Guild (International): [The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry](#). April-May 2016.

Otago Daily Times (New Zealand): ['Thrilled' to host Scottish Diaspora Tapestry show](#). 14 April 2016.

The Star (New Zealand): [Celebrating Scottish Diaspora](#). 14 April 2016.

Dunedin TV News (New Zealand): [Tapestries illustrate Scottish migration](http://www.dunedintv.co.nz/news/tapestries-illustrate-scottish-migration). 15 April 2016. Available: <http://www.dunedintv.co.nz/news/tapestries-illustrate-scottish-migration>.

Northern Natal Courier – KwaZulu (South Africa): [Dundee makes its mark thanks to Scottish heritage](#). 20 April 2016.

Scottish Banner (Australasia edition): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry Exhibition Recipient of the Burnside Community Event of the Year Award 2016](#). April 2016.

Harbour Living (Canada): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry Exhibition](#). 14 May 2016.

Times Colonist, Victoria (Canada): [Tapestry tells the story of Scots around the world](#). 19 May 2016.

CBC Radio Victoria (Canada): [Celebrating in Tapestry](#). 19 May 2016.

Press Reader Canada (Canada): [A Scottish Tapestry: Cathedral hosts exhibit of embroidered images of Scots around the globe](#). 19 May 2016.

SewArtsy (North America): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry – visit it this side of the Pond](#). 25 May 2016.

OneSmallStitch Blog (International): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry – stitched on Scottish linen](#). 26 May 2016.

CBC TV Winnipeg Weekend Round Up (Canada): [Terry MacLeod visits the Diaspora Tapestry at Manitoba Legislature](#). 17 June 2016.

CBC Radio Winnipeg Weekend Round Up (Canada): [Terry MacLeod visits the Diaspora Tapestry at Manitoba Legislature](#). 19 June 2016.

Winnipeg Free Press (Canada): [Tapestry depicting Scottish history on display at Legislative building](#). 24 June 2016.

The Lance community newspaper (Canada): [Stitching their place in History](#). 27 June 2016.

Montello Historic Preservation Society Gazetteer (USA): [Scottish Tapestry comes to Vaughn Hall](#). June 2016.

Marquette County Tribune (USA): [Tapestry panels to arrive in Montello for exhibit starting July 16th](#). 30 June 2016.

Marquette County Tribune (USA): [Scottish Tapestry Opens July 16th: come to tea with Mary Queen of Scots](#). 7 July 2016.

East Lothian Courier (Scotland): [Diaspora Tapestry on show at childhood home of county-born naturalist Muir](#). 9 July 2016.

Portage Daily Register (USA): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry makes sole U.S. stop in Montello](#). 13 July 2016.

Marquette County Tribune (USA): [Scottish Tapestry Exhibit Opens July 16 at Vaughn Hall](#). 14 July 2016.

Marquette County Record (USA): [Scottish Fest Comes to Montello](#). 15 July 2016.

Marquette County Record (USA): [Scottish heritage is celebrated in Montello at Scottish Fest & Opening of Tapestry Exhibition](#). 21 July 2016.

CBC News, Charlottetown PEI (Canada): [Tapestry Exhibition planned for The Concourse of the Arts](#). 13 September 2016.

Toronto Star (Canada): [Scottish Tapestry weaves tale of a nation](#). 29 September 2016.

CTV, Charlottetown PEI (Canada): <http://atlantic.ctvnews.ca/video?clipId=971862> [accessed August 2017].

CBC, Charlottetown PEI (Canada): [PEI Scottish History part of a huge tapestry on display](#). 14 October 2016.

The Guardian PEI (Canada): [Scottish Diaspora Project comes full circle](#). 14 October 2016.

PEI Theatre (Canada): [Scottish Tapestry Goes Big](#). 16 October 2016.

The Buzz on PEI (Canada): [Scottish Diaspora: Large Tapestry on display at Confederation Centre Art Gallery](#). October 2016.

The News, NS (Canada): [The Story of Our Stories](#). 31 October 2016.

The Initial Stitch – Winnipeg Embroiderers Guild Newsletter (Canada): [Signing your work: Initials and Dates](#). November 2016.

The News, NS (Canada): [Story of Migrating Scots on Display](#). 31 October 2016.

The News, NS (Canada): [Tapestry Display of Scottish Connections includes Pictou](#). 8 November 2016.

HayEvent Montreal (Canada): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry explained](#). 22 November and 1 December 2016.

La Societe Ecosaise d'Ottawa (Canada): Scotland's contribution to the world comes to Ottawa. 29 November 2016.

CBC News (Canada): Tapestry on Display in Montreal celebrates experiences of Scottish Diaspora. 3 December 2016.

Global Late News Montreal (Canada): Interview Jenny Bruce and Bruce Bolton. 4 December 2016.

Webacom-lokalee Montreal (Canada): Tapestry on display in Montreal celebrates experiences of Scottish Diaspora. 5 December 2016.

Westmount Independent (Canada): Tapestry weaving tales of the Scots at Atwater Library. 6 December 2016.

CTV News (Canada): Scottish Diaspora Tapestry: interview with Jenny Bruce. 8 December 2016. Available: <http://montreal.ctvnews.ca/mobile/video?clipId=1012965> [accessed June 2017].

The Scots Canadian (Canada): Forget not your past, for in the future it may help you grow. Vol. 44, Fall 2016.

Wire Service, Canadian Free Press (Canada): First Look at the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry. 29 December 2016.

Ottawa Family Living (Canada): See the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry exhibit at OPL. 4 January 2017.

1310 News Ottawa, the Carol Anne Mehan Show (Canada): In discussion with Jenny Bruce on the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry Tour. 4 January 2017.

Out of the Box Fibre Artists newsletter (Canada): Ottawa, The Scottish Diaspora. January 2017.

John O'Groat Journal (Scotland): Was county's new Iceland connection work of the Gods? 17 February 2017.

N4 Iceland TV (Iceland): LANDNÁMSSÝNING FRÁ SKOTLANDI Í EYJAFJARÐARSVEIT. 23 February 2017.

Embroidery – the Textile Art Magazine (International): Review: the Art of Narrative Embroidery. March/April 2017.

UK Parliament website (United Kingdom): Scottish Diaspora Tapestry in Westminster Hall between 20 March and 29 April 2017. 6 March 2017.

What's On, London (England): Scottish Diaspora Tapestry at Westminster Hall, Houses of Parliament. 9 March 2017.

History Scotland – Celebrate Scotland (Scotland): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry returns to UK with London Exhibition 20 March to 29 April 2017](#). 9 March 2017.

Britain Magazine: official magazine of Visit Britain (United Kingdom): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry returns to the UK](#). 22 March 2017.

East Lothian Courier (Scotland): [Diaspora Tapestry and the terror attack at Westminster](#). 31 March 2017.

Church of Scotland News Online (United Kingdom): [London welcomes "amazing" Scottish Diaspora Tapestry](#). 3 April 2017.

Scottish Daily Record (Scotland): [Diaspora will be exhibited \[for the first time in Scotland\] at Crieff](#). 5 April 2017.

What's On for Families in Central Scotland (Scotland): [Scottish Diaspora Comes Home to Scotland](#). 3 May 2017.

Emito.net – Polski Portal w Wielkiej Brytanii (United Kingdom): [Szkoci w Polsce – Wystawa wraca z Westminster do Szkocji](#). 3 May 2017.

BBC Scotland TV, Breakfast Show & Reporting Scotland (Scotland): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry goes on display in Edinburgh](#). 4 May 2017.

BBC News Online (United Kingdom): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry goes on display in Edinburgh](#). 4 May 2017.

The Scotsman newspaper (Scotland): [Global tour sees Scottish diaspora weave their stories into tapestry](#). 5 May 2017.

Marketing Edinburgh (Scotland): [Scottish Tapestry Goes on display in Edinburgh](#). 5 May 2017.

I newspaper (Scotland): [From the Highlands and Beyond: story of globe-trotting Scots told in embroidery](#). 5 May 2017.

Edinburgh Evening News (Scotland): [Scottish Stitch-Up at St Giles](#). 5 May 2017.

East Lothian Courier Online (Scotland): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry panel stolen from St Giles Cathedral](#). 8 May 2017.

BBC News Online (United Kingdom): [Panel stolen from Scottish Diaspora Tapestry display in Edinburgh](#). 8 May 2017.

Edinburgh Evening News (Scotland): [Panel of Scottish Diaspora Tapestry stolen from St Giles](#). 8 May 2017.

STV News Online (Scotland): [A 'priceless' piece of Scottish Diaspora Tapestry has been stolen in Edinburgh](#). 8 May 2017.

Church of Scotland Online News (United Kingdom): [Panel of Scottish Diaspora Tapestry stolen from St Giles](#). 9 May 2017.

Apollo- the International Art Magazine (International): [Panel stolen from epic tapestry in Edinburgh's St Giles Cathedral](#). 10 May 2017.

Provinciale Zeeuwse Courant (Netherlands): [Veers panel na reis gestolen](#). 10 May 2017.

East Lothian Courier (Scotland): [Police probe as 'priceless' tapestry panel is stolen](#). 11 May 2017.

Omroep Zeeland Radio (Netherlands): [Interview with Hanneke de Vroe](#). 11 May 2017.

STV News Online (Scotland): [Thief sorry for stealing panel from diaspora tapestry](#). 24 May 2017.

BBC News Online (United Kingdom): [Panel stolen from Scottish Diaspora Tapestry in Edinburgh found](#). 24 May 2017.

East Lothian Courier (Scotland): [Thief writes letter of apology for stealing panel of Scottish Diaspora Tapestry](#). 26 May 2017.

BBC Radio Scotland (Scotland): [Time Travels: Susan Morrison talks of her visit to The Scottish Diaspora Tapestry at St Giles Cathedral](#), 30 May 2017.

The Caledonian (Scotland): [Stitches in Time](#). Summer 2017.

Scottish Field (Scotland): [Tapestry of Life](#). July 2017.

Perth & Kinross Courier (Scotland): [Patriotic Scottish Diaspora Tapestry goes on show at Crieff](#). 25 July 2017.

St Andrew's Church of Scotland in Corby newsletter (England): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry at Westminster](#). Autumn 2017.

Scottish Daily Record (Scotland): [Crieff's Tapestry Display: Hundreds take in iconic Scots art](#). 25 August 2017.

John O'Groat Journal & Caithness Courier (Scotland): [Scottish Diaspora Tapestry comes to Helmsdale](#). 15 September 2017.

APPENDIX FOUR

Exhibitions programme of the Scottish Diaspora Tapestry 2014-2017.

Locations listed in bold type were personally attended by the author.

DATES	LOCATION	COUNTRY	TYPE OF VENUE
2014: 31 May – 8 June	Prestonpans	Scotland	Community hall
2014: 24 June – 23 July	Stirling	Scotland	University campus
2014: 6-31 August	Edinburgh	Scotland	Church (cathedral)
2014: 6-22 Sept	Paisley	Scotland	Mill
2014: 27 Sep – 5 Oct	Inverness & Wick	Scotland	Gallery
2014: 28 Oct – 9 Nov	Helmsdale	Scotland	Community hall
2014: 14-21 Nov	Doncaster	England	Church
2014: 24 Nov- 6 Dec	Corby	England	Community hall
2014: 11-20 Dec	Musselburgh	Scotland	Museum
2015: 16 Mar – 11 April	Bergen	Norway	Civic building
2015: 30 May – 26 July	Veere	Netherlands	Museum
2015: 8-26 August	Barga	Italy	Church
2015: 29 Aug – 26 Sept	Picinisco	Italy	Community hall
2015: 3-17 October	Boussy St-Antoine	France	Civic building
2015: 21-29 October	Paris	France	Civic building
2015: 13-21 November	Goolwa	Australia	
2015: 29 Nov – 13 Dec	Adelaide	Australia	Civic building
2016: 9-23 January	Hobart	Australia	Civic building
2016: 3-24 February	Albury	Australia	Museum/civic building
2016: 28 Feb – 12 March	Wangaratta	Australia	Civic building
2016: 23 March – 2 April	Sydney	Australia	Gallery
2016: 9 – 30 April	Otago	New Zealand	Museum
2016: 13-30 May	Victoria	Canada	Church (cathedral)
2016: 13 June – 3 July	Winnipeg	Canada	Civic building
2016: 16 – 31 July	Montello	United States	Community hall
2016: 19 Sept – 1 Oct	Scarborough	Canada	Church
2016: 8-22 October	Charlottetown, PEI	Canada	Gallery
2016: 7-12 November	New Glasgow, NS	Canada	Theatre
2016: 19 Nov – 10 Dec	Montreal	Canada	Civic building
2016: 31 December	Ottawa	Canada	Civic building

2017: 1-25 January	Ottawa	Canada	Civic building
2017: 2-28 February	Nodorland	Iceland	Music venue
2017: 20 Mar – 29 Apr	Westminster/London	England	Civic building
2017: 4-18 May	Edinburgh	Scotland	Church (cathedral)
2017: 2-11 June	Prestonpans	Scotland	Community hall
2017: 22 July – 12 Aug	Crieff	Scotland	Community hall
2017: 16-30 September	Helmsdale	Scotland	Community hall
2017: 5-18 October	Irvine	Scotland	Civic building

APPENDIX FIVE

Coding tree for content analysis of the tapestry panels.

Categories are not mutually exclusive.

Time Period:

- Early period (pre-1000)
- Medieval (1000-1500)
- 16th Century
- 17th Century
- 18th Century
 - o 1700-1750
 - o 1750-1800
- 19th Century
 - o 1800-1850
 - o 1850-1914
- First World War
- Interwar (1918-1939)
- Second World War
- Post-war (1950-2000)
- Present day

Content imagery:

- Buildings
 - o Religious buildings
 - o Historic built heritage structures
 - o Civic buildings (inc. schools, universities)
 - o Private dwellings
 - o Cityscapes or major landmarks
- People
 - o Named individuals
 - o Unidentified people
 - o Family groups
 - o Native people
 - o Politicians or royals
 - o Women
- Soldiers/War
 - o Uniformed individuals in civic roles
 - o Soldiers/warriors or uniformed individuals in active military roles
 - o Other conflict images, inc. military hospitals, wounded soldiers, barbed wire

- Commercial/Industrial
- Exploration
 - o Transport
 - o “Opening up” exploration
- Sport
 - o Football
 - o Golf
- Reverse Diaspora
 - o Formation
 - o Present experience
- Symbols of Scottishness (or other nationality)
 - o Saltire
 - o Burns
 - o Bagpipes/music
 - o Tartan
 - o Homeland images
 - o Union Jack
 - o Host country flag

